

Exploratory study of ethnic entrepreneurs from Sri Lanka: how they enhance customer trust and loyalty in the UK.

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Abstract

Small-medium enterprises (SME) play a vital role in any economy. Over 90% of the UK job market and employment relies on the jobs generated by these SMEs. The recent pandemic situation in the UK has demonstrated governmental concern and support for these businesses. Thus, entrepreneurship can be regarded as the driver of these SMEs. Among them, ethnic minority entrepreneurship also plays a significant part of the UK economy. Nevertheless, Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs in the UK and their characteristics have rarely been mentioned in the UK literature. Recently, scholars have turned their attention to ethnic minority ventures to study the intangible resources, such as customer service skills. However, current ethnic minority entrepreneurship research in the UK relating to understanding customer trust and loyalty practices is a relatively under-researched area. Therefore, this research attempts to address the empirical (Sri Lankan) and theoretical gap (customer trust and loyalty practices in the ethnic minority entrepreneurship) found in the literature. The study employed an inductive qualitative inquiry with multiple cases focused on ethnic minority entrepreneurs in the retail (grocery) context. Unstructured in-depth interviews with field notes have been used for data collection, and a thematic technique adopted for coding/analysis of the data.

The findings suggested that ethnic culture plays a vital role in shaping their entering into the business, success perception and access to entrepreneurial resources (e.g. human, financial and labour capital). Importantly, findings also revealed that Sri Lankan entrepreneurs are enhancing customer trust and loyalty in multiple ways. First, they focus on a customer-centric approach/service to increase customer satisfaction. Second, they tend to develop a good business reputation over time by managing/practising business ethics. Lastly, thesis findings also argue that their culture may have influenced them to maintain their business reputation by practising good business ethics. Both theoretical and empirical contributions are highlighted and the implications of this research study for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers are discussed. In addition, the research limitations and future research paths are mentioned.

Declaration of Authorship

“I, Malitha vikum samasundara hettige, hereby declare that this thesis and the work presented in, it is entirely result of my own work, Where I consulted the work of others have always clearly stated”.

M.V.S Hettige.

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Table of Contents

Chapter 1: Introduction	12
Introduction	12
1.0 Overview	12
1.1 Research Motivation/justification	12
1.2 Statement of the problem	15
1.2.1 The main research question, aim and objectives of this study	17
1.3 Methodology	18
1.4 Thesis Structure	19
Chapter 2: Sri Lankans in the UK	20
2.1 Ethnic minority entrepreneurship in the UK	20
2.2 South-Asian entrepreneurship in the UK	21
2.3 Quantitative decline of South-Asian entrepreneurship	22
2.4 Background information about Sri Lanka	23
2.5 Sri Lankans in the UK	24
2.6 Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in London	25
2.7 Summary	26
Chapter 3: Literature review	27
3.0 Introduction	27
3.1 Defining the entrepreneurship	27
3.2 Definition of ethnic entrepreneurship	28
3.2.1 Definition of Immigrant entrepreneurship:	28
3.2.2 The relationship between Immigrant entrepreneurship and Ethnic entrepreneurship.	29
3.2.3 Operationalised definition of ethnic entrepreneurship	29
3.3 Motivation	30
3.3.1 Necessity migrant entrepreneurs	32
3.3.2 Opportunity migrant entrepreneurs	33
3.4 Success -Perception and Business Performance of minority entrepreneurs	33
3.5 Theories of ethnic entrepreneurship	35
3.5.1 Cultural approach:	35
3.5.1.1 Middleman Minority Theory	35

3.5.2 Structuralist approach.....	36
3.5.2.1 Disadvantage theory	37
3.5.2.2 Enclave theory	38
3.5.2.3 Social embeddedness theory.....	40
3.6 Ethnic entrepreneurship models and concepts.....	42
3.6.1 The interactive model	42
3.6.2 The mixed embeddedness model	44
3.7 Ethnic entrepreneurship resources	45
3.7.1 Social Capital.....	46
3.7.1.1 Family relations in a business context.....	48
3.7.1.2 Supplier relationship.....	49
3.7.1.3 Employee relationship	49
3.7.1.4 Customer relationship	50
3.7.1.4.1 Loyalty	51
a. Trust.....	51
a. 1 Operational benevolence	52
a. 2 Problem- solving orientation.....	53
a. 3 Operational competence	53
b. Customer satisfaction	54
c. Customer service.....	54
d. Image and Reputation	56
d. 1 Image.....	56
d.2 Reputation	56
3.7.2 Human Capital	57
3.7.3 Financial Capital	58
3.7.4 Cultural Capital	59
3.7.5 Labour Capital	60
3.8 Conceptual framework.....	62
3.9 Summary.....	67
Chapter 4: Methodology.....	68
4.0 Introduction.....	68
4.1 Research philosophy	68
4.1.1 Positivism	69
4.1.2 Critical realism paradigm	70

4.1.3 Interpretivism.....	71
4.1.4 Philosophical selection for this study: Interpretivism	72
4.2 Research approach.....	74
4.2.1 Deductive approach:	74
4.2.2 Inductive approach:	76
4.3 Preferred research approach: Inductive.....	77
4.3.1 Qualitative methodology.....	77
4.3.1.1 Research strategy: Case study	80
4.3.1.2.1 Multiple Cases	81
4.3.1.2.2 Unstructured interviews	82
4.3.2 Techniques and procedures.....	84
4.3.2.1 Purposive Sampling	84
4.3.2.2 Preconditions to research	85
4.3.2.3 Data processing	86
4.3.2.3.1 Data Analysis	86
4.3.2.3.2 Thematic coding	87
4.3.2.3.3 With-in case study analysis	88
4.3.2.3.4 Cross-case analysis.....	88
4.3.2.4 Ethical Considerations.....	89
4.3.2.5 Research Validity	91
4.3.2.6 Research reflexivity and positionality	92
4.3.2.6.1 Positionality of the researcher.....	94
4.3.2.6.1.1 The influence of mixed embeddedness model.....	95
4.3.2.6.1.2 Insider/outsider status	98
4.3.2.6.1.3 Politics of representation	100
4.4 Strengths and weaknesses	103
4.4.1 Data collection challenges due to Coronavirus.....	104
4.5 Summary.....	105
Chapter 5: Findings	106
5.0 Introduction.....	106
5.1 The individual case description and summaries:	106
Case 1 description and key insights:	106
Case 2 description and key insights:	111
Case 3 description and key insights:	116

Case 4 description and key insights:	121
Case 5 description and key insights:	125
Case 6 description and key insights:	130
Case 7 description and key insights:	135
Case 8 description and key insights:	140
5.2 Cross-case analysis	145
5.2.1 Motivation to be in the business	145
5.2.1.1 Pull factors	146
a. Independence:	146
b. Financial benefits:	148
c. Previous work experience:	149
5.2.1.2 Push factors:	149
a. Lack of job opportunities:	150
b. Family maintenance:	150
c. Case unique factors:	151
5.2.2 Success perception	152
a. Individual satisfaction:	153
b. Support for the family:	155
5.2.3 Human capital	157
5.2.3.1 Having a family business background in Sri Lanka:	157
5.2.3.2 Previous work experience:	159
5.2.2.3 Knowledge and information sharing through social network:	162
5.2.4 Social capital	164
5.2.4.1 Access to finance/financial capital:	164
5.2.4.1.1 Access to financial capital through family members:	165
5.2.4.1.2 Access to financial capital through social networks:	166
5.2.4.2 Access to labour capital:	167
5.2.4.2.1 Labour capital through family members:	167
5.2.4.2.2 Labour capital through social network:	169
5.2.5 Supplier relationship	171
5.2.6 Employee relationship	173
5.2.7 Customer Relationship	176
5.2.7.1 Trust:	176
5.2.7.1.1 Operational benevolence:	176

5.2.7.1.2 Problem-solving orientation and Operational competence:.....	180
5.2.7.2 Service	183
5.2.7.2.1 Customer orientation:.....	183
5.2.7.2.2 Customer centricity:	185
5.2.7.2.3 Developing empathy	187
5.2.7.2.3.1 Empathy as an aim to build customer satisfaction	188
5.2.7.2.3 Developing patience	192
5.2.7.2.4 Let the customer make the buying decision.....	195
5.2.7.3 Business reputation	198
5.2.8 Opportunity structure	202
5.2.8.1 Serving in places that others missed.....	203
5.2.8.2 Sri Lankan ethnically concentrated area	204
5.2.8.3 Current Challenges and opportunities within the market	206
5.2.8.4 Coronavirus impact	209
5.2.8.4.1 Supplier delays due to pandemic	210
5.2.8.4.2 Working environment challenges	211
5.2.8.4.3 Business uncertainty	213
5.2.9 Institutional embeddedness	216
5.2.9.1 Overall positive feedback on rules and regulations UK	216
5.2.9.2 Issues with rules and regulations	218
5.2.9.2.1 Having too many regulations to follow.....	218
5.2.9.2.2 Government policy on migration.....	219
5.2.9.2.3 Import regulations	221
5.2.9.3 Coronavirus support.....	221
5.3 Summary.....	224
Chapter 6: Discussion	225
6.0 Introduction.....	225
6.1 Motivation to be in the business.....	225
6.2 Success perception	227
6.3 Human capital	229
6.4 Cultural capital	230
6.5 Social capital.....	231
6.6 Supplier relationship	232
6.7 Employee relationship	233

6.8 Customer Relationship	235
6.8.1 Customer trust	235
6.8.1.1 Operational benevolence	235
6.8.1.2 Problem-solving orientation	236
6.8.1.3 Operational competence	236
6.8.2 Customer service	237
6.8.2.1 Customer orientation	237
6.8.2.2 Customer centricity	238
6.8.2.3 Developing empathy for the customer	238
6.8.2.4 Developing patience for the customer	239
6.8.2.5 Letting the customer make the buying decision	239
6.8.3 Business reputation	240
6.8.4 Loyalty	242
6.8.4.1 Loyalty determinants	242
6.8.4.1.1 Customer Trust	242
6.8.4.1.2 Service	243
6.8.4.1.3 Reputation	244
6.9 Opportunity structure	247
7.0 Institutional embeddedness	249
7.1 Summary :	252
Chapter 7: Conclusion	256
Introduction 7.0	256
7.1 Research contribution	256
7.1.1 Key findings and contribution to the customer relationship marketing	257
7.1.2 Key findings and contribution to the mixed embeddedness model	258
7.2 Implications and recommendations of the findings	260
7.2.1 Implications for researchers	260
7.2.2 Implications for practitioners	261
7.2.3 Implications for policymakers	263
7.3 Limitations of the research	264
7.4 Contributions to methodology	265
7.5 Future research	265
7.6 Summary:	266
References	268

Appendices	294
Appendix 1: Defining Key Concepts	294
Appendix 2: Nvivo word cloud	306
Appendix 3: Individual Case Analysis	307
Analysis of Case 1 (Ravi-C1)	307
Analysis of Case 2 (Van -C2)	324
Analysis of Case 3 (Dan-C3)	338
Analysis of Case 4 (Ken-C4)	351
Analysis of Case 5 (Sura -C5)	364
Analysis of Case 6 (Hesh-C6)	377
Analysis of Case 7 (Mahi -C7)	393
Analysis of Case 8 (Sachin -C8)	406

List of Tables

Table 1: Number of cases and demographics	85
Table 2: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case one.....	110
Table 3: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case two	115
Table 4: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case three	120
Table 5: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case four.....	125
Table 6: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case five	129
Table 7: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case six.....	134
Table 8: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case seven	139
Table 9: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case eight	144
Table 10 : Motivation factors of individual cases.....	145
Table 11:Subjective and objective measures of success.....	153

List of Figures

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework	66
Figure 2 : Case 1 key insights Individual analysis (Micro-analysis).....	107
Figure 3 : Case 1 Key insights of Opportunity structure(Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)	108
Figure 4: Case 2 key insights Individual analysis (Micro-analysis).....	112
Figure 5: Case 2 Key insights of Opportunity structure(Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)	113
Figure 6: Case 3 Key insights of Individual analysis (micro analysis).....	117
Figure 7: Case 3 Key insights of Opportunity structure(Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)	118
Figure 8: Case 4 Key insights of Individual analysis(micro analysis).....	122
Figure 9: Case 4 Key insights of Opportunity structure (Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)	123
Figure 10: Case 5 Key insights of individual analysis (micro analysis).....	126
Figure 11: Case 5 Key insights of Opportunity structure (Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)	127
Figure 12: Case 6 Key insights of individual analysis (micro analysis).....	131
Figure 13: Case 6 Key insights of Opportunity structure (Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)	132
Figure 14: Case 7 Key insights of individual analysis (micro analysis).....	136
Figure 15: Case 7 Key insights of Opportunity structure (Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)	137
Figure 16: Case 8 Key insights of individual analysis (micro analysis).....	141
Figure 17: Case 8 Key insights of Opportunity structure (Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)	142
Figure 18: Summary of cross case findings from section 5.2.1-5.2.6	175
Figure 19: Summary of Customer Relationship cross case analysis	201
Figure 20: Summary of opportunity structure cross case analysis	215
Figure 21: Summary of institutional embeddedness cross case analysis.....	223
Figure 22: Ethnic cultural influence on micro level of the discussion section 6.1 to 6.7	234
Figure 23 Ethnic culture, customer trust, loyalty, customer satisfaction, ethics, reputation, and its relationship with each theme.....	246
Figure 24: Summary of opportunity structure discussion.....	249
Figure 25:Summary of the institutional embeddedness discussion.....	251
Figure 26: conceptual model to explain Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurship and how they enhancing trust and loyalty of their customers with in the retail grocery businesses in UK	255

Chapter 1: Introduction

Introduction

1.0 Overview

This chapter will enable an understanding of the overall picture of this research, which explores how Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance customers' trust and loyalty in their businesses. Thus, this study will closely analyse and report on the Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurial characteristics, processes, and engagements/ interactions within the environment that they have currently embedded in the UK. It gives a rich insight into the motivations, perceptions, and cultural values by interpreting the lived experiences which the Sri Lankan entrepreneurial communities possess in the host country. Lived experiences are particularly important because this shapes how they define their success (customer trust and loyalty), business practices and motivations to enter the entrepreneurial journey in the first place. In this chapter, the researcher presents the overall outline of this thesis. This chapter is further divided into: Research motivation/justification, statement of the problem (the gap); the main research question; aim and objectives of the study; chosen methodology; and overall, the thesis structure.

1.1 Research Motivation/justification

SMEs can be considered as the backbone of the economy in any country. There are various articles and information regarding SMEs and their contribution to the UK economy. Indeed, over 90% of the UK job market and employment relies on the jobs generated by these SMEs (Federation of Small Businesses, 2021). The recent pandemic situation in the UK has demonstrated governmental concern and support for these businesses, especially financially (Albonico, Mladenov, and Sharma, 2020). On the other hand, entrepreneurship can be regarded as the driver of these SMEs.

There are various descriptions of entrepreneurship. Many of them are regarded as either mainstream entrepreneurs or ethnic minority entrepreneurs. Mainstream entrepreneurs run economic activities in the countries where they were born and represent the majority of ethnic society and culture (Volery, 2007).

On the other hand, ethnic minority entrepreneurs are viewed as immigrants who arrived and settled within decades in the host country and conducted economic activities (Volery, 2007). It is interesting to mention that these immigrants are more likely to enter into entrepreneurial activities in the host country than their mainstream counterparts (Ram, Jones, and Villares-Varela, 2017). Thus, scholars also argue that promoting ethnic entrepreneurship brings economic benefits, and at the same time, it enhances diversity and integration (Haq, 2015). Various approaches/theories/models have been introduced to explain the phenomenon of ethnic minority entrepreneurship over the years. For instance, the culturist approach explains entrepreneurial predispositions and motivations of certain ethnic communities in the host country (i.e. middleman minority theory) (Turner and Bonacich, 1980). The structuralist approach explains the external environmental factors that influence ethnic minority individuals to start entrepreneurial activities (Jones *et al.*, 2014). In this regard, the most popular arguments are the discrimination they face in the host country, language barriers, low-paid jobs, lack of employment etc. (Ram and Jones, 2008). Yet, many scholars argue that either of these approaches alone did not completely explain the phenomenon (Krippner *et al.*, 2004). Therefore, an integrative model was introduced, which emphasizes the structure and the agency (Volery, 2007). Then again, criticisms were made of the model, such as the inability to explain ‘how changing patterns of globalization and racialization of immigrant minorities in many western countries influence the dynamics and characteristics of immigrant entrepreneurs’ (Collins and Low, 2010, p. 102).

Nevertheless, in response to these criticisms and to develop the theory of ethnic minority entrepreneurship, the mixed embeddedness model approach has been introduced in the literature. According to Ram, Jones and Villares-Varela (2017, p.5), ‘the greatest single theoretical leap forward in this field occurred at the very close of the last century’. The model takes the view that these ethnic entrepreneurs are embedded in social networks, and at the same time, they are also embedded in a broader external business context (Kloosterman, 2010). First,

the external business context consists of markets where these ethnic entrepreneurs must compete to survive; and second, the state, which is the regulatory regime that all businesses must comply with and follow (Kloosterman, Van der Leun and Rath, 1999). In essence, it highlights the importance of ethnic minority embeddedness in their social networking transactions and resources to become entrenched in broader structures of political, institutional and economic environments (Rath and Kloosterman, 2002).

The model also received critiques of lacking a historical view, being not vigorous enough to take other factors (i.e. diaspora entrepreneurship and transnational entrepreneurship) into account and not explaining how the migration flows are gendered etc. (Ram, Jones and Villares-Varela, 2017). Yet, the mixed embeddedness perspective enables us to expand and look beyond the traditional ethnic resources approach. The main importance of mixed embeddedness research is that it can identify various issues that ethnic entrepreneurs face (Rath, 2006). These issues could be related to the social-political conditions of their host country. For instance, these can be start-up capital, suppliers, skills and training, competition, customers, human resources, and various political/regulatory responses (Kloosterman and Rath, 2006). Therefore, some of these ethnic entrepreneurs seek to go beyond their traditional ethnic strategies and tend to develop structural and personal strategies to compete in the market (Jones and Ram, 2013). Hence, the scholars paid attention towards opportunity structures and markets in different locations/countries or regions in order to explore ethnic entrepreneurship (Ram and Jones, 2008). Importantly, this has paved the way to analyse the challenging business environment in which these ethnic minority businesses are embedded.

Thus, some scholars have recently stressed the need to identify factors that constrain the development and growth of ethnic businesses (Haq, 2015). Many of these ethnic ventures are formulated around the low value-added sectors (Ram, Edwards and Jones, 2007). Retailing is one of the popular sectors for these immigrant entrepreneurial individuals (Ram and Jones, 2008). However, there are limited studies conducted over the years relating to ethnic retail shops, specifically small ethnic grocery shops (Jamal, 2005; Clarke and Banga, 2010). Perhaps scholars have given less attention to these micro-managed minority firms, believing that these firms might not generate valuable data (Ram and Jones, 2008; Ram, Jones and Villares-Varela, 2017). Yet, some scholars recently found that these small businesses possess great customer

service skills, which turns out to be vital for their business sustainability (Haq *et al.*, 2021). Retaining customers for any business is challenging. Hence, in this case, it would be interesting to investigate how these ethnic entrepreneurs retain their customers in the long run; specifically, how these community retail grocery shops build long-lasting customer relationships, or in other words, customer trust and loyalty towards their businesses. This thesis attempts to address this gap, explained extensively in the problem statement section below.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The UK is a diverse country, and there are various minority ethnic communities across the nation. London is particularly popular in this case (Sturgis *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, out of these ethnic businesses, South-Asian ethnic minority entrepreneurs own or manage most of the firms (Haq, 2015). Thus, statistics suggested that these South-Asian originated businesses recently faced slow growth, compared to the 1990s (Office for National Statistics, 2021). Various reasons contribute to the decline previously mentioned in the literature. For instance, there are more paid employment opportunities than before, less discriminatory regulations, and children or second-generation migrants are less attracted to businesses than their parents once were (Haq, 2015). Therefore, many of the researchers turned their attention to supporting South-Asian businesses (Clark and Drinkwater, 2010; Haq, 2015).

However, culture appears to play a vital role for ethnic entrepreneurial activities, particularly for South Asians (Haq *et al.*, 2021). For instance, Victor, Martin, and Zubair (2012) mentioned that South Asian customers require a family-like, friendly customer service. Another mentioned that compassion and characteristics such as patience, exist when dealing with their customers (Gilboa, Seger-Guttmann and Mimran, 2019). Consequently, they value customer presence in their businesses and prioritise customer satisfaction rather than monetary objectives, particularly in micro-businesses (Victor, Martin and Zubair, 2012). These scholars concluded that South Asian/minority ethnic entrepreneurs who present customer-centred, personalised services tend to have strategic importance, therefore creating a competitive advantage for their businesses and improving its sustainability (Haq *et al.*, 2021). Consequently, some scholars studied customer service from a resource-based viewpoint and

found that their service skills also led to customer satisfaction. Hence, it can be used as a source of competitive advantage (Liu and Yang, 2019). Customer satisfaction often leads to customer loyalty and retention (Altinay, Saunders and Wang, 2014). Thus, some studies found that a satisfied customer relationship with the business would increase customer trust over time (Ganesan, 1994). For this reason, customers who do not trust a business tend not to be loyal and eventually find an alternative (El-Manstrly, 2016). Therefore, loyalty cannot be gained without earning trust. Furthermore, there are some practices that work to enhance customer trust and loyalty (Altinay, Saunders and Wang, 2014). These South Asian/ minority ethnic entrepreneurs focused heavily on customers and valued their relationship with the business (Haq, *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, it is interesting to investigate their view of customers. In this regard, the customer trust and loyalty practices of these businesses are indeed under-researched. Recent studies on either South Asian/ ethnic minority entrepreneurship or related customer relationship articles lack these important contributions (Esmark and Noble, 2016; Haq *et al.*, 2021).

Nevertheless, recent scholars stressed the need for intra-ethnic group differences and their characteristics in order to understand the business activities better and offer support (Haq, 2015; Ram, Jones and Villares-Varela, 2017). In line with this, some entrepreneurial communities that can be categorized as South Asian entrepreneurship appeared to be less researched than others (Haq, 2015). One such community can be identified as the Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in the UK. Consequently, their entrepreneurial activities and contribution to the economy rarely appear to be in the UK literature. Similarly, other disciplines have mentioned this recently (Siddhisena and White, 1999; Fernando and Kenny, 2018) and in the UK literature, some even described the Sri Lankan community as a neglected ethnic group (Aspinall, 2019) - (for a full contextual review of Sri Lankans, please see Chapter 2).

Therefore, first, it can be argued that there is a theoretical gap regarding customer trust, and that loyalty practices are under-researched within ethnic minority entrepreneurship. Second, there is an empirical gap in the UK literature regarding Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs (please refer to Chapter 2). Therefore, this thesis will address the identified empirical and theoretical gap by forming the main research question, along with the aim and objectives as below

1.2.1 The main research question, aim and objectives of this study

The research aim, objectives and questions:

The research aims to explore how Sri Lankan ethnic minority entrepreneurs enhance customer trust and loyalty in the retail grocery context. This main aim is interconnected to further four research objectives.

The first objective is to conduct a comprehensive literature study to critically review ethnic entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial orientation, trust, and loyalty towards the customer within the retail business context.

Second, to investigate Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs' current status/backgrounds to understand their retail entrepreneurship activities.

Third, to understand how they enhance trust and loyalty for their customers in the retail grocery business context.

Finally, to contribute to the knowledge by generating implications/recommendations to enhance their trust and loyalty practices.

In order to satisfy the aim and the objectives above, the researcher formulated the main research question below:

How do Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance the trust and loyalty of their customers within the retail grocery businesses in UK?

1.3 Methodology

Given the exploratory nature of the research question, the researcher has chosen the interpretivist paradigm. The interpretivist paradigm attempts to understand the human lived experience subjectively. On the other hand, the interpretivist seeks to understand the subject's point of view, and their interpretations of the world around them in natural settings. In line with this philosophical view, the nature of the reality is subjective, and it recognises the importance of interaction between the researcher and the main subject of the study - the ethnic entrepreneur in retail SMEs. Thus, retail SMEs and ethnic entrepreneurs considered through relationship marketing, is a relatively under-researched area. Therefore, an exploratory approach has been chosen with an interpretivist paradigm for conducting this research, enabling the achievement of the main aim of the research through the objectives and in answering the research question.

This study aims to explore how Sri Lankan ethnic minority entrepreneurs enhance customer trust and loyalty in retail grocery context. Therefore, this is an exploratory study and not one deducing any hypothesis or elaborating any theories; the researcher selected an inductive approach for this research. Complementary to this and to the interpretivist research design a qualitative methodology was employed, where in return, the researcher expected to find the answer to the main research question by analysing 'raw data' given by the qualitative methods.

A multiple case study strategy has been employed as the chosen strategy. The main method of collecting the data has been unstructured, in-depth-interviews with field notes. The purposive snowball sampling technique was used to gather relevant Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs who owned/managed retail businesses. All interviews were tape-recorded and transcribed by the researcher. The Nvivo software was used for data analysis and thematic coding was used for themes across cases in the study to address the main research question and objectives.

1.4 Thesis Structure

Chapter 2 (contextual background) introduces the contextual background of Sri Lankan ethnic minority entrepreneurs in the UK. It begins with recent researches focusing on ethnic minority entrepreneurship in the UK; then South-Asian minority entrepreneurship, and its current status. Lastly, it also highlights the empirical gap about Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in the current context.

Chapter 3 (literature review) discusses the current relevant literature regarding ethnic entrepreneurship and customer relationship marketing literature relevant to customer trust and loyalty practices. Then the theoretical framework selected for this thesis and its justification.

Chapter 4 (Research methodology) highlights the philosophical assumption of the study (interpretivism); research approach (inductive); research methodology (qualitative); research strategy (multiple case study) along with data collection method; sampling; ethical considerations; research validity; research reflexivity and positionality; Strengths and weaknesses of the research design; data collection challenges during the Coronavirus pandemic.

Chapter 5 offers an individual case description along with ‘case specific’ key insights. Then a **(Cross-case analysis)** presents the findings that emerged from the data analysis in various themes.

Chapter 6 offers a critical **discussion** of the themes relating to Sri Lankan entrepreneurial characteristics, challenges in the UK and customer relationship related themes (achieving the 2nd and 3rd objectives of the study, hence answering the main research question).

Chapter 7 (Conclusion) summarises the findings of the thesis and its theoretical and empirical contribution to the literature. Then the implications and recommendation for the researchers, practitioners, and policymakers. Lastly, this concluding chapter ends with the limitation of the study, and a contribution to the methodology and future research.

Chapter 2: Sri Lankans in the UK

2.0 Introduction

This chapter outlines ethnic minority entrepreneurship in the UK and recent research trends in the literature. There follows an outline of South-Asian entrepreneurship in the UK and its slow growth in recent years. After that, the literature narrowed the focus to an understanding of the Sri Lankans and their socio-cultural background in Sri Lanka. The next section then discusses the Sri Lankan population in the UK, then discusses the recent studies conducted on Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in the UK and their contribution. Lastly, the chapter ends with a summary.

2.1 Ethnic minority entrepreneurship in the UK

Recent studies conducted in the UK have found that ethnic minority small businesses are likely to be more innovative than small non-ethnic businesses (Haq *et al.*, 2021). Thus, the policymakers and researchers often overlooked the phenomenon, especially in microbusinesses (Haq, 2015). Interestingly, these businesses created self-employment and new small ventures, even in the global financial crisis (Kitching and Smallbone, 2012). The Covid-19 pandemic has also highlighted the importance of researching small businesses (Bartik *et al.*, 2020).

Hence, this has the potential to support the local, regional, national economy, employment and its recovery (Vershina and Rodgers, 2020). In line with this, current ethnic minority entrepreneurship research has focused on effective policies on their businesses that are vital for its existence (Ram *et al.*, 2012). These businesses and their existence are vital for economic growth and reduce inequalities at local and national levels (Haq *et al.*, 2021). The literature has also focused on supporting networks (Kitching, Smallbone, and Athayde, 2009), financial challenges, and barriers to entrepreneurial development (Carter *et al.*, 2015).

Furthermore, ethnic minority entrepreneurship research recently paid attention to start-ups, business improvement or growth, ethnic entrepreneurial orientation, value co-creation, and human resource management studies (Haq. *et al.*, 2021). These studies stress the growing

interest in micro-level ethnic minority entrepreneurship (Vershina and Rodgers, 2020). However, recent research found that immigrants are more likely to be entrepreneurial than mainstream nationals (Haq *et al.*, 2021). Some studies focused on ethnic entrepreneurs and their cultures (Basu and Altinay, 2002; Altinay, Saunders and Wang, 2014). In particular, South-Asian culture, hence the South-Asian migrants, value friendly and family-alike customer services regardless of economic outcomes (Victor, Martin, and Zubair, 2012). These ethnic minority businesses pass their knowledge from one generation to another informally. A small business benefits when established locally and is focused on niche markets (Bamiatzi and Kirchmaier, 2014). Recently, researches indicate that terms like compassion and patience drive their success and sustainability; in particular, customer-focused, personalised service positively influences customer satisfaction, retention, and loyalty (Haq *et al.*, 2021).

2.2 South-Asian entrepreneurship in the UK

There are two circumstances whereby South Asians immigrated to the UK. One was to fill the shortage of labour; and a second was in the instance of South Asian originated immigrants from colonised countries like Uganda and Kenya after slavery was abolished (Haq, 2015). These immigrants arrived with a basic amount of money, and a determination to succeed in an alien environment where language, finance, and entering the mainstream job market were serious challenges (Basu, 1998). Nevertheless, at the end of 1980s, one-third of retail ventures were independently owned by South Asians (Ram and Smallbone, 2003).

This success is evidently shown in the census which took place in 1991 where around 7% employed in the SME sector was offered by South-Asian ethnic minority ventures over 3% of the employment offered by mainstream community (Basu, 1998). This pattern was sustained until the low economic growth rate among OECD countries back then (Blanchflower, 2004). It had a much greater impact on the Asian business activities than the mainstream counter parts. This was partly due to their business activities being based on low-value business sectors and their subsistence-like entrepreneurial activities, even though they maintained their dominance in the self-employment sector (Jones and Ram, 2013). Consequently, this has attributed to

gaining sub-contracting in industries like manufacturing, and the influence of social factors such as behavioural changes in lifestyles and the popularity of South-Asian cuisine in the UK (Ram and Smallbone, 2003). For instance, in 1970, there were around 1000 South-Asian restaurants around the country, and at the end of 1998, the number increased to well above 8000, generating more than £ 1.5 billion into UK economy (Ram *et al.*, 2012).

2.3 Quantitative decline of South-Asian entrepreneurship

Regardless of the increase in these South-Asian ethnic ventures and their success, poverty, underemployment, and unemployment are commonly seen in these communities (Haq, 2015). Hence, this achievement should not overlook the reality (Brah, 1996). Notably, the 1990s downturn in these businesses was mainly caused by two reasons (Jones and Ram, 2013). The first reason mentioned in the literature was the appearance of supermarkets and their sharp growth in the industry; second, the introduction of the retail units in petrol stations and motorway stations. Moreover, revoking the Shops Act 1950 also contributed negatively to the South Asian retail businesses. It allows supermarkets in particular to open 24 hours and or to open on Sundays as well (Haq, 2015). In return, this caused these small businesses to work even harder to survive and resulted in a number of businesses closing over time (Ram and Smallbone, 2003). Similarly, paid employment also contributed negatively, particularly to South-Asian entrepreneurship (Ram and Jones, 2008). One reason is that the second generation of entrepreneurs (i.e. their children) were mostly born in the UK (Jones *et al.*, 2013). These offspring do not face the same type of discrimination in the mainstream job market as their parents once did. Their language, skills and educational qualifications are generally higher than their parents (Ram and Smallbone, 2003; Clark and Drinkwater, 2010).

Nevertheless, there were around 4.8 million private sector businesses in 2010 compared to over 5.8 million in 2019 in the UK (an increase of approximately one million businesses over the years) (Office for National Statistics, 2021). Also, over 99% of businesses are Small-Medium Enterprises (SME), while their combined turnover is approximately £2 trillion as of 2019 (FSB, 2021). Over half of the private sector employment is generated by SMEs in the UK. On the

other hand, over 5% of UK SMEs are ethnic minority employers. It is estimated that these enterprises contribute approximately £25-30 billion annually to the UK economy (Haq, *et al.*, 2021). In these businesses, ethnic origins included Indians (26%), Pakistanis (16%), other Asian categories (14%), black African (around 11%), Chinese (approx. 8%), other mixed white and Bangladeshi (combined together 5%) (Office for National Statics, 2021). Thus, even though South-Asian minority groups have the largest ownership over the other ethnic groups, the statistics still suggest no significant growth overall in the sector since 2015 (Office for National Statistics, 2021). However, Sri Lankan entrepreneurs also come from South Asian countries.

2.4 Background information about Sri Lanka

With a population of just over 21 million, Sri Lanka is an island located in the continent of South-Asia in the Indian Ocean. Sri Lanka was influenced by colonials such as Portuguese, and Dutch, and gained their independence from Britain's last colonial rule in 1948. Despite its socio-political hardships over the years, Sri Lanka, as a country, managed to achieve a high literacy rate (approx. 92 %) among adults, free education, a well-managed health care system (indicating life expectancy (74yrs) and infant mortality rate (approx. 13 deaths in 1000 births), in comparison to the South-Asian continent (World Bank, 2021). Apart from these achievements, the country is far from attaining its 'economic development' as it faced ongoing socio-political instability due to the civil war from 1983-2009. Sri Lanka is a diverse country that consists of multicultural and religious backgrounds across the island. The majority of the ethnicities represent Sinhalese (74.9%), Tamils (15.3%) and Muslim (9.3%). Thus, the leading religious practices are Buddhism (70.1%), Hinduism (12.6%), Islam(9.7%) and Christianity (6.2%), and these religious backgrounds heavily influence their social, cultural and political life (Fernando and Kenny, 2018). Similarly, according to Fernando and Jackson (2006), these religious practices could significantly influence leadership in terms of motivation, judgment, emotions, and decision-making processes.

2.5 Sri Lankans in the UK

The Asian population constitutes around 7% of the UK population (Office for National Statistics, 2021). The Sri Lankan-born minority population within England and Wales is about 127,000 which compares to British Pakistanis (around 1.2 million) and British Indians (about 1.5 million) in the UK (Office for National Statistics, 2021). Nevertheless, according to the literature, three primary immigration waves from Sri Lanka to UK occurred (Fernando and Kenny, 2018). The first wave of immigration is known to have occurred between 1950-1980s. This first wave was mainly due to the job opportunities offered in the UK. For instance, there were many vacancy opportunities for doctors in national health services in the UK due to understaffing (Siddhisena and White, 1999). The second wave of migration from Sri Lanka occurred due to the civil war in the 1980s, resulting in Tamil minorities flying to the UK to claim asylum (Aspinall, 2019). The third wave is still emerging as professionals continue to arrive in the UK on highly skilled immigrant visas.

Scholars have noted that the Sri Lankan minority groups are educated and competent compared to other minority groups (Fernando and Kenny, 2018). Thus, like any other South-Asian cultural backgrounds, Sri Lankan culture also shows the collective's characteristics (Aspinall, 2019). They maintain close community bonds (Kailasapathy and Metz, 2012), valuing the presence of their elders and respecting them (Herath, 2015). According to Samaratunge and Nyland (2006), family support and savings, and the embeddedness of their culture are vital ingredients of the Sri Lankan social security system and play a significant role in Sri Lankan culture. In Sri Lanka, Buddhism is recognised as an important social institution as it plays a vital role in the national identity and Sinhalese, who represent the country's majority ethnic community (Azmat and Zutshi, 2012). Apart from these country-specific characteristics, other particular factors could further differentiate this group from its South-Asian counterparts, such as the women's social status in Sri Lanka (Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapaksa, 2015). The country had a literacy rate of over 92% (Fernando and Kenny, 2018), yet there was no substantial gender disparity in these literacy rates. Even in the UK, Sri Lankans appeared to show these characteristics in an attempt to maintain their identity (Siddhisena and White, 1999). For example, the Sri Lankan diaspora gathers together in various Buddhist temples to

organise and celebrate national events to educate the younger generation about their cultural values and traditions (Fernando and Kenny, 2018).

2.6 Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in London

According to the Office for National Statistics (2021), around two-thirds of Sri Lankan born immigrants reside in London. These findings also align with the recent increase in their economic activities in London (Siddhisena and White, 1999). Thus, there is still a significant lack of knowledge in this sector. Moreover, some scholars viewed Sri Lankans as a neglected population in the UK (Aspinall, 2019). Consequently, there is a lack of literature about Sri Lankan entrepreneurial or business activities, especially in the UK (Siddhisena and White, 1999; Aspinall, 2019). However, there is some limited literature about Sri Lankans in the UK, although these do not necessarily discuss Sri Lankan entrepreneurial activities. For instance, Siddhisena and White (1999) discussed the migration and settlement of the Sri Lankan population in the UK. They stressed that this migratory community needs scholarly attention regarding their economic activities. To this effect, Jones (2014) studied the social identity of the Tamil community in the UK, highlighting community differences between Sri Lankan Tamils and other non-Sri Lankan Tamil. Similarly, Fernando and Kenny (2018) conducted a study on Sri Lankan employees and found that these individuals may have their own unique cultural identity to distinguish them from other South-Asians. Lastly, Aspinall (2019) stresses the issue of limited literature on Sri Lankans in the UK. These studies mainly discuss Sri Lankan socio-cultural identity in the UK. Therefore, it can be argued that there are no significant contributions to the literature regarding the Sri Lankans, their economic and particularly their entrepreneurial activities, and their economic contributions to the UK. Therefore, this thesis has identified and attempts to address this gap in the literature.

2.7 Summary

First, the chapter discussed the recent studies regarding ethnic minority entrepreneurship in the UK. These studies highlighted the importance of these small businesses and their contribution, even in the ongoing pandemic situation in the UK and across the world. Furthermore, some studies focused on policymaking to support networks, financial challenges and reduce inequality overall. Thus, recent studies have turned their attention to smaller micro-businesses. Some of the themes that emerged from the literature can be highlighted as: human resources, value co-creation, entrepreneurial orientation, and growing interest in micro-level entrepreneurship. The researcher discussed South-Asian entrepreneurship and their business growth in the UK, highlighting some of the impeding factors such as supermarkets, the revoking of the Shops Act 1950, paid employment and the fact that the second generation is less attracted to these businesses due to their higher skills and educational achievements in the host country. The next sections highlighted the Sri Lankan descendants and their immigration history, discussing their socio-cultural values, highlighting their family support, religious beliefs, and women's role in Sri Lanka. The last section underlines the need for further Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurial research to contribute to the literature and its gap.

Chapter 3: Literature review

3.0 Introduction

Chapter 3 mainly reviews the literature regarding ethnic minority entrepreneurship and customer relationship marketing theories relating to trust and loyalty practices. The chapter begins by defining entrepreneurship and moving to define ethnic entrepreneurship. The next sections then discuss the main theories and concepts relating to ethnic minority entrepreneurship and literature relating to customer relationship marketing. Then the last section highlights the main theoretical framework chosen to conduct this thesis.

3.1 Defining the entrepreneurship

Lee and Peterson (2000, p. 402) viewed entrepreneurship as ‘a propensity toward risk-taking, high achievement, or an internal locus of control; entrepreneurs are thought to be leaders of innovation or catalysts who provide the “spark” for economic growth and development’. Thus, Uhlaner *et al.* (2012, p. 2) view entrepreneurship as ‘the pursuit of increasing the value of a business’s assets by seeking out and/or creating new business opportunities’. Business opportunities are key for the entrepreneur as he/she identifies or generates them and then explores them through the small-medium sized enterprises (SME). On the other hand, a person who takes the risk for the firm and (more recently) adds value to the novel products/ services generated is also called an entrepreneur (Chandra, 2018). An entrepreneur (he/she) innovates, identifies, captures, and converts opportunities into much more practical business ideas (Rahman, Ullah and Thomas, 2018). Recently, looking at various definitions of entrepreneurship, some describe entrepreneurship as ‘a process of discovering opportunities’ (Shane and Venkataraman, 2000). According to number of entrepreneurship definitions mentioned in the literature and above, it is obvious that these descriptions highlight ingredients to entrepreneurship such as: venture creation; formation of any kind of self-employment; combining various resources; recognising and exploring opportunities in any given market; applying innovation in various business contexts; and serving/ producing under risk and

uncertainty (Langlois and Cosgel, 1993; Thornton, Ribeiro-Soriano and Urbano, 2011; Chandra, 2018).

Thus, the question of why to become an entrepreneur has been found to be a multi-dimensional phenomenon. Many scholars provided several reasons over the years (Basu, 1998 ; Dana and Dana, 2005 ; Clark and Drinkwater, 2010 ; Chandra, 2018). Aligned with those findings, Haq (2015, p.502) provided a summative statement in his article as:

Non-for-profit motives... self-esteem... desire for conquering new markets and or earning fame through business success in a new venture or filling a gap in the market which could be beneficial for consumers... to keep their family members together and in employment through a coordinated family strategy... and to gain social status in their community.

3.2 Definition of ethnic entrepreneurship

3.2.1 Definition of Immigrant entrepreneurship:

There are various definitions of entrepreneurship. However, the immigrant entrepreneurship definition can be identified as, 'the process of an immigrant who establishes a business activity in a host country (or country he/she where he is seeking settlement or is settled), which is not the immigrant's country of origin' (Khosa and Kalitanyi, 2014, p. 206). In other words, an immigrant who carries out entrepreneurial activities in the host country, not long after the first generation's arrival in the host country, by using personal social networks or by their own initiatives (Chand and Ghorbani, 2011). This can also be viewed as self-employment of an immigrant in a host country. Therefore, business activities operated and owned by the immigrants in the host country can be referred to as an immigrant-owned business (Volery, 2007). On the other hand, according to Tengeh (2013), it is often found that immigrant entrepreneurship links with their respected 'co-ethnic' group of the host country.

3.2.2 The relationship between Immigrant entrepreneurship and Ethnic entrepreneurship.

Furthermore, ethnic entrepreneurship is also viewed as, or often used as, an interchangeable term for immigrant entrepreneurship. However, there is a slight difference between these two definitions (Chand and Ghorbani, 2011; Khosa and Kalitanyi, 2014). The general definition of ethnic entrepreneurship can be stated as ‘a set of network connections and routine patterns of engagement/interaction between the people who share the same national background or migration experience’ (Azmat, 2010, p.41). The term ‘immigrants’ describes the people who arrived into the host country over the past years or within decades and these migrants are often excluded from the ethnic-minority groups who have migrated, settled, and lived in the host country for generations (Volery, 2007). Moreover, the concept of ‘ethnic’ is a much wider term, which includes minorities or immigrants (Azmat, 2010). On the other hand, ethnic minorities are far more likely to be integrated and recognizable in the host society than the immigrants (Khosa and Kalitanyi, 2014). Thus, Immigrant entrepreneurship can be identified or referred to as the early involvement in the process of ethnic entrepreneurship (Azmat, 2010; Khosa and Kalitanyi, 2014). Therefore, this thesis will also use the terms ethnic entrepreneurs and immigrant entrepreneurs interchangeably to investigate the phenomenon.

3.2.3 Operationalised definition of ethnic entrepreneurship

In addition to the above descriptions of immigrant and ethnic entrepreneurship, Tengeh, Ballard and Slabbert (2011, quoted in Khosa and Kalitanyi, 2014, p.206) notes the term ‘minority entrepreneurship’. According to his explanation, scholars have also used the above term to describe the immigrants who conduct entrepreneurial activities. Similarly, Volery (2007) conceptualises the ethnic minority entrepreneurs as immigrants who arrived and settled within decades in the host country and conducted economic activities. Highlighting the similar ‘immigrant’ and ‘economic activities’ in the host country, Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse (2015, p.782) Described the ethnic minority entrepreneurship as ‘Entrepreneurial activity by immigrants in their new home country is often labelled ethnic entrepreneurship’.

Nevertheless, the researcher will use the adopted definition below to describe the ethnic/immigrant entrepreneurship throughout the thesis:

‘The entrepreneurial activities of recent migrants by the means of starting a business or engaging in self-employment’ (Chand and Ghorbani, 2011, p.594).

3.3 Motivation

There have been various studies conducted in order to study the motivations of entrepreneurship over the years (Kirkwood, 2009). Thus, in the case of ethnic entrepreneurs, scholars have identified several factors that could be influential to them becoming entrepreneurs (Basu and Goswami, 1999). For instance, disadvantages of the mainstream job market, being part of an ethnic enclave, cultural disposition, the fact of family members entering the business, underemployment, barriers to upward mobility and support from the institution (Ram and Jones, 2008). These were also categorised as pull or push factors (Kirkwood, 2009). The literature in the various contexts mentioned that mainstream entrepreneurs have been ‘pulled’ into entrepreneurial activities by, for example, ambition, recognitions of opportunities and the inspiration of role models (Chandra, 2018). This could somewhat differ from the ethnic minority entrepreneurs, mainly due to factors such as discrimination and unemployment in the host country, or in other words, they were ‘pushed’ into these activities (Ram, Jones, Villares-Varela, 2017). On the other hand, religious, cultural, socio-historical and economic differences are present within the ethnic minorities who have migrated from the same region (Kirkwood, 2009). The most likely reason for mainstream entrepreneurs to enter into entrepreneurship activities is for financial gain while ethnics look for more than financial gain. It may include the aforementioned factors plus social recognition, political gain, spiritual beliefs and giving back to their co-ethnic community etc. (Haq, 2015). Similarly, Basu and Goswami (1999) found seven factors which could be categorised as ‘pull’ factors: to gain social status, independence, better personal discipline, former business experience, potentially high growth markets, freedom to use their expertise and financial advancement; and four ‘push’ factors: lack of opportunities to find a salaried job, underpaid

jobs, redundancy and discrimination among the minority (South-Asian) community (Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse, 2015).

It was further found that the former (pull) was more influential than the latter to motivate the South Asians to engage in entrepreneurial activities (Basu and Goswami, 1999). These findings somewhat disagree with the previous findings in the literature, such as in Aldrich and Waldinger (1990) and Ram (1994). This is why some scholars critique that the push or pull model cannot explain the complete picture of why these individuals enter into business activities (Jones and Ram, 2013). This is because of the complex nature of the factors that come with ethnicity, which should be determined correctly and viewed in the right perspective (Kirkwood, 2009; Madduma and Watkins-Mathys, 2019).

On the other hand, other factors that could trigger an individual to become an entrepreneur could fall under three categories. Those are factors triggered by the environment, incubator organisations, and influenced by the antecedent entrepreneurial activities (Crump *et al.*, 2015). Environmental influences are generally external and consist of the cultural disposition of the respective social group, institutional support, aspiring role models, and access to capital and funding etc. (Soydas and Aleti, 2015). Developing entrepreneurial skills, promoting or helping them become entrepreneurs, are recognized as incubating organisations (Chandra, 2018). Some of the antecedent entrepreneurial activities can be noted as educational attainment, the circumstances of the family and certain genetic factors (which could especially correlate with skills), intelligence and perception, employment skills and experience etc. (Crump *et al.*, 2015). Similarly, some are involved in entrepreneurship due to training programs (Brunjes and Diez, 2013). Due to unemployment or underemployment, some individuals were pushed to create a new business, which was through necessity (Scholman, Van Stel, and Thurik, 2015), while others were pulled in to create a business to take the opportunity given in the market (Kirkwood, 2009).

3.3.1 Necessity migrant entrepreneurs

In the case of migrant entrepreneurs, migrant individuals of a specific ethnic minority group who start or are involved in business activities caused by job market discrimination or obstacles in the host country, are described as necessity migrant entrepreneurs (Block, Sandner and Spiegel, 2015). Also, the main purpose for these individuals in establishing these business is to survive in the host country (Fairlie and Fossen, 2018). Likewise, conventional small business features cannot be seen in these businesses activities of these migrants, therefore, general success or growth indicators of smaller businesses will not be effectively applicable to the necessity of entrepreneurial business activities (Block and Koellinger, 2009). Thus, these immigrants will be in these businesses because it might be their last chance of survival despite it not being their best option (Basu and Goswami, 1999). There are some characteristics found in the literature which can identified as a necessity entrepreneur. Chrysostome (2010) claims that these migrants became entrepreneurs in an effort to make a living in their host country. Usually these necessity entrepreneurs are immigrants from developing countries (Fairlie and Fossen, 2018). Thus, finding capital is very challenging for them. Generally they are educated in their home country, implying they may not be as educated compared to the host country. They tend to develop relationships based on solidarity among their co-workers who are generally from the same ethnic group (Haq, 2015). Consequently, these co-workers from the same ethnic community offer flexible work to support the necessity entrepreneur; in return they will get the status and recognition among their community. Lastly, these necessity entrepreneurs are generally middle aged, male migrants (Khosa and Kalitanyi, 2014; Chrysostome, 2010).

3.3.2 Opportunity migrant entrepreneurs

Opportunity migrant entrepreneurs on the other hand, are the ones who grab an opportunity in the host country and turn into a business activity, based mainly on their own self-motivation (Short *et al.*, 2010). Generally, mainstream entrepreneurs fall into this category. For instance, many of the entrepreneurs in the US are attracted to establish their own business based on the opportunities that occur in that country (Braunerhjelm and Henrekson, 2013). Thus, business organisations which gained success in their sustainability and operations tend to be opportunity entrepreneurs, compared to necessity entrepreneurs (Thompson, Jones-Evans and Kwong, 2010). Nevertheless, in terms of migrant opportunity entrepreneurs, some characteristics can identify as migrant opportunity entrepreneurs in the literature (Block and Wagner, 2010). Most of these migrant opportunity entrepreneurs hold a professional stature, which allows them to access the financial capital from the financial firms (Short *et al.*, 2010). Likewise, these types of entrepreneurs tend to have a degree qualification from a university in the host country; hence for the most part, they are highly educated (Fuentelsaz *et al.*, 2015). In comparison to necessity entrepreneurs, these opportunity migrant entrepreneurs are usually fluent in the English language (Thompson, Jones-Evans and Kwong, 2010). They not only rely on their co-ethnic employees, but employ mainstream job market employees, and therefore generate job opportunities for the local people as well (Short *et al.*, 2010).

3.4 Success -Perception and Business Performance of minority entrepreneurs

The term 'success' also has no universally accepted definition, particularly when reviewing the literature of entrepreneurship (Walker and Brown, 2004; Drnovsek, Wincent and Cardon 2010). Some claim that success as a concept is multi-dimensional, hence it is complex, integrating different views and aspects of the business and its owner (Fisher, Maritz and Lobo 2014). Success is hard to define as it could represent different meanings in various contexts (Beaver, 2003; Hollen, Lengfeld and Konrad, 2020). In the context of entrepreneurship in particular, generally the entrepreneur may see his/her success in terms of profits; while on the other hand, another might see it as a personal fulfilment (Cho, Moon and Bounkhong, 2019).

Therefore, scholars attempt to define success by using financial or other quantifiable objective measures (for example; sales, return on investment, profit gains, etc.) (King and Levine, 1993). On the other hand, others attempt to define success by using non-financial subjective measures, such as personal development and the achievements of goals etc. (Manzano-Garcia and Ayala-Calvo, 2020). Furthermore, some scholars defined success by using both objective and subjective measures for the definition (Paige and Littrell, 2002). They used measures such as achievement, autonomy, financial gains, and personal income.

Nevertheless, migrant entrepreneurs and their venture related objective measures (particularly performance-related) seemed to be criticized in the literature (Basu and Altinay, 2002). One apparent reason is that they are hesitant to expose financial related data (Rhodes and Butler, 2004). These small ventures do not often consider financial performance as the mark of their success, so these performance-related measures are rather strange for them (Walker and Brown, 2004). This is mainly due to their own views (perceptions) about their business and the reason(s) they are involved in them in the first place (Kotey and Meredith, 1997; Rhodes and Butler, 2004). Instead, these individuals are much more into subjective measures to consider their success (Brockhaus, 1982; Walker and Brown, 2004), such as their religious and cultural beliefs, social status among the community, investing their time and efforts to improve their managerial skills, the individual satisfaction of running a business (Solymossy, 1998; Ryan and Deci, 2000; Walker and Brown, 2004; Madduma and Watkins-Mathys 2019), and asserting that they have placed their personal traits to good use (Ibrahim and Goodwin, 1986, Basu and Goswami, 1999).

3.5 Theories of ethnic entrepreneurship

There are many theories which have attempted to describe ethnic entrepreneurship and its process (Ram and Jones, 2008; Ram, Jones and Villares-Varela, 2017). Still, those theories could not explain the phenomenon completely. These theories can explain the business activity decisions formulated by the single ethnic entrepreneur, similar immigration history and business activity of the ethnic entrepreneur (Ram, Edwards and Jones, 2007). However, most prominent theoretical models in the literature recognize social embeddedness, the interactive model, and the mixed embeddedness model (Jones *et al.*, 2014). On the other hand, these models and concepts adopt two main aspects in the ethnic entrepreneurship literature. Those are the structuralist and culturalist approaches.

3.5.1 Cultural approach:

3.5.1.1 Middleman Minority Theory

The middleman minority theory is explained in the culturalist view and suggests that the ethnic minority individuals become entrepreneurs by using their ‘minority’ status of a particular country as a key determinant (Turner and Bonacich, 1980). These minority groups enter into entrepreneurship by using the political and social exclusion of the host country and achieving (social) recognition from their ‘ethnic capital’ (Volery, 2007). As the name suggests, ‘middleman’ represents the ethnic minority entrepreneurs who operate as intermediate agents, creating bridges between ethnic goods/ services to customers and co-ethnic minority employers to their employees (Bonacich, 1973). Thus, these entrepreneurs are likely to form their business activities in low-entry barrier sectors and ventures which are easy to liquidate. These businesses are not guaranteed to be permanent due to the host country's limited opportunities and discriminations (Morokvasic, 1993). In essence, these entrepreneurs act as negotiators or traders, enabling them to liquidify their business activities easily or change and move if necessary. These ethnic entrepreneurs heavily rely on their family, friends and their ethnic community based social networks for capital, information about the businesses, and labour

(Turner and Bonacich, 1980). It was found that these ethnic entrepreneurs form strong social bonds of harmony and trust, which increase social capital.

On the other hand, as some suggest, this social capital creates a mechanism where numerous resources are dispersed within their community (Aldrich and Waldinger, 1990). Likewise, firms created around these communities mainly present as a market for employing their respective co-ethnics. Thus, some indicate that it operates as enclaves (Wilson and Portes, 1980; Zhou, 2004). Lastly, recent scholarly articles critique the theory in several aspects, such as market conditions, alternatives to employment, host country immigration policies and accessibility to the capital etc. (Volery, 2007).

3.5.2 Structuralist approach

The external environment of the ethnic entrepreneur is influential in start-up business activity; for instance, opportunities available in the host community/country, entry barriers to the labour market, maintaining an excellent social identity and socio-political abundance are named key reasons (Jones *et al.*, 2014). Much more importantly, immigrants/ethnic groups from various countries respond to these factors/forces in their own different ways (Jones and Ram, 2013). Therefore, this approach proposes that groups/individuals are being ‘pushed’ into self-employment where they have no chance of becoming employed. On the other hand, they have been ‘pulled’ from paid employment into self-employment because of rewards and benefits (Borooah and Hart, 1999).

3.5.2.1 Disadvantage theory

Disadvantage theory is rooted in the structural approach. According to this theory, ethnic minority immigrants are considerably 'disadvantaged' in the job market in the host country basically due to the fact of racism and de-industrialisation (Ram and Jones , 2008). Other reasons for this phenomenon are the lack of language and communication skills, experience, discrimination, education and lack of knowledge about the local culture etc. which force (push) them into self-employment (Fatoki and Patswawairi, 2012). The theory views ethnic entrepreneurship not as a sign of success, but as an alternative type of employment (Kirkwood, 2009). Some argue that for this reason, low skilled employment is higher among immigrants than the natives (Ram, 1994). Hence, they further stressed that the earning gap could be linked to ethnic composition (Lofstrom, 2011). Similarly, Jones, McEvoy, and Barratt (1992) found that the South-Asian and Caribbean minority business environment is likely to be exposed to racism just as in everyday life. Entrepreneurs are subject to hostility and resistance from direct customers, and financial institutions such as banks and insurance organisations (Ram *et al.*, 2002). Fluency in English, education, and a reliance on the co-ethnic market significantly impacts their business growth (Jones, Ram and Edwards, 2006; Altinay and Altinay, 2008).

Moreover, Ishaq, Hussain and Whittam's (2010) study of the independent retail sector, or in other words 'corner shops' in Scotland, has found that many of these shopkeepers have experienced racism (verbally and physically). It can be called an occupational hazard for these entrepreneurs, which is a disadvantage when competing with the mainstream business enterprises. According to Jones *et al.* (2014), there is a mismatch between the qualifications of the migrant entrepreneurs and the occupations they follow. Thus, a recent study in the Netherlands (Beckers and Blumberg, 2013) shows that despite being highly socio-culturally integrated as the second generation of immigrants, this does not lead to a better business future. Thus, the labour market and educational discrimination are common disadvantages for the immigrants, and also the fact that racism still exists in various forms (Ishaq, Hussain and Whittam 2010). Moreover, Lassalle and Scott (2017) found that the Brexit process and its uncertainty could trigger further challenges for migrant integration in the UK society and could be even more disadvantageous for migrant entrepreneurs. The high regulatory environment and

immigration rules have profound effects, especially regarding access to the ethnic labour market by Scottish ethnic entrepreneurs (Rahman, Ullah and Thompson, 2018) .

However, the disadvantage theory can help to describe the informal and illegal employment activities, but the theory lacks details explaining the creation or formulation of the immigrant business activities (Brekke and Mastekaasa, 2008).

3.5.2.2 Enclave theory

The ethnic enclave theory also adopts the structuralist view (Forment, 1989). According to the theory, the demand for ethnic goods and services can only be supplied by the co-ethnics who are familiar with the buying preferences and the needs of the ethnic groups, which in turn results in start-up ethnic business activities (Greve and Salaff, 2005). On the other hand, the theory also suggests that these entrepreneurs are based on sophisticated co-ethnic social networks within a self-sustaining ethnic enclave (Rafiq, 1992), yet are limited to its co-ethnicity, location and co-ethnic social structures (Zhou, 2004). There are good examples for these ethnic enclaves such as China town, Peckham and Brixton, where new immigrants could arrive and hide from the foreign environment (Ryan *et al.*, 2008). Thus, these locations also provide more economical business activities for newly arrived immigrants. These enclave societies provide great economic implications for ethnic business activities (Ram, Edwards and Jones, 2007) . Consequently, some of the immigrant entrepreneurs and their co-workers (who are commonly found to be their co-ethnic group) earn and gain more than those who are employed in the main stream corporate economy (Portes and Bach, 1985).

The structuring of enclave economies links traditional concerns with background cultural, historical, and situational influences (Wilson and Portes, 1980). Similarly, Schwartz *et al.*, (2006) investigate the ethnic enclave using acculturation from the point of view of cultural approaches. Johnston, Forrest, and Poulsen (2002) deal with it in light of political perspectives. The ability of certain ethnic groups to create a self-sustaining entrepreneurial class is the basis for the development and vitality of two key mechanisms. Those are ethnic vertical integration

and resource mobilization through ethnic ties. The residential segregation of ethnic groups in urban areas remains an important issue for policymaking in multicultural societies (Ram and Jones, 2008); for instance, in England, with levels of segregation frequently linked to questions of social exclusion and equal treatment (Johnston, Forrest, and Poulson 2002). Zhou (2004) stated that the ethnic enclave provides positive earnings and returns on education and other human capital characteristics to immigrant minority workers. Immigrant workers in the enclave labour market achieve greater returns on human capital than those who participate in the outside economy (Ram, Edwards and Jones, 2007). Notably, residing in ethnic enclaves affects the labour market outcomes of refugees. A key proposition in the theory of ethnic enclave economies is that the enclave opens opportunities for its members which are not easily accessible to society as a whole (Ram, 1994). The enclave housing market, labour market, and capital market partially shelter ethnic group members from competing with other social groups. Thus, it also saves them from discrimination and abuse, because of their ethnic origins, government surveillance and regulation (Zhou, 2004; Jones *et al.*, 2014). In many respects, these boundaries around the enclave provide tangible benefits to group members and seem to offer a positive alternative to assimilation (Logan, Alba and Stults, 2003).

Thus, many of the enclave enterprises based on the informal sector consist of many unregistered firms. These firms could employ illegal immigrants, avoid all tax types, and employ benefits and other government regulations. As a result, in these informal business activities, the methods employed to hire, how the place is run and managed, and the codes of conduct are mainly based on mutual trust and culture (Ram, 1994; Jones, Ram and Edwards, 2006). Breaching these cultural values and trust would be a huge loss for the business and employees (Hyun-soo Kim, 2016). Some argue that these cultural values and mutual trust often reduce the risks associated with informal firms (Ram *et al.*, 2001).

3.5.2.3 Social embeddedness theory

Essentially, the embeddedness approach outlines the nature, depth, and extent of an individual's connection(s) with the environment and its influence on their business activity (Aldrich *et al.*, 1986; Granovetter, 1985; Whittington, 1992). Furthermore, it allows an understanding of these wide-ranging socio-economic factors (such as, political, cultural, structural, and even cognitive) and their influence. Hence these factors could encourage/promote and /or impede the entrepreneurial process/activities (Dacin, Beal and Ventressca, 1999; Karlsson and Dahlberg, 2003). According to Jack and Anderson (2002), the most important things in business, such as resources and access to information, are determined by the entrepreneur's social network position. However, Rath (2006) claims that immigrant entrepreneurs involve their 'ethnically specific economic networks' to enhance or facilitate their entrepreneurial activities. These networks could often provide vital resources to their day to day business activities (Ram, 1994), such as labour, capital, engagement with clients, suppliers, start-up knowledge, etc.(Rath and Kloosterman, 2002). Thus, there are other benefits of social embeddedness. For example, having access to important economic resources, reducing transaction cost, avoiding expensive formal contracts (Ram *et al.*, 2002), and enabling reliable prospects while avoiding regulatory or legal boundaries (Cope, Jack and Rose , 2007; Ram, Edwards and Jones, 2007). Much more specifically, in some cases, the entrepreneur's key input for their business is having relatively cheap and flexible employees, which is true for some of the industry sectors (Ram *et al.*, 2001; Wang and Altinay, 2012), such as manufacturing, retail and catering industries (Arrowsmith *et al.*, 2003; Ram and Jones, 2008). On the other hand, these economic decisions/outcomes are not exclusively rational decisions made by using computations of cost or benefit, but are also affected by being embedded in the comprehensive social structures (McKeever, Anderson and Jack, 2014) . Portes (1995) claims that these 'overarching social structures' that individuals are embedded in, which is a form of network(s) of relations, and interpersonal relations, are built on trust, enforceable norms and mutual expectations. Therefore these wider networks are tied through the diversity of social relationships of the entrepreneurs (Hoang and Antocic, 2003).

Over the years, scholars have claimed that the entrepreneurship phenomenon and its social context and ongoing personal relationships of networks are related to their economic goals

(Sarasvathy and Venkataraman, 2011). Johannisson, Ramirez-Pasillas and Karlsson (2002) conceptualised the social embeddedness further into three different layers in order to explain the phenomenon. These layers later emerged as key research themes around processes, performance implications and structural contexts of embeddedness for the entrepreneurs. Some argue that the embeddedness approach is essential to understanding ethnic minority small businesses and how these business activities enter the mainstream markets/networks (Jones *et al.*, 2014). On the other hand, some argue that attempting to move beyond their co-ethnic market and family ties often hinders their growth and long term viability (Ram and Smallbone, 2003; Rusinovic, 2008).

However, like other theories, there are some critiques for the social embeddedness theory; first some theorists argue that this theory can be stretched to almost anything, which means it becomes pointless (Krippner *et al.*, 2004). The embeddedness theory could link the sociological and economic factors to business activities (McKeever, Anderson and Jack, 2014) . Yet, the theory has a theoretical indefiniteness, mainly because it attempts to combine complex social connections with economic propositions and its effects on entrepreneurial activities (Rusinovic, 2008).The social embeddedness theory made little effort to describe the entrepreneur's self-motivation or energetic mechanisms even though it helped to move social science forward (Halinen and Tornroos, 1998). Kalantaridis (2009) claims that embeddedness does not always help growth and survival of the business, but that being dis-embedded could link to the firm's high performance.

3.6 Ethnic entrepreneurship models and concepts

3.6.1 The interactive model

Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward (1990) introduced the interactive model which attempts to illustrate that the success and growth of ethnic minority businesses depend on various characteristics, rather than one. They further explained that much more complicated and continuous interactions between their ethnic group resources and the host country's opportunity structure are accountable for encouraging entrepreneurs. On the other hand, some suggest that entrepreneurship evolved around supply and demand (Light and Gold, 2000). Similarly, for the ethnic entrepreneurs, it can be assumed that ethnic group characteristics as the supply side and the host country's opportunity structure as the demand side (Volery, 2007).

Nevertheless, this concept attempts to merge both culturalist and structuralist approaches to the phenomenon. They highlight the link with co-ethnic group resources and the related host country's opportunity structure (Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward 1990). Condition(s) of the market, socio-cultural norms, and policies of the government are suggested as the opportunity structure. On the other hand, family bonds and kinship ties which create the social capital are viewed as the co-ethnic resources of the ethnic entrepreneur (Volery, 2007). Therefore, when creating a business venture in a foreign environment there is often a need to interact with these aforementioned dual dimensions. For a newly settled ethnic community, demand for ethnic-specific goods/services becomes a niche market, and only their co-ethnics could supply that (Ram and Jones, 1998). The difference in the culture within the host country and ethnic group is key here as the greater the difference, the greater the demand for the ethnic product/services, and the larger the market for the ethnics (Ram, 1994; Light and Gold, 2000). Likewise, apart from the market size, the opportunities generated and access to such are normally obstructed by the host country's (high)market entry barriers (Aldrich and Waldinger, 1990).

Furthermore, (co-ethnic) social networks and their cultural traditions appear to be characteristics of ethnic resources. Primarily, it assumes that culture influences them to become an entrepreneur (Haq, 2015), where this should not be overstated or mentioned as the only reason. Thus, social networking or inter-relational contacts with their ethnic community and

the family plays a crucial role in their entrepreneurial success. Likewise, the interactive model then summarises that these ethnic resources and any given host country's opportunity structure continuously interact. Therefore, having a solid social network could impact and further improve the opportunity structure (Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward 1990). Furthermore, ethnic strategies could supply solutions during this interaction between these two dimensions. These entrepreneurs face challenges with supplies, customers, financial capital, gathering business information, skills and training, competition, human capital, and political influence (Ram, Edwards and Jones, 2007).

Lastly, there are also critiques to this approach. Apart from its comprehensive theoretical approach to the ethnic entrepreneurship phenomenon, some have criticized its lack of attention on gender and social class (Carter *et al.*, 2015). While other scholars give critiques on methodology (Light and Gold, 2000). Collins *et al.*, (1995), critiques regarding the racialization of ethnic minorities seem insufficient whereby these ethnic entrepreneurs act differently compared to conventional entrepreneurship (Rath and Kloosterman, 2002). Thus, scholars argued that the interactive model neglected the impact of the host country's society on ethnic minority entrepreneurial activities (Light, Bachu and Karageorgis, 1993). For example, non-ethnic social networks may also have an advantage, yet interactive models have ignored this feature. In addition to these criticisms, it largely ignores other important factors such as the host country's banking system and other complex policy frameworks and regulatory bodies (Jones *et al.*, 2014).

3.6.2 The mixed embeddedness model

The mixed embeddedness model was introduced by Kloosterman, Van der Leun and Rath, (1999) in another attempt to explain the ethnic entrepreneurship phenomenon. This also has its roots in the structuralist approach and tries to explain the phenomenon in multi-levels, which, includes market dynamics and the impact of regulation of the host country (Rath and Kloosterman, 2002). Thus, the model stresses the significance of cultural and social factors to the development of economy (Rath, 2006). Likewise, the model considers the entrepreneurial individuals' embeddedness in their social networking, institutional regulatory environment, and the economic and social context of the host country (Kloosterman, Van der Leun and Rath, 1999; Kloosterman, 2010). It is a known fact that these various entrepreneurial business ventures do not appear out of nowhere and therefore this is due to the practice of being embedded in social and cultural activities (Kloosterman, Van der Leun and Rath, 1999).

Furthermore, the model contributes to the understanding that the economic variation creates a considerable number of opportunities from level to level. Thus, these opportunities are locally, regionally, and nationally different (Kloosterman, 2010). Therefore, it should be studied at each level (locally, regionally and nationally) (Ram, Jones and Villares-Varela, 2017). The main assumption in using this model is that the possible entrepreneur should identify any opportunity given and be able to grasp it in a tangible way, where regulatory bodies of the government or barriers to entry to market must not prevent any opportunities offered (Kloosterman, 2010). The entrepreneur's actions are discouraged/facilitated by the cultural practices and much wider institutional environment. This institutional environment includes business and social networks, leading organisational and politico-economic structures (Yeung , 2002). Therefore, mixed embeddedness is viewed as a broad theoretical model for studying ethnic minority entrepreneurship in various levels (micro, meso and macro) (Jones *et al.*, 2014). It stresses the significance of ethnic minority embeddedness in their social networking transactions and resources to being entrenched in broader structures of political, institutional and economic environments (Rath and Kloosterman, 2002). Thus, the institutional context accepts the law and enforcement of new rules and regulations regarding economic activities (Rath, 2006). Therefore, a greater level of regulations in institutional environments, for instance, social

welfare, can sometimes have a negative impact on self-employment (Ram and Smallbone, 2003).

In summary, the model outlines the importance of the individual's strategic link to embeddedness in the social-political and economic environment. It is now a known fact that this mixed embedded model is an advancement of the interactive model (Kloosterman, Van der Leun and Rath, 1999). It suggests that the local economic structure and legal body together strongly influence the formation and growth of SMEs (Rath, 2006).

Nevertheless, the concept has equally been criticized by some scholars. One critique is that it lacks a historical view (Razin, 2002). Thus, the model only considers male-oriented entrepreneurs and their informal activities (Apitzsch, 2004). The concept is not vigorous enough to take the other factors into account (e.g., entrepreneurial motivation, behaviour etc.), being rooted in transnational or diaspora entrepreneurship (Ojo, 2012). According to Razin and Light (1998), differences in urban features could cause spatial variations; particular community sizes and differing from one to another also affects ethnic minority entrepreneurship.

3.7 Ethnic entrepreneurship resources

Resources for business activities can be recognised as capital, and that capital is viewed as value, which helps produce and improve productivity (Kontos, 2004). Ethnic entrepreneurship resources discuss the nature and various types of resources accessible to the particular ethnic group. These are relevant to the current topic, as they contribute to the current theory in order to understand how these ethnic resources are deployed and explored for the sake of economic development (Dana *et al.*, 2020). These resources are vital tools for ethnic minority entrepreneurs as they could significantly help to gain success and minimise the disadvantages faced (Villares-Varela, Ram and Jones, 2018). These ethnic entrepreneurs use five common capitals: financial, social, labour, human and cultural capital. These capitals are significant for these entrepreneurs as they improve the chances for the growth and development, and smooth business activities (Kloosterman, 2010).

Nevertheless, the literature suggests that there are two types of these resources; ethnic resources (Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward, 1990) and class resources (Yoon, 1991). These two types shape the phenomenon in their own different ways.

3.7.1 Social Capital

According to Ryan *et al.* (2008), social capital can be viewed as a social structural function that can produce an advantage; while Putnam (1992) described social capital as ‘connections’ within and in-between the social network and its value creation to the individual. Generally, social capital describes the relationships, connections, and interdependencies among individuals/organisations or groups based on shared trust, respect, and confidence in a reciprocal way (Ram; 1994; Danes *et al.*, 2009; Ivy, Larty and Jack, 2015). Likewise, there are two types overall to the social capital: ‘bridging’ social capital and ‘bonding’ social capital. Bridging social capital means forming the value from the networks outside their ethnic group (Beaudoin, 2011); while bonding social capital is the value formation from or in-between ‘homogenous’ groups (Danes *et al.*, 2009).

However, these social networks developed by using investment strategies to institutionalise these relationships created within the group(s) and turned them as sources/advantage to access other various benefits available for them (Portes, 1995) . There are two key elements to success in social capital: resource quality; and any social network which enables the individual to access the resources (Ryan *et al.*, 2008). In this trusted network within/in-between in their group(s), they exchange things like employment, equipment, goods and loans (tangible) as well as other resources such as business information, social support and apprenticeships etc.(intangible) resources (Ram and Jones, 2008). Woolcock (1998) claims that sharing social capital could improve the relationship between the employees and the ethnic entrepreneurs which is based on trust. Exchanges or interactions within these informal networks are generally known to be trust-based, which makes this exchange process more effective and flexible. Therefore, it sparked a debate that this form of capital has broader applicability than their ethnic society (Ram *et al.*, 2001).

Consequently, being part of a social network(s) is vital for these ethnic entrepreneurs to grow their ethnic business activities. Ethnic networks are closed in nature, which could provide an operational advantage for the members in the group/network compared to the non-members, who usually do not have access to them (Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward, 1990). Community and family are at the centre of these kinds of ethnic, social network(s), and they heavily rely on trust to survive (Ram, 1994). However, these trust relationships could be used as a resource for gaining a competitive advantage (Smith, Wistrich and Haynes, 2001).

On the other hand, Moore *et al.*, (2009) and Hyun-soo Kim (2016) mentioned the negative side of social networks. They argued that social capital could restrict the individual's creativity and limit their freedom. Entrepreneurial activities could also be negatively affected by having strong social networks (Moore *et al.*, 2009). Individuals who are successful with their business activities are often asked to help other group members. Hence, this could affect maintaining their own entrepreneurial activities (Hyun-soo Kim, 2016). Similarly, having strong ties in the social network(s) may have narrowly bound, emotional barriers, and overlapping of information etc. (Granovetter, 1985).

Nevertheless, relational capital is a type of social capital which exists in the form of the amount of trust, respect and reciprocity between the actors (Cousins *et al.*, 2006). Relationships are formed and used as capital to benefit the business activity within the social network that the entrepreneur is embedded in (Yee, 2015). As mentioned before briefly, these ethnic entrepreneurs use special relations and benefit as social capital, which is worth reviewing.

3.7.1.1 Family relations in a business context

One of the main characteristics where family businesses differentiate from non-family businesses is the presence and the influence of the family relationships/members on the business activity. This has a strong influence on how these business activities are managed, organised/governed, and even passed on to the next generation (Aronoff and Ward, 1995; Sageder, Mitter and Feldbauer-Durstmuller, 2018). Family influence and relationships with the business are also known as ‘the concept of familiness’. Familiness is described as a business venture resource and its systems resulting from family interactions (Habbershon, Williams and MacMillan, 2003; Habbershon, 2006). There are apparent benefits, found in the literature, as a result of family interaction with the business and disadvantages (Danes *et al.*, 2009). Similarly, some scholars argue that family interactions help firms navigate towards success (Masuo *et al.*, 2001). These firms use much more subjective success measures; hence firm success is multidimensional (Danes, Loy and Stafford, 2008). However, many small businesses manage to survive because of family benefits, such as family members working without wages or using family assets to gain loans (Danes *et al.*, 2009). Thus, it has also found that family members who do not work for the business also have a significant influence (VanAuken and Werbel, 2006). They not only support financially, but they also support through introducing family values to the business goals when necessary; they positively influence the owner decision making processes; and offer other ways which benefit or interact/advice family business interface (Elizabeth and Baines, 1998). Exposure to a family business atmosphere can develop unique tacit knowledge (Williams Jr and Mullane, 2019). The particular owner and his family characteristics affect business income, growth, and overall profitability (Rowe, Haynes and Bentley, 1993). Some argue that family businesses also have faster access to problem-solving and allow faster adaptation to change. Danes *et al.*, (2009) defined these kinds of benefits/resources as ‘Family Capital’.

3.7.1.2 Supplier relationship

Developing a good supplier relationship with the customer is vital for these ethnic minority businesses and its importance has been mentioned in the literature (Cannon *et al.*, 2010). Many of these ethnic minority businesses employ informal relationships with the suppliers. These relationships could also be explained by a psychological contract, which means looking after each other's' needs while the business exchange occurs (Hill *et al.*, 2009). In other words, it is mutually beneficial to both parties. The small business literature also recognises the significance and impact of the supplier relationship (Wang and Altinay, 2012). Cultural aspects could also influence social recognition and reputation (Samaratunge and Nyland, 2006; Madduma and Watkins-Mathys, 2019). Hence, it can argued that these informal relationships tend to be maintained by long-term interaction and maintaining a good reputation (Bendixen and Abratt, 2007).

3.7.1.3 Employee relationship

There are various explanations regarding the firm-employee relationship. Traditionally, in the management literature, the discipline that often deals with 'managing people at work' is known as Human Resource Management (HRM) (Wapshott and Mallett, 2015 p.8). According to Marlow (2006, p.467), HRM is viewed as a 'managerial approach aimed at re-ordering the employment relationship to ensure employee efforts were strategically focused on achieving organisational performance and competitiveness in increasingly volatile markets'.

Thus, in the small business literature, some scholars stressed that employee relations or HRM practices are relatively under-researched; hence, sufficient empirical or conceptual researches are needed to highlight the role of HRM as a managerial approach, particularly in the UK (Markusen, 2003). Nevertheless, this thesis focuses on ethnic minority entrepreneurship and their small ventures. In the case of ethnic minority small ventures, the literature suggests that, unlike mainstream small ventures, ethnic minority entrepreneurs manage their employee relationships on an informal basis (Ram, Edwards and Jones, 2007). Thus, scholars argue that informality works for these businesses because it allows flexibility while they operate, and at

the same time, it enables them to address challenges and opportunities (Wapshott and Mallett, 2015). Woolcock (1998) claims that sharing social capital could improve the relationship between the employees and the ethnic entrepreneurs, which is generally based on trust. They manage this trust relationship by employing family members and co-ethnic members (see the labour capital section). Co-ethnic culture also plays an important role in managing these employer-employee relationships (Lareau and Weininger, 2003).

3.7.1.4 Customer relationship

Customer relationship is vital for any business activity as it can be used as a source of competitive advantage (Haq *et al.*, 2021) and to gain the economic benefits in retaining them. Customer relationships can be formed as social and/or instrumental relationships (Victor, Martin, and Zubair, 2012; Haq, 2015). Nevertheless, besides those types, ethnic minority entrepreneurs view customers as the most important business element in their business (Gremier and Gwinner, 2008; Haq *et al.*, 2021). Thus, similar to the family business context, these families involved in businesses tend to develop superior customer relationships, which in turn increases their competitive advantage which results from high customer loyalty, views of their trustworthiness and general goodwill in the relationship (Esmark and Noble, 2016). Customer relationships and its importance are found in the literature of relationship marketing (Gilboa, Seger-Guttmann and Mimran, 2019). Gronroos (1996, p.7) defined relationship marketing in the following terms:

‘Relationship marketing is to identify and establish, maintain, and enhance relationships with customers and other stakeholders, at a profit, so that the objectives of all parties involved are met, and that is done by a mutual exchange and fulfilment of promises’.

In line with the definition, popular topics on relationship marketing are commonly based on customer interaction, customer satisfaction, customer trust and loyalty (Orth and Green, 2009). The main focus of this thesis is to find out how these ethnic entrepreneurs enhance trust and

loyalty in their retail businesses. Therefore, the literature below will extensively focus on loyalty and its related topics only.

3.7.1.4.1 Loyalty

According to Oliver (1999, p.34), loyalty is viewed as:

‘a deeply held commitment to rebuy or repatronize a preferred product/service consistently in the future, thereby causing repetitive same-brand or same brand-set purchasing, despite situational influences and marketing effort having the potential to cause switching behaviour’.

The loyalty of a customer to a particular business activity is usually demonstrated in a number of ways; for instance, repeat purchasing, the tendency to spend a good amount of money on the business, and positive word-of-mouth are commonly found in the literature (Orth and Green, 2009). Thus, there are antecedents of loyalty (El-Manstrly, 2016). These various antecedents are significant for the topic as it can enhance loyalty. Most common antecedents are trust (Ganesan, 1994); customer satisfaction (Oliver, 1999); service (Haq *et al.*, 2021); image and reputation (De Wulf, Odekerken-Schroder and Lacobucci, 2001). These are also called loyalty determinants (Orth and Green, 2009).

a. Trust

Trust is one of the most important, yet critical factor to impact relationships significantly (Moorman, Deshpande and Zaltman, 1993; Morgan and Hunt, 1994). The level of (‘perceived’) trust between these relationships is recognised as a vital building block and can found in most trust related models (Wilson, 1995). Creating trust between customer and the salesperson (most of the time, the business owner is the one who serves their (regular) customer as they actively work in the shop) has been extensively mentioned in the literature over the years (Morgan and

Hunt, 1994; Orth and Green, 2009). Therefore, trust is regarded as one of the main elements of developing relationships and is included in many relationship models and concepts (Ganesan, 1994; Orth and Green, 2009). According to Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol (2002, p.17), trust is defined as ‘the expectation held by the consumer that the service provider is dependable and can be relied on to deliver on its promises’. Thus, consumer trust appeared to develop with retailers in two distinguishable ways. Those are Front line employee (FLE) behaviours and Management policy practices (MPP). Trustworthiness is regarded as an ‘antecedent’ to the existence of trust (Anderson and Narus, 1990) . Therefore, again according to Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol (2002, p. 17) trustworthiness is defined as including ‘Front line employee (FLE) behaviours and Management policy practices (MPP) that indicate a motivation to safeguard consumer interest’. It has been found that observable behaviours and management practices are important for both FLE and MPP trustworthiness. These observable behaviours and practices can further be categorised to operational benevolence, problem-solving orientation and operational competence (Orth and Green, 2009).

a. 1 Operational benevolence

Operational benevolence can be viewed as behaviours that highlight the primary motivation to put the consumer’s interest first rather than self-interest (Ganesan, 1994). Further, having a benevolent motivation is not enough, but it should be visible/ demonstrate in MPPs and FLE behaviours clearly, which is central to the idea of favouring the customer interest, even if this behaviour(s) or practices comes at a cost for the business (Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol, 2002; Gummesson, 2008) This benevolent behaviour gives important (or diagnostic) evidence of trust (Orth and Green, 2009). These types of business behaviours tend to indicate limiting self-serving opportunism - ‘Self-interest seeking with guile’ (Williamson, 1975, p.6 as quoted in Morgan and Hunt 1994, p.25); or prioritising to make money, willingness to assume fiduciary responsibilities and positive consumer motivations (Ganesan, 1994; Morgan and Hunt, 1994).

a. 2 Problem- solving orientation

Problem-solving orientation is defined as ‘ the consumer’s evaluation of FLE and management motivations to anticipate and satisfactorily resolve problems that may arise during and after a service exchange’ (Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol 2002, p.18). Problems commonly occur during the service encounter or after the exchange (Orth and Green, 2009). Interestingly, problem-solving perceptions are influenced by the promptness, and the nature of the company effort (Goodwin and Ross, 1992). Failure of a problem-solving in-service encounter is more significant to customer dissatisfaction than tangible problems, such as limited stock (Smith, Bolton and Wagner, 1999). Therefore, Hart, Heskett, and Sasser (1990, p.151) note that ‘every customer’s problem is an opportunity for the company to prove its commitment to service (and build trust)—even when the company is not to blame’.

a. 3 Operational competence

Mayer, Davis and Schoorman (1995 as quoted in Orth and Green, 2009, p.249) observed that ‘operational competence is that group of skills, abilities, and characteristics that enable a party to perform a task within a specific domain effectively’. Similarly, operational competent FLE and MPPs should show the visible behaviours of ‘service in action’ (Orth and Green, 2009). For example, front line employees may have enough abilities or knowledge to perform their duties; but, if he/she does not translate this valuable knowledge into observable behaviour, it is less likely to be treated as an indication of trustworthiness (e.g. helping a customer in finding a desired flavour/style of a product) (Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol, 2002). In regards to MPPs, customers are less likely to make competency judgements unless it has been shown by visible practices (e.g. providing enough checkout machines to reduce the waiting time) (Orth and Green, 2009).

b. Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is regarded as the main outcome of customer and seller relationships (Anderson and Sullivan, 1993). According to Orth and Green, (2009, p.250) customer satisfaction is viewed as ‘consumers’ assessment of the extent to which retailer performance on specific dimensions meets or exceeds prior expectations’. Various scholars mentioned customer satisfaction and their loyalty towards the businesses (Oliver 1999; Sirdemukh, Singh and Sabol, 2002). Thus, according to Ball, Coelho and Machas (2004), higher customer satisfaction leads to higher customer loyalty. Thus, there is also a well-established link between customer satisfaction and customer trust towards the business entity. Some scholars suggest customer trust increases their confidence in the business, which eventually leads to satisfaction and vice versa (El-Manstrly, 2016). In the retail context, service, product quality, price and convenience have been noted as influencing customer satisfaction. In these factors, customer service is vital for the ethnic small businesses as they tend to make an effort and create a competitive advantage for their businesses over the other variables in the highly saturated retail market (Haq *et al.*, 2021).

c. Customer service

As mentioned before, having good customer service skills has the potential to achieve long-term business success (Haq *et al.*, 2021). Some scholars view customer service as a unique source for competitive advantage and explain it by using Resource-based theory (RBT) (Clottey, Collier and Stodnick , 2008). Personalised customer service consists of customer orientation and customer centricity, being empathetic and patient with the customer, and letting the customer make the buying decision (freedom of buyer decision making)(Haq *et al.*, 2021). Huang and Ha (2020) argue this form of personalised customer service will lead to better customer satisfaction. It is also a great driver of customer loyalty and retention (Ram, Jones and Villares-Varela, 2017). Brown *et al.* (2002, p. 111) define customer orientation as ‘a retail frontline salesperson’s focus on meeting customer needs in performing their job responsibilities’. In other words, the concept focuses on customer satisfaction in the long term and over the achievement of short-term sales targets and can be applied at both firm and

individual level (Brown *et al.*, 2002). Equally, customer centricity is defined as ‘a customer-centric enterprise that places the demands and wishes of each customer in the centre of value creation’ (Tseng and Piller, p.3). Thus, focusing on a customer-centric approach will lead to customer satisfaction (Shah *et al.*, 2006), and strong customer loyalty (Habel *et al.*, 2020).

On the other hand, these ethnic retail enterprises demonstrate empathy as a part of their personalised customer service. According to Wieseke, Geigenmuller and Kraus (2012, p.317) empathy is defined as ‘a person’s intellectual understanding of the internal state of another person’. Similarly, some scholars view empathy as ‘perspective-taking’, which allows an individual to understand another person’s point of view, anticipate his or her reaction and to deliver their (perceived) needs, opinions or motivations (Devoldre *et al.*, 2010). These ethnic entrepreneurs tend to show their empathy as an aim for satisfying the customer (Haq *et al.*, 2021). Indeed, customer satisfaction will eventually lead to customer retention and loyalty (Anderson, 1998; Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003). Ethnic culture could also influence a demonstration of empathy (Parasuraman, Berry and Zeitbaml 1991; Beatty *et al.*, 1996). According to Hagedoorn *et al.*, (1999, p.310) patience is defined as ‘the act of waiting optimistically’. Thus, developing patience has also been viewed as a skill in service (Beatty *et al.*, 1996). Parasuraman, Berry and Zeitbaml (1991) claimed that it is related to customer satisfaction, hence to customer retention. Lastly, freedom of buying or letting the customer make the buying decision has appeared to be a part of their personalised customer service. This freedom of buying can also be regarded as collaborative selling. The main indication of this type of selling is through giving the correct product information and allowing these customers to make their decision (on buying). Thus, appears that they do not greatly believe in traditional hard selling techniques, which are considered as a ‘shotgun salesperson ’ approach towards the customer, where these type of selling approaches ignore customer needs and offer very little care after-sales (Alessandra and Barrera, 1993; Haq *et al.*, 2021).

d. Image and Reputation

d. 1 Image

Bernstein (1984, as quoted in da Camara, 2011. p. 48) observes corporate image as ‘feelings and beliefs about a certain company that exists in the minds of its audiences’. In other words, having several associations in memory about a particular company (Gray and Balmer, 1998) . These mental associations could be related to price, product, service and even atmosphere (Orth and Green, 2009). Therefore some argue that the corporate image resides mentally with their respected stakeholders. The image can be generated relatively quicker through changing programs or communication (Orth and Green, 2009). It is then linked with someone’s current and latest beliefs about a particular company, rather than the long-term perspective of a company (da Camara, 2011). The long term perspective is related to reputation.

d.2 Reputation

Fombrum and Van Riel (1997, as quoted in Mella and Gazzola, 2015 p.41) define business reputation by stating that:

‘a corporate reputation is a perceptual representation of a company’s past actions and future prospects that describe the firm’s overall appeal to all of its key constituents when compared with other leading rivals’.

In other words, an interpretation of a particular organisation’s behaviour over a long period (da Camara, 2011). Thus, reputation is more durable than it seems and can perform as a goodwill support and avoid negative distrust with the company (Melewar, 2003). Customers refer to reputable companies with the characteristics of being credible, responsive, reliable and trustworthy. Therefore, some argue that reputation is important and is regarded as building customer trust over the long term. Furthermore, maintaining a good set of ethics leads to maintaining a good reputation, which is vital for an organisation’s survival in the long term (Mella and Gazzola, 2015). According to Miesing and Preble (1985, as quoted in Mella and

Gazzola 2015, p.41) ‘ethics are frameworks for human conduct that relate to moral principles and attempt to distinguish right from wrong’. Therefore some argue that ethics could essentially gain customer trust (Azmat and Zutshi, 2012). Trust is an antecedent to loyalty (Orth and Green). Then it can be argued that practising good ethics will lead to gaining trust, hence loyalty, over time (Mella and Gazzola, 2015). Thus socio-cultural influence could also impact business reputation, especially for family businesses (Zellweger *et al.* 2013), because these businesses are not only making decisions for financial achievements but also achieving socio-emotional goals. Hence, these businesses often consider their family reputation along with their business activities (Sageder, Mitter and Feldbauer-Durstmuller, 2018).

3.7.2 Human Capital

Becker (2009) described human capital as ‘knowledge and skills collected by any given individual’s learning process to enhance productivity’; whereas Armstrong (2006, p.14) defined the concept as ‘individuals who create, retain and practice skills and knowledge and generate intellectual capital’. Similarly, Light and Gold (2000) describe in any investment made by individuals’ for their productivity; whereas the term productivity means an individual’s capability for ‘adding value’ by doing their work (Bhatti and Zaheer, 2014). There are many forms of human capital available (Sanders and Nee, 1996). However, the most primary examples for human capital can be noted as work experience, education and apprenticeship (Becker, 2009). This form of capital increases the efficiency and productivity for business ventures, as well as for the entrepreneurs who can eventually grow their business into bigger ventures (Basu and Goswami, 1999). Thus, access to the information, enhanced labour market experience and participation, fluency in the host country language, and job-related training and skills are stressed in the human capital view of ethnic minority entrepreneurship (Basu, 1998; Borjas, 1992). Human capital also improves the motivation to become entrepreneurs (Reeves and Ward, 1984). Consequently, human capital is vitally important and affects the entrepreneurs, depending on how they gain and use them to survive and grow (Rauch *et al.*, 2009; Unger *et al.*, 2011). Thus, family influence could also help to gain specific knowledge (Danes *et al.*, 2009). For instance, having exposure to the family

business background could also help individuals gain necessary skills and knowledge that is hard to write down or codify (Habbershon, 2006; Danes *et al.*, 2009). This form of human capital is called ‘tacit’ knowledge (Dessi *et al.*, 2014).

According to Li, Savage and Warde (2008), increasing human capital tends to improve the financial capital, which allows them to gain social capital. Thus, human capital, gained through higher education in the ethnic groups, tends to increase the chance of involving them in entrepreneurship (Boyd, 1990) and improves the possibility of growth and success (Basu, 1998). Contrary to this view; some claim that higher education could lead them to seek paid employment (Ram and Smallbone, 2003; Clark and Drinkwater, 2010). Therefore, work experience and educational achievements are not enough to explain why/how these minorities switch from one employment to another or become entrepreneurs. However, the value of education is mentioned often in the literature as a complement to the ethnic entrepreneurship as it could promote entrepreneurship growth and development (Basu, 1998).

3.7.3 Financial Capital

The element of financial capital attempts to explain accumulated wealth among the members of ethnic groups and their entry into the host country's financial resources (Schmitt-Rodermund and Silbereisen, 2008). Developing a business idea into a venture involves start-up funds and other essential financial capitals to minimise the barriers and risks (Ram *et al.*, 2002). However, access to finance for the minorities and their small ventures in their host country (for example, accessing bank loans) seems to be much harder than the mainstream entrepreneurs (Ram and Smallbone, 2003). To overcome this barrier, ethnic entrepreneurs look for alternative methods to gain financial capital, such as their social network (often their family members and friends) (Kraybill, Nolt and Wesner, 2010). According to the theory of ‘credit rationing under asymmetric information’ this explains the inability to access the sources of credits, basically low track records and other related issues, like high risk (or in other words moral hazard) (Stiglitz and Weiss, 1981). The literature recognized that these minority entrepreneurs are

being discriminated against in accessing the host country's financial credit market (Curran and Blackburn, 1994; Ram *et al.*, 2002).

Nevertheless, some scholars argued that is not caused by discrimination, hence ethnicity had nothing to do with limiting access to, or creating barriers for the credit resources (Fraser, 2009). Likewise, others claimed that these ethnic minority business activities being refused access to financial resources (for instance from banks), is based on non-ethnic risk factors, such as lacking a solid business plan or language skills (Smallbone *et al.*, 2003). Further evidence suggests that other non-enterprise or an individual's capital requirements (due to their cultural or social situations in the host or their home country) also push their financial resources to the edge (Ram *et al.*, 2002). Comparison studies have shown that one ethnic group in the host country may struggle more than another group to access finance, particularly in the initial stages of the business (Ram and Jones, 2008).

3.7.4 Cultural Capital

According to Light and Gold (2000), cultural capital viewed is as a 'class resource' rather than a 'materialistic resource'. Some view this as cultural capital, an asset which symbolizes cultural value (Throsby, 1999). This could be music, food or cuisine, fashion, art and literature etc. (Light and Gold, 2000). Those types of cultural knowledge are interpreted as cultural capital, hence, it is used for economic purposes or to an individuals' advantage for increasing their business network or welfare (Waldinger, 1986). Generally, cultural capital is gained through the family or by schooling (Habbershon, Williams and MacMillan, 2003; Danes *et al.*, 2009). Similarly, when compared to human capital, this could lead to an enhancement of the entrepreneur's productivity and growth; moreover, cultural capital may lead to prestige or recognition, which could ultimately gain more jobs or personal contacts and other personal benefits like marriage (Light and Gold, 2000; Samaratunge and Nyland 2006). Thus, inherent in cultural capital, especially habits passed down due to being part of the culture or other cultural dispositions, could play an important role for pursuing success (Bourdieu and Passeron, 1979). Furthermore, culture could potentially also have economic values that could

eventually lead to generating profit and a competitive advantage for individuals such as entrepreneurs (Horvat, Weininger and Lareau, 2003).

On the other hand, motivation for an entrepreneur's business activities, ethnic cohesion, access, and utilising of ethnic resources, such as finance, can differentiate cultural diversity among ethnic groups (Ram, Jones and Villares-Varela, 2017). This also ultimately leads to variation in the performance of their business activities (Basu and Altinay, 2002). Furthermore, in line with this argument, their entrepreneurial activities could benefit from their unique cultural factors such as, commitment, reliance on their family and ethnic networks, and a good work ethic (particularly Chinese and South Asians) (Metcalf, Modood and Virdee, 1996; Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse, 2015). However, others suggest that these cultural factors could also hinder the growth of their entrepreneurial activities (Basu and Altinay 2002; Nathan and Lee, 2013).

3.7.5 Labour Capital

There are two dimensions for ethnic-centred labour capital when attempting to explain the phenomenon. The first dimension is that of employing ethnic labour; and the second is the circumstances that occur after the succession of the ethnic entrepreneur. Minority enterprises and their collective resources, like labour, business information, and necessary capital from their co-ethnic group, are particularly important when forming the business (start-up stage). Hence, it is vital for survival and existence (Waldinger, 1986; Ram *et al.*, 2001). Through employing family members (Hoffman, Hoelscher, and Sorenson, 2006; Danes *et al.*, 2009) or members from their co-ethnic community, these ethnic entrepreneurs attempt to develop a 'trust' relationship (Ram, 1994; Ram and Jones 2008). These relationships are viewed as an operational advantage for entrepreneurs, such as privacy and efficient communication (Pearson, Carr and Shaw, 2008). Culture could also contribute to building good long-lasting employee-employer relationships (Haq, 2015). For instance, being able to speak the same language and sharing similar cultural values or norms may be beneficial to managing these employees effectively and at the same time, using them to develop a good relationship with the

customer (Lareau and Weininger, 2003; Altinay, Saunders and Wang, 2014). Thus, this could also pave the way to employment for newly arrived migrants (Zhou, 2004). Being employed by an ethnic economy, these employees exploit opportunities and gain experience for their own growth (Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward, 1990).

The second dimension occurs, as mentioned above, when succession takes place. For instance, Asian firms are likely to operate and survive by consistent participation and contribution of their family members (Ram *et al.*, 2001; Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse, 2015). Therefore, family integration in the business is vital for the ethnic entrepreneur as it helps towards the sustainability of the venture (Kidwell, Hoy and Ibarreche, 2012). However, some found it could also lead to failure (Danes *et al.*, 2009), as families can influence the owner's decision-making process (Elizabeth and Baines, 1998). There are other factors such as generational differences and conflicts which may also influence the business towards a decline (Griffeth, Allen and Barrett, 2006). Likewise, and this claim is backed up by some scholars such as Jones and Ram (2013), the second generation of ethnic minorities minimise their involvement in entrepreneurship activities as they seek employment in the mainstream job market. However, low income and long hour working patterns have contributed to this being labelled as 'less attractive' for the younger generation (Clark and Drinkwater, 2010).

3.8 Conceptual framework

Using Mixed embeddedness model for the development of conceptual framework for this study and its justification.

It is evident that looking at the overall theories and concepts cannot fully explain the phenomenon of ethnic minority entrepreneurship. For instance, the middleman theory explains the entrepreneurial activities of minority ethnic individuals who create a link between the majority of society and ethnic minority communities in a given country (Bonacich, 1973). Generally, this is seen as describing an ethnic minority entrepreneur with an opportunity-seeking attitude; hence it does not include the necessity ethnic entrepreneurs (Kloosterman and Rath, 2001). On the other hand, the interactive model explains and is based on entrepreneurial economic opportunities, which are generated due to cultural differences between any given ethnic community and majority host society (Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward, 1990). Consequently, these economic opportunities are equally available and accessible for all. But, ethnic minority entrepreneurs may have a potential advantage over others due to their better understanding of cultural differences between the mainstream society and ethnic community. Equally, within the structuralist view, these ethnic minority individuals are not described as they have made a choice. Instead, theorists argue that they enter into entrepreneurship due to the need to survive or to avoid potential unemployment, discrimination, and other factors that restrict them from accessing the labour market in the host country (Borooah and Hart, 1999). Therefore, the researcher needed a better explanation for the phenomenon, covering almost all the aspects of ethnic minority entrepreneurship. As a result, the researcher considered the mixed embeddedness model to answer the main research question, as justified below.

The mixed embedded model is suggested by Kloosterman, Van der Luen and Rath (1999) in a study of migrant economic activities in Netherland. Despite being critiqued by some scholars, who highlight that the model is too structuralistic, this is, to date, one of the significant contributions to ethnic entrepreneurship (Barberis and Solano, 2018). The mixed embeddedness model gained the attention of scholars over the other theoretical and models, mainly because it recognises the entrepreneurial activities and their processes in the boundaries of the framework, in any defined context (Rath and Kloosterman, 2002; Rath, 2006). These

scholars viewed the concept as the ‘concrete embeddedness’ of entrepreneurial minorities and their economic activities established in social, economic, institutional and politically distinctive conditions in the host country. In other words, it allows for an analysis of the ‘crucial interplay’ between institutional, economic and social settings (Kloosterman, Van der Luen and Rath, 1999). Thus, the model grasps the importance of socio-cultural instruments to the development of economic activities (Rath, 2006). It is useful in studying the ethnic group dynamics in various contexts that the entrepreneur is embedded in.

Similarly, the mixed embeddedness model puts entrepreneurship in social networks, institutions and various market conditions (Kloosterman, 2010). Interactions of these instruments in micro, meso, macro stages of the entrepreneur's operating environment explain how this influences the entrepreneur and their outcomes (Yeung , 2002;). Thus, Ojo (2012) claims it can be used to examine the entrepreneur’s outcomes and processes. On the other hand, the model could reveal the significance of cultural dynamics, ethnically based social ties, and their relevance to the entrepreneur's survival and business activities (Barberis and Solano, 2018). Furthermore, it questions how the customer relationship marketing is explained in the mixed embeddedness model. Customer relationship can be viewed as a social capital of the ethnic entrepreneur who is socially embedded in the operating environment. Hence, customer relationship can be viewed as a social connection to the ethnic entrepreneur (Tang, 2015). Then, there is customer relationship marketing related concepts such as trust and loyalty. Therefore, the aforementioned micro level analysis (individual level) and meso (opportunity structure) and macro analysis(institutional embeddedness) will enable the researcher to answer the main research question; *‘How do Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance the trust and loyalty of their customers within the retail grocery businesses in UK?’*

Furthermore, the mixed embeddedness model notes that minority entrepreneurs rely on their social networks, but also that the legal and regulation bodies play a vital role in shaping their businesses activities (Kloosterman, 2010). When analysing this, social embeddedness of the minority entrepreneur is at the ‘micro’ (individual) level of the model and, indeed it enables them to identify the opportunities and economic improvement (Jones *et al.*, 2014). Thus, the phenomenon of ethnic minority entrepreneurship and its outcomes is affected by the

entrepreneur's economic and social context they are embedded in, as they did not appear from a vacuum (Barberis and Solano, 2018).

Opportunity structures are presented in the 'meso' level of the entrepreneurial environment. The phenomenon of ethnic entrepreneurship is mainly based on these opportunity mechanisms within the country/region of the host country which these individuals are embedded in (Kloosterman, 2010). This mechanism/structure allows market access opportunities and even enables creating service(s) and product(s) as well. Thus, these opportunities and their availability are generally regulated by the host country's institutional or legal factors, which can be examined locally, regionally, or nationally (Kloosterman and Rath, 2001; Ram, Jones and Villares-Varela, 2017). Moreover, the entrepreneur's opportunities are only seized when barriers to entry and government regulation bodies enable them to do so and play a crucial role in supporting these individuals to establish their business activities (Kloosterman Van der Leun and Rath, 1999). Recognition of opportunity by the entrepreneur and his/her opportunity may be promoted or obstructed by their social ties, cultural views or politico-economic structures in the host country (Yeung, 2002).

The wider 'macro' level of the model looks at such factors as government regulatory and legal boundaries of the host country and its impact on the minority entrepreneur and their ownership to their business activities from an economic standpoint. For instance, allowing any shops to open all day, seven days a week, in the UK which, in turn, allowed main stream supermarkets to have an advantage in operating their retail network twenty four hours. Consequently, this forced small ethnic retail businesses to close or have a similar outcome (Ram and Jones, 2008).

On the other hand, paying a low wage to staff, justified by the government minimum wage act (1998) is commonly found in Asian migrant firms in the UK (Arrowsmith *et al.*, 2003), particularly, in the catering and clothing sector (Jones, Ram and Edwards, 2006). This could explain why British born Asians move away from being employed by these migrant firms (Haq, 2015), resulting in recruitment issues, which then becomes an illegal immigrant's paradise (Ram, Edwards and Jones, 2007). Other characteristics such as moral values could be seen as ambiguous in these informal sectors (Jones, Ram and Edwards, 2006).

Moreover, despite undermining the influence of regulatory bodies on migrant entrepreneurs, recent government policies have been brought in to encourage ethnic entrepreneurship in the mainstream formal sector (Ram, Jones and Villares-Varela, 2017). This seems to be working as there is some evidence in the literature that ethnic minority entrepreneurial activities can recently be found in high value sectors in the UK (Ram and Smallbone, 2003; Clark and Drinkwater, 2010). Therefore, some called this duality of ethnic minority entrepreneurship a ‘two-track affair’ (Ram and Smallbone, 2003; Barberis and Solano, 2018). Thus, South Asian minorities are starting to appear in these sectors as well (Haq, 2015).

Even though these UK policies seemed to be changing in favour of the ethnic minority entrepreneurs in the UK, other operating factors, such as the sustainability of these minority firms, have still not been achieved successfully (Ram and Jones, 2008). Thus, these ethnic business ventures heavily rely on either financial capital or human capital. They depend on their co-ethnic community and or family to obtain these types of capital in order to survive (Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse, 2015). Similarly, these ethnic entrepreneurs are more likely to choose labour-demanding entrepreneurial activities rather than capital-demanding entrepreneurial activities (Jones, Mascarenhas-Keyes and Ram, 2012). While on the other hand, higher educational qualifications/attainment in the South Asian ethnic entrepreneurs, particularly Indians, positively impact their business activities in the UK (Haq, 2015). Thus, some argue that the younger generations of Asians and other racial backgrounds are involved in the entrepreneurial activities because of the opportunities given in the host country rather than necessity (Crump *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3.9 Summary

A comprehensive literature review has been presented in this chapter. However, drawing from the ethnic entrepreneurship theories and concepts, it has found that many of these theories, and some of the models, cannot fully explain the phenomenon. However, the researcher found that the mixed embeddedness model has the potential for explaining the phenomenon (such justification can be found in the theoretical framework section). Furthermore, how is the customer relationship marketing explained in the mixed embeddedness model? Customer relationship can be viewed as a social capital of the ethnic entrepreneur who is socially embedded in the operating environment. Therefore, customer relationship can be viewed as a social connection to the ethnic entrepreneur. Therefore, this study uses two concepts as a conceptual framework to answer the main research question of *'How do Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance the trust and loyalty of their customers within the retail grocery businesses in UK?'*. Hence, the researcher expects to contribute to ethnic minority entrepreneurship and customer relationship marketing disciplines in this thesis.

Chapter 4: Methodology

4.0 Introduction

This chapter defines the main philosophical assumptions that are commonly found in the business research, before describing and justifying the main philosophical view adopted for this research: 'Interpretivism'. The next section delivers the details of the employed research approach, the research strategy, the choice of research methods, sampling strategy, collection of the data, and its analysis and techniques. Lastly, along with the strengths and weaknesses of the research design, ethical considerations will also be discussed.

4.1 Research philosophy

Generally, the research methodology contains the choices and justification of the researcher's philosophical stance, cases for study, method(s) for collecting the data, analysis of these data and other decisions that paved the way to execute and plan the study (Silverman, 2011). In other words, it summarises the theory of 'how the study should be conducted', which consists of the philosophical and theoretical assumptions it is based on, and the implications for the adopted method(s) (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). Therefore, it is necessary to justify the philosophical stance that the researcher has adopted for this study as this defines the entire methodological approach for this research.

4.1.1 Positivism

Auguste Comte (1798-1857), a French philosopher, first introduced and defined the positivist paradigm - a worldview which is recognised in research methods as the 'scientific method of investigation'. Further, Comte (1856) suggested that the observation, experiment and experience based on reason(s) could be the foundation for understanding the behaviour of humans and the world around them. Therefore, this is the only valid means of extending the knowledge and understanding (Hasan, 2016). In its extreme, the positivist (or in other words scientific method) goes through a mechanism of experimentation that explores answers to the questions and observations (Baert and Rubio, 2008). It is normally used to examine the interrelationship of the cause and effect by default. It is the most preferable worldview for the purpose of research, which attempts to understand the observations in a basis of measurable facts or entities (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2015). A research within the positivist paradigm depends on the deductive approach, which involves generating hypotheses, testing these hypotheses, mathematical equations/formulas, mathematical expressions, and extrapolations to draw conclusions. Positivist research aim to deliver explanations, predictions and facts based on the quantifiable outcome (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017).

However, one of the characteristics that appears in the literature about positivism is that the theory is universal and can be made 'law-like generalisations' throughout the contexts (May and Williams, 2002). Thus, positivism believes that the knowledge/ truth is available 'out there' and is to be revealed by conducting research, debating about the context and its importance or general assumption that, context is irrelevant. A positivist recognises that the cause and effect is distinguished from each other. It could be separable analytically (Baert and Rubio, 2008), and the assumption of the results of the research is quantifiable (Aliyu *et al*, 2014). Moreover, positivism believes that the theories can regulate and/or foresee the outcomes; that the research should be investigated under a scientific method, as mentioned above; it should rely on generating and testing of those hypothesis; and employ empirical or analytical methods to the inquiry. A positivist investigates an objective search of facts/evidence. Positivist research always believes in observable knowledge and lastly, the positivist's main aim is to create a

theory that is universal and comprehensive, which accounts for social behaviour and for human beings (Easterby-smith, Thorpe and Jackson 2015).

4.1.2 Critical realism paradigm

The critical realism paradigm first appeared in 70s-80s from a philosopher called Bhaskar (Bhaskar, 2016). It was further debated and practised by various philosophers/ practitioners (Brannan *et al.*, 2017). Critical realism came into the philosophical world research as a different philosophical approach to other paradigms such as positivism and constructivism (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Basically, this philosophical paradigm claims that the nature of the reality (or in other words, ontology), cannot be reducible to knowledge of the reality (epistemology). Knowledge is generated by us (humans) who only grasp a small slice of a complex yet deeper reality. In simple words, the us, the researcher, sees only a small chunk of a bigger piece (Fletcher, 2017). Because of this point of view, critical realism departs from the aforementioned paradigms. Thus, according to Bhaskar (2016), positivism encourages ‘the epistemic fallacy’. Also, he mentioned that the same could be applied to constructivism, which is the knowledge constructed within and across discourse or human knowledge. Moreover, critical realism claims the world as not theoretically determined but as ‘theory-laden’ (McAvoy and Butler, 2018). Critical realism does not disagree that there is a ‘real social world’ and us, the researchers, can still try to understand using social science and philosophy (Bhaskar, 2016; Easterby-smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2015)

Thus, it argues that some sort of knowledge could be ‘closer’ to reality than other knowledge (Danermark, Ekstrom and Jacobson, 2005). In this paradigm, it can gain knowledge in the basis of theories, which could be lesser or more truth-like (Saunders, Lewis and Thronehill 2009). These theories support us (the researchers) to reach closer to the reality (Archer *et al.*, 2013). A critical realist will appreciate the importance of studying in multi-level (level of the organisation, the group of people and the individual) (Edwards, O’Mahoney and Vincent, 2014). Each of these stages in this multi-level has the ability to change the researcher’s

understanding of what is being researched/studied (Fletcher, 2017) .This is due to the existence of these different kinds of processes, procedures and structures, and the ability of these things to interrelate or interact with each other (Maxwell, 2012). Therefore, in the view of a critical realist paradigm, academics argue that the social world around them keeps changing, much like the purpose of research in business and management, which is too common for investigating the motive for the phenomenon leading to propose change (Easterby-smith, Thorpe and Jackson 2015).

4.1.3 Interpretivism

The interpretivist paradigm attempts to investigate or understand the human lived experience subjectively (Packard, 2017).In this paradigm, the researcher attempts to understand what the human(subject) is thinking and attempts to interpret the context of the subject's thinking or contextual meaning (Leitch, Hill and Harrison 2010). The important viewpoint here is the subject's viewpoint and their interpretation of the world they live in, rather than the observer's (researcher's) viewpoint (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Furthermore, the main principle with interpretivism is the socially constructed reality (Burrell and Morgan, 2017). Interpretivist paradigm-based research follows theories but is not lead by the theories.

On the other hand, interpretivism has a balanced axiology of the methodology of a naturalist, the ontology of a relativist and the epistemology of a subjectivist (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). From ontology, relativist ontology assumes that the researcher believes there are multiple realities of the phenomenon being studied. These multiple realities can investigate and examine the underlying meanings or can be reconstructed through interactions of the research subject, other participants of the research, and the researcher (Goldkuhl, 2012). Interpretivist has a subjectivist epistemology. This means that the given data of research subject or participants by interacting with them, the researcher tries to understand or makes meaning aforementioned data from their own cognitive processing and their own thinking (Myers, 2015). Thus, the researcher will generate new knowledge socially, because of his/her individual

experiences of real world life within the context that is investigated in natural settings (Punch, 2013) . Furthermore, the interpretivist paradigm is based on researchers, and their subject(s) of the research, who are involved with the process of interacting with listening, reading, writing, dialogues and recording of research data (Bevir and Rhodes, 2012) . The balanced axiology of the interpretivist ensures that the result of the investigation will reflect the researcher's values, by making an effort to produce a 'balanced report' of the results/conclusions. And lastly, the assumption of a naturalist methodology means that the researcher is involved as an observer of the participant being studied and uses them with data gathered through interviews, text messages, reflective sessions and discourses (Bryman, 2012).

Consequently, some of the characteristics of research that can be adopted by the interpretivist paradigm are as follows; there are multiple realities and yet they are socially constructed (Burrell and Morgan, 2017). Unavoidable interaction between the research participants and the researcher believes that the importance of the context to knowing the knowledge gives much more priority to the individual rather than the need to know the universal laws (Bryman, 2012) .There is an assumption that the causes and its effects are interdependent to each other. Lastly, the belief of understanding a phenomenon, contextual factors, and its importance is taken into consideration when conducting the study (Creswell, 2014) .

4.1.4 Philosophical selection for this study: Interpretivism

The researcher avoided using the positivist paradigm because it would be not realistic to remain detached, independent, or neutral towards what was studied (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2015). Thus, due to its structured approach, inflexibility and incapability to understand the importance of the people or the processes assigned with them, the positivist approach was avoided by the researcher for this research, as the researcher tries to find how Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance the trust and loyalty of their customers and generate implications/recommendations to improve their business practices (Donaldson, 1997) . The researcher should determine the most appropriate research paradigm between interpretivism and critical realism. Both these

philosophies value the importance of social construction (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2009). The researcher arguably could have used either of interpretivism or critical realism. Critical realism does not suit this study, as it demands that the researcher is as objective as possible (Bhaskar, 2016). However interpretivism, as mentioned above, attempts to understand the human lived experience subjectively.

On the other hand, an interpretivist seeks to understand the subject's point of view, and their interpretations of the world around them in natural settings (Leitch, Hill and Harrison 2010). In line with this philosophical view, the nature of the reality is subjective, and it recognises the importance of interaction between the researcher and the main subject of the study; the ethnic entrepreneur in retail SMEs. Thus, retail SMEs and ethnic entrepreneurs through relationship marketing is a relatively under-researched area (Ram, Villares-Varela and Jones, 2017; Haq *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, an exploratory approach has been chosen with an interpretivist paradigm for conducting this research, enabling the achievement of the main aim of the research and objectives and answering the research question.

This study aims to explore how Sri Lankan ethnic minority entrepreneurs enhance customer trust and loyalty in retail grocery context . The interpretivist paradigm allows the researcher to understand the phenomenon through the subject's point of view (Packard, 2017). Simultaneously, it is flexible enough to enable different points of view on the same phenomenon (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). Within this context, it enables the researcher to 'view' the subject of 'customer' from the view of the subjects; i.e. UK retail SMEs owned by Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs, their perspectives of enhancing customer trust and loyalty and not just their actions towards it, but also their reasons/justifications whether not to take, or to go-ahead with these actions. Moreover, being flexible, the interpretivist paradigm can capture different point of views from ethnic entrepreneurs who own UK retail SMEs on the subject of customer trust and loyalty, but it may also be able to gain new concepts or ideas while carrying out this research (Punch, 2013). According to Bryman (2012), one of the main features when conducting a qualitative research is that it allows the researcher to have an opportunity to influence the subject's world, collaboratively or independently. Even though the interpretivist paradigm is cost and time intensive and it relies on limited data sample sizes

which are less generalizable to other settings, its selection as the research aims to create valuable rich data which will be capable of generating findings precisely applicable to the Sri Lankan owned retail SMEs businesses. Therefore, adopting the interpretivist approach with a qualitative inquiry would allow the researcher to understand and generate the most applicable implications/recommendations for the Sri Lankan owned retail SMEs.

4.2 Research approach

4.2.1 Deductive approach:

The deductive approach in research recognises a type of analysis that sets out to test whether the data aligned with the researcher's assumptions, identified hypotheses, or theories generated through various literature (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). The induction approach is seen as generating theories with validity. Thus, deduction is needed to 'test and refine' the theories further (Harriman, 2010). Because of this mechanism, these two approaches to the research were recognised as complementary to each other in the early development in science (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). However, in later developments a divide was formed between inductive and deductive research (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). The deductive approach became much more dominant in scientific research and the advancement of knowledge, due to the influence and critiques made by David Hume and Rene Descartes, who argued the validity of the human senses when generating knowledge. Further, because of it, we should depend much more on existing theories and/or 'natural ideas' and generate hypotheses from these theories and ideas (Johnson, 2015). Hence, induction was seen as an invalid or inferior way to generate new knowledge (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). Some other scientists also supported the deductive approach over the inductive; they argued that knowledge cannot be advanced from empirical findings (Ormerod, 2009). This, in fact is clearly showed in the evolving fields of management research at that time, which were employing deductive methods for finding legitimacy and answers (Hambrick, 2007; Porter and McKibbin, 1988). Indeed, this begs the question; where do new concepts/ theories comes from in the first place, if these

theories/concepts are not ‘induced’ from empirical findings? (Ormerod, 2009; Harriman, 2010).

Nevertheless, reviewers, editors and authors have been influenced by the regular deductive approach, which includes a research model based on hypothesis and progressive ‘under the review philosophy’ mechanism, and often views inductive approaches as insufficient and recommends adding deductive foundations (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). According to Locke (2007), adapting an inductive approach does not allow a theory to be confirmed, falsified, or refined but gives a clear purpose to finding answers for the questions raised by a phenomenon that has not been answered so far. In other words, no initial hypothesis has been formed to test this; instead, the researcher concentrates on the main research question and the study to progress what has already been found.

Apart from its dominance in scientific research, the deductive approach has been criticized over the years. Ormond (2009) claimed that, despite its popularity, the deductive approach does not effectively grasp how people really think. On the other hand, according to the cognitive and psychologists, the deductive approach and its ‘logic’ cannot describe the way people react to their surroundings (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). Philosophers of science argued that the deductive research approach does not effectively describe the scientific methods (Harriman, 2010). According to some researchers, the inductive approach has played an important role in terms of generating new knowledge, especially in the organisational studies and psychology (Locke, 2007; Johnston, 2014).

4.2.2 Inductive approach:

The researchers use the inductive approach mainly to generate themes, models, or concepts by interpreting the 'raw data'. In other words, the inductive approach is one which 'allows theory to emerge from the data' (Corbin and Strauss, 2014). The main purpose of this approach is to let the findings of the research evolve from more frequent, significant or dominant themes hidden in the raw data, without any restrictions placed by other structured methodologies (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). For instance, in deductive analysis (which is used to test hypothesis and experimental research projects), the key themes are generally found to be obscured, and/or reframed due to the preconceptions of the data collection and analysis procedures executed by the researchers (Johnston, 2014). Some researchers argue that the inductive research is a 'goal-free evaluation' where the investigators are willing to explain the real program effect instead of 'planned effects' (Youker, 2013). Similarly, finding essential features and their interrelationship in a 'systematic descriptive way' is one of the main focuses of the inductive analysis, or in other words, 'how things work' (Azungah, 2018). Thus, recognising any significant unexpected and unplanned effects or 'side effects' while carrying out or implementing the inductive research is identified as an evaluation of an important task (Gioia, Corley and Hamilton, 2013). According to Thomas (2006), some of the main purposes of adopting an inductive approach in a research project can be identified as follows:

- a. To shrink down the varied and extensive 'raw text data' into a much more compact and summary type format.
- b. To generate a clear link between study objectives and the summary of the findings extracted from the raw data and make sure that these connections are derived from the research findings and the data are transparent and justifiable (with the objectives of the research project).
- c. To generate a theory or a model about underlying structures regarding processes or experiences by using text data as evidence.

4.3 Preferred research approach: Inductive

Nevertheless, the inductive approach is based on empirical evidence; while the deduction is rooted in logic and sets out to test whether the data aligned with the researcher's assumptions (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). This study attempts to answer the research question of *'how do Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance the trust and loyalty of their customers within the retail grocery businesses in the UK?'* Generally, the inductive approach was employed to understand *'How things work'* (Azungah, 2018). Section 4.2.1 and 4.2.2 highlights one of the most used research approaches in entrepreneurship studies. Thus, this study is based on Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurship, which is exploratory in nature.

Consequently, an understanding of customer trust and loyalty practices in the Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurship is a relatively under-researched area. Therefore, the study does not expect to deduce any hypothesis or test any theories, but to explore the phenomenon. The researcher selected the inductive approach for this study (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). Complementary to this and the interpretivist research design, a qualitative methodology is employed where, in return, the researcher expects to find answers to the main research questions by analysing 'raw data' given by the qualitative methods.

4.3.1 Qualitative methodology

This study aims to explore how Sri Lankan ethnic minority entrepreneurs enhance customer trust and loyalty in retail grocery context. In line with the interpretivist philosophical view of this study, to successfully achieve the objectives and the aim, a qualitative methodology was employed. According to Creswell (2014), a qualitative study allows the researcher to better understand human or social phenomenon/problems by creating a holistic, multifaceted picture with words in order to describe the various viewpoints of the research participants and organisations in their own natural settings. Similarly, Hindle (2004) claims that research into

entrepreneurship would be much benefitted by using qualitative research, which in return allows the researcher to gain a broader, in-depth understanding of the phenomenon, and have an ability to learn directly from the research subjects (Allwood, 2012). Furthermore, Dana and Dana (2005) supports the above statement, which claimed that the qualitative research into entrepreneurship is particularly suitable because of its flexibility and evolving research design. Equally, employing qualitative research enables the researcher to interpret the experiences, opinions and views of research participants in their specific settings (Bryman, 2012). Thus, one of the uniqueness of employing a qualitative approach is that it enables the researcher to 'see' the 'subject' of studying through the 'eyes' of research participants. It also highlights rich description and is equipped with a more flexible structure than the quantitative, which enables the researcher to adapt to the changes that may occur while conducting the research (Dana and Dumez, 2015).

Furthermore, effective research projects into the entrepreneurship should be able to find the answers to questions of 'how' (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2009). Dana and Dana (2005) mentioned the nature of the research questions of entrepreneurship, such as: how do these entrepreneurship and its businesses survive in such diverse environments? How can others be encouraged into entrepreneurship and succeed? How do entrepreneurs or ethnic entrepreneurs from different ethnicities identify and explore opportunities? They stressed that these questions are better not be answered by quantitative researches, which employs surveys, questionnaires or brief interviews (Neergaard and Ulhøi, 2007). Short interviews and surveys are often criticised as 'open to manipulation' by allowing responses to be gathered, which are socially desirable from participants denying representations relating to current social standards (Henry, Foss and Ahl, 2016). When compared to quantitative research, which is popular for its well-structured and inflexible mechanism, the qualitative research, with its flexibility and ability to hold multiple viewpoints of social actors about the subject being studied, makes it far more suitable to explore the retail SMEs of ethnic entrepreneurs i.e. the opinions, perspectives and views of the factors that affect customer trust and loyalty practices.

Moreover, the qualitative approach is selected over the quantitative, which is often limited by its narrow and restricted method. It could end up generating unrealistic theories, and lead to 'missing a real understanding of actual world behaviours of novel cultures' (Silverman, 2011).

The qualitative is known as an inductive-holistic approach that lacks the manipulation by the researcher of what was being researched; also the inquiry depends on naturalistic settings. Qualitative research based on observing the individuals, events, interactions, situations, open ended questions, and document analysis etc. generates in-detail and verbal evidence (Dana and Dumez, 2015). Therefore, data of the qualitative research should produce solid description and quotations straight from the people, regarding their experiences, attitudes, beliefs, thoughts and actions etc.(Keegan, 2009). On the other hand, a qualitative researcher must always keep in mind never to assume the meaning of the concepts, behaviour or the words in order to produce effective research findings. Furthermore, the researcher can reduce type III error (the wrong question) and type IV error (trying to solve the wrong problem) as these are much more common with the quantitative methods such as survey studies. Thus, qualitative research can be used to generate internal validity which can be proven by quantitative inquiry (Dana and Dana 2005; Dana and Dumez, 2015).

Finally, there are also limitations to qualitative research; one of the most common limitations which can be found within the literature is the volume of the data, the analysis and its complexity, and record classification details (Beck, 2009) . Others argue that the qualitative inquiry is said to be ‘messy’ (O’Dwyer, 2004). These researches never go according to plan as the researchers need to be conscious about the ethical and political ‘ups and downs’ when they carry out qualitative research in the real-world (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011; Aluwihare-Samaranayake, 2012).

4.3.1.1 Research strategy: Case study

The researcher is aware that there are a number of methods available to be used in order to collect the data, such as surveys, ethnography, grounded theories, case studies, action research and experiments (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). Each of these methodologies generates different combinations of data collection mechanisms and their analysis methods. Thus, some of these methods may be employed by various research methodologies. For instance, interviews, which are generally employed by action research and case study methodologies. However, investigating the ethnic entrepreneurs with a customer trust and loyalty lens, the researcher considered whether to select the multiple qualitative, or the mono-method qualitative because there were several methodologies with methods for support to achieve this study's main research aim. In this case, four out of six methodologies were avoided because of the following reasons: survey-avoided; the literature on employing survey methodologies and this research topic could not be aligned and were at such nascency that the investigator could not recognise the variables to study using survey methodology (Easterby-smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2015). Experiment-avoided; the literature on employing experiment methodologies and the topic of this research could not be aligned and were at such nascency that the investigator could not recognise the variables to test using experiment methodology (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). The action research and ethnography were dismissed basically because of the time limitations and the other resource constraints; and also, interacting with the practitioners and the number of the cases where it would be impossible to achieve the outcome of the research within the given timeframe (Bryman, 2012). Lastly, there were two methodologies left to consider, namely, the grounded theory and the case study methodology.

The grounded theory:

The researcher identifies that this research may use grounded theory methodology. According to Birks and Mills (2015), adopting a grounded theory methodology is suitable when:

- ‘usually, very little seems to be known about the research area’.

- ‘generating a theory which has an explanatory power as a preferred outcome’.
- ‘potential of likelihood to explain/interpret research phenomenon and its ‘inherent process’ embedded in the research situation’.

These conditions above might align and could be illustrated in this current study. However, in this situation, the researcher understood that the grounded theory is a methodology which rejects all current/existing theories (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2015). However, the researcher expected to investigate the phenomenon by using current existing customer relationships (trust and loyalty) and ethnic entrepreneurship theories. Therefore, the grounded theory has been avoided in this exploratory study. As a result, the most suitable methodology to execute this research, which allows the researcher to investigate multiple cases of retail ventures, employs the ‘multiple case study methodology’ which enables the researcher to get the best benefits for this research project.

4.3.1.2.1 Multiple Cases

According to Gerring (2006), case study strategy can be defined as a type of strategy which engages an empirical inquiry of a particular modern day phenomenon, using different sources of evidence within its real-world context. Case study strategy will be much more suitable to be employed where the researcher attempts to achieve a ‘rich understanding’ of the phenomenon (Creswell, 2014). On the other hand, case study method has the ability to answer the research questions based on the ‘how’, ‘what’, and ‘why’ (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). Thus, ‘what’ and ‘how’ research questions are much more in favour of employing survey strategies. For this very reason, case study methodology is often used in the exploratory and explanatory type of research projects (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2015). There are different types of case study strategies employed including: a single case study method i.e. where the researcher only looks in to one case of the phenomenon to study; or the multiple case study which, as the name says, is where the researcher looks into multiple cases to study. The main rationale of looking into multiple cases is to ascertain whether the findings of the first case

could be aligned with other cases and, as a result, generalize these findings. Therefore, the multiple case study is preferred by researchers compared to the single case study (Yin, 2017).

Data collection techniques used in case study methodology vary and depend on the situation, the objectives of the research and are often used as a combination. Typical techniques include observations, documentation, interviews, archival records and physical artefacts (Yin, 2017).

Following the aforementioned reasoning, and aligned with the research objectives of this study the researcher decided to look into multiple cases, instead of a single case.

4.3.1.2.2 Unstructured interviews

On the other hand, as this is an exploratory study, interviews were conducted in an unstructured style by the researcher. The researcher followed three steps when conducting the unstructured interview approach:

- The researcher built a mutual interest with the research participants (business owners) by sharing his intention of working towards much-improved customer trust and loyalty practices.
- The researcher presented relevant questions in order to gain an understanding of the starting up and the managerial process of the business.
- Lastly, as part of the investigation, the researcher asked relevant questions concerning the customers when the entrepreneurs were interacting and managing them in their businesses.

Yin (2017) tried to align the case study interview approach with the survey approach, highlighting that the case study interviews should be based on ‘well guided conversations’ rather than manipulated structured queries. With that being said, while conducting the interviews the researcher accepted and followed the above guidance of Yin (2017), noting how subtleties such as the questioning style of the researcher might be perceived by the interview participants (for instance; certain choices of words and the intonation while carrying out the

conversation). Therefore, for the purpose of this research, the researcher mainly collected data through unstructured, in-depth interviews with field notes.

4.3.2 Time horizons

Considerations of the time horizon impacts the design of the research in terms of how much time is spent in the total research process. There are two ways of conducting the research in this manner, the cross sectional and the longitudinal. The cross-sectional means an investigation of a particular phenomenon with multiple cases in a single point in time. Some argued that the cross-sectional studies are popular, are employed in positivist research designs and fit well in the quantitative contexts, thus it can be used and is also suitable for the qualitative designs (Bryman 2012; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). In particular, the qualitative designs that employ the semi or unstructured interviews are more appropriate for ‘the cross-sectional investigation’ (Bryman 2012). On the other hand, longitudinal studies are suitable for studies of change and development over a long period of time. In a longitudinal study, the data are collected on several occasions from the same subjects and used to understand the change and its process over a period of time. Typical examples for this type of longitudinal study include ethnographic studies and also quasi-experimental researches (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2015; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). Nevertheless, this particular study has been conducted through cross-sectional research; in other words, this represents a ‘snapshot’ of ethnic retail SMEs’ customer relationship practices to enhance customer trust and loyalty in specific point in time. On the other hand, time and financial limitations for this study are major issues and selecting a cross sectional study makes this study more practical and feasible. Thus, based on the outcomes of this particular study, a longitudinal research can be conducted at a later point in time.

4.3.2 Techniques and procedures

Most of the procedures, methods and techniques that were used in this thesis for collecting data have already been mentioned in the research methodology. Practically, and for the feasibility of this study, the multiple case study based on qualitative inquiry allowed the researcher to investigate different cases of Sri Lankan ethnic retail grocery SMEs. The following paragraphs will briefly present how the researcher did the case sampling, processed the obtained data and lastly, completed the analysis alongside with synthesis. A detailed description and justification for the adoption of such procedures and techniques is given in the appropriate sections throughout this thesis.

4.3.2.1 Purposive Sampling

The researcher selected multiple cases of Sri Lankan retail SMEs as samples. The approach to selecting the samples for this study was influenced by three main reasons; information gathered through reviewing the literature of the research subject; good understanding of the qualitative research and its methodology; and access to the data and its convenience. The researcher leaned much more towards small start-ups, rather than larger established, well known ventures. The smaller and relatively established Sri Lankan owned retail ventures were more suitable to the interest of this research and its research objectives.

The researcher adopted Miles, Huberman and Saldana (2014) directions on conceptually based sequential sampling - this is a sampling technique that is 'purposive' and evolves while carrying out the field work. This allowed the researcher to snowball into relevant cases with their differences and also importantly with their similarities, which exposed the important perspectives that warranted further research. Furthermore, by following the aforementioned Miles, Huberman and Saldana (2014) sampling techniques, the researcher progressively narrowed down the focus of the research and created a portfolio of cases which allowed 'rich' sampling throughout, within the cases of Sri Lankan ethnic owned retail businesses. For the

purpose of this investigation, there will be eight multiple cases that will have similar retail business models. Eight cases were selected due to resource and time constraints.

Case no.	Participant name and abbreviation	Gender	Age group	Location	Years in the retail business (Approx.)	Number of employees	Estimate Turnover (£.annually)
1	Ravi (C1)	Male	50-55	London	25	4	£25000
2	Van (C2)	Male	50-55	London	30	5	£38000
3	Dan(C3)	Male	50-55	London	5	3	£35000
4	Ken (C4)	Male	45- 50	London	8	3	£40000
5	Sura(C5)	Male	45-50	London	10	10+	£80000
6	Hesh (C6)	Male	30-35	London	5.5	4	£35000
7	Mahi (C7)	Male	45-50	London	10	3	£35000
8	Sachin (C8)	Male	45-50	London	13	5	£40000

Table 1: Number of cases and demographics

4.3.2.2 Preconditions to research

There were two pre-conditions necessary to be met in order to execute this research plan: 1) access to a phenomenon which can be observable; and 2) existence and availability of instruments in order to collect, analyse and process the observations. In this case, access and availability to the aforementioned phenomenon required the small ethnic retail ventures to allow the researcher to carry out the interviews on site and make relevant field notes regarding customer interactions and other relevant notes. The researcher visited one of the small retail ventures in January 2020. The researcher experienced the venture’s readiness and was able to provide interview data and venture visit proposed that investigator could be able to enter similar/same levels of access to the data and information with other retail ventures. The researcher initiated the capacity of collecting the data which following research questions through the site observed field notes and unstructured interviews. Thus, the researcher made sure that the second pre-condition had been followed closely throughout the process. Once the permission to access the collecting of data was initiated, the researcher himself understood that he would act as the primary instrument for collecting the data. As per the aforementioned

exploratory nature of this research and its anticipated research outcomes, the researcher also acted as the primary instrument for processing, analysis and synthesis of the collected data.

4.3.2.3 Data processing

Data processing refers to memoing and transcribing. Memoing and transcribing help the researcher to deal with converting 'raw' complex data into a much clearer, intelligible product. Miles, Huberman and Saldana (2014) note that an intelligible product is something which is not only useful for the investigator, but for everyone. Some researchers choose to outsource the transcription of the interviews. Nevertheless, the researcher valued the importance of transcribing interviews himself as this would enable him to get much closer to the data. Therefore, the researcher transcribed all the interviews and meetings with the participants. The field notes were transcribed back to word document as a reflective writing as soon as the interview finished, especially the customer interactions with the business owner during the visit. Lastly, this means that the interview recordings and conversations were visited multiple times by the researcher during the process.

4.3.2.3.1 Data Analysis

Data analysis in this research focuses on recognising the emergent themes concerning Sri Lankan entrepreneurs and their customer relationship practices in order to study how Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance their customer trust and loyalty. According to Marshall and Rossman (1995, p. 111) 'data analysis is the process of bringing order, structure and meaning to the mass of collected data'. For data organisation, management and assigning meaning, "Nvivo" Qualitative software is used for this study. Nvivo was used as the main driver for organising the data by coding the main transcribed interview data using open coding to identify the main emerging themes (Miles, Huberman and Saldana, 2014). Data analysis began after all the interview recordings were transcribed, along with the field notes, to generate case reports for all eight selected cases. This enabled the researcher to construct a 'thick'

description of all the data available(Langley, 1999). The data transcribed was either from the audio recordings or field notes as applicable (especially customer interactions with the entrepreneur himself). Then again, interview audio recordings and notes were reviewed along with the transcribed interview documents to ensure there were no errors or inconsistency. The researcher visited the transcripts and relevant notes several times to recognise the themes of the data and to understand the story/ meaning it reflects. The Nvivo software is used to code the data using open coding first as this research is based on an inductive approach. Coding was done as the analysis of this research progressed, based on the key emergent themes, and continued until reaching the point where there were no new coding themes found (i.e. reached saturation).

Single case open coding analysis leads to thematic coding, which is fundamental for cross-case analysis in this study. Apart from employing a multiple case study analysis, maintaining an overarching integrity of these cases and its study is a major concern in this study. To address the problem, Yin (2017) recommended that researchers take an analytical strategy, which the researcher attempted to implement throughout the entire analysis. The main advantage of adopting this analytical strategy is that it improves the quality of case study implementation and rigour of individual cases and cross-case analysis.

4.3.2.3.2 Thematic coding

As mentioned before, thematic coding was employed in this study (Gibbs, 2007; Miles, Huberman and Saldana, 2014). Transcripts based from the interview and notes were used for the purpose of implementing codes based on themes. Braun and Clarke (2006, p.6) mentioned the thematic analysis as ‘a method for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data’. Emergent themes within cases and across cases are recognised from multiple level of coding using the Nvivo software. The thematic analysis allows flexibility as it offers detail and richness towards the complex account of data (Miles, Huberman and Saldana, 2014).

4.3.2.3.3 With-in case study analysis

This approach generates implications/recommendations by understanding how the ethnic entrepreneurs enhance customer trust and loyalty in their business activities, depending on the outcome of the across case patterns (Eisenhardt, 1989). The researcher chose the individual case analysis above the cross-case patterns to see what themes arrived from the data. These themes are categorised as individual (micro); opportunity structure (meso); and institutional and regulatory embeddedness (macro). In other words, the main theoretical framework for this thesis. The main reason to do an individual analysis is to find if there are any themes of particular interest emerging from the data. According to Eisenhardt (1989, p.539) ‘analyzing data is the heart of building theory from case studies, but it is both the most difficult and the least codified part of the process’.

4.3.2.3.4 Cross-case analysis

This study also employs cross-case analysis to understand the patterns across the cases (Eisenhardt, 1989). Cross-case patterns are especially useful in developing rich insights into the studies, where multiple case studies are employed. The main importance for this cross-case analysis stresses the need for the researcher to go beyond the initial level of impression given by the data. Rather it allows for a focus on a more diverse lens of data (Eisenhardt, 1989). Also, this will enhance the rigour of the study. Thus, a cross-case analysis will avoid the risk of arriving at conclusions from limited data (Yin, 2017). It also eliminates being influenced by a respondent who impacted the researcher’s view as an ‘elite’ (Miles and Huberman, 1984). This study will employ the cross-case patterns informed by with-in cases, as well as Nvivo software. First, as mentioned before, with-in case analysis has allowed the researcher to identify the themes relating to the theoretical framework in this study. Then, the cross-case analysis will be employed to see whether the patterns will match across the cases. In the with-in cases several themes were identified, such as motivation factors, success perception, human capital, social capital, labour capital, access to finance and customer relationship related themes. It enabled

the researcher to find the answers to the main research question of How do Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance the trust and loyalty of their customers within the retail grocery businesses in UK. In addition, other themes relating to opportunity structure, institutional embeddedness and the Coronavirus pandemic themes also emerged from the data.

4.3.2.4 Ethical Considerations

It is important to raise the importance of ethical issues. Ethics describe how to conduct the research in a more moral and responsible way (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2008). For instance, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009, p.184) mentioned that ‘research ethics therefore relates to questions about how we formulate and clarify our research topic, design our research and gain access, collect data, process and store our data, analyse data and write up our research findings in a moral and responsible way’. Therefore, this research also follows a good standard of ethics. Data collection process follows the University of the West of Scotland ethics guidelines to achieve integrity and gain rich data while minimising the research bias. In this research the ethical considerations outlined below are followed:

Informed consent:

According to Zikmund *et al.* (2000, p.73) ‘Informed consent [is] the expressed or implied acknowledgement waiving an individual’s right to privacy when he or she agrees to participate in a research study’. The consent forms were presented to the participants before they took part in the interview. Therefore, the researcher was responsible for maintaining the procedures highlighted and presented to the participants (Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler, 2008).

Explaining the benefits of the study:

The researcher presented the participant information sheet to the potential individuals. This participant information sheet included the main aim and objectives of the research, along with basic information about the researcher. Thus, it also included details of the University of the West of Scotland. This enabled the researcher to build the confidence of the participants and gain trust. This also enabled the researcher to start a believable discussion and increase the richness of the data.

Explaining the participant's rights and protection:

Participants were well informed with their information sheet and consent form. The researcher made sure the rights of the participant were understood in the paper given, and at the same time explained these more thoroughly as well; in particular, about the right to withdraw from the interview and the information given at any time during the interview. The main purpose of the right to withdraw and any other relevant information is to make them comfortable and ensure that they understand the process and their rights.

Anonymity and confidentiality:

Anonymity and privacy of the participants were ensured throughout the research process, especially their particulars and their business identities, which were kept anonymous to make sure confidentiality and privacy was protected (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009).

4.3.2.5 Research Validity

Overall qualitative research quality depends on the trustworthiness of the study conducted. Lincoln and Guba (1986) demanded four categories to judge the trustworthiness of a qualitative research inquiry. Those are: transferability, confirmability, dependability and credibility.

Transferability means ‘the extent to which the results of a specific research can be transferred or generalised to other settings or contexts’ (Forero *et al.*, 2018, p.3). Thus, unlike quantitative research (which focuses on statistical generalizability), qualitative studies commonly aims at internal generalizability which is, according to Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson (2015, p.216) ‘the capacity to explain what has been researched within a given setting’. Consequently, qualitative research studies cannot be duplicated as these inquiries are led by individuals who engage with a specific setting(s) at a particular time. Therefore, the qualitative research contribution often relies on its uniqueness (Bryman, 2012). In order to describe the transferability of this research, a clear description of relevant cases, data collection process, and analysis has been presented in their respective sections. Each individual case description, along with their case-specific characteristics and background information, has also been described. Thus, the findings of this study are also presented with rich verbatim statements/quotations from the data. The researcher used the purposive sampling technique as the data sampling method which allowed him to snowball into relevant cases with their differences and also, importantly, with their similarities. This enabled the researcher to get in-depth interviews as well as observational data with different views and rich information from the participants. Thus, all the participants in the case studies had the opportunity to comment on the interviews and field notes gathered by the researcher. It has led the researcher to have a prolonged interaction with the participants. Data gathered through audio recording of the interviews was carefully transcribed and analysed by the researcher, who ensured that all the themes and sub themes were clarified as they evolved from the data. Fieldnotes were also taken into an account as they were important in order to record the behaviours of participants with their customers. This has also contributed to an explanation of the phenomenon of the study. Meticulous documentation was also maintained during the data interpretation as a record to ensure transparency and consistency throughout the process - also called an ‘audit trail’ (Carcary, 2009, p.11).

According to Bryman (2012, p.390) ‘dependability parallels reliability’. Dependability was achieved with the help of two other research colleagues (one is a post- doc and the other is still working on his research project) who are also researching ethnic minority entrepreneurship. These colleagues reviewed the anonymous transcribed case data and validated the identified main and sub-themes given by the researcher. At the same time, supervisor advice and comments are taken on each stage of this study, a process also known as ‘self-correcting’ (Morse *et al.*, 2002, p.13). This procedure enhances the research quality and improves the credibility of this study.

Korstjens and Moser (2018, p.122) argue that ‘confirmability concerns aspect of neutrality’. This is similar to objectivity in quantitative research (Bryman, 2012). In order to achieve the confirmability of this research, a journal was used during this study in order to reflect the researcher’s own feelings and thoughts; this is known to be good practice to reduce researcher bias (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2015). Also, once the coding was completed, the main findings, along with transcripts, have been presented and further discussed with five participants. All these participants agreed that the findings of this research broadly align with what they previously said in the interviews. This process is also referred as ‘participant validation’, which is known to improve the overall quality of the research, and importantly minimises the researcher bias (Burnard *et al.*, 2008, p.431).

4.3.2.6 Research reflexivity and positionality

According to Alvesson and Skoldberg (2000, as quoted in Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2015, p.181), reflexivity is defined as,

‘continuous awareness and attention to the way different kinds of linguistic, social, political and theoretical elements are woven together in the process of knowledge development, during which empirical material is constructed, interpreted and written’.

Therefore, including reflexivity in a qualitative study informs the researcher’s awareness of how various identity elements (e.g. gender, class, and ethnicity) become significant in the

research process (Palaganas *et al.*, 2017). Hence, reflexivity recognizes that we, as researchers, are part of the social world we intend to study (Ackerly and True, 2019). It is crucial to understand that the inevitable bias of the researcher should, in some ways, be identified and explored. In line with the argument and to understand ourselves as researchers, Johnson and Duberley (2003, p.1279) mentioned that ‘we must engage with ourselves through thinking about our own thinking’. This is known as a continuous process of introspection to subjectivity in the research. Therefore, Hesse-Biber (2007, as quoted in Palaganas *et al.*, 2017, p.427) referred to reflexivity as ‘a reflection process of recognising, understanding, and examining how the researcher’s social background, location and assumptions affect their research practice’.

On the other hand, one of the main techniques for having a good reflexive process in the research is to keep a reflexive journal. A reflexive journal can be used to make explicit the researcher’s prior understanding about the study (Palaganas *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, in this research, the researcher has used a journal in order to reflect the researcher’s thoughts, feelings (as mentioned above) and even decisions he made during the process. Thus, reflexivity touches on ethical issues as well (Guillemin and Gillam, 2004). From an ethical point of view, case study researchers need to be sensitive to various differences such as culture, race, gender, and class (Mills, Durepos and Wiebe, 2009). In this case, the researcher was cautious concerning the expressions given by the participants, which may raise ethical sensitivities (especially when interviewing/analysing), and carefully negotiated around them throughout the research.

However, some scholars critiqued that reflexivity is unnecessary and baseless; involved too much introspection of the researcher; and can be paralytic and problematic to the research (Cunliffe, 2003).

Nevertheless, according to Mills, Durepos and Wiebe (2009, p.789)

‘reflexivity is operationalized when researchers can articulate their awareness of the interconnectivity between and among themselves, the participants, the data, and the methods they use to interpret and represent their findings’.

This could be demonstrated by attempting to situate the positionality of the researcher. In fact,

‘the relationship between positionality and reflexivity is an organic one: the researcher engages in the process of self-analysis and self-scrutiny, thereby reflecting on their research in the context of their own positionality’ (Fremlova, 2018, p.102).

4.3.2.6.1 Positionality of the researcher

According to Holmes (2020, p.1) ‘the term “positionality” both describes an individual’s world view and the position they adopt about a research task and its social and political context’. Thus, Savin-Baden and Major (2013, p.71), positionality ‘reflects the position that the researcher has chosen to adopt within a given research study’. Indeed it influences how the study is conducted, its results and outcomes (Palaganas *et al.*, 2017).

I identify as an immigrant, international student in the UK, who is from Sri Lanka. As I was admitted to a doctoral degree, I was asked to conduct research as part of the programme. After many attempts at considering which of the disciplines to study, I decided I wanted to study entrepreneurship. I think as a person, this is what I would do, and I would be a researcher who might also practice the findings of this thesis in the future. After I discussed my research needs with my supervisor, he showed me an area of an entrepreneurship discipline that did not gain the same recognition as the mainstream entrepreneurship phenomenon; this is called ethnic minority entrepreneurship. As the name suggests, it is about the people who are conducting entrepreneurial activities within the minority ethnic groups in the host country. In fact, I would also be an ethnic minority entrepreneur if I form a (future) start up in the UK. To be precise, I would be categorised as a South Asian ethnic minority entrepreneur in the UK. So, I then turned my attention to the literature regarding ethnic minority entrepreneurship, focusing on South Asian ethnic minority groups in the UK. There are eight countries in the South Asian region, of which Sri Lanka is one. Yet, apparently, Sri Lankan ethnic minority entrepreneurial activities and their contribution have not been recognised/ are under-researched by scholars in the UK. It is therefore no wonder that some scholars stress the need for research and describe these small ethnic group as ‘neglected’ (Aspinall, 2019).

My working experience also put me in a position to form this research project. I have worked in numerous places over the years as a part time student to cover my expenditures. One of the

regular jobs I took was either being a bartender in the hospitality sector or a customer assistant in retail supermarkets. Attracting or retaining the customer for these businesses is very important. Indeed, it impacts survival and growth (Haq *et al.*, 2021). Thus, creating a long-lasting relationship with the customer is inarguably valuable for the business over time. Hence, many articles regarding earning the trust of the customer and loyalty studies exist in the literature. However, almost all of them were focused on either larger SMEs, or other corporations. There were very few studies focussed on ethnic minority entrepreneurs and their customer relationship in the literature. As I mentioned before, it would be beneficial for me to be informed as a (future) Sri Lankan ethnic minority entrepreneur who might step into the retail sector (preferably grocery) in the UK.

4.3.3.6.1.1 The influence of mixed embeddedness model

I have reviewed several theories/concepts (Chapter 3) regarding the ethnic minority entrepreneurship. These theories stem from either culturist or structuralist approaches. As a result of an up-to-date development to the field, many of these theories have been integrated into models to explain the ethnic entrepreneurship as a whole. Two apparent models can be found in the literature: the ‘interactive model’ and ‘mixed embeddedness model’ (Volery, 2007, p.34). Briefly, the interactive model takes the view that the success of the ethnic entrepreneurial business depends on many factors. At the same time, the model suggests that the success of these ethnic businesses depends on complex interaction between the opportunity structure and ethnic group resources. Moreover, these opportunity structures are made up of conditions of the job market in the host country, market conditions, institutional and legal frameworks and access to the ownership (Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward, 1990).

Consequently, these economic opportunities are available and accessible for all. But, as I mentioned in Chapter 3, ethnic minority entrepreneurs may potentially have an advantage over others due to their better understanding of cultural differences between the mainstream society and ethnic community (Volery, 2007). This model allows us to understand their success strategies and ethnic resources, but it does not allow us to understand the other underlying issues, such as how they decided to become entrepreneurs in the first place; and importantly,

as an immigrant living in the UK, I had to question myself as to how regulatory bodies shape these entrepreneurs in the host country.

These questions lead me to find and adopt a better explanation for the phenomenon, covering almost every aspect of ethnic minority entrepreneurship. This is where I have to expose my position in terms of choosing the theoretical lens. After reviewing various ethnic minority entrepreneurship theories/concepts, I think I lean much more towards the structuralist approach in explaining ethnic entrepreneurship, rather than the culturist view. The structuralist approach does not believe that ethnic entrepreneurship appears out of nowhere. Instead, it suggests that these individuals became entrepreneurs due to external influences. In other words, ethnic minority individuals are not described as doing this by choice. Instead, theorists argue that they become entrepreneurs due to the need to survive or to avoid potential unemployment, discrimination, and other factors that restrict their access to the labour market in the host country (Borooah and Hart, 1999). Therefore, choosing the interactive model as the main theoretical lens has been avoided.

Nevertheless, the mixed embeddedness model is also rooted in the structuralist approach to explain the phenomenon (Volery, 2007). The model suggests that these ethnic entrepreneurs are embedded in social networks, and at the same time, they are also embedded in a broader external business context. In essence, it highlights the importance of ethnic minority embeddedness in their social networking transactions and resources to become entrenched in broader structures of political, institutional and economic environments (Rath and Kloosterman, 2002; Kloosterman, 2010). The ethnic entrepreneurial social context is better known as the ethnic entrepreneur's social embeddedness in the environment. Simply put, the social embeddedness approach argues for the nature, depth, and extent of an individual's connection(s) to the environment and its influence on their business activity (Aldrich *et al.*, 1986; Granovetter, 1985; Whittington, 1992). This is also described as the micro-level of the business, where I could analyse the individual motives, perceptions, ethnic resources, cultural dynamics and other relationships. Then again, my unique research question (How do Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance the trust and loyalty of their customers within the retail grocery businesses in UK) leads me to argue that how do I view customer relationship marketing theories through the mixed embeddedness model. As a researcher, at this point, I

can acknowledge that the mixed embeddedness model itself was very challenging to understand. But, with the help of the literature, I could conceptualize that customer relationships can be viewed as the social capital of the ethnic entrepreneur who are socially embedded in the operating environment. Hence, customer relationships can be viewed as the social connection to the ethnic entrepreneur (Kloosterman, 2010; Tang, 2015).

The other fact that influenced me to adopt the mixed embeddedness view is how it explains the economic environment of the (aforementioned) business context in which these entrepreneurs are embedded (Kloosterman and Rath, 2006). The model suggests that opportunities for entrepreneurs are linked to markets. Indeed, markets are vital components of the opportunity structure. Therefore, these opportunity structures are locally, regionally, and/or nationally different (Kloosterman, 2010). These markets are facilitated or impeded by the host country regulatory system - hence the opportunity structure. This opportunity structure analysis sits at the meso-level of the entrepreneurial environment. Analysing the opportunity structure will be beneficial in order to understand current opportunities in the retail grocery market and, at the same time, the challenges these ethnic entrepreneurs face.

The entrepreneur's actions are either discouraged or facilitated by the cultural practices and much wider institutional environment (Kloosterman and Rath, 2006). This institutional environment includes business and social networks, leading organisational and politico-economic structures (Yeung, 2002). This wider “macro” level of the model looks at the government regulations, legal boundaries of the host country, its impacts to the minority entrepreneur, and their ownership of their business from an economic standpoint. This view aligns with my position as an immigrant who lives in the UK, and it adequately explains how regulatory bodies shape these entrepreneurs in the host country. Also, the model acknowledges my position as a researcher who leans much more towards the structuralist approach to entrepreneurship, as this views the phenomenon of ethnic minority entrepreneurship and its outcomes as affected by the entrepreneur's economic and social context they are embedded in, since they did not appear from a vacuum (Barberis and Solano, 2018).

However, there are some critiques of the mixed embeddedness model, such as the fact that the model is unable to explain a historical view (Volery, 2007). I do not think that a historical view is necessary for this study to explain the phenomenon. Yet, my position was to understand how

their cultural dynamics play within their entrepreneurial activities. Hence, as I demonstrated throughout this thesis, their culture (Sri Lankan) plays a vital role in shaping their entrepreneurial activities. Thus, some argue that the mixed embeddedness model is not vigorous enough to consider other factors, such as diasporic and transnational entrepreneurship (Volery, 2007; Kloosterman, 2010). In this regard, my research focus is to explore the Sri Lankan ethnic minority entrepreneurship and their customer relationship in the grocery sector. Therefore, these critiques did not influence me against using the mixed embeddedness model as the primary theoretical lens of this study.

4.3.2.6.1.2 Insider/outsider status

This section reflects how my own ethnic identity and culture may have inevitably influenced the research process. In doing this study about Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs, I think it brought out different dynamics, in the sense of insider/outsider positionality, politics of representation, and across other dimensions of social differentiation above commonality in ethnicity or nationality. These ethnic entrepreneurs placed me in certain categories, demonstrated their authority, ‘othered’ me, and repeatedly negotiated the researcher-participant relationship (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). Nevertheless, my common background with the participants, such as my nationality, ethnicity, gender, and ability to speak in the native language, enabled me to bridge the gaps and become more accepted as the research process progressed. As many participants told me, I was, after all, a fellow Sri Lankan boy. I made a considerable effort to mix as much as I could and be aware of my difference and the power relations that come with it. It would not be practical to assume that I became a complete ‘insider’ or that participant’s relationships were fully equal (Sultana, 2007). But, on the other hand, I believe what matters was the fact that who I am (identity) and how I interact with these Sri Lankans helped me to develop a rapport, and hence, build up trust (Holmes, 2020). This allowed me to ask more insightful questions, understand non-verbal cues and at the same time, secure more honest responses from the participants with thick descriptions.

Even though they claimed me as one of their own (Sri Lankan), they were not particularly ready to hand over the data to me. That is where they viewed me as the ‘other’ (Sultana, 2007). The

positionality as a Sri Lankan did not give me the privilege to interview these participants in the first place. I, however, have been living in the United Kingdom for almost a decade. I think the fact that I basically grew up and was educated in a foreign environment influences our behaviour and other characteristics over time. Hence, I assimilated Western norms (Bhugra and Becker, 2005). In this regard, I think I can position myself as a Western educated research scholar. I went to a number of Sri Lankan retail grocery shops around London prior to the data collection process. I would normally be dressed formally and greeted these people when I was visiting their premises. I gave them the participant information sheet and consent form and explained that I would need their consent to audio tape and write down notes while interviewing them. Soon after, I realised that many of these participants had not agreed to do the interviews. Indeed, I was refused by many of these places. I was running out of time with the research process, so how was I to access these interviews and other relevant data? After a while, I met another shop keeper, a participant who changed the scenario and explained what was going wrong. He said that my attire needed to be changed as it looked 'too formal'. Then he said again that I had to talk to them as a Sri Lankan, not as another foreigner. He also suggested that it would be better if I was referred by someone they knew. Furthermore, he also advised me to dress more casually, as these people do not conduct their businesses in a formal environment. In fact, these individuals would not trust anyone outside their social network. It is also reflected in the literature that the Sri Lankans are very conservative when sharing data with third parties (Azmat and Zutshi, 2012). Then he gave me the interview and allowed me to observe how he interacted with the customers and other activities. He later referred me to one of his colleagues, who happens to run a similar shop. This piece of advice allowed me to snowball into appropriate cases for the study afterwards. Importantly, the first case in this research gave me enough confidence and information to carry on the data collection process with other relevant cases. I think this whole scenario also revealed my positionality as an outsider to the group (reflecting a class difference) (Sultana, 2007). As I mentioned before, I have previous working experience in retail settings, but I acknowledge that I have never worked in an ethnic minority grocery shop. I realised that these ethnic shops are nothing like the supermarkets or larger retailer SMEs, where I could also position myself as an outsider to these businesses.

4.3.2.6.1.3 Politics of representation

As I mentioned earlier, after interviewing the first participant, I went to see the other participants following the advice given by the first interviewee, especially on how I should approach or represent myself to the future participants. When I went to see the next participant, I experienced warmth and hospitality from him, even though he was actively working in the field. I told him that I had been referred by X (first participant name), and he told me Mr. X had informed him about my research study. This scenario (using referrals from their group members) was common to other participants as well. It seemed to me that they were keen to help me with this research process, as the members informed them of their social network. They accommodated me while carrying out their work, frequently offering me food and drink while I was on site. Sometimes this made me feel uncomfortable, but refusing such treatment seemed offensive to them. Therefore, I had to negotiate my position constantly through these kinds of everyday activities, i.e. what I drank or ate and how I situated myself while interviewing (when participants interact with customers or carry on their duties). Despite our differences most of them stressed our commonality as Sri Lankans. These conversations raised questions of how I could use different positionalities to build trust and rapport with participants while paying attention to the politics and ethics involved in the development of 'blend in' and power relations that generally come with it (Sultana, 2007). Therefore, I have always kept that in mind (especially ethics) when visiting and negotiating daily with participants in the field.

I also found that on some occasions in the field visits, not only the participant would accept me in the site but also their family members who were present at the time. I particularly felt that their wives would indirectly allow me permission to interview their husbands. At some point, they raised the questions ('you talk to him a long time now, isn't that enough ?'), reflecting scepticism. I found that these people regarded me as a person who was working for the educational institution instead of studying; in other words, that I was working for the government, even though I handed out the participant information sheet and other relevant documents for them to know in the first instance. On the other hand, there were more frequent sentiments of acceptance ('I think your work might be helpful to us small businesses, let me know the outcome'), as well as some occasions and scrutiny ('how can you help me to get more

customers?’). Such placements in multiple locations always reminded me that research ethics must be in practice and negotiated in order to proceed any further.

On other occasions, some participants were not really interested in the area I was questioning them on. Instead, they were keen to know about my political affiliations, who I know in Sri Lankan society in the UK, and my family background. I had to listen politely, engage in such interactions and direct them back to the research questions. Even though some of these conversations were uncomfortable for me, I carefully and ethically negotiated in order to get the interview done while not offending the participant.

On the other hand, the Coronavirus lockdown situation in the UK has made my research study even more challenging. The biggest challenge was visiting some of the participants right after the first lockdown in the UK, which took place (the lockdown) between March and July 2020. This caused some participants to disregard the pre-agreed appointments, wait a long time outside the businesses due to social distance rules, and have interviews at a distance (impacting interaction and audio taping on site). We (the participant and me) carefully followed the rules given by the health bodies in the UK in order to conduct the interviews as safely as we could after the lockdown. This put me in a position where I had to think about myself and the participant’s health during these challenging times. Finally, I still think that we worked together flawlessly, ethically and in a morally acceptable manner to produce knowledge, which was mutually defined.

However, to be considered the same (insider) or different (outsider) involves reference to another group or a person. According to Fay (1996, p.241), ‘there is no self-understanding without other-understanding’. Applying this statement to research requires noting the ways we are similar to others as well as noting the ways we are different from others (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009). In this aspect, I have clearly mentioned above how I was seen as an insider, which revealed my similarities with the group. And at the same time, I also noted how I possibly differed from the group, which acknowledged my positionality as an outsider. Yet, there were occasions where I was a neither an insider nor outsider. I observed their customer interactions, noting special conversations between the participant and customer, navigating the questions

towards the research focus, and steering the participants back into the research questions, especially when I felt that they went beyond and attempted to share sensitive information. I was careful enough to respect their views/privacy, and at the same time not to breach any research ethics. I realised throughout this process that I was in a constant changing state where I was insider, outsider and neither (or the space between) (Holmes,2020). This (position) was reflected in the literature;

‘we may be closer to the insider position or closer to the outsider position because our perspective is shaped by our position as a researcher (which includes having read much literature on the research topic), and we cannot fully occupy one or the other of those positions’ (Dwyer and Buckle, 2009, p.61).

Nevertheless, the knowledge produced in this thesis is based on the context of intersubjectivities and the places we, as researchers, occupy at that particular time (socially, institutionally, politically, physically, as well as spatially). Knowledge produced is partial, and knowledge gained through field research consists of power relations, in which the researcher must be taken into account when conducting ethical research (Palaganas *et al.*, 2017). These types of (intersubjective) learnings are vital in such processes that are often iterative and hard to pre-define in (institutional) ethics forms. The research and its knowledge occur within its research process, entrenched in wider social relationships and other development processes that situate the researcher and his participants in different locations (Sultana, 2007). Therefore, my findings of this research will always be partial and interpretive. Thus, telling the stories might go untold (in the case of Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs and their customer loyalty practices), as too, revealing wider patterns which might or might not be consistent over space and time. Being honest, truthful and particularly maintaining good ethics were very important to me as a researcher. Equally, the responsibility to others, the outcome of the research, discipline and its boundaries, and university ethical approval were kept in mind during the site visits.

4.4 Strengths and weaknesses

The main strength of the research design was its ability to provide the researcher with rich descriptive data that informed the open-ended research questions. Another strength of the research design was all of the learning that came with the collection and analysis of the qualitative data. The selected methodologies demanded that the researcher learn to be hyper-aware of potential biases and influences, and also to be critical of how and in what situations truths emerge. It was important for the researcher to observe appropriate research ethics. Case study methodology stimulated a great deal of discussion about the topic. The wealth of writing on the topic allowed the researcher to develop a strong foundation in research ethics.

The selected methodology and the literature on qualitative research methodology emphasizes the importance of establishing relationships of trust within research settings, particularly with those who participate in interviews and observation environments, in order to truly unlock the knowledge of people within the research setting. The shared interest in understanding how to develop better retail ventures and enhancing their customer loyalty was a strong starting point for establishing the trusting relationship.

Equally, the researcher is a Sri Lankan who also shares the same cultural values and the language. Therefore, it was beneficial when conducting an interview with the owner/ manager to better understand what they were trying to say and interpret exactly. Thus, it could generate a good relationship and trust between the researcher and the venture owner(s).

The research had its weaknesses as well. While the data was rich and descriptive, it was also messy and plentiful. The researcher recognizes that given the interpretive element of both the data and the analysis, two researchers were not guaranteed to come to the same conclusions. The exploratory nature of this research enabled the researcher to collect an abundance of data, which could have been analysed in a number of ways. The work presented in this thesis represents just a snapshot of what the data has to offer. The analysis and synthesis involved in all exploratory qualitative research come with uncertainty, and the research progress in the present research sometimes slowed down beyond the researcher's expectations.

The chosen research design clearly has both strengths and weaknesses. The research produced an abundance of rich and meaningful data. While the researcher analysed only a portion of what the data had to offer, the quantity of the collected data was a strength. The researcher was able to collect data from eight different cases. Miles, Huberman and Saldana (2014, p. 33) commend the collection of data across multiple cases, pointing to the confidence such data collection can add to findings: ‘Multiple-case sampling allows us to strengthen the precision, validity, stability and trustworthiness of the findings’.

4.4.1 Data collection challenges due to Coronavirus

The researcher started to collect the data around January 2020. He successfully collected two samples between the months of January and February. However, he could not collect the data from March 2020 to July 2020. This is due to the Coronavirus national lockdown from March 2020. This had serious consequences to the data collection process of this research. Many of the participants were denied participation in the interviews during the national lockdown. At the same time, as a researcher, I could not leave the house during this time because it was a legal requirement. The data collection started again in July 2020 to September 2020, immediately after the lockdown rules were lowered. Another impact is that the researcher had to limit the time spent inside the shops during the interview because of the social distancing rules. This had serious consequences to making valuable field note data for the research and limited the time to finish the research project. Also, it was very challenging to gain access to data from the participants after the lockdown. It took three months to gain access to six more samples.

4.5 Summary

This chapter has discussed the philosophical position of the study - interpretivism, and the justification for this choice. Then, the inductive research approach was selected to explore the phenomenon. It adopts a case study approach with multiple cases, purposive sampling technique, and unstructured interviews as the main data collection method, along with field notes. It has discussed the analysis of the data with-in cases as well as cross-case analysis. Ethical considerations were also mentioned during the data collection process. Research strength and weaknesses were mentioned, particularly during the Coronavirus pandemic. Lastly, research validity discussed to demonstrate the trustworthiness of the research, reflexivity, positionality along with the politics of representation discussed to demonstrate the awareness of various elements which may have influenced research process.

Chapter 5: Findings

5.0 Introduction

The collection of case study summaries can be used as a reference for the reader. As mentioned in Chapter 4, this thesis is designed with traditional case study analysis, which includes the with-in case analysis, and cross case analysis. The first section includes case descriptions, and this is then followed by the key themes generated in each case which will be presented in a summative format. For a full comprehensive with-in-case analysis, please see Appendix 3. Finally, the cross-case findings will be presented in section 5.2.

5.1 The individual case description and summaries:

Case 1 description and key insights:

Ravi (C1) runs a small retail shop in West London, UK. According to Ravi, he has been running this business for over twenty-five years. Ravi came to the UK about thirty years ago from Sri Lanka to pursue his career in IT (information technology). He successfully completed his Higher National diploma in IT and had secured a job. However, he had been made redundant from his job at the time and since it was difficult to find another job at the time and he wanted extra money to have a good family life in the UK, he ended up opening a retail shop in the aforementioned area. According to him, his father also used to have a family business back in Sri Lanka, and he was also involved in that family business in Sri Lanka when he was young. He managed to open up two other businesses gradually but closed them due to the family life imbalance. He said he is currently happy with one business and that is why it has been running for over twenty years.

Individual analysis (Micro-analysis): Case 1 Key insights/ findings from the data

Entrepreneurial orientation

- Due to redundancy and lack of job opportunities at the time, C1 had to form a business. However, C1 mentioned that decision making power and independence kept motivating him to be in the business for a long time.
- C1 revealed that he has achieved enough in his life through his business for him and for his family.
- C1 learned his customer interaction skills through his family business in Sri Lanka, and his wife and his son are currently involved with him in the business in the UK..
- C1 used his social network to gain business knowledge and access to financial capital for his business.

Emerged themes

Push factors, Pull factors, subjective measures for success, Family relations (or familiness), and social capital

Customer relationship

- Case 1, data given by C1 suggest that he cares more about customer satisfaction than making money and tends to show the customer that as a business, he values and cares for them in his business.
- C1 mentioned that he is re-orienting his business in order to make it more emerging European-customer friendly due to declining South-Asian customer presence in the area.
- C1 makes changes in his business often based on regular customer feedback.
- C1 treats the customer in the same way it would feel for himself if he was in the same situation as a customer and he tends to treat them as his close friend, and is more into satisfying them than making a sale.
- C1 tends to calm the customer by listening to them in such scenarios, because he believes that being patience towards the customer has an influence to retain them.
- C1 also appeared to be developing collaborative selling and does not call himself a 'salesperson'.
- C1 creates customer convenience by offering valuable products at an affordable price near to the locals' houses.
- C1 mentioned that practicing good business ethics and responding to the customer's complaints immediately may have contributed to earning his business reputation in the area.

Operational benevolence, problem-solving orientation, customer orientation, customer centricity, empathy and patience for the customers, collaborative selling, and business reputation

Figure 2 : Case 1 key insights Individual analysis (Micro-analysis)

Economic/opportunity structure (Meso level analysis):

- C1 has an opportunity to serve the emerging European customer demand.
- Due to the arrival of new European customers instead of South-Asian/Sri Lankan customers, he struggles to communicate efficiently with these new customers due to their lack of knowledge of speaking English.
- C1 mentioned that South-Asian/Sri Lankan customer demand is declining in his business. He believes that this is due to the cost of living/rental property market in the area.

Emerged themes

Emerging European customer demand, language barriers, and declining South-Asian customer demand

Institutional embeddedness (Macro analysis):

- C1 is currently facing new customers in his business, particularly people from European economic area. On the plus side, he re-orientes his business towards serving these people in the area. On the negative side, is the gradually declining demand for South-Asian or Sri Lankan products, and C1 also mentioned that these new customers can barely communicate with him, as they have difficulty understanding the English language. Perhaps this could be partly due to these migrants who do not have any form of entry requirements, such as testing their ability to speak English or any other professional qualifications when they arrive in UK.
- He also mentioned that South-Asian people are disappearing from his area, perhaps, this is could also be due to the government’s highly regulated approach on non-EU migration.
- C1 mentioned that current import regulations not motivating him to import from Sri Lanka, hence he much more relying on local suppliers

EU migration to UK, non-EU migration to UK, and government support for the small businesses in UK

Figure 3 : Case 1 Key insights of Opportunity structure(Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)

Main theme and its subtheme(s) of Case 1	
Main theme	Subtheme(s)
Individual-level of Analysis (Micro)	
Push factors	Redundancy, Lack of job opportunities
Pull factors	Independence
subjective measures for success	Individual Satisfaction
Family relations (or familiness)	Tacit knowledge (having a family business background in Sri Lanka), Labour capital, Access to finance through family members
Social capital	Gaining business knowledge, financial resources through social network
Customer Relationship Related themes	
Operational benevolence	Limiting self-serving opportunism, values customer presence
problem-solving orientation	Favouring customer's interest even it cost to the business
Customer orientation	Orient the business to meet emerging (European) customer needs
Customer centricity	Prioritising customer feedback (especially long term customers) and make changes according to them
Empathy	Treating customer as if their family member, perspective-taking and using empathy as an aim to build customer satisfaction
Let the customer make the buying decision	Not convincing the customer to buy things that they don't need, does not believes in sales promotion

Business reputation	Not practising unethical marketing strategies, Does not want to drain customer money.
Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)	
Emerging European customer demand	Language barrier to communicate
Declining South-Asian customer demand	Difficulties to build good customer relationship
Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)	
Government policy on migration	EU migration to UK, non-EU migration to UK
Issues with Rules and Regulations	Import regulations

Table 2: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case one

Case 2 description and key insights:

Van (C2) came to the UK as a student for study purposes over thirty-five years ago to obtain a degree in electrical engineering. His father was a politician in Sri Lanka, and his mother was a housewife. He has one brother in his family, and he used to have a business in the UK and Sri Lanka as well. As time passed, he didn't complete his degree and he started working in a supermarket as a sales assistant. He said he left the degree because it was a very hard time for him, and he wanted a break from his student life. He then joined a supermarket for work. After five good years, he left the supermarket as a manager and joined a partnership with his friends to run a retail business as a joint venture. It did not take long for him to realise that he could do much better without his partners, as they were consistently letting him down for various reasons. So he took a risk and left the partnership to open his own business on his savings in the area in which he lived at the time. Eventually, as time went by, he got married and has two children with him at the moment. After thirty years in business, he is optimistic about the future as he is planning to grow his small business to become a bigger brand one day. His business is situated in a Sri Lankan immigrant concentrated area and there are other Sri Lankan ethnic shops visible to his shop. His business serves mainly these Sri Lankan immigrants as he offers Sri Lankan ethnic retail products and other South-Asian retail products through his shop.

Individual analysis (Micro-analysis): Case 2 Key insights/ findings from the data

Entrepreneurial orientation

- Independence and decision-making power (autonomy) motivated C2 to form a business.
- Having no debts, making enough money to satisfying the needs of the family is viewed as success.
- His wife is involved in the business, and he seeks business knowledge from his brother.
- Knowledge was primarily gained from previous work place
- C2 shows a good relationship with his surroundings and suppliers. But interestingly, his case shows the downside of the social embeddedness where his friends (later became business partners) had a negative impact for his previous business. And at the same time he experienced issues with the employees as well.

Emerged themes

Pull factors, subjective measures for success, family relations (or familiness), and social capital, knowledge and skills

Customer relationship

- C2 demonstrated that he shares his honest view with customers, and values them in his business.
- C2 specifically targets Sri Lankans in the area, develops item variety based on customer feedback, and makes sure there are no complaints repetitively concerning the same products.
- C2 mentioned that he focusses much more on satisfying the customer than making money, and treats the customers as if they are family members
- C2 makes sure that his customers feel that they are being listened. He also believes that it will show the customers that he, as a businessman, has kindness and patience towards them; hence that is good sign of quality service, which they can't get from supermarkets.
- C2 does not wants to pressure the customer to buy a product from him, yet gives the necessary information needed for the product decision.
- C2 maintains his product quality through well branded products in the market and suppliers.
- C2 buys them as bulk from aforementioned suppliers so he can offer a cheap price.
- C2 creates convenience to enable the Sri Lankans who live in the area to buy the Sri Lankan products near to their houses.
- C2 stayed in the business for thirty years, which he believes he earned by working hard to satisfy the customers and over time it built it to a brand value. He believes also that he has a good supplier relationship with them due to his brand reputation.

Operational benevolence, problem solving orientation, operational competence, customer orientation, customer centricity, empathy and patience for the customers, collaborative selling, product quality, convenience, price and business reputation

Figure 4: Case 2 key insights Individual analysis (Micro-analysis)

Economic/opportunity structure (Meso level analysis):

- C2 has an advantage of low language barriers when interacting with his customers as his business situated in a Sri Lankan immigrants concentrated area.
- C2 does not see the importance of online presence to his business.
- He uses much more traditional marketing strategies, such as word of mouth to promote his business.
- C2 has an opportunity to serve evolving European customer presence in his area.

Emerged themes

Low language barriers, online presence, ethnic enclave, and evolving European customer market

Institutional embeddedness (Macro analysis):

- C2 wanted to open a restaurant back in the day, but due to the council restrictions at the time he did not manage to get a licence to open a restaurant in the same place. So, he opened a retail shop instead, which he found raised no issues with the council, and he managed to pay the mortgage at the time.

Government support for the small businesses in UK.

Figure 5: Case 2 Key insights of Opportunity structure(Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)

Main theme and its subtheme(s) of Case 2	
Main theme	Subtheme(s)
Individual-level of Analysis (Micro)	
Pull factors	Independence
Subjective measures for success	Having no debts and support for the family
Family relations (or familiness)	Labour Capital, gaining/sharing business knowledge (having a family business background in Sri Lanka)
Human Capital	Previous work experience
Social capital	Supplier Relationship, employee relationship, downside of the social relations
Customer Relationship Related themes	
Operational benevolence	Limiting self-serving opportunism, values customer presence
problem-solving orientation	Favouring customer's interest even it cost to the business
Operational competence	Product knowledge transferred to observable behaviours.
Customer orientation	Orient the business to meet the Sri Lankan customer needs
Customer centricity	Prioritising regular customer feedback and make changes according to them
Empathy	Treating customer as if their family member, perspective-taking and using empathy as an aim to build customer satisfaction
Developing patience for the customer	Giving time to Listen to the customer and values kindness towards them

Let the customer make the buying decision	Not convincing the customer to buy things, giving necessary information to customer to make the buying decision.
Business reputation	Able to Buy products on credits from suppliers, working hard over time to give good impression of the business.
Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)	
Sri Lankan ethnically concentrated area	Low language barrier
Online presence	Traditional ways of marketing
Emerging european customer presence	
Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)	
Government policy on migration	EU migration to UK, non-EU migration to UK
Issues with rules and regulations	Had to change the initial business idea

Table 3: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case two

Case 3 description and key insights:

Dan (C3) runs a small retail shop in Central London. Recently, he left the full-time job he held for around sixteen years in the UK to evolve as an entrepreneur. Dan came to the UK around twenty years ago. He said he came with his wife for life change and to explore career opportunities in the UK. His wife had a job offer in the UK as a nurse and so he immigrated to the UK with his wife. He has a degree in philosophy. However, due to his lack of English knowledge at the time, he started his career in the food and hospitality sector and then slowly rose to the top experienced position by the time he left the job. However, he had an opportunity to own a premise which he often passed during his full-time employment days. He came to know this place was available through one of his friends. At the time, he was also looking for opportunities to open a business, so he opened a business as a retail shop, but much more focused on Sri Lankan food ingredients and other smaller retail foods. He said his wife supports him greatly and so do his friends as well. Fast-forward to today, he has been in the business for a little over five years now. He intends to diversify his business by opening a plant-based food factory in the near future.

Individual analysis (Micro-analysis): Case 3 Key insights/ findings from the data

Entrepreneurial orientation

- Mainly freedom of decision making (autonomy) , and financial benefits have influenced C3 to form a business.
- Profit generation through the business to maintain a healthy cash flow and family life have been viewed as success.
- C3 involved his wife in the business as an accountant, and his brother for gaining business information.
- C3 mainly used his social network for finding staff and obtaining the premises for his business.

Customer relationship

- C3 does not charge for an unsatisfactory product, instead he offers a free item to compensate, without asking for payment proof as he believes that will increase the customer trust over the business and he values the customer.
- C3 tends to listen to the customers and orient the business towards it to serve their needs.
- C3 demonstrated that focusing on customer satisfaction and adopting their point of view is more important than earning profits, hence it will increase the loyalty and retention.
- C3 tends to avoid unnecessary arguments with the customers by making the customers calm and showing compassionate behaviour towards them; hence he believes it contributes to customer retention as well.
- C3 tends to allow customers to make the buying decision by giving the correct information.
- C3 revealed that he is much more concerned about product quality than the product quantity. Hence, he handpicked his products from top brands from the sector.
- C3 argues that he takes time and energy to create the value for the customer in his business, hence the price should be 'reasonable' rather cheap.
- C3 mentioned that Sri Lankans who work in central London can come to his shop, rather than take the tube to Wembley (ethnic concentrated area)
- C3 thinks that integrity, credibility, quality, hard work and the way business present itself to the customer also matter to reputation

Emerged themes

Push factors, subjective measures for success, family relations (or familiness), and social capital

Operational benevolence, problem-solving orientation, operational competence, customer orientation, customer centricity, empathy and patience for the customers, collaborative selling, product quality, convenience, price and business reputation

Figure 6: Case 3 Key insights of Individual analysis (micro analysis)

Economic/opportunity structure (Meso level analysis):

- C3 took an opportunity to serve Sri Lankans who work/live in Central London.
- C3 also has also been impacted by the Coronavirus. decreasing sales and profits, supplier delays, lack of staff due to safety measures, working environment challenges due to safety measures, managing the business, and business uncertainty due to Corona virus.
- However, his online sales appeared to have increased during that time.

Emerged themes

Opportunity to serve missed by others, increased online sales, and Coronavirus impacts.

Institutional embeddedness (Macro analysis):

- He currently uses the government furlough scheme to pay his staff wages
- C3 since he opened the business, he had to comply with many regulations, and these regulations sometimes lead him to spend a lot (health safety regulations in the building)
- Allowing less customers into the building at once, making some customers wait for a long time, or leaving without any shopping at all.
- Lastly, C3 believes that overall rules and regulations must be in place to run the business safely for the people and for others.

Furlough scheme, government support for the small businesses in UK

Figure 7: Case 3 Key insights of Opportunity structure(Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)

Main theme and its subtheme(s) of Case 3	
Main theme	Subtheme(s)
Individual-level of Analysis (Micro)	
Pull factors	Independence, financial benefits
subjective measures for success	Maintain a good family life
Objective measures of success	Business profit and cashflow
Family relations (or familiness)	Labour capital, gaining/sharing business knowledge
Social capital	Obtaining business information, access to labour capital (finding staff)
Customer Relationship Related themes	
Operational benevolence	Limiting self-serving opportunism, values customer presence
Problem-solving orientation	Favouring customer's interest even it cost to the business
Customer orientation	Orient the business to meet customer needs
Customer centricity	Prioritising customer and make changes according to them
Empathy	perspective-taking and using empathy as an aim to build customer satisfaction
Developing patience for the customer	Giving time to Listen to the customer and make them calm
Let the customer make the buying decision	Giving necessary information to customer to make the buying decision
Business reputation	Concerning integrity, credibility and focus on hard work towards earning customer impression

Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)	
Serving places that others missed	
Corona virus Impacts	Decreasing sales and making fewer products, supplier delays, working environment challenges, increased online sales, business uncertainty.
Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)	
government support for the small businesses in UK	Financial support from the government, positive feedback on rules and regulations
Issues with the rules and regulations	Many regulations to follow

Table 4: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case three

Case 4 description and key insights:

Ken (C4) runs a small retail shop in South London. He came here for higher studies from Sri Lanka nearly eighteen years ago. He also has a business background as his father used to run a property business in Sri Lanka. He said he didn't work for his family business because he came to the UK for higher studies at a very young age. He currently holds a degree in business administration. He used to work as a manager in a retail business for over five years before he opened his own business. He said he wanted to build everything from scratch and be independent. He left his managerial job and then he opened up a retail business, focusing on local people in the area. He has been in the retail business for nearly eight years and enjoys spending time at his business. Furthermore, he mentioned that this is his choice of life rather than using education qualifications and ending up with a white-collar job. In his business, he currently sells day to day groceries, plus beverages. Since he comes from a family business background in Sri Lanka, Ken still asks for advice and sometimes receives business knowledge from his father. He said it was very helpful for him when he was setting up the business, particularly in the early stages. However, he is married now and has a supportive wife. He also mentioned that his friends were also supporting him. He is willing to expand his business further within the next five-ten years, but all plans are stopped temporarily due to the Coronavirus situation.

Individual analysis (Micro-analysis): Case 4 Key insights/ findings from the data

Entrepreneurial orientation

- Independence, financial benefits and previous work experience have influenced C4 to form a business
- C4 views family wellbeing as a success
- C4 gained business knowledge from his father and their family business back home, and his wife is currently involved his business.
- He learnt many of the business knowledge and skills from his previous workplaces
- C4 uses his social network to get cheaper product information, obtain equipment and finding staff.

Customer relationship

- Giving more honest opinion on products, so that a customer can make the right decision is important to C4 rather than always attempting to make a sale.
- C4 is concerned about identifying the needs of the customers, so he no longer selling ethnic products as he believes it does not meet the needs of the customers in the area.
- Paying attention to the customer and adding or removing products from his shop according to their feedback regularly is also important to his business.
- C4 tends to think on the customer side first rather than the business objectives
- C4 thinks his tolerant nature has helps him to calm some customers, making them feel good by using humour.
- C4 believes that making money while losing the customer is pointless for him.so he makes the customer buy the right product by giving them an honest opinion even though he loses money.
- Length of time in the business and no wrong doings (good business ethics) in between have contributed to earning his business reputation.

Emerged themes

Pull factors, subjective measures for success, family relations (or familiness), knowledge and skills, and social capital.

Operational benevolence, customer orientation, customer centricity, empathy and patience for the customers, collaborative selling, business reputation

Figure 8: Case 4 Key insights of Individual analysis(micro analysis)

Economic/opportunity structure (Meso level analysis):

- Lack of retail shops around the time he took over the business has made him set up the retail shop in the area.
- C4 currently faces mini-supermarkets as increased competition in the area.
- Managing stock for the business is also a challenge for him.
- C4 business was also impacted by Coronavirus situation. Coronavirus safety standards, supermarkets as challenges and limited staff were highlighted in the case.

Emerged themes

Supermarkets as a challenge, stock management as a challenge and Corona virus impacts.

Institutional embeddedness (Macro analysis):

- Government regulations over closing time has made his business lose the late-night sales
- C4 appreciates the furlough scheme, as he uses it to pay his staff wages
- C4 believes that UK has straightforward laws and regulations which makes it easier to follow.

Furlough scheme, and government support for the small businesses in UK.

Figure 9: Case 4 Key insights of Opportunity structure (Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)

Main theme and its subtheme(s) of Case 4	
Main theme	Subtheme(s)
Individual-level of Analysis (Micro)	
Pull factors	Independence, financial benefits, previous work experience
Subjective measures for success	Making good enough money to support the family, having a good mental and physical health
Family relations (or familiness)	Labour capital, gaining/sharing business knowledge
Social capital	Obtaining business information, access to labour capital (finding staff), supplier relationship
Customer Relationship Related themes	
Operational benevolence	Limiting self-serving opportunism, values customer presence
Customer orientation	Orient the business to meet customer needs
Customer centricity	Individual customer service
Empathy	perspective-taking and using empathy as an aim to build customer satisfaction
Developing patience for the customer	Being Tolerant towards customer
Let the customer make the buying decision	Giving necessary information to customer to make the buying decision
Business reputation	No illicit practices, able to buy on credit with suppliers.

Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)	
Serving places that others missed	
Mini supermarket as a challenge	
Stock management as a challenge	
Corona virus Impacts	Sales were up during pandemic, working environment challenges.
Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)	
Government support for the small businesses in UK	Financial support from the government, positive feedback on rules and regulations, coronavirus support

Table 5: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case four

Case 5 description and key insights:

Sura (C5) came to the UK around fifteen years ago as a result of the ongoing conflict situation in Sri Lanka at the time. Once he landed in the UK, he immediately started to work in a retail shop in London, owned by his relative from Sri Lanka. He worked in this retail shop for around five years as an employee. Then the shop owner started to make losses and eventually wanted to sell the business. As a result, Sura took over the business with the help from the previous owner. He has run the business himself for nearly ten years now. In this short time, he has managed to expand the business into multiple shops across London and employs around 60-70 employees across his multiple shops by the time of this interview. He is still actively working in his main shop, side by side with other employees. By the time all this happened, he got married and has two kids in his family. He is still connected to his family back in Sri Lanka as well. He also came from a business family background where his father also ran a retail business in Sri Lanka. His father's business is also one of his main suppliers as he imports many of his products directly from Sri Lanka. However, Sura expects to open another shop in October in London, but this is on hold as the Coronavirus uncertainty continues.

Individual analysis (Micro-analysis):

Case 5 Key insights/ findings from the data

Entrepreneurial orientation

- Opportunity to take over a business because of job insecurity and financial gains supporting the family
- Wants to invest in the hotel and accommodation industry due to declining second generation demand for ethnic foods in the future.
- Business growth as a success
- Advice from parents and getting products through their business often involved in his business
- Experience from the previous workplace helped him to expand the business
- Finding staff, financial access, getting help from friends with some labour works and having a good

Emergед themes

Push factors, Family relations (or familiness), social capital, success perception, knowledge and skills.

Customer relationship

- Always think about the customer's point of view.
- Orienting product selection to serve the customer needs
- Treating the customer individually believing each customer is different.
- Making the customer comfortable when sharing feedback towards the business.
- Making the customer calm and ready to listen before sharing his views with them.
- C5 believes dealing with customers takes time to learn as it is a skill.
- Increase in product variety so that people can make a choice. He also does not want to involve or make a buying decision for the customer.
- C5 does not sell cheap products, as he believes it will damage his reputation.

Operational benevolence, Customer orientation, Customer centricity, empathy and patience for customers, collaborative selling and business reputation

Figure 10: Case 5 Key insights of individual analysis (micro analysis)

Economic/opportunity structure (Meso level analysis):

- Family-related business owner gave him an opportunity to take over a business.
- Living in Sri Lankan immigrant concentrated area allowed him to identify the market opportunity to evolve as a Sri Lankan retail shop.
- C5 does not have more online presence than his competitors
- Coronavirus has impacted his business as well, such as supply delays, service delays and created a challenging working environment.
- However, overall sales increased during the lockdown.

Emerged themes

Family relations, ethnic enclaves, Coronavirus impacts

Institutional embeddedness (Macro analysis):

- Using government support during a pandemic to pay the staff.
- Using council information to open a new shop in another area in London.
- Current import and tax regulations take longer to clear his goods, hence it is affecting product quality.
- He believes rules and regulations help him to run his business smoothly in UK.

Furlough scheme, government support for the small businesses in UK

Figure 11: Case 5 Key insights of Opportunity structure (Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)

Main theme and its subtheme(s) of Case 5	
Main theme	Subtheme(s)
Individual-level of Analysis (Micro)	
Push factors	Job insecurity, family maintenace
Objective measures for success	Business growth
Family relations (or familiness)	Gaining/sharing business knowledge
Human Capital	Previous work experience
Social capital	Access to financial capital, Labour capital, Supplier Relationship, employee relationship
Customer Relationship Related themes	
Operational benevolence	Prioritising the customer interest
Customer orientation	Orient the business to meet customer needs
Customer centricity	Individual customer service
Empathy	perspective-taking and using empathy as an aim to build customer satisfaction
Developing patience for the customer	Being Tolerant towards the customer and views patience as a skill.
Let the customer make the buying decision	Does not want to be a sales person.
Business reputation	Focused more on quality, rather than cheap items.
Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)	
Sri Lankan ethnically concentrated area	Gap in local market
Family relations helped him to acquire a business	Opportunity recognition promoted by social relations
Online Presence	Online presence way behind than the other businesses

Corona virus Impacts	Sales were up during pandemic, supplier delays, Service delays, working environment challenges.
Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)	
government support for the small businesses in UK	Financial support from the government, positive feedback on rules and regulations, Using council information to make decisions.
Issues with rules and Regulations	Import regulations.

Table 6: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case five

Case 6 description and key insights:

Hesh (C6) came to UK about ten years ago for his higher studies from Sri Lanka. During his studies, he used to do part-time jobs to cover his living expenses. According to Hesh, he used to work in various sectors during this short time. He has worked in retail, hospitality, health and hygiene sector-related jobs. After completing his degree in accounting, plus numerous part-time job experiences with contacts he had created during this time, he wanted to look for the opportunities to run his own business, rather than work for someone. So, he decided to open a small retail shop which would require less manpower and start-up capital. The influence to run his own business didn't come out of nowhere, as he also came from a family business background from Sri Lanka. His parents currently run a successful catering business in his home country in Sri Lanka. He said his father helped him financially, and he found reliable staff and promoting his business in the beginning through his contacts in the UK. Around five and half years ago, Hesh managed to put everything together, and opened his owned retail business in an area where he is lived and spent most of the time in London. He got married three years ago and has one child and are expecting their second child soon. He mentioned that his wife is also a big help for him in running his business, as she helps him in busy times and does various administration work for him. He wants to expand his retail business further, particularly online. He opened another business in the health sector recently as well. However, at the moment it is closed and the retail business expansion is currently on hold due to the Coronavirus situation and its economic impacts.

Individual analysis (Micro-analysis): Case 6 Key insights/ findings from the data

Entrepreneurial orientation

- Previous job dissatisfaction, independence and greater decision making power(autonomy) motivated him to open a business
- Customer satisfaction, no debts and family needs have been seen as success
- Building a business reputation is the future for him
- His parents running a family business
- Father helped him financially
- social networking helped him to share business knowledge and find trustworthy staff

Emerged themes

Pull factors, Push factors, subjective measures for success, family relations (or familiness) and social capital

Customer relationship

- Giving the right product information for the customer with the right price, makes the customer feel cared for.
- Changed to serve the locals; Sri Lankan/South Asian locals helped him to operate without any more losses.
- Personalised service for regular customers
- Treating the customer as he or his wife would expect to receive as a customer in another shop.
- C6 thinks good service is linked to customer retention
- Giving full attention to the customer is key to understanding them
- C6 thinks patience and kindness towards the customer helps to grow business reputation.
- C6 Does not like to drain the money of the customers
- C6 also offers well-branded quality products for the customers
- C6 thinks offering a good price is linked to customer retention but cannot offer the same as supermarkets
- Practising business ethic allows him to maintain family business reputation

Operational benevolence, customer orientation, customer centricity, empathy and patience for the customers, collaborative selling, business reputation

Figure 12: Case 6 Key insights of individual analysis (micro analysis)

Economic/opportunity structure (Meso level analysis):

- Low market entry barriers helped him to form a business in the retail sector
- The Sri Lankan immigrant concentrated area helped him to have cultural advantages
- Cultural values for better job performance
- Language barriers when dealing with foreign people
- Coronavirus impacted his business as well, such as lack of staff, increased price, having a challenging work environment, and business uncertainty.
- Overall the number of new customers has increased during lockdown

Emerged themes

Market entry barriers, ethnic enclaves, cultural identity, language barriers, and Coronavirus impacts

Institutional embeddedness (Macro analysis):

- C6 mentioned that financial access through institutions is long and difficult
- C6 thinks Tax and other costs are high in London
- C6 on furlough scheme and actively using it
- C6 believes that rules and regulations allowed him to regulate his business and make a safer place for everyone

Furlough scheme, government support for the small businesses in UK

Figure 13: Case 6 Key insights of Opportunity structure (Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)

Main theme and its subtheme(s) of Case 6	
Main theme	Subtheme(s)
Individual-level of Analysis (Micro)	
Push factors	Job dissatisfaction
Pull factor	Independence
Subjective measures for success	Individual satisfaction (Social status), having no debts, having a good life with own terms, and fulfilment of family needs
Family relations (or familiness)	Tacit Knowledge (having a family business background in Sri Lanka), access to financial capital, access to labour capital.
Social capital	Sharing/gaining business knowledge, access to labour capital, Employee relationship
Customer Relationship Related themes	
Operational benevolence	Limiting self-serving opportunism
Customer orientation	Orient the business to meet customer needs
Customer centricity	Individual customer service
Empathy	Perspective-taking and using empathy as an aim to build customer satisfaction, Values customer presence
Developing patience for the customer	Giving time to Listen to the customer and make them calm
Let the customer make the buying decision	Does not want to be a salesperson.
Business reputation	No illicit/cheap practices
Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)	
Sri Lankan ethnically concentrated area	Low language barriers, similar cultural values for better job performance
Low market entry barriers	Low start-up capital

Corona virus Impacts	Number of customers increased during the pandemic, lack of staff, price increase on products, working environment challenges, Business uncertainty.
Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)	
government support for the small businesses in UK	Financial support from the government (furlough scheme), positive feedback on rules and regulations,
Financial access through institutions	Long Processing time

Table 7: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case six

Case 7 description and key insights:

Mahi (C7) came to the UK around twenty years ago to study a degree in accounting and finance. Then, after a year, he realised that studying to become an accountant was not for him. He started to work full time in a retail supermarket and other part-time works to keep the expenses minimum while he was studying. In the meantime, he got married here in the UK and currently, he has two kids with his wife. As time went by, he and his wife felt that they were living in an expensive area, and they wanted to give their kids a good education as they were getting older. Mahi looked for alternative places which he could afford and at the same time have a good community with good schools. He mentioned that it took a long time to find a place which 'ticked all the boxes' and it was difficult to find a place where he could reach his friends and relatives at the same time. Then he found a place in South London, where his business is currently operating. He looked for job opportunities in the area according to his work experience but found that a difficult task too as he could not do the same jobs because of the distance and time it would take to travel to them. So, he came up with the idea of opening a small retail business and moved with the family to the present location. Mahi also comes from a family business background, where his uncle (mother's sibling) runs a retail business in Sri Lanka and he used to work for him before he came to the UK. He mentioned that this has also helped him to develop good customer relationships in his business. He has been running his business, for ten years now. His wife and his brother support him, and actively engage in the business. However, his business is currently facing uncertainty and developing difficulties due to the Coronavirus pandemic.

Individual analysis (Micro-analysis):

Case 7 Key insights/ findings from the data

Entrepreneurial orientation

- Lack of job opportunities within the local market, family support/survival, and language barriers have motivated him to open the business
- Business as a result of teamwork, stress free family life/support and family bond with business has been seen as success
- His wife is currently involving in the business
- He used to work in his family relative's business in Sri Lanka before landing in UK
- Good supplier relationship, information sharing, financial access, opportunity exploring, and human capital gained through his social surroundings

Customer relationship

- Giving honest opinions to the customer even if he does not necessarily made a sale out of it; hence he thinks customers keep coming back to visit his shop.
- He thinks he knows what the local customers need in the area, so he attempts to provide them through his shop
- He thinks every customer is different in their own way, treating them individually may actually have earned his business reputation
- Making profit is not only objective as he not pushing the customer to make a sale but treating them nicely is a priority
- He exemplifies his tolerance at rush hour when customers pressure him to provide for their needs
- C7 mentioned that he does not want to 'push' the customer to make a sale.
- Individualised service, business ethics, moral principles and truly caring for the customer earned him his reputation.

Emerged themes

Push factors, subjective measures for success, familiness, and social capital

Operational benevolence, customer orientation, customer centricity, empathy and patience for the customers, collaborative selling, and business reputation

Figure 14: Case 7 Key insights of individual analysis (micro analysis)

Economic/opportunity structure (Meso level analysis):

- Low risk, low entry and exit market barriers gave him an opportunity to form a business
- Community with good spending power and lack of retail shops around the area influenced him to decide on a business location
- Coronavirus has impacted business for C7 as well. Low sales, lack of staff, supply delays, high product cost, and uncertainty were most significant in his case

Emerged themes

Market opportunities to entry/exit
Coronavirus impacts

Institutional embeddedness (Macro analysis):

- C7 is certain that the government can avoid uncertainty for his business
- Currently staff in furlough scheme
- Overall he believes that rules and regulations must be in place to operate the businesses successfully in the UK.

Furlough scheme, government support
for the small businesses in UK

Figure 15: Case 7 Key insights of Opportunity structure (Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)

Main theme and its subtheme(s) of Case 7	
Main theme	Subtheme(s)
Individual-level of Analysis (Micro)	
Push factors	Lack of job opportunities, Family maintenance, Language barriers
Subjective measures for success	Earn enough to have a stress-free life and family needs
Family relations (or familiness)	Access to labour capital, Tacit Knowledge (having a family business background in Sri Lanka), Access to Financial Capital, Gaining/sharing business knowledge.
Social capital	Supplier relationship, Sharing/gaining business knowledge, Access to financial capital.
Customer Relationship Related themes	
Operational benevolence	Limiting self-serving opportunism
Customer orientation	Orient the business to meet customer needs
Customer centricity	Individual customer service
Empathy	Using empathy as an aim to build customer satisfaction, Values customer presence
Developing patience for the customer	Giving time to Listen to the customer and make them calm, Being Tolerant towards the customer
Let the customer make the buying decision	Does not want to be a salesperson
Business reputation	No illicit practices

Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)	
Sri Lankan ethnically concentrated area	Low language barriers, similar cultural values for better job performance
Low market entry barriers	Low risk, could exit any time and find a job
Serving in places that others missed	Having a good community and lack of retail shops
Corona virus Impacts	Low sales, lack of staff, price increase on products, supplier delays, Business uncertainty.
Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)	
Government support for the small businesses in UK	positive feedback on rules and regulations.

Table 8: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case seven

Case 8 description and key insights:

Sachin (C8) came to UK around twenty-two years ago. He and the rest of his family moved together to the UK as a result of civil war in Sri Lanka at the time. He mentioned that he had just finished his GCSEs in Sri Lanka and was around 16+ years old when he arrived in London. When he arrived here, he started to work in a retail shop owned by an Indian. He worked there for 4+ years. Then he mentioned that he started to work for a supermarket for around two years. After that, he opened his own shop in the same area where he used to live most of the time in London. He believes that freedom, decision-making power, financial benefits and previous work experience influenced him to make this decision. In fact, he has run his business for thirteen years now and has managed to open another a branch in a nearby area. At the present, he is married and has two kids with him. He mentioned that his wife is actively involved in the business and supports him in every way. Sachin also came from a family business background in Sri Lanka. His father used to run multiple businesses back home. But he could not become involved in those businesses because he was very young at the time. He has two brothers and they help him in his business also, even though they not actively involved in it. He expects to grow his business into a well-known brand in the future. The current pandemic situation has created uncertainty and impacted his business as well.

Individual analysis (Micro-analysis): Case 8 Key insights/ findings from the data

Entrepreneurial orientation

- Previous work experience, independence and financial benefits have motivated C8 to form a business
- C8 views independence as success
- C8 does not want to take too much risk for fear of losing customers by increasing prices
- C8’s wife is currently involved in the business and his younger brothers also helps him.
- He also used his social network to access finance. Finding staff, and socially connecting with people in the area helped him to run the business easily

Emerged themes

Pull factors, subjective measures for success, family relations (or familiness), social capital, knowledge and skills

Customer relationship

- Does not want to increase the price as an opportunistic reaction to the pandemic situation
- C8 believes he understands every ethnic groups needs in the community, plus he tends to assess these needs by comparing his shop with other competitors in the area
- C8 tends to think customer point of view and making customer needs are a priority
- C8 also elaborates that caring for the customer is his priority rather than attempting to make a profit
- C8 believes that listening while being calm and polite might be a path to build a good reputation
- C8 also does not want to pressure the customers to make a sale and appreciates collaborative selling
- C8 offers products with branded products in the market, as it helped him to retain the customers and earn the trust over time.
- He does not want to increase the price of his product, as it risks losing them to a nearby supermarket which offers cheaper price
- Convenience as one customer mentioned that the customers can shop near to their houses with reasonable price with good quality
- Tolerant behaviour, politeness and running business in genuine ways has mainly helped him to earn his reputation among the community.

Operational benevolence, customer orientation, customer centricity, empathy and patience for the customers, collaborative selling, and business reputation

Figure 16: Case 8 Key insights of individual analysis (micro analysis)

Economic/opportunity structure (Meso level analysis):

- Access to finance, high competition in the market, lacking online presence and language barriers to serve emerging European customers in the area are where he currently faces challenges in his business.
- Coronavirus also impacted his business, such as lack of staff, supplier delays, creating a challenging working environment and creating future business uncertainty.

Emerged themes

High market competition, lacking online activities, European customer presence and Coronavirus impacts

Institutional embeddedness (Macro analysis):

- Some of his staff still in furlough scheme
- C8 overall positive regarding the rules and regulations in the UK
- But stresses that supermarkets and other retail giants should be regulated as they are attracting customers by opening mini supermarkets near to their businesses

Furlough scheme, government support for the small businesses in UK

Figure 17: Case 8 Key insights of Opportunity structure (Meso) and institutional embeddedness (Macro)

Main theme and its subtheme(s) of Case 8	
Main theme	Subtheme(s)
Individual-level of Analysis (Micro)	
Push factors	Independence, Financial benefits, Previous work experience.
Subjective measures for success	Independence/individual satisfaction
Family relations (or familiness)	Access to labour capital
Human Capital	Previous work experience
Social capital	Access to financial capital, Access to labour capital.
Customer Relationship Related themes	
Operational benevolence	Limiting self-serving opportunism
Customer orientation	Orient the business to meet customer needs
Customer centricity	Making decisions by centralising customer.
Empathy	Values customer presence
Developing patience for the customer	Giving time to Listen to the customer and make them calm.
Let the customer make the buying decision	Not stressing the customer to buying things
Business reputation	No marketing strategies that drain customer money, No illicit practices
Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)	
Access to finance	Low start-up capital due to difficulties to accessing finance.
High competition in the market	Supermarkets as a challenge
Emerging European customer demand	Language barriers to serve them

Lacking online presence	
Corona virus Impacts	Overall sales went up, supplier delays, Challenging working environment Business uncertainty.
Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)	
Government support for the small businesses in UK	positive feedback on rules and regulations, supermarket needs regulation.

Table 9: Summary of Main themes and its subtheme(s) of Case eight

5.2 Cross-case analysis

This section presents the findings from the cross-case analysis themes informed by individual case analysis. Each theme develops insights by using illustrative quotes that have emerged within case analysis. The main themes of these individual cases are: motivation to be in the business, success perception, human capital, social capital with sub-themes such as access to finance, labour capital, supplier relationship, employee relationship, and customer relationship. All the subthemes that emerged in the cross case will be analysed extensively under its respected main theme.

5.2.1 Motivation to be in the business

Factors	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6	Case 7	Case 8
(Pull)								
Independence	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓
Financial benefits			✓	✓				✓
Previous work experience				✓				✓
(Push)								
Job dissatisfaction						✓		
Lack of job opportunities found in the market	✓						✓	
Redundancy	✓							
Job insecurity					✓			
Family maintenance					✓		✓	
Language barriers							✓	

Table 10 : Motivation factors of individual cases

5.2.1.1 Pull factors

In the table above (Table 10) cross-case analysis shows how motivating factors have spread across the individual cases. Interestingly, many of these individuals have mentioned that they have been attracted to form a business influenced by three main factors: independence, financial benefits, and previous work experience (Case1, 2, 3, 4, 6 and 8).

a. Independence:

While many of these cases include the term independence in forming their business, it is interesting to mention how they view independence on their terms.

C1 mentioned that the ‘power to do anything’ within the business is a motivation for him, which exemplifies independence from his point of view:

“We have managed to run this business for a long time now. But you have the power to do anything. That is the motivation for doing business. Obviously, I had a business background before. And we decided - why should we work for somebody else, let’s work for ourselves instead. And we just went through it.”

Similarly, in Case 2, C2 formed a business as there should be no one telling him what to do, so he left the supermarket he was working at the time. In other words, having no one above him allowed him to do anything he wanted within his business, which could also refer to autonomy:

“I worked in a supermarket for five years and got experience. Then I felt that was enough of working for somebody, why not open a shop on my own, so nobody tells me what to do and that’s the freedom I wanted. So I left the job.”

Equally, C3 mentioned something similar, which was that he would rather create jobs by forming a business than work for somebody else. This is also very much aligned with C2, where C3 does not want to have anyone telling him what he should do next. This implies the ‘decision-making power’ he has once he formed the business, or in other words, the benefit of achieving the autonomy:

“I would rather create a job than a do a job. Nobody says anything as to what I do. There is nobody on top commanding me.”

Then, C4 views independence as ‘doing what he likes to do’, where he sees a full-time job is ‘something you have to do’. So, over the years, he relied on his business, survived, and continued with the business, hence it gave him back independence:

“There is a difference between jobs that you have to do, and in business, that you like to do. So, this is my choice, I like to do this. I rely on this, I survived on this and I got on with business. I feel like I’m more independent in this way.”

While C6 mentioned again in a statement the freedom of decision-making power he has with his business, which also can be interpreted as autonomy:

“When you run your own business, no one tells you what do to, you do what you want to do, whether it is right or wrong.”

And then, lastly, C8 added a similar statement which could also reflect autonomy:

“when you are running a business, you can work whenever you want to, you are your own boss, nobody tells you what to do, you will make mistakes, you will make losses and you will learn from them. Nobody is here to say anything and sack you. There are a lot of benefits for standing on your own feet.”

b. Financial benefits:

It appeared that some of these individuals were ‘pulled’ into forming a business, because it is indeed more financially rewarding than a full-time job. For instance, C3 said:

“plus, I make more money than I can make from a full-time job.”

C4 also shares a similar statement where he can earn more money than a full-time job, while enjoying the business:

“I find this as a business, not only hoping to get more money than a fulltime job, but I enjoy this.”

Lastly, C8 mentioned that a full-time job would get a fixed amount of salary every month, but in a business, the earnings are unlimited:

“Once you get employed by someone, you will almost always get a fixed salary every month. Here, nobody is stopping you making money - you can earn.”

c. Previous work experience:

In Case 4 and Case 8, data appeared to suggest that previous work experience and employers also influenced these individuals to form a business.

For instance, C4 mentioned that he gained his confidence and knowledge to form a similar business over time, and his employer helped him:

“Basically, I was running the business, I managed all the in and out like purchasing, to recording, selling and even employing as well. I think I did a better job over there. That’s where I decide, I can do this on my own. The thing is my boss taught me so many things and he helped as well.”

And then C8 added:

“I started work in different Off Licence shops for years. I learnt about these kinds of businesses a lot as I got older. Also, these business owners encourage me one day to run my own business.”

5.2.1.2 Push factors:

Data across the cases suggest that Case 1, Case 5, and Case 7, ‘pushed’ factors have influenced them to form a business. For instance, the lack of job opportunity in the market, redundancy, job insecurity, family maintenance and language barriers have been highlighted within the individual case study analysis.

a. Lack of job opportunities:

The lack of job opportunity in the market was reflected by C7, as it took a long time for him to find a job and the ones available were underpaid:

“This was a very hard process and took a long time. I found some jobs in retail, but not the same amount of money I was used to getting paid in my previous jobs, it's lower than that.”

Thus, C1 could not find a similar job after facing a job redundancy. So, he ended up owning a business.

“In Sri Lanka, I used to run our restaurant, jewellery shop, stationery and came here (UK), got back in to study IT and landed a job. Then I lost the job due to redundancy, couldn't find any good job relating to the field and ended up starting a business in retail.”

b. Family maintenance:

Moreover, family maintenance also became a push factor for some participants to form a business. For instance, C5 mentioned that he mainly got into the business for financial gain to support his family:

“I would say mainly profit or money, because you know you have a family to support.”

Meanwhile, C7 reflected a similar story about his motivation for forming a business. That is earning money through business for family survival and giving a good education to his children:

“We need money to survive, to feed the family. We are four of us. My kids need to have a good education - that requires money.”

c. Case unique factors:

There are four unique elements to push factors: language barriers, redundancy, job dissatisfaction, and job insecurity.

Only one case has experienced language as a barrier (English language) at the beginning of the business. He mentioned that he did not understand the English accent, particularly:

“I experienced this until I get to know the people and importantly the language. Sometimes I didn’t understand their accent in the beginning.”

C6 reflected job dissatisfaction in his statement:

“When you work for someone else, they don’t know how to get 100% out of you. It happened to me in the past.”

C1 also reflected job redundancy in his statement:

“In Sri Lanka, I used to run our restaurant, jewellery shop, stationery and came here (UK), got back in to study IT and landed a job. I lost the job due to redundancy, couldn’t find any good job relating to the field and ended up doing a business in retail.”

C5 reflected that one of the benefits he gets from owning a business is that nobody tells him to leave the job, which can be interpreted as job insecurity:

“I think at one point they will tell you to leave the job. But here, you have no one to get me out of this business because I am the boss.”

5.2.2 Success perception

Data that emerged from the cross-case analysis suggest that Sri Lankan minority ethnic entrepreneurs also view their success much more subjectively than objectively. Cases 1,2,4,6, and 8 primarily used subjective types of measures to explain their own terms of success. Other cases, such as Case 3 and Case 5, do not appear to have a similar view. But Case 3 used both subjective and objective measures to describe success while Case 5 primarily used objective measures of ‘business growth’ to view success. The table below gives a good idea of how these Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs view success as a summary.

Case no	Subjective measures of success	Objective measures of success
1	Individual satisfaction	
2	Having no debts, and fulfilment of family needs	
3	Maintain a good family life	Business profit and cashflow
4	Making good enough money to support the family, having a good mental and physical health	

5		Business growth
6	Individual satisfaction (Social status), having no debts, having a good life with own terms, and fulfilment of family needs	
7	Earn enough to have a stress-free life and family needs	
8	Independence/individual satisfaction	

Table 11: Subjective and objective measures of success

In the table above (Table 3), it is clear that these entrepreneurs view their success on their terms by using ‘subjective measures’. Hence, a few factors frequently emerged in the data. Those are: individual satisfaction, family support, and having no debts.

However, it is interesting to see these entrepreneurs hardly ever separate their personal/individual family life from their business. For instance, Case 4 (C4) Statement reflected this view;

“you should be a success in your family life and support them, your kids should have a good education, and your wife should support whatever you do and love you. You should make a good amount of money to support them and for you to have good mental and physical health.”

Cases 1, 2, 6, and 8 appear to have a common link with individual satisfaction in viewing success.

a. Individual satisfaction:

Various factors would contribute to the individual satisfaction of the entrepreneur, hence there is no exact definition to explain it (Cooper and Artz, 1995). However, some theorists suggest that this could be determined by looking at the difference between actual performance and their expected outcomes (Manzano-Garcia and Ayala-Calvo, 2020). Thus, scholars have mentioned

individual satisfaction as a success factor for entrepreneurs over the years (Solymossy, 1998; Walker and Brown, 2004).

C1 mentioned that he had achieved more than he wanted over time through the business for himself and his family. The statement below could elaborate on his individual satisfaction by comparing his past and present economic conditions:

“how you measure your success is, in a way, how you want to look at it. I believe I'm a successful person, I'm a successful leader, and I'm successful in business. There are ups and downs in the period. But overall in this time, I'm a successful person. I came into this country, with nothing. Today, 30 years down the line, I think I have achieved more than I wanted and for my family.”

According to the self-determination theory (Ryan and Deci, 2000), relatedness (connected with others) is one of the psychological needs for self-satisfaction. Similarly, Madduma and Watkins-Mathys (2019) found that gaining social recognition/status for success within their community is also important for Sri Lankan individuals to enter business activities. According to him, this is exemplified by C6, where customer satisfaction leading to gaining social recognition can be viewed as a success:

“in my view, if the customer is satisfied by our service and products, and they recommend us to another potential customer or share within the society, then I see this business is successful.”

On the other hand, gaining independence or autonomy is also an important psychological need to achieve self-satisfaction (Solymossy, 1998; Ryan and Deci, 2000). C8 mentioned that in a similar statement(s), he thinks that gaining independence /freedom is important.

First, C8 mentioned that he works every day and trains his mind to become independent, and then one day he can become the person he always wanted to be:

“Day by day you need to train your mind, then you have a plan on how to become independent, standing up from your own feet. Then you work hard for the person you want to be.”

Then he further added that he likes to work on his own (by forming a business), and the freedom it gives back, so he does not want anyone’s approval:

“I like to work for myself, and I like the freedom it gives back. I can make decisions at any time. I don’t need anyone’s approval.”

b. Support for the family:

According to Samaratunge and Nyland (2006), family support and savings, and embeddedness in their culture are vital ingredients of the Sri Lankan social security system and play a significant role in Sri Lankan culture. Perhaps, this is why almost all the cases explained their success by supporting the various family needs.

C4 mentioned that when his kids get a good education, the emotional support from his wife, and when he earns enough money to support (financially) them, this has been viewed as success:

“you should be a success in your family life and support, your kids should have a good education, your wife should support whatever you do and loves you. You should make a good amount of money to support them and for you to have good mental and physical health.”

Similarly, achieving financial security for the family is also demonstrated by C2:

“earning enough money to have a good stress free life for me and my family. One of the reasons I have started this business is my family.”

C6 mentioned that having no debts (financial security) and fulfilling family needs are also important to him:

“In terms of personal life, having no debts, earning enough living on my terms with a good life and fulfilling my family needs.”

Thus, C2 mentioned that achieving millionaire status is not his objective, but that success is achieved when earning enough money to gain financial security for his family and his business:

“All we need is to live nicely and safely, that’s all. I don’t even want to be too blind to believe that I want to become a millionaire one day, no and I don’t want to think like that. I don’t want that much and the reason is, I just want to live nicely with no fear of debt for the business and family and that’s it.”

5.2.3 Human capital

It seemed to be that having a family background in Sri Lanka, previous work experience, and social networks have helped them to gain their necessary skills to perform the entrepreneurial activities in the UK.

5.2.3.1 Having a family business background in Sri Lanka:

Ethnic entrepreneurs face difficulties when running a business in the host country. Some quickly adapt to the new business environment and learn important skills faster, while others may struggle for success. The family background in business appeared to have helped some of these entrepreneurs learn the necessary skills and knowledge to perform, or impact, their businesses positively, especially, on some occasions, while they were growing up. Some of the essential skills and knowledge appeared to be learned from back home and used within their current business activities in the UK. Thus, this provided tacit knowledge which is also related to positive attributes that family members can contribute to their family business as human capital. ‘Tacit knowledge’ means that knowledge is hard to codify and may transfer in experience and straight exposure (Dessi *et al.*, 2014). Some of the participants can be related to the literature.

For instance, C1 reflected in his statement that he used to work in his family business after leaving school. It helped him to learn customer interaction since his early days:

“Yes of course. We were running a small stationery business, which needed to be manned 9-5 every day. After leaving school, I was there all the time. At my early stage, it helped me to understand how to interact with customers, understand them and give them what they want.”

Similarly, C6 mentioned that he was involved in the business back home and learned the skills such as managing customers and staff:

“it is a family business you know, everyone is helping each other, regardless you gonna get pay or not. I couldn’t be involved in my family business back home at the moment as I settled here. But I have a good experience from back home on customer handling, how to manage and treat your staff well in your business.”

While C7 mentioned that a previous family business back home helped him to learn necessary skills that he appeared to use for his business today:

“Like I told you before, I used to work for him part-time back home. It has helped me a lot to learn how to interact with the customers, give a nice service and work along with them.”

Family relations help the owner’s decision-making process positively. In other ways, such interaction benefits the family business interface (Elizabeth and Baines, 1998). The literature findings can be reflected in Case 5. C5 mentioned that his father, who is currently running a similar business in Sri Lanka, has helped him increase the variety of the items in his shop, which exemplifies gaining and transferring knowledge among family members, hence influencing their decision making:

“I increased the variety of the items, my parents from back home also supported me a lot on this. Especially my father, I think he is an expert in these kinds of things.”

On the other hand, even though not working in their family business directly, they still gain knowledge or information from their family members of family businesses in Sri Lanka (VanAuken and Werbel, 2006).

C2, C3, and C4 are also in line with this argument.

C2 mentioned that his brother shared knowledge and experience on certain things:

“sometimes my brother shares his views and experiences on certain things as he used to have a business.”

C3 also mentioned that he seeks information from his family relative who runs a business in Sri Lanka:

“I ask for some business information from my brother in Sri Lanka who runs MDK back home.”

C4 similarly added that he seeks advice from his father as he believes his father is good at managing people:

“I did ask for advice and I still do ask, especially from my father from time to time. Not only in the business sense but in my personal life as well. My father was really good with managing people.”

On the other hand, many of the participants gained their knowledge and training skills through their previous workplaces in the UK as well.

5.2.3.2 Previous work experience:

However, the primary examples for human capital can be noted as: work experience, education and apprenticeship (Becker, 2009). This form of capital increases the efficiency and productivity for business ventures and entrepreneurs who can eventually grow their business into a bigger venture (Basu, 1998).

In the case of Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs, it has emerged that they gained their necessary retail knowledge and skills from their previous workplace.

C2 mentioned that he had enough experience from his retail supermarket job, so he left the job to form his own business:

“I worked in a supermarket for five years and got experience. Then I felt that was enough working for somebody, why not open a shop on my own so nobody tells me what to do and that’s the freedom I wanted. So I left the job.”

Then in a separate statement, C2 mentioned how work experience helps him manage his business today, in various ways, and commented that it would be hard to manage if he didn’t have such a job experience beforehand:

*“of course, work in the T***o helped me a lot. Managing people, the till, and dealing with customers and more. Otherwise, I would be lost.”*

Similarly, C4 mentioned that previous work experience has helped him learn customer buying behaviour, and communicating and building a relationship with the customer. On top of this, managing financial records and taking responsibility were also gained as skills:

“I worked so hard on the tills of other businesses, I got experience from those businesses. And I saw and experienced how people buy things, how to talk to them to get to know them. You have to be very careful when you work in those shops. Because you need to keep every receipt you make every day, properly arrange them and record them. Because you need to make two sets of receipts in a day You need to keep them, you need to stack them and you need to hand

them over to every day to the accountant or I would say the owner of the business at the time with the till balance. It was a very responsible job at the time.”

Similarly, C5 also added:

“By that time I also had a good experience in the field, and with that, I managed to expand the business.”

C8 mentioned that he came here when he was 16+ years old, and he started to work in different Off Licence shops over the years. Hence he learnt about the business model, managing customers, and his English speaking ability improved:

“I came here when I was 16+ years old. I started work in different off-licence shops over the years. I learnt about a lot these kinds of businesses as I got older. My English is way better now and I can handle two businesses, plus I know how to manage customers.”

5.2.2.3 Knowledge and information sharing through social network:

Cross case data suggest that these entrepreneurs also use their social networks to gain information and share knowledge within their social groups (Ram *et al.*, 2001).

For instance, C1 mentioned in a statement that sharing knowledge helps him solve the problems he faces in his retail business:

“Because if you are running a shop, you are able to solve any problem that comes towards you or your business. At the same time, if you are socially involved either community wise or business-wise, networking I mean, working all kind of these things, if you have a problem you put it to them, and they will come up with their own ideas. Okay, I did it like this - can you try it this way so then we can make a judgement, so when we applied that particular solution, most of the time you ended up solving the problem or you can look for alternative solutions by asking the people or friends who do the similar business. So, we gather a lot of knowledge by talking to our fellow friends, family relatives, fellow Asians. They may or may not be necessary in the business. Sometimes I speak to the customers as well.”

On the other hand, C6 also reflected in his statement about sharing/gaining business knowledge/information through his social network:

“you are asking about the networking, yes we help each other if they need some knowledge regarding the business or any sort, we are kind of like a small group, or you can say in this case, some sort of network of trustworthy people who help each other.”

C4 mentioned getting information regarding cheaper products, which is strategically important for his business so that he can offer his products at a competitive/ cheaper price:

“some of my friends have businesses in the Croydon area and some of them in the North London area. You know sometimes we need to buy bulk, it could be in big supermarkets or cash

and carries I told you before. We communicate with each other once we have found out where the cheapest place is to buy these kinds of product and how much this costs. So we get these kinds of information from each other so it helps us a lot keep the costs down as well.”

Similarly, C3 revealed that he has been living the area for a long time as he moved in more than twenty years ago. He often passed by this place not knowing that this place was up for sale at the time when he was intending to open a business in this area. He also mentioned that one of the reasons for selecting the place was that he knows a lot of people nearby, which could benefit him even more. Finally, he came to know that the premises were available through his friends in the area and they convinced him to buy the place as well.

“I basically grew up in this area in London, I know a lot of people in this area. I just saw an opportunity to start a business in this area, so I took it. I have a lot of friends around and I was passing by this shop for many years, and I didn’t know this was available. And one day one of my friends told me this place was available for sale, they are the ones who persuaded me to get this place.”

Lastly, One of the benefits of having a social network is sharing information between them to run their businesses smoothly. C7 appeared to maintain a good social business network:

“I have friends who own or run businesses, who are Sri Lankans. We sometimes share relevant information.”

5.2.4 Social capital

Being part of a social network(s) is vital for these ethnic entrepreneurs to grow their ethnic business activities. Ethnic networks are closed in nature, which could provide an operational advantage for the group/network members compared to the non-members, who usually do not have access to (Waldinger, Aldrich and Ward, 1990). Community and their family are at the centre of these kinds of ethnic social network(s) and they heavily rely on trust to survive (Ram, 1994). This trust could be used as a resource for a competitive advantage as well (Smith, Wistrich and Haynes, 2001).

In line with the literature, Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs rely on their family and social network to access the finance, labour and manage a good supplier and employee relationship.

5.2.4.1 Access to finance/financial capital:

Some of these respondents mentioned that they still have difficulties in accessing mainstream financial resources, such as through banks.

C1 shared that accessing finance takes a long time and it is uncertain whether it would be granted or not, but he is certain that it is much faster through his friends than the financial institutions:

“You may get the loan, most of the time you are not sure, it takes a long time, and they (bank) keep telling us to give this, give that document and it takes for ever. If you can't pay it back, you might be running into all sorts of troubles you know. When you are asking for money from your friends, most of the time I can get it done hours or within a day or two; that is the kind of reputation I have built with them.”

And C2 exemplifies a similar view, which appeared to be a less helpful attitude from these financial institutions in the UK:

“ some reason they can't do anything, now everything is in a computer you know, even bank managers can't do anything now, whatever the computer saying, like they are saying you can't have the loan or not, just by looking at the computer. That's it. This has happened to me recently, I don't want to go into details - that's all about it.”

Perhaps this is one of the reasons why these small ethnic businesses still rely on their family members and use their social networks to access finance (Ram *et al.*, 2002).

5.2.4.1.1 Access to financial capital through family members:

For instance, C1 mentioned that he borrows money from his friends and family without relying on the bank, and that distinguishes him and his business from mainstream corporations:

“We borrow from friends and family and we borrow our own money. That's the big difference between a bigger corporate company and a smaller family run business. We never rely on banks.”

Then C6 also mentioned that his father back home also helped him financially in the beginning, demonstrating financial capital through family members:

“from the beginning in financial terms, yes, my father is a huge help for me.”

Lastly, C7 also mentioned that he sold off some of the family assets to be able to invest money in his business in the beginning:

“The main issue was I wasn’t financially stable. I invested all my savings from the full-time job, I had to sell some of my assets like my car and wife’s jewellery, even what she was given by her family and all that. We, as a family, sacrificed a lot to this business. We had to start from scratch, we didn’t have much stock, to be honest, in the beginning.”

5.2.4.1.2 Access to financial capital through social networks:

Then again, these Sri Lankan entrepreneurs also use their social networks outside their family, to access finance.

This was demonstrated by C5, where he mentioned that his friends helped him financially in the beginning:

“Financially I was struggling a lot. But some of my few friends helped me during that difficult time.”

C7 also mentioned access to finance through social capital in a similar statement:

“probably my friends, some have recently helped me financially as well.”

C8 mentioned that he has borrowed money from his friends, exemplifying accessing finance through his social network:

“I borrowed some money from my friends and put all the money into the business. Eventually, I have been able to pay their debts and run this business properly.”

C1 explained how much quicker he can access finance through his social network than accessing finance through a financial institution in the UK:

“You may get the loan, most of the time you are not; it takes a long time, and they (bank) are telling us to give this, give that documents and it takes forever. If you can’t pay back, you might be running into all sorts of troubles you know. When you are asking money from your friends, most of the time I can get it done within hours or within a day or two, that kind of reputation I built with them.”

5.2.4.2 Access to labour capital:

Data emerged from the cross-case analysis that Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs seek and access labour by employing their family members and employing staff members through their co-ethnic social network.

5.2.4.2.1 Labour capital through family members:

For instance, C1 mentioned that his wife, son, and brother were involved with the business, elaborating his family involvement within the business and their contribution:

“my wife and my family are highly involved with this business. Like my son comes and helps me out, my brother when he is around, he helps me out you know. We are all acting and contributing to the business in different ways.”

Several scholars have mentioned the significance of family influence and its importance when running a business (Sirmon *et al.*, 2008). Some have found that these types of social capital, formed through interacting and maintaining the trustful relationship, are vital to initiate self-

employment (Hoffman, Hoelscher and Sorenson, 2006; Pearson, Carr and Shaw, 2008) among minority ethnic entrepreneurs (Sanders and Nee, 1996).

It appeared that Sri Lankan entrepreneurs also value the presence of the family and its importance, such as maintaining a 'trustful' relationship. Here, C1 mentioned that family members are the most trusted in his business and if there is not a family member in the business this means there is not a trustful staff member for him:

“When you don't have a family business that basically means you don't have any trustful staff. We have brought up our children behind the counter. This is like my home. Then we are a little bit better with our business, and then we employed the staff.”

Then again, C2 shared a similar statement about his family members. He mentioned that, even though his wife was not employed directly, she occasionally came to the business to do the paperwork (could be relating to admin work). And these serious matters should be done by someone he can trust:

“I registered my wife's name in this business. She comes sometimes to do some paper work with me. Because it is very important, in these serious matters, it is very important that I must ask help from someone I can trust.”

Other participants, namely C3, C4, C7 and C8, also mentioned that, importantly, their wives are involved directly and indirectly when necessary to the business. This exemplifies availability and access to labour capital through family members when required, which appeared to be easier; hence this was more productive among these participants (Danes *et al.*, 2009).

For instance, C4 exemplified this in his statement:

“my wife, she is a huge helping hand, she comes now and then helping me out with my paperwork, gets my lunch, she sometimes helps me on the till and gives a hand with my staff as well.”

Similarly, C6 mentioned his wife’s involvement and her contribution to the business whenever needed:

“my wife is involved as you can see. When I need a hand, when I'm busy document processing, I always ask her to help.”

5.2.4.2.2 Labour capital through social network:

Accessing labour capital outside of their family members is also prominent with these individuals (Ram, 1994). Almost all the cases have employed their staff through social contacts.

This is exemplified by C3:

“I did not advertise, I know a lot of people in the area as well. Then, through my contacts, I got to know some employees and then I employed them.”

One of the benefits of employing through social contacts is that (according to them) it allows them to know who they are employing. C6 mentioned that he does not want to hire someone from the internet or a stranger, as he does not know his/her background as to whether they are a ‘good person’ or a ‘bad person’. He further mentioned that having a ‘bad person’ may lead to leaving a bad business reputation:

“I should know who I employ; in that way I can know who I am dealing with rather than finding them on the internet and employing a complete stranger, who we don’t know is a good person or not. If they are a bad person, certainly it is a hard and time consuming because these people know how to get around the law, leaving a bad business reputation.”

C5 also mentioned that he prefers to employ someone he knows through social contacts:

“through my contacts, family members and friends. I also put an advertisement in front of the shop. But I prefer to employ someone I know.”

Similarly, C4 also mentioned that he needs to find ‘trustworthy people’ as he and his business deal with money:

“When I employ people, I always get them through contacts, you know in this kind of business, we all are dealing with money and all that, so I need to find trustworthy people.”

Aligning with C4’s statement, C8 mentioned that he should know who he is employing, reflecting the trust relationship. And at the same time, he finds co-ethnic employees are ‘easy to work with’:

“I have also found them from my contacts. You have to know who you are employing, plus it is much easier to work with people who have same background as you.”

Relationships are formed and used as capital to benefit the business activity within the social network that the entrepreneur are embedded in (Yee, 2015). The findings suggest that these Sri Lankan entrepreneurs use their supplier relationship and employee relationships to benefit their businesses, which may lead to a competitive advantage.

5.2.5 Supplier relationship

In this case, the participants (especially Case 2, Case 4, Case 5, and Case 7) demonstrated that they built a good relationship with their suppliers over the years and this positively benefited their business.

For instance, in Case 2, C2 added that he gets discounts, i.e. a lower price when he buys in bulk from them, and so this enables him to offer these products at a lower price back to the customer:

“they always ask me if I'm doing good, they give me really good discounts, low prices when I buy bulk from them, so I can give it at a cheaper price to my customers. I think I do have a really good connection with them.”

Again C2 mentioned that one of the benefits he gets from managing a good supplier relationship is that he can get products anytime for credit (buy now, pay later), which he thinks these suppliers will not do for every shop in the area:

“if I say to them that I don't have any money or can I pay later, they never say no, they know who I am, they deliver to me straight away. They don't do this to every shop.”

Again, Case 4, C4 mentioned his supplier (cash and carry) relationship reflected a similar view:

“I can buy from the cash and carry on the account as well; for example if I say I don't have money they will always provide me with credit. I have been in this business for a long time now so they know who I am.”

Similarly, in Case 5, C5 mentioned that he gets numerous benefits from having a good relationship with the supplier, such as notification of early product availability, offering products at a low price, and buying products on credit. But he always managed to pay them on time, once the delivery was made:

“they were very helpful, they called me whenever a product came available to buy from them, they know me very well. Also, they managed to give me the items for a low price at that time as well. You know I could also get the product on credit as well. But I didn’t do it, once delivery was done to the shop, I paid them on time with cash, so they were also happy during that time as well.”

C7 also shared his views on his suppliers, who have supplied their products for a long time, and expressed that they were ready to supply anything he ordered according to their availability.

“I have my good old regular suppliers. They have been with me for a long time. Milk and newspapers. Whenever I ask something about their availability, they supply it to me fast. I pay on time. I have had good suppliers over the years.”

5.2.6 Employee relationship

Woolcock (1998) claims that sharing social capital could improve the relationship between the employees and the ethnic entrepreneurs, which is based on trust. This culture could potentially also have economic value. Hence, it could eventually lead to generating profit and using it as a competitive advantage, especially for individuals like entrepreneurs (Lareau and Weininger, 2003).

Data emerged from Case 2, Case 5, Case 6 and Case 8 who mentioned about their employee relationship, particularly employing people from Sri Lankan background, which benefitted their business positively.

For instance, C5 mentioned that Sri Lankan originated employees are easy to understand due to speaking the same language and this develops a good customer relationship and connection:

“They know our culture and the way we operate - it is a bit different from other retail shops. The languages we speak, it is much easier and you can understand them if you are from the same country. On the top of this, you get the Sri Lankan customers all the time in this shop, and every customer is different, they want us to know them most of the time individually and that's exactly what we give them. So you can have good communication and a connection with the customers as well.”

Similarly, C6 mentioned that having employees who come from the same cultural background and who speak the same language as him is beneficial for his business in certain ways; such as it is easy to communicate and manage them, and these employees tend to develop good customer relationships for his business:

“I believe that Sri Lankan staff - for me, I found that I can easily control them. Easy to understand them, as most of the time we are from the same cultural background, and speaking

the same language is an extra skill for the job and creates a relationship with them. I normally evaluate them by increasing positive feedback from the customers, how they approach them and help them to find what they want. I found most of the time, Sri Lankan staff I have here are very helpful for the customers.”

Thus, C8 similarly added that it is easier to work with the people who are from the same background (Sri Lankan) as him:

“I have also found staff from my contacts. You have to know who you are employing, plus it is much easier to work with the people who have the same background as you.”

C2 also mentioned similar benefits, and he treats his employees as family members, exemplifying the trust relationship he has with his employees overtime:

“speaking the same language and coming from Sri Lanka makes it very easy to work with. Especially customers, not only from Jaffna, but if they speak Tamil or Sinhalese, I can easily understand the customer and start a good conversation. That way I make a good connection with them. One guy still works for me here, and he came from Jaffna Sri Lanka. Since I came to London nearly thirty years ago till now, he is still with me. I'm not treating him like any other staff, but I like to treat him as my close friend or like a family guy.”

At the same time, he also mentioned the negative aspect of these trust relationships, where he ran into trouble, and ultimately this led to closing one of the businesses:

“I had terrible trouble also, you know I've had a business before this, that time I couldn't do that properly, because a trusted lot of staff over there they have done terrible things to my business, so I lost a lot of money over there as well. I finally sold that business there (Surbiton) while I'm doing the business here. At the moment I'm staying with one business because I don't want to lose any more money or get into trouble by trusting people.”

Figure 18: Summary of cross case findings from section 5.2.1-5.2.6

5.2.7 Customer Relationship

Customer relationship is vital for any business activity as it can be used as a source of competitive advantage (Haq *et al.*, 2021), and to gain economic benefits by retaining them. Customer relationships could be formed as social and/or instrumental relationships.

5.2.7.1 Trust:

Trustworthiness is regarded as an ‘antecedent’ to the existence of trust. According to (Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol 2002, p. 17) trustworthiness is defined as ‘including Front line employee (FLE) behaviours and Management Policy practices (MPP) that indicate a motivation to safeguard consumer interest’. These FLE and MPP practices include operational benevolence, problem-solving orientation and operational competence.

5.2.7.1.1 Operational benevolence:

Cross case analysis revealed that these individuals showed operational benevolence by limiting self-serving opportunism and showing the behaviour of valuing the customer presence.

For instance, C1’s statement appeared to reflect the limiting of self-serving opportunism by not making the customer buy more than was necessary from his business; for instance, this is one of the reasons he does not offer ‘buy 1 get 1 free’ deals from his shop:

“I don’t know much about it. But I feel that to get more customers to do these kinds of things is wrong you know. Because you may get more money, but you actually waste their money to get you more money. I don’t want to feel it on me about my business.”

Similarly, C2 gave his opinion which also reflected a limited self-serving opportunity where he could make more money, but according to him, 'money is not the point'. He would offer a full refund if the customer was not happy with his product after the purchase, demonstrating that customer satisfaction is his priority:

"If I am honest with you, I would take Sri Lankan curry powder over the South-Indian one. This one (South-Indian) is nice and I get more profit out of it too. Money is not the point but really, it doesn't have the Sri Lankan flavour. Take my word, have the Sri Lankan one, use it if you not happy, bring that back to me and I will refund your money in full."

Similarly, As it emerged in the data in Case 3, C3 appeared to show limited self-serving opportunities while interacting with a customer. A customer came into the shop in Case 3 to get a refund for an unsatisfactory product which she had bought before. After a conversation with C3, she changed her mind to exchange it for a similar product. The product she chose from the shop was more expensive than the faulty item she wanted to replace it with. C3 exchanged it happily for the customer and didn't charge her the balance as he demonstrated the 'limiting self-serving opportunity' on himself.

"No Madam, you don't need to do that. If you took an even more expensive one than this, I would still exchange it for you."

Thus, C4 added that he gives his honest opinion even if he might lose money. But he thinks that making the customer buy the right product is more important to him than taking an opportunity to generate money out of the situation:

"I give them my honest opinion. I might lose money, but making the customer buy the right one is the key."

A similar view was also shared by C6, reflecting limited self-serving opportunism:

“if you give good service, give them the right product information, no misinformation, the right price, no high prices and if you honestly care about your customers, they always come back. I witnessed this over and over again, customers trust you when they feel that you honestly care for them.”

Thus, C7 and C8 can also be aligned with the C6 view: C7 added:

“You should talk to them if they pass the other shop and come to you. That means you have built a good connection with the customers. You should be honest with them as much as you can be, sometimes you are not gonna make a sale out of it, but normally I see them back in here. I get their feedback and use tis to improve. I always manage to keep quality products in-store. No fake things or lies.”

Lastly, C8 reflected again on limited self-opportunism even in the pandemic situation:

“I don’t want to increase the price. I’m not pressing on the price. Because, in this shop, 90% of the customers are locals living in the area and all the locals know me, they know I’m not like that - taking advantage of the whole lockdown situation, and increasing the price for the products I sell here - it’s not good in the long run.”

According to Macintosh and Lockshin (1997), interpersonal ties or social relationships with the customer are important for increasing the salesperson-client trust relationship. Thus, showing that the business cares for the customer, and communicating/demonstrating this with them is good for the customer-business relationship, but even more beneficial for the business. Hence it might lead to a long term relationship (O’Malley and Prothero, 2004). Similarly, these individuals also demonstrated that they value the customer presence by regarding them,

or treating them, like they are ‘family members’; ‘we care for the customers’; and other similar views in their statement (s).

C1 added that he cares for the customers so that even supermarkets cannot compete with him. Again, C1 mentioned here that money is not central when delivering service for the customer. He further explained that a personal relationship with the customer is important for his business:

*“We are very caring about the customers, it is not like t***o like don’t care about them and you don’t even know your customers. I just don’t treat them like I really need their money and I’m gonna make them spend as much as they can. You see this is not my philosophy. Here we care about them. I know most of my regular customers - about what is happening in their life or even in their family. So that’s how much the customers are bonded with us. We joke around, they joke with us, and we laugh together and give them a pleasant time. Each individual here is different from others, so we keep that in mind when we interact with them. And we have to work like that to keep the customers happy and give a different approach than the other big ones.”*

Also, similarly, C2 mentioned that regular customers who come to his shop are like his family members:

“I have been here for thirty years, I know my regular customers, most of them very close to me. I listen to them often, these customers are like my family members, I think they are very honest in terms of their opinions. You need to respect them first and earn their respect over time and it takes some time.”

While C4 mentioned that, according to him, valuing customer presence shows that you are treating them nicely. By showing them that, as a business, you care for the customer is an attraction for his business:

“You need to treat them nicely. Like, show you care and welcome them. If you put these together, that's it and you are going to do well. I mean you need to know how to treat them or serve them. I think you need to have that attraction for your business, especially when you do retail.”

5.2.7.1.2 Problem-solving orientation and Operational competence:

In the Sri Lankan context, these entrepreneurs also demonstrated their trustworthiness through their problem solving-orientation and operational competence. In summary, they appear to defend the characteristics of favouring the consumer's interest, even if this attitude is costly to the business.

Case 1, Case 2, and Case 3 data can relate to the literature.

For instance, C1 changed an unhappy customer into a much more satisfied customer by offering a free product exchange, right after she expressed her disappointment with the shop owner. This reflects his problem-solving orientation towards favouring the customer, even at a cost to the business:

Customer 1: “you told me last time this (a crisp packet) would be good.”

The customer sounds a bit disappointed.

The shop owner (the participant): “why is it not good?”

Customer 1: “it was ok for me, but my daughter didn't like it at all.”

Shop owner: “oh, I am really sorry for the disappointment. Don't worry, I'll get you the one you buy normally.”

The shop owner went to one of the aisles and came back with the packet of crisps.

Shop owner: “here take this one, Madam.”

He handed it over to the customer.

Customer 1: “oh, you know what I want. Thank you. How much is it altogether?”

Shop owner: “ahh, don’t worry, Madam. You get this one for free from me. Say hello from me to the little girl.”

C2 had a similar situation. Before purchasing the product, the customer asked the owner about a product recommendation for two similar product variations. One product was more expensive than the other. After listening to the customer’s need to use the product, C2 appeared to give his recommendation that he thought would be most suitable for the purpose. Interestingly, this was the less expensive option. He later mentioned that ‘money is not the point’, and he offered a free refund if the customer was still unsatisfied with his product. Therefore, this can be interpreted as exemplifying problem-solving orientation based on favouring the customer’s interest, even before the purchase and after. On the other hand, this behaviour can also link to operational competence. His product knowledge translated into observable behaviours (Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol, 2002), which helped a customer make the desired product choice. This conversation followed, as below:

Shop owner 2 (C2): “may I help you, sir?”

Customer: ” yes, anna (brother) I am a bit confused about two curry powders I have here.”

Shop owner2: “yes, one is from Sri Lanka, the other from South India.”

Customer: “oh I see, which one is better?”

Shop owner: “well these curry powders are both great, I don’t sell anything here of low quality. All top brands from top suppliers in this shop.”

Customer: “hahaha, I know, that’s why I have come here for a long time. Which one is better? Normally my wife comes here often.”

Shop owner2: “I know you are a Sri Lankan; if you like the spiciness, I would go with the Sri Lankan one obviously. The South Indian one is less spicy than the Sri Lankan one and has a slightly different smell after you cook it. If you are making a Sri Lankan curry you can go with Sri Lankan curry powder, I just gave my honest opinion, but still, the choice is yours.

Customer: " Oh I see, I thought they basically looked the same and the South Indian one is a bit more expensive than the Sri Lankan one. I will take your advice this time. Thank you."

Shop owner2: yes, the South Indian one sells here in UK more than the Sri Lankan one. It is £3.00 more expensive than the Sri Lankan one, I think

Shop owner 2: "may I ask what curry you are trying to make with this powder?"

Customer: "we are making some dishes over the weekend. Hmm, which one is especially most suitable for a prawn curry?"

Shopowner2: "if I am honest with you, I would take the Sri Lankan curry powder over the South Indian one. This one (South Indian) is nice and I get more profit out of it too. Money is not the point but really, it doesn't have the Sri Lankan flavour. Take my word, have the Sri Lankan one, use it. If you not happy bring that back to me and I will refund your money in full."

A similar situation was also demonstrated by C3, where he turned a very disappointed customer into a much more calm and satisfied customer at the end of the exchange. C3 faced the customer while the researcher was carrying out the interview with him in the shop. The customer came up with a product, which she claimed that she bought from the participant's (C3) shop. The shop owner listened to the disappointed customer, calmed her down, and gave her relevant information regarding the product she had bought before. In this way she could avoid such scenarios in the future. Thus, C3 even exchanged the product, which was a little more expensive than the one she bought in the end, demonstrating customer satisfaction was more important to him than making money. On the other hand, similar to Case 2, this can also be interpreted as an operational competence, where C3 demonstrated that he gave the right product information (knowledge) to the customer (observable behaviour) and made her choose a product as a replacement (Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol, 2002):

Customer: "this was not the rice I wanted, plus you can't eat this rice; it tastes and smells horrible once it cooked."

Shop owner 3 (C3): “oh, I see (he is looking at the bag of rice, put his hand inside the rice bag, and took out some of the seeds). Nothing wrong with the rice and it has not gone bad, Madam. This is called ‘Samba’. This type of rice smells, but back home, it is not a bad smell for us; there is a way to prepare the rice for cooking and there are certain Sri Lankan curries that go with it. Not all people like it even in Sri Lanka. But, no problem Madam - what do you want from us, full refund or exchange?”

(Now the customer changes her mind and she looks much calmer than before)

Customer: “can I have an exchange, please? Because I don’t want to come on another day.”

Shop owner 3: “yes of course madam. Malli (called his staff member), take this madam with you and let her decide what rice she wants and bring it here. I will sort it out.”

5.2.7.2 Service

As mentioned before, having good customer service skills has the potential to achieve long-term business success. In line with the literature, these individuals also include in their service: customer orientation, customer centricity, developing empathy, developing patience, and letting the customer make the buying decision (Haq *et al.*, 2021).

5.2.7.2.1 Customer orientation:

Customer orientation prioritizes long-term customer satisfaction over the attainment of short-term sales targets and has been conceptualized at both the firm and individual level. In this context, ‘customer orientation defined as a retail frontline salesperson’s focus on meeting customer needs in performing their job responsibilities’ (Brown *et al.* 2002, p.111).

These individuals seemed to be concerned about meeting the customer needs, and orienting their business to meet those needs appeared to be important for them.

Case 1, Case 4, and Case 6 reflected this view outstandingly:

For instance, C1 added that he changed his Sri Lankan, South Indian and English items. But now, due to the demand, he changed it to Eastern European/European retail products:

“I started with Sri Lankan, South Indian and English retail items. Now I have ended up with mostly, Eastern European/European retail products.”

In a similar statement, C4 also appeared to be changed his offering in order to meet customer demands:

“My customers are locals, English and European people. So, I don’t sell ethnic-specific products here anymore as I don’t have customers to sell it to in this area nowadays.”

On the other hand, a lack of understanding customer needs may often lead to business failure. In Case 6, C6 mentioned that he offered to serve every community in the market. But understanding the needs of the regular customers and focusing on their needs led him to run a successful business:

“Things I offer here are a mixture of everything, like some of the things are for local English/European people and others are for Sri Lankan/South Asian people. The idea was to serve everyone in the local area, but it didn't work for me. After a while you slowly identify your customers’ backgrounds, where they come from, particularly frequent visitors. When you try to talk to them they give you feedback, and that's the key. Slowly, I increased the product variety with some well-branded quality products based on their feedback. Fast forward five years, I would say I am running a business without any loss. You need to understand what they want and adjust your business to give it.”

5.2.7.2.2 Customer centricity:

On the other hand, it is apparent that these individuals are mostly concerned about fulfilling their customer needs and identifying these needs and its decisions which mainly comes from interacting with their regular customers. It has appeared that they appreciate the regular customer feedback and use that to improve their business offering.

For instance, C1 mentioned in his statement that long term customers are very important to him to get essential feedback to improve the business:

“you talk to the customer, trust me, most of the time you can really count on the customers, especially ones have come to the shop for a long time. In terms of feedback. I talk to the customers like - what do you like to see here and there like that you know. So like that, I make sure I do changes to meet the customer needs.”

In other words, this illustrates making decisions based on customer feedback and hence making decisions by prioritising the customer, and allowing the customer to play a central role in their business decisions and orientation. This description is much more in line with the concept of ‘customer-centricity’ where it means ‘putting the customer first’ or as Tseng and Pillar (2003, p.3) define it as, ‘a customer-centric enterprise that places the demands and wishes of each single customer in the centre of value creation’.

For instance, C2 mentioned how his product selection depends on customer complaints. He said that if a customer complained about certain products, he either improved the quality of the product or removed them accordingly. So, he makes sure there are no reoccurring customer complaints, which can be interpreted as encouraging the customer to play a central role in his product selection:

“my regular customers, I'm very familiar with them, they trust me, I trust them. If they come up with anything I make sure, they are treated well and make sure they come back again to the store.”

On the other hand, C3 added a similar statement, where he removed certain food items by listening to some customers and readjusting his offerings:

“I had to reduce the spiciness, ingredients and increase the simplicity of these food items. There were a lot of complaints, especially from these tourists, in regards to the spiciness. I had to remove some foods because some Sri Lankan foods cannot have without chillies and other spices.”

Thus, he provided a much more individualised customer service which is also seen as an aspect of a customer-centric businesses (Gummesson, 2008). It has emerged that these participants also possess individual customer service in their businesses as well.

For instance, C7 reflected in his statement, that every customer's needs are different, hence every customer is different, and these needs cannot be ignored:

“You can't ignore your customers. Everyone is different in their own way. They have their own needs.”

Also, C5 has a similar view, which reflects individual customer service:

“you get the Sri Lankan customers all the time in this shop, and every customer is different, they want us to know them most of the time individually, and that's exactly what we are giving them.”

C4 gave a similar statement which also reflected individual customer service. When customers look confused or are wandering around, he communicates with the customer and is able to give them what they want most of the time; if not, at least he gives a substitute. In that way, he does not let the customer down:

“Sometimes if the customer looks confused or is moving around, I ask them what they want directly. If I can understand what they are asking for and I have it in my shop, I always give them what they need without wasting their time. If not, I see if I can provide at least a substitute, that way I hardly let my customer down. That's the main thing.”

5.2.7.2.3 Developing empathy

According to Wieseke, Geigenmuller and Kraus (2012, p.317) empathy is defined as ‘a person’s intellectual understanding of the internal state of another person’. Or some others mentioned that it as ‘perspective-taking’, which means a person’s ability to understand a point of view of another person; i.e. to address the perceived needs of the other person, opinions, and motivations (Devoldre *et al.*, 2010).

According to the literature, the cases suggest that these individuals are also empathetic towards the customers. Many of these individuals think of the customer’s point of view and work towards satisfying their needs.

C1 gained empathy by considering how he would feel himself if he had been in the same situation as the customer:

“she has been a regular customer in my shop for years. And I don’t want to lose her. And the other thing is that you can’t sell something that customer doesn’t like, especially their kids. I have kids too. I know what it feels like.”

5.2.7.2.3.1 Empathy as an aim to build customer satisfaction

As an aim in itself, empathy is perhaps related to customer retention, because satisfied customers become loyal and/or repeat customers (Anderson, 1998 ; Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003); also ‘satisfying customer needs and wants is the key to building loyal customers’ (Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003, p. 83). Thus, it can also be argued that where empathy is involved ‘the employee’s behaviour suggests he or she is truly looking out for the customer rather than trying to make a sale’ (Gremler and Gwinner, 2008, p. 316).

C1 can be also aligned with the literature as well, where he looks out for the customer more than attempting to make a sale. C1 satisfied a disappointed customer with a free replacement when he could have charged for it. This can be interpreted as the fact that money is not always the objective for Case 1 and hence, he takes the customer’s side. The whole situation went as follows:

Customer 1: “you told me last time this (a crisp packet) would be good.”

The customer sounds a bit disappointed.

The shop owner (the participant): “why is it not good?”

Customer 1: “it was ok for me, but my daughter didn’t like it at all.”

Shop owner: "oh, I am really sorry for the disappointment. Don't worry, I'll get you the one you buy normally."

The shop owner went to one of the aisles and came back with the packet of crisps.

Shop owner: "here take this one, Madam."

He handed it over to the customer.

Customer 1: "oh, you know what I want. Thank you. How much is it altogether?"

Shop owner: "ahh, don't worry, Madam. You get this one for free from me. Say hello from me to the little girl."

Again, C7 explained that he or his wife never had issues with the customers; then he mentioned about not pushing the customer to make money. Hence their objective is not to earn money but to make the customer happy. This behaviour also shows the customers that C7, as a businessman, truly cares about the customer rather than attempting to make a profit:

"We never had any issues with the customers, we know how to treat them, they know we are not running after the money, we are not pushing them to make more money, we make sure they are happy at the end of the day and that's what matters to us."

Thus, some believe that honestly caring for the customer (in this argument termed as empathy) will actually link to customer retention (Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003).

Then again, C6 revealed that giving the right product information without giving misinformation, and asking the right price, is a way to care for the customer. By doing that, C6 experienced that the same customer tended to come back frequently to his shop. This emphasises that money is not the priority, and customer satisfaction seems to be an objective here, as it links with customer retention:

“if you give good service, give them the right product information, no misinformation, the right price not a high price and if you honestly care for your customers they always come back’ I witnessed this over and over again.”

C5 mentioned that he is always thinking about the customer’s side in terms of customer feedback, whether it is good or bad. First, before getting these views from the customer, he makes sure that the customer feels good and comfortable sharing their views with him. Perhaps this could be linked back to the literature that empathy is a well-known tool for rapport building, allowing front line service people like C5 to see the customer’s point of view (Gremler and Gwinner, 2008):

“I greet them, I talk to them - is everything is ok - and once the customer familiar with me, they always talk good or bad. I always think of the customer’s side.”

C3 shared a similar view, which is that caring for the customer and prioritising their satisfaction has the benefit of increased loyalty and retention (Anderson, 1998; Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003).

“Ceylon tea bags might cost me a little. But I know one thing for sure - at the end of the day, she is satisfied and left, and I know she is going to come back again. You kind of keep the loyalty for your business like that.”

C4 achieved empathy here by thinking about the customer, understanding her needs rather than business objectives, even for one customer. Here, C4 explains that he has a regular customer who buys one particular product often. But this item has almost no sales with other customers. C4 believes that removing that item from the shelf would make her unhappy. So, he keeps it on the shelf just for her so she would not be disappointed:

“I have a regular customer, and she always comes to buy one particular food item from my shop. She really needs it, but there aren’t many sales of it with other customers. But I would keep it just for her and she is not going to be happy if I removed it from the shelves anyway. I would say she is a good purchaser as well. She sometimes buys a good amount of shopping as well. So, I don’t let her down, I make sure the product is there for her.”

C6 mentioned that they treat their customers as if they were visiting another shop and how they would want to be treated as customers in that shop. Hence, this behaviour can link with empathy as C6 seeks to understand another person’s (customer) view and provide their (perceived) needs (Devoldre *et al.*, 2010) :

“me or my wife, whenever we go to any other shop, how we want to be get treated by the staff of that shop, the same way we do with the customers here. Every time it works.”

Some cases, for instance C1 and C2, mentioned that they would treat their customers as family members. Treating the customer as a family member is also mentioned in the literature as being empathetic with the customer (Parasuraman, Berry and Zeithaml, 1991; Beatty *et al.*, 1996).

On one occasion, C1 demonstrated empathy towards the customer and her family members as well. This shows how C1 bonded with his regular customers by sharing each other’s day to day events. Once again, this shows how C1 built a rapport with the customer using empathy as a tool:

Shop owner: “how is your sister now Madam?”

Customer 2: “she is a bit ok now, she is going to the hospital for the clinic regularly. You know she can do things on her own now. But thank you for asking.”

Shop owner: " ahh, that's good news. God bless for her."

The shop owner packed the stuff for her. Customer 2 paid the bill.

Customer 2: "where is your wife? I haven't seen her today."

Shop owner: "ohh, she is on her way, she went to pick up our kids from the school."

Customer 2: " oh, I see, say hello for me. See you then, bye."

Shop owner: "I will. See you, take care, bye."

A similar view was shared by C2. He mentioned that he has been in the business a long time and treats his customers as family members:

"I have been here for thirty years. I know my regular customers, most of them are very close to me, I listen to them often, these customers are like my family members, I think they are very honest in terms of their opinions. You need to respect them first and earn the respect over time. It takes some time."

5.2.7.2.3 Developing patience

The skill of being patient with customers is considered as bringing wide-ranging benefits in retail environments (Beatty *et al.*, 1996). It could satisfy the customer and it may bring more of them back (Parasuraman, Berry and Zeithaml, 1991).

Again, many of the participants demonstrated that they develop patience with the customers when interacting with them. Interestingly many of them reflected that they develop patience by making the customer feel calm and listened to. They tend to develop patience in order to keep the customer, or in other words, retain the customer through customer satisfaction, as these individuals are delivering a customer-centric service.

C3 added that developing patience towards the customer is central to the idea of satisfying the customer or, in their words, ‘making the customer happy’:

“you saw that one customer was not happy. The other thing is that giving the exchange back, I lose the money. But if I deny giving her an exchange or refund, if I argue and make her even angrier this doesn’t solve the problem. You need to show you care, you make them calm, and show compassion towards to them. If not, possibly I lose a regular customer.”

C4 added that his naturally tolerant nature helps him face difficult customers. Using a sense of humour also helps to make these customers leave the building happy in the end:

“Since the morning, I have talked to different customers if they are interested. Some of them don’t talk much. Some of them are not in a good mood when they are talking to me. I understand them. I’m a tolerant person. I’m very careful and am patient when they are around. There were some times I had to calm them down, listen to them, and throw some jokes to get their happy face back. I think it took some time for me to learn how to face these kinds of customers. But many of the regulars like to talk to me. They leave the building happy.”

Hagedoorn *et al.* (1999, p.310) describe patience as ‘the act of waiting optimistically’. This view was reflected by C5. He added that patience is a skill and it takes time to learn:

“Sometimes you have to make the customer calm and ready to listen. Then you can contribute your point of view. If you get angry very easily at someone, this is not the job for you, definitely take time to learn to deal with customers. That’s what I learnt from my fifteen years of work experience.”

Giving the customer time shows a good indicator of how much a business cares for the customer and how much it is central to their business (Shah *et al.*, 2006). Similarly, C2 mentioned that taking the time to listen to the customer and showing kindness and patience is important to him, as these characteristics differentiate him from supermarkets:

“When a customer comes to the shop and asks questions like that, you need to make the customer feel that we are listening. I took the time to listen to him, he is a young one like you. I am older than both of you, so I need to show that I am the older person (maturity) here. Sometimes it feels some customers are really annoying or impatient, especially at rush hours like now. But you need to be very kind and be patient with them. If you not, you not giving a good service. Then this shop becomes more or less like those big supermarkets. At the end of the day we need to make sure he goes out from this shop with a happy face and satisfied, so he will return here again.”

Similarly, C6 suggests listening to the customer by giving them your full attention as a staff member, because he thinks listening first and giving output second is a basic communication skill. Lastly, he mentioned that as a small business like them, kindness and patience is very important to them:

“Being nicer, giving a warm welcome, a good understanding of what they want, especially if the customer gets an impression that you don’t understand what they are asking and shake your head, they are getting very angry and that’s not a good impression for the business. We need to show them we understand them by really listening to them, giving full attention to them, no magic in that, it is just basic language skills. I always tell my staff as well, patience and kindness are very important to any business like us.”

5.2.7.2.4 Let the customer make the buying decision

These participants demonstrated that they do not want to be involved in the customer buying decision. Instead, these individuals furnish their customers with correct product information and allow them to make their own decision. Thus, it has appeared that they do not believe in traditional hard selling techniques, which are considered as a ‘shotgun salesperson’ approach towards the customer, where they ignore the customer needs and care very little about after sales (Alessandra and Barrera, 1993; Haq *et al.*, 2021).

This was reflected by C1 when a conversation took place while the researcher was carrying out the interview on the site, regarding being a product promoting salesperson. C1 mentioned that he does not want to convince customers to buy things that they do not need, and he does not want to be a salesperson:

“Listen, I don’t convince my customers to buy things that they don’t need. They will buy anything they want if needed. I’m not going to be a salesperson. You bring something that can be sellable, a quality one. I tried this drink myself and it doesn’t taste good. I am sorry my friend, I can’t allow this product in my shop. You have to take this with you.”

An observation of C2 within a customer interaction showed the characteristics of collaborative selling, where C2 gave all the information needed for the customer to make a decision about a product; he did not pressurize the customer to buy the expensive one or any of those products, but still gave the customer a choice to buy:

“I know you are a Sri Lankan - if you like the spiciness, I would go with the Sri Lankan one obviously. The South Indian one is less spicy than Sri Lankan one and has a slightly different smell after you cook. If you are making a Sri Lankan curry you can go with Sri Lankan curry powder. I just gave my honest opinion, but still, the choice is yours.”

Similarly, this was also reflected in C5's statement, where he mentioned that he does want to be a salesperson and he does not want to make the (buying) decision for them:

"I think it was a really good idea to increase the item variety, so the customer can make a good choice by themselves. I don't like them walking up to me and asking which one is better, is there any more choices and at the end, I have to make the decision for them. I don't think I should do that, this happens to me especially with regular customers who know me."

Similarly, C6 mentioned that, unlike the supermarkets, customers are not neglected and they can buy whatever they want, and he (owner) is not draining their (customer) money. Perhaps, it implies that these supermarkets use sales promotions to maximise their profitability, where the customer ends up paying for unnecessary things or spending more than they should be (Gilbert and Jackaria, 2002; Prendergast, Shi and Cheung, 2005):

"We give quality service in comparison with other supermarkets. You are not neglected, you get what you want, especially for Sri Lankans. Nothing more nothing less, they can buy whatever they want from my shop, if they want. For sure we are not draining their money."

C7 mentioned his view reflecting the selling approach of his shop:

"We know how to treat them, they know we not running after the money, we are not pushing them to make more money, we make sure they are happy at the end of the day and that's what matters to us."

C8 statement can also be related here:

“you can’t stress customers to buy stuff from your business to increase sales.”

Moreover, giving the right product information seemed to be important here as they mentioned that the customer can then make the right decision as his/her choice.

C4 reflected on the statement above, in which he mentioned that giving the right product information is important to him because there is no purpose in making money while losing the customer. He gives them his honest opinion, even though he loses money by making the customer select the right product based on his advice. This is very important to him:

“There is no point in making money while losing my customers. So, I need to look after them. They ask my opinion on certain products here. I give them my honest opinion. I might lose money, but making the customer buy the right one is the key. I’ve been here more than eight years now, I think I did the right thing, they know it and they listen (customers) to me, especially regulars.”

5.2.7.3 Business reputation

Data emerging from the case studies suggest that these individuals also practise good business ethics over time which leads to earning a good reputation.

First, C1 reflected that he does not push the customer to buy anything from his business, and he does not practise any marketing strategies which drains customer money. This implies that he is making money in a responsible way by not practising unethical marketing strategies (Sihem, 2013):

“I never push the customers to buy something. I don’t have value for money deals like ‘buy one get one free’. Customers tend to think that this gets you more value for money. I would say no, because most of the products you buy end up in the bin; either it has expired before you use it, or you have to throw it away because your house is full.”

Since these owners and their businesses show the characteristics of family firms, the literature finds that they are not only making decisions to improve its economic activities, but also working towards achieving socio-emotional objectives; such as maintaining a good image and the reputation of both business and family. Hence, these socio-emotional objectives motivate the family firms to initiate activities that may benefit other stakeholders out with their family (Zellweger *et al.* 2013). This can be related to the statement that C1 further added, where he mentioned that practices which drain customer money are wrong and he does not want to feel bad about his business in this way:

“But I feel that to get more customers to do these kinds of things is wrong you know. Because you may get more money, but you actually waste their money to get you more money. I don’t want to feel it on me about my business.”

C6 added that, as an entrepreneur, he is honest about what he does, and he does not practice anything which is represented as unreliable or illicit. If not, customers would not trust them as a business:

“I think you should be honest about what you are doing, if you are doing anything dodgy or fake, eventually customers won't trust you or your business. Your image as a family business I think also matters to the customers.”

Similarly, C7 mentioned he also does not practice anything unreliable or illicit, because customers in the area have known him for a long time:

“I find people always tend to talk with me, the locals. They have known me over the years, how hard I work to serve them. They know I don't do any dodgy things. They know they are gonna get quality products from me, in this family shop.”

According to the Fombrun and Van Riel (1997), customers describe ‘good reputable’ companies as being credible, responsive, reliable, and trustworthy. Similarly, C3 also added that integrity, credibility, quality and hard work will give a customer a good impression about the business and eventually earn the trust of the customer:

“I think integrity, credibility, quality and hard work. And you have to earn the trust of customers. You can't create the trust. I think it develops over time. The quality of your food products, customer service and the way you handle each and every customer. You need to talk to them and in that the way you present yourself as a business which gives the customer a good impression about your business in the long run.”

Similarly, C8 added:

“A customer will trust you as a business because you are not selling cheap and low-quality products to make money stay in the business. When you open the same shop nearby or in another area, people know your business already, you don't have to do marketing or anything, they just come to your shop just by the name. Also people in this area know me, they are my customers and they know I do not do any fake things.”

C4 also reflected that he does not do illicit practices with unattended belongings, and he will keep the belongings with him until they return:

“Sometimes they leave things in the shop, like umbrellas, bags, wallets and all that. I always keep their things with me, till they come back again and I hand them over to them. They never lose anything they have left in my shop.”

On the other hand, having a good reputation among other stakeholders is also important. C2 and C4 reflected this in their statements. Having a good reputation among the suppliers brings benefits like buying products on credit, for instance. This is reflected in a statement given by C2:

“if I say to them I don't have any money or can I pay later, they never say no, they know who I am, they deliver to me straight away and they don't do this to every shop. There are a lot of Sri Lankan shops in London, and among those there are a couple of Sri Lankan shops that you can really count on!! And one of them is my business.”

On the other hand, C4 also mentioned that he can also get products on credit from his suppliers:

“I can buy from this cash and carry on account as well. For instance, if I say I don't have money they will always provide me with credit. I have been in this business for a long time now

they know who I am. I have never, as a business or person, damaged my reputation and this is facilitated when you have your own name.”

Figure 19: Summary of Customer Relationship cross case analysis

5.2.8 Opportunity structure

Market conditions create opportunities for ethnic entrepreneurs, particularly when there is a product(s) or service(s) targeted at the co-ethnic community of the host country (Aldrich and Waldinger, 1990). However, the opportunities and its structural components continuously change due to facts like disruptive technological developments, various complex market scenarios and globalisation etc. (Kloosterman, 2010). On the other hand, being part of an ethnic enclave gives an opportunity for the ethnic minority entrepreneur to establish business activities with limited start-up capital and other resources. But most of the time these business activities ended up serving the same group of co-ethnic customers (Ram and Jones, 2008). Therefore, these entrepreneurs are often limited to serving a low income earning and saturated co-ethnic market, where those customers have low spending power. As a result of these factors, ethnic entrepreneurs are sometimes engaged in informal business activities as a strategy for their own survival (Jones, Ram and Edwards, 2006). However, apart from these facts, open market conditions in the host country give an opportunity for ethnic entrepreneurs to serve mainstream customers. Market entry is controlled by the host country's regulatory bodies and political landscape, which facilitate or impede access for ethnic entrepreneurs (Jones *et al.*, 2014).

It is essential to understand how Sri Lankan ethnic retail entrepreneurs recognize their opportunities within the UK market. Entrepreneurial opportunity recognition can result from external triggers or internal triggers (Bhave, 1994). External triggers (stimuli) occur where the entrepreneurial individual decides to form a business activity and therefore to look out for the market opportunities. On the other hand, internal triggers occur where entrepreneurial individuals recognise the needs or problems for which they can provide solutions in the market and so form a business to provide the solution or need (Singh and Gibbs, 2013).

In this context, cross case analysis findings suggest that these individuals have been influenced by external triggers, where they decided to start a business and actively look out for the opportunities within the market. These Sri Lankan retail entrepreneurs identified their opportunities in two ways.

5.2.8.1 Serving in places that others missed

Serving in places that others missed means they actively looked out for opportunities to form a business where they recognised places that lacked retail shops. The location seemed to be the key factor to forming these businesses.

Case 3's business is situated near Central London, where there are no Sri Lankan-focused retail food shops. This is an opportunity that has been missed by others especially working Sri Lankans in Central London. C3 mentioned this in his interview, and was reminded how he used to go to these enclaved places while working in Central London:

“Sri Lankans working in Central London and who don't want to take a separate tube to go to Harrow or Wembley to buy Sri Lankan stuff, just like me in the past.”

C4 said that one of the main reasons he took over the current business is that there weren't many retail shops in the area. Plus, he knows the people in the area, and it is also much easier for him to travel after the job and look after his family:

“Here, there were not many retail shops around at the time, not as much as now. Also, what kind of people live in this area and I also live nearby this area. I know the people here, and it is easy to travel and look after my family.”

C7 mentioned that, in the beginning, he checked the community before he formed a business in the area. He found that it was made up of professionals and it looked to be a 'posh' area. Perhaps 'posh' means that to him that there was a low crime rate in the area, and where the people had good spending power. At the same time, he revealed that there weren't many retail

shops around where he was looking and this influenced him to take an opportunity to form a retail business in the area:

“I checked the community in the area, what people live in this area. Here people are quiet professionals and it is a ‘posh’ area. No troubles. The area hasn’t got many shops around - this was a bonus for me. Population-wise, I knew it is not going to be busy. But I realised I could do something. So now I have a good clientele and I have got to the point where customers sometimes shop with a trolley rather using a basket. That means my business has improved a lot from what it used to be.”

5.2.8.2 Sri Lankan ethnically concentrated area

C5 mentioned that he has lived in an areas of concentrated Sri Lankan immigrants for a long time. But according to him, there is no quality Sri Lankan retail shop around the area. It may have persuaded him to take over the business as an opportunity to serve the local market gap:

“I have lived in this area for more than fifteen years. I know the community, there are a lot of Sri Lankan people also living in this area. I know all these Sri Lankan people coming to this shop for sure. We live near to them and I can close the shop and go home in walking distance. It is easier for me and we don't have quality Sri Lankan retail shop near to us.”

C6 mentioned that he found it easy to manage the business once he had familiarised himself with the people and the area. And then again, he said that Sri Lankan and South Asian people are living in the area as well. Perhaps he might be attempting to express a reference to having similar cultural background and languages:

“it is very easy to handle a business when you know the area and the people. As you know, Sri Lankan people and South Asian people are living here as well.”

One of the advantages of serving the co-ethnic community is that of a low-entry barrier to the market; and at the same time having the same cultural values, such as customers and staff who speak the same language; and having the same knowledge and behaviour, which in turn may allow them to engage with the customer more easily and work with the staff effectively (Zhou, 2004).

Case 2’s business is situated in a Sri Lankan ethnically concentrated area. One of the main advantages of business within an ethnic enclaved area is engaging with customers easily due to low-language barriers, where these customers (Sri Lankans), business owners and even staff speak the same language and share similar cultural values. In Case 2, C2 shared a similar statement, where he mentioned that he can be much more connected with the customers with Sri Lankan languages than with the English language.

“yes, speaking the same language and coming from Sri Lanka is very easy to work with, especially with customers not only from Jaffna, but if they speak Tamil or Sinhalese, I can easily understand the customer and start a good conversation, that way I make a good connection with them.”

5.2.8.3 Current Challenges and opportunities within the market

Supermarkets as a challenge

In the retail context, it is clear that supermarkets dominate the consumer retail market within the UK, and even possibly around the world. Some of the participants mentioned that they have to compete with the retail supermarkets within the area. Case 1, Case 4 and Case 8 mentioned that specifically.

C1 reflected how supermarkets challenged him as a business and possibly pressurized him to offer a lower price point due to the buying power of the big businesses:

“You know, supermarkets have their buying power, these cost-cutter chains alike have their own buying power.”

He further added that people who have low spending power compare their business with the big supermarkets around the area and ask him to lower the prices. This is because these supermarkets achieve better economies of scale, which can offer a lower price point, therefore creating price competition:

*“And one more thing, here are middle-class people, they always look for value, they compare us with the bigger supermarkets, I don’t know what to say that, but it is for me very unreasonable, not the regular ones, but some random people come up and ask - oh, I bought these on that t***o Express down the road at a lower price than this, can you lower the price for me - and the arguments go on. Sometimes the difference is around 50p, but some people want to lower the price. We can’t lower more than that, but if I say to them, they won’t come here.”*

Similarly, C4 believes that the mini supermarkets are giving his business great competition. There are two big retail names in the area, and these supermarkets attract more customers for fresh products by offering cheaper prices than his business. Hence, he had to reduce his fresh product offerings to reduce waste:

*“business is the competition from big-name mini supermarkets. When I talk about the competitors, they are like Express stores. There are two of them around the corner now, one from the S***** and the other t***o. With the fresh products, I can't even compete with them. They have nice refrigerators and they get more fresh products at a cheaper price than me. After they opened these shops, I had to reduce the stock to minimize waste.”*

C8 is facing high competition within the current market as well. He mentioned that if the service is slow, then product variety and the price point will determine his business survival, especially with supermarkets and other retail shops in the area:

“In this business people won't give you a chance, if you are late to serve, they will go to next door, if you don't have what they looking for they will go to supermarkets and if you increase the price, they will find a cheaper place like that.”

Lack of online presence

C5 said that he is far behind other businesses when it comes to online presence, which he currently lacks:

“I need to have more online presence for my business. Currently, we are very behind other businesses.”

Even though there are many more opportunities available online, especially for promoting the business, C2 focused on a traditional way of marketing rather than using new technologies to promote the business. For instance, using the search engine optimisation, where social media appeared to be unimportant to him:

“I don’t put it on Google, I’m not involved in these things very much, but somebody has put it on for me on the search engine.”

C8 claimed that he does not have any online activities to promote or to seek growth opportunities within the online retail market:

“We don’t have an online presence and promotions at the moment.”

Evolving European customer demand

C1 explained that he changing his product range to meet the Eastern European customer demand. C1 further added how he was coping with the situation as an opportunity:

“Every month we have to think about what sort of things we need to change, like what items we have to cut out or introduce. I started with Sri Lankan, South Indian and English retail items. Now I have ended up with mostly Eastern European/European retail products. It is a total shift, and still, we are learning, what to keep and what not to keep; as you can see, some of the Sri Lankan products are highly reduced, due to low Sri Lankan presence - there are Sri Lankans here, but they are very low compared to a decade ago.”

C2 mentioned that he witnessed over time that there was more of a European customer presence in the area than there used to be. This could be partly due to the arrival of European labour migrants. He said he has an opportunity to serve these European customers in the area as well, but he doesn't want to be in any other retail shops around the area and lose his business' authenticity as a Sri Lankan business:

“If you go outside, there are a lot of European people walking by than there used to be 10-15 years ago. But what I realised that if I added European items in my shop, it would become like any other Off Licence. No, this is pure Sri Lankan I want it to be that way.”

C8 mentioned that he recently experienced customers of European origin in the area. He further mentioned that these customers were having difficulties understanding or speaking English and that he struggled to serve them as a result:

“Recently there are a lot of Europeans starting to live here. Sometimes I can't understand what they are saying or questions regarding some product or items, because they can barely speak English.”

5.2.8.4 Coronavirus impact

Data on the impact of Coronavirus were recorded only with Case 3 to Case 8. The researcher collected the first data from Case 1 and Case 2 in January and February, respectively, just before the first lockdown. No data were collected during the first lockdown. However, the researcher collected data again between July and October.

Several findings emerged through data related to the impact of Coronavirus.

5.2.8.4.1 Supplier delays due to pandemic

Case 3, Case 5 and Case 8 mentioned that they had supplier delays during the first lockdown. C3 also said he had issues with supplies, which was problematic as it kept letting him down as a business:

“Lack of supplies, supplier delays to delivery and low sales stats kept letting us down.”

C5 mentioned that there were supplier delays due to Coronavirus lockdown. But C5 managed to restock as soon as possible as a result of a good supplier relationship:

“We had issues with supply delays, but we managed to stock up just right on time. You know I have other shops and I have good suppliers - I kept ordering and they kept delivering.”

C8 mentioned that his overall sales during the lockdown increased with high demand. And at the same time, his business experienced supplier delays during the period:

“I know a lot of businesses might have told you a different story, but for me, I'm was very busy. During the lockdown, my sales went up, I almost couldn't keep up with the demand. Supplies were late, to be honest.”

5.2.8.4.2 Working environment challenges

Lack of staff due to safety measures

Case 3, Case 4, Case 6, Case 7 and Case 8 reported that they had limited staff available during the first lockdown. C3 mentioned that lack of staff was another issue for his business. So it led to him and his wife having to work even harder as a business. During the lockdown period, he employed one staff with him who lived nearby. The other two staff members went on furlough:

“Problem was who was going to work in the lockdown. So I had to work myself, my wife whenever she could and one other staff member who lived nearby and all the others have gone on furlough.”

C4 described that he had limited staff available during the lockdown and afterwards. He further mentioned that he didn't have many options other than to furlough them. Therefore, he had to increase his own working hours in the shop:

“Two of my staff were furloughed due to the health conditions they have. I did not have any options. So all I did was to expand my working hours in this business and other businesses as well.”

C6 revealed that he had to cut down some of the staff during the lockdown due to their health risks:

“I had to cut down the staff. Three of my staff in this business and all the people in the health service have stopped their jobs. We have got single mothers, students and older people as our staff.”

C7 said that he sent his remaining staff on furlough, mainly due to cutting the cost and the lack of stock managing or other duties. And at the moment, he and his wife are serving behind the till:

“I don’t have staff these days in my business. I had to furlough them to cut the cost, and me and my wife stand behind the till and serve our customers. The other thing is, we don’t have many customers, we don’t have much stock managing or refills. I think it is good to furlough them.”

C8 mentioned that he had to reduce staff during the lockdown; after the lockdown, he managed to get two of the staff members back to work after being furloughed, but with reduced hours to reduce the costs:

“I had to cut the staff. Two of them I got back after furlough. I can't give many hours because we close the shops early nowadays to reduce some cost.”

Managing hygiene standards due to Coronavirus and at the same time managing the business made this a difficult and challenging time. Therefore, C3 said that he had to limit the number of customers inside the shop as well:

“the shop floor needs to be cleaned continuously. There is a health risk for everyone. So I limit the number of people inside the shop as well. Managing everything at once was a very difficult time for me.”

C6 also revealed that lack of staff made it necessary for him and his remaining staff to work harder than usual, especially when the shop floor got busy:

“I just work myself with the other remaining staff to run this shop. It is very hard to manage when it gets busy and needs a refill.”

C8 explained how he managed the business during the lockdown and after. As a family business, his wife helped him due to the shortage of staff; in particular, updating paperwork with suppliers and managing the stock was vital to them:

“it is hard nowadays. My wife was helping me during the lockdown because we were short of staff. We needed to check the stock and orders for the next day when supplies were delayed, and we needed someone to look after that and paper work. Normally me or my staff do that, now my wife has to do them. She also works hard. Because you need to update your stock.”

5.2.8.4.3 Business uncertainty

C3 has stopped his investment activities due to the uncertain environment created by the pandemic, where he thinks it is too risky to continue at the moment:

“We just put the brakes on due to the pandemic. It is too risky to spend on marketing or anything else, because this is a very uncertain time for everyone.”

C6, on the other hand, believes that the pandemic situation damaged his business. He stopped expansion plans for his current business due to the uncertainty:

“But this Coronavirus situation hit our businesses really hard. So, I still can't say, because I'm not sure what's gonna happen in the next few months.”

C7 believes that he does not have a permanent plan if the current lockdown situation continues but thinks that he can adapt to the new uncertain environment. However, C7 reflected that he is still unsure how he can get the supplies to sell as he currently has issues with supply delays:

“I don't have a fixed plan of what I going to do if this continues. What I have to do is to change according to the new uncertain environment. And see how it goes. But if there are no suppliers to give the supplies and cash and carry outlets don't have the goods I need. Then what can I sell?”

C8 mentioned that he thought the pandemic would end soon. But, as the vaccine had not been deployed when he gave this interview, he believes that people might have to live with the virus for months. Due to new social distancing rules and regulations placed by the government, he allows fewer customers inside and leaves others to wait or find another shop. He does not want to plan anything as this creates uncertainty:

“I don't know to be honest. It is very uncertain now. I thought this was going to finish soon. But I think until we find a vaccine, we will have to live with the virus, we have to allow fewer customers inside the shop than we used to. Some of them don't want to wait, and they go next door sometimes. It is impacting our business negatively as well. I won't plan anything yet, and I will see how it goes.”

Figure 20: Summary of opportunity structure cross case analysis

5.2.9 Institutional embeddedness

The wider “macro” level of the model looks at factors such as government regulatory and legal boundaries of the host country, and the impact on the minority entrepreneur and their ownership of their business activities from an economic standpoint. For instance, allowing any shops to open all day, seven days a week in the UK, results in main stream supermarkets having the advantage to operate their retail network twenty-four hours a day. Consequently, this forced small ethnic retail businesses to have lower sales or forced them to close their businesses (Ram and Jones, 2008).

5.2.9.1 Overall positive feedback on rules and regulations UK

However, almost all of the cases shared an overall positive view on government regulations in the UK. C3 overall is optimistic about the rules and regulations in the UK for small businesses. He further mentioned that implementing those rules and regulations results in good health and safety standards and a safe environment for people and businesses. Therefore businesses should always follow them:

“Rules and regulations are implemented to make sure there will be good quality standards of our food items, provides a good business environment for us as businesses and for the people, health and safety of all of us. I think we should follow them.”

Similarly, C5 reflected a positive view:

“I think it would be easier to run a business in the UK than in Sri Lanka. I think because of the rules and regulations in the UK, it is really helpful for us to run a business smoothly.”

C5 further added that his council was helpful to him by providing information:

“The council have been very helpful over there. They gave us the precise information we needed. I think it was a huge deal for us before making a decision.”

Again, C6 mentioned that regulations make a safer place for everyone, reflecting a positive impression:

“there is a big difference - in Sri Lanka as a developing country we don't have as many rules and regulations as we do here; in the UK, we have a lot of rules and regulations which actually help to regulate the businesses, work according to the rules and make a safer place for everyone. There are a lot of rules to follow which I sometimes find a bit difficult to cope with as a small business owner.”

C7 mentioned that it is easy to work with UK regulations:

“in here I found it pretty straight forward and easy if you have the money and the people. But back in Sri Lanka, there are not many government regulations or even though we have them, it is not properly executed, corruption everywhere, and the underworld. Here in the UK, you have sets of rules and regulations that work, are safe to work, have good police around the area, and have a security system. And I am happy to be here.”

C8 also mentioned that the UK is a safer place and it is easier to run a business here than in Sri Lanka:

“I think running a business is easier here than in Sri Lanka. I'm Tamil, so you know what kind of situation there was twenty years ago. Plus, as a Sri Lankan, we need to put regulations and law systems in place. At the moment, I don't think those kinds of things are working there effectively yet. In Sri Lanka, rules and regulations are very important to run any kind of a business. I am very happy about running a business here. But there are some regulations to put in place for the big supermarkets. They are taking away customers from us by opening a mini supermarket around our businesses. I think we need some laws or regulations to control this.”

5.2.9.2 Issues with rules and regulations

5.2.9.2.1 Having too many regulations to follow

Findings also revealed that these participants mentioned their critiques on UK regulations, such as having too many rules and regulations to follow. This was noted by a few of the participants. C3 mentioned that the local council in the area follows strict health and safety regulations, especially in food and retail businesses. Hence, he had to spend a lot of money to bring the standards back up to meet the local council standards, particularly when he took over the building from the previous owner, who had left the place dirty:

“Another thing is like so many rules and regulations in the council. Since this is a food retail shop, health and safety regulations are very strict. I took over this business from another owner on lease. They made this very dirty. I had to spend a lot of money on health and safety standards to meet government regulations.”

C6 has a similar experience with the regulations. He has positive views about government rules and regulations. However, he sometimes finds these regulations challenging to cope with as there are so many of them:

“there is a big difference, in Sri Lanka as a developing country, we don’t have as many rules and regulations as we do here, in the UK, we have a lot of rules and regulations which actually help to regulate the businesses, work according to the rules and make a safer place to everyone. There are a lot of rules to follow which I sometimes find, a bit difficult to cope with as a small business owner.”

However, one participant mentioned that he had to change his initial business idea and change it to a retail shop. C2 initially wanted to open a restaurant. However, the council refused to give him a license to operate as a restaurant, so he came up with the idea of a retail shop instead and wanted to pay the mortgage through the business:

“This area’s council refused to give me the a3 licence because I wanted to open a restaurant, but they didn’t give me it to me at that time but not now, nowadays they (council) gives it to everybody. So I have to pay the mortgage somehow isn’t it, so I eventually opened this little shop in our small community.”

5.2.9.2.2 Government policy on migration

C1 mentioned that, on one occasion, he observed that the number of customers of South Asian origin was decreasing and the number of European people coming to his shop was gradually increasing. This could be partly due to the high number of European migrants into the UK in recent years. These migrants do not necessarily need to have any form of entry requirements (free movement of people) such as speaking the English language and any other educational or professional qualifications. These are one of the benefits of being a member of the European Union (EU) for any country. There were almost no restrictions on EU migrants to work or settle

which has led in recent years to a high number of European people coming into the UK. Perhaps this might have negatively impacted on the South-Asian ethnic minority businesses:

“You are having lots of different types of people and because of that reason you have lots of different customers here. In that way, getting to know customers is not stable like it used to be before. One day you see Indians, Sri Lankans and all sorts of South Asians and slowly now you see all these Eastern Europeans who are not able to speak to you or you can't speak to them, they do not speak English as well you know. So yeah, I have to face different customers, customers moving around this area often, it's very dynamic.”

C8 similarly reflected about language barriers in serving these European customers:

“Recently, there are many Europeans starting to live here. Sometimes I can't understand what they are saying or questions regarding some product or items, because they can barely speak English.”

Thus C2 reflected a similar view, where he mentioned that he does not want to lose his authenticity as a Sri Lankan business because of the new European customers in the area:

“If you go outside, there are a lot more European people walking by than there used to be 10-15 years ago. But what I realised that if I added European items in my shop, it would become like any other Off licence. No, this is pure Sri Lankan and I want it to be that way.”

5.2.9.2.3 Import regulations

Some of the cases mentioned their views regarding the import regulations in the UK. C1 sees importing regulations as not motivating him to import anything from Sri Lanka. Therefore he relies much more on local suppliers.

“We don’t import anything directly, but we are relying on the suppliers at the moment. Because a lot of rules and regulations have been involved when attempting to import here. It is very difficult.”

C5 reflected a similar view:

“Sometimes we bring stuff from Sri Lanka, but also not really easily, because here they put on taxes and take a long time to clear.”

5.2.9.3 Coronavirus support

On the other hand, the participants have also mentioned government support concerning the Coronavirus. Most of them were positive and appreciated the help they have received so far from the government, especially the furlough scheme. C3 appreciates the UK government approach to a small family run business like his. He further mentioned that this kind of encouragement motivated him to be in business throughout the lockdown:

“This is the most generous and helpful government I have witnessed so far. People should appreciate these kinds of encouragement to small family-run businesses like us.”

C4 statement reflected a similar view:

“the furlough scheme is really good. Otherwise, I don't know how I would pay staff wages. It is a big relief, to be honest.”

Then, C6 appreciated the government taking care of the vulnerable staff and others during the lockdown:

“We have got single mothers, students and older people as our staff. They are being furloughed. I really appreciate the government taking this action.”

Some participants revealed that several of the Coronavirus rules had consequences for their businesses as well; for instance, the 2m rule. C3 said that he had to limit the number of customers who were allowed to be in the shop at one time due to regulations:

“like the 2m rule and face masks - this almost brought us down. This is a small business you can see we have very limited space. Since there is this 2m rule we can't allow more than 6-7 people inside the shop at one time. Either the customer has to wait, or like many of them they leave. Now this is frustrating for me.”

One participant criticized the trading hours of retail businesses in the UK. Due to Coronavirus, the government has made it compulsory for businesses to close earlier than usual, on special days and Sundays. C4 mentioned that he could manage to go home early due to the government Coronavirus regulations, but that has impacted his sales, especially on late nights, and particularly with alcohol and beverages:

“the government made us shut the shop early as well. I could go home early, but that impacted the sales as well, especially the alcohol section at night.”

Figure 21: Summary of institutional embeddedness cross case analysis

5.3 Summary

This is the outline of the thesis findings and it helps to achieve both the second and third objective in the thesis and hence, to answer the main research question. The themes were extracted from individual cases, which were categorised under the individual (micro), opportunity structure (meso) and institutional embeddedness (macro) level of the mixed embeddedness model. Importantly, Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in the retail context revealed their motivation factors: success perception; human capital, social capital; access to finance, access to labour; supplier relationship, employee relationship, and customer relationship themes that have emerged from the data. The wider opportunity structure revealed the findings of their opportunity structures which explained how they gained their opportunities, current challenges and further opportunities within the market, and the impact of the Coronavirus pandemic on their businesses. Lastly, further institutional embeddedness (macro) analysis revealed the themes, such as positive attitude with the current rules and regulations in the UK, as well as the issues surrounding the same regulations. Government policy on migration and Coronavirus support by the government emerged as main themes.

Chapter 6: Discussion

6.0 Introduction

This chapter discusses the findings of this research relating to achieving the second objective (*‘investigate Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs' current status/background to understand their retail entrepreneurship activities’*); and the third objective (*‘to understand how they enhance trust and loyalty for their customers in the retail grocery business context’*). Therefore, it discusses the findings relating to Sri Lankan ethnic minority entrepreneurship and their characteristics: motivation to be in the business, success perception, their resource employability; Human capital, Cultural capital, Social capital; and supplier, employee, and customer relationships. Then, the opportunity structure which consists of current opportunities, challenges and future opportunities. Lastly, the regulatory environment (institutional embeddedness).

6.1 Motivation to be in the business

Table 2 in Chapter 5 gives an overall picture of motivation factors spread across the cases. According to the findings, it can be argued that many of these Sri Lankan entrepreneurs have been ‘pulled’ in to form a business rather than been ‘pushed’ into business activities. The main pull factors from the findings across the eight cases were independence (Case 1, 2,3,4,6 and 8), financial benefits (Case 3, 4, and 8), and previous work experience (Case 4 and 8). Independence is seen as a pull factor by several scholars (Basu, 1998; Kirkwood,2009). Many of these entrepreneurs regarded their independence as having autonomy (Gelderen, 2016). However, in the South-Asian ethnic minority entrepreneurship context, independence is also a major motivation for attracting these entrepreneurs into business activities (Basu, 1998).

Similarly, this also appeared to be valid for Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs. According to Dawson and Henley (2012), financial benefit is also a pull factor for entrepreneurial activities. Thus, they mentioned entrepreneurial occupational decisions based on the expected earning difference between full-time employment and self-employment (Rees and Shah, 1986). According to the findings, this is also true for these Sri Lankan individuals, where these entrepreneurs mentioned their earning power as ‘making more money than a full-time job’. On the other hand, Basu and Goswami (1999) found that previous work experience positively related to a business formation in the South Asian ethnic entrepreneurs. Therefore, findings suggest that this also appeared to be true for Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs as well.

Overall, data from across Cases 1, 5, 6, and 7 found several push factors along with unique case factors (which only emerged in within-case analysis and not with cross-case analysis). These are: a lack of job opportunities found in the market (after redundancy or finding a similar job in a different area due to change of residence); family maintenance (business formed as a means of supporting the family and unique case factors); job dissatisfaction; job insecurity (fear of redundancy); and language barriers. However, these findings resonate with Dawson and Henley (2012) findings, and Kirkwood (2009) argues that these factors occur due to external market conditions.

Interestingly, it is obvious when looking at the overall findings of the motivation factors for Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs that they suggest to us a mixed picture (where some cases emerged with pull factors and others possess push factors). Equally, some cases (namely Case 1 and Case 6) seem to possess both push and pull factors within the individual case analysis. Therefore, it can be said that it is difficult to explain/categorise motivation factors of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in the UK by using the traditional push-pull theory of motivation. Some researchers argued that this is because these factors are based on individual, situational and specific characteristics (Dawson and Henley, 2012; Jones and Ram, 2013). Therefore, researchers suggest that these motives depend on various factors, and are generated from both push and pull motivational factors (Kirkwood, 2009; Madduma and Watkins-Mathys, 2019). Similarly, recent findings of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in other contexts suggest that these individuals possess both push and pull motivation factors when they are forming business activities. For instance, Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse (2015) found from the research

conducted in Australia that Sri Lankan ethnic minority entrepreneurs tend to possess push and pull factors when entering business activities. Thus, cultural and social capital plays a huge role in their entrepreneurial orientation. Consequently, Madduma and Watkins-Mathys (2019) found similar findings from Sri Lanka and argued that these individuals in Sri Lanka have been motivated by both push and pull factors, and these factors are influenced by their situational, cultural and social context. Then again, this can also relate to the research findings of this study because some of the findings, such as family maintenance (cultural), lack of job opportunities (situational) and characteristics (such as independence) align with the literature. Lastly, therefore, drawing from the findings and the literature in this research, it can also be argued that Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in the UK have also been motivated by both push and pull factors to enter entrepreneurial activities. Similarly, these factors are influenced by their situational, cultural and specific characteristics.

6.2 Success perception

The cross-case findings suggest that these Sri Lankan migrant entrepreneurs view their success much more subjectively than financially, or in other words, objectively. Table 11 gives us an idea of how these individuals see their success in summary format. The main themes that arose from the data are: individual satisfaction, support for the family, and having no debts (financial security mainly for family). There are different interpretations and definitions of individual satisfaction in the literature (Cooper and Artz, 1995). However, according to the discrepancy theory (Higgins, 1987), the entrepreneurial satisfaction process is a ‘cognitive comparison process’ where these entrepreneurs determine their success by comparing (‘perceived gap’) what they have at the moment and what they want to have (Manzano-Garcia and Ayala-Calvo, 2020). C1 mentioned that he formed the business due to job redundancy when he could not find a suitable job afterwards. In his statement, he compares his current situation with his past by stating, ‘I came into this country with nothing. Today, thirty years down the line, I think I have achieved more than I wanted and for my family’. He reflects on his satisfaction as an achievement in the current situation. This argument is also in line with McClelland (1988),

where he argued that these kinds of entrepreneurs ‘ push to form a business supplying basic life needs’, which could end up having powerful entrepreneurial motives.

According to the self-determination theory (Ryan and Deci, 2000), relatedness (connected with others) is one of the psychological needs for self-satisfaction. Similarly, Madduma and Watkins-Mathys (2019) found that gaining social recognition/status for the success within their community is also important for Sri Lankan individuals to enter business activities. It was also found that ethnic entrepreneurs view success as the earning/achievement of social recognition from their particular community which they are embedded in (Solymossy, 1998; Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse, 2015). Thus, according to the self-determination theory mentioned above, social status or ‘relatedness’ is also one of the psychological needs for entrepreneurial satisfaction (Ryan and Deci, 2000). A similar situation has been demonstrated by Case 6, where he (C6) mentioned that if the customer is satisfied with the business's products/services and shares this positive status possibly with other customers within the society, this is a success for him. On the other hand, autonomy is also seen as one of the important psychological needs to achieve individual satisfaction (Ryan and Deci, 2000; Walker and Brown, 2004; Madduma and Watkins-Mathys 2019). In Case 8, data suggest that C8 satisfied himself by achieving independence/ autonomy through his business.

Thus, support for the family also emerged in the data to describe these individuals' success. These participants think that, in summary, being able to supply the needs of the family is viewed as a success for them. According to Samaratunge and Nyland (2006), family support, savings and embeddedness in their culture are vital ingredients of the Sri Lankan social security system and play a significant role in Sri Lankan culture. Similarly, Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse (2015) found that family support is one of the main reasons why Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Australia entered business activities in the first place. This is also in line with Madduma and Watkins-Mathys (2019) findings, where family support/ influence plays a major role in their entrepreneurship activities. Perhaps this is also the reason here in the UK as to why these individuals view their entrepreneurial success as supporting the family and their needs.

6.3 Human capital

Even though many of the participants admitted that they have a good educational background, all the cases have mentioned gaining necessary knowledge and skills from their family business background, (and) or previous work experience and social network. Ethnic entrepreneurs face difficulties when running a business in the host country. Some quickly adapt to the new business environment and learn important skills faster, while others may struggle for success. Thus, coming from a family business background has helped some of these entrepreneurs learn the necessary skills and knowledge to perform or impact their business positively (Elizabeth and Baines, 1998), especially, on some occasions, while they were growing up. Some of the necessary skills and knowledge appeared to be learned from their home country and used within current businesses in UK. This form of knowledge is also called ‘tacit knowledge’ which means that knowledge which is hard to codify and may be transferred in ways of experience and direct exposure (Lane and Lubatkin, 1998; Dessi *et al.*, 2014) (Case 1 (C1), Case 6 (C6), and Case 7 (C7)). Thus, the literature has also found that family members who do not work for the business directly also have a significant influence (VanAuken and Werbel, 2006). Family relations help/influence the owner decision-making process positively and add benefit in other ways, and interact/advise in the family business interface (Danes *et al.*, 2009). This can also be related to most of the individual cases in this analysis (Case 2 (C2), Case 3 (C3), Case 4 (C4), Case 5 (C5)).

Looking at the cross-cases also suggests that these individuals gained their necessary skills through previous work experience. Light and Gold (2000) regarded previous work experience as one of the primary examples of human capital found within these minority individuals (Case 2 (C2), Case 4 (C4) and Case 5 (C5), and Case 6 (C6)). The analysis also suggests that these entrepreneurs also use their social network to gain information and share knowledge within their social groups (Ram *et al.*, 2000), particularly within Case 1 (C1), Case 4 (C4), and Case 6 (C6).

6.4 Cultural capital

The findings regarding cultural influence can align with the classical theorists, where (Sri Lankan) ethnic culture plays an important role in their ethnic entrepreneurial activities (Aldrich and Waldinger, 1990; Light and Gold 2000). For instance, motivation factors appear to be influenced by their culture. According to Samaratunge and Nyland (2006), family support, savings, and embeddedness in their culture are vital ingredients of the Sri Lankan social security system and play a significant role in Sri Lankan culture. Therefore, as findings suggest, one of the motivating factors and success perception is themed around the family. Analysis also suggest that gaining the knowledge and necessary skills to run a business in the UK is also influenced by their family or in other words, their culture. Family influence seems to play an important role in these Sri Lankan businesses (Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse, 2015). Employing family members either directly or indirectly seems to be common with these businesses. Their connection with the family members back home also plays a role in their businesses, even though these members are not directly involved (Danes *et al.*,2009), such as acquiring and seeking advice from their elders (their fathers and other family/relative siblings). This can be found in the data. This is because Sri Lankan culture values and respect elders (Madduma and Watkins-Mathys, 2019) and sharing the same culture and language is beneficial for managing a good employee relationship (Horvat, Weiningger and Lareau, 2003). At the same time, culture is also befitted to maintaining customer relationship (empathy; treating the customer as a family member). Thus, other cultural-specific knowledge about products also benefitted them in demonstrating their competence and problem-solving orientation (see the discussion on trust) (Throsby, 1999).

On the other hand, their success perception (as mentioned above) is subjective, which is influenced by the culture (success as an ability to support their family). Literature suggests subjective measures could limit business growth opportunities (Smallbone *et al.*, 1999). Findings also indicate co-ethnic based relationships may also have a negative side (employee relationship cross-case analysis) (Hyun-soo Kim,2016).

6.5 Social capital

The cross-case data suggests that these Sri Lankan individuals also rely on their family and social network to access finance as they appeared to more reliable than financial institutions. For instance, Case 1 (C1), and Case 2 (C2) revealed that they do not want to rely on the bank and other financial institutions in the UK, because it takes a long time to process and at the same time, it is not guaranteed that they will receive money or not; hence expressing their uncertainty (Kraybill, Nolt and Wesner, 2010). On the other hand, in line with the literature, almost all the other participants mentioned that they mostly rely on their family members (Danes *et al.*, 2009) and social network to access their financial capital, especially in the start-up stage (Yoon, 1991; Ram *et al.*, 2010). This is more in line with the findings of the Sri Lankan entrepreneurial activities in Australia. These entrepreneurs have had access to finance and overcame other entrepreneurial barriers through support from their family and social network (Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse, 2015).

Thus, findings suggest that these Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in the UK also have access to their labour capital through family members and their social network. The significance of family influence and its importance when operating a business has been found in the literature (Habbershon, Williams and MacMillan, 2003; Sirmon *et al.*, 2008). One of the important aspects of family influence is the ability to maintain a trustful relationship between their members (Hoffman, Hoelscher, and Sorenson, 2006; Pearson, Carr, and Shaw, 2008), and with their social networks (Ram, 1994). These Sri Lankan individuals also mentioned that they employ family members and employees through their social network because of the trust-relationship (Ram, 1994; Smith, Wistrich and Haynes, 2001). Hence, these kinds of relationships are viewed as an operational advantage for entrepreneurs, such as privacy and efficient communication (Tagiuri and Davies, 1996). Other participants, namely C3, C4, C7 and C8 also mentioned that importantly, their wives were involved, directly and indirectly, when necessary to the business. This exemplifies availability and access to labour capital through family members when required, which is also demonstrated by Sri Lankan entrepreneurs, as this can bring productivity into their business activities (Portes, 1995; Danes *et al.*, 2009).

6.6 Supplier relationship

Developing a good supplier relationship and its importance has been mentioned in the literature (Cannon *et al.*, 2010). Thus, factors such as market competition and its dynamics impact these small businesses creating enormous pressure to compete and survive (Kloosterman, 2010). These individuals develop their own strategies to overcome the challenges given by market structure and other external factors. One apparent challenge that these family-centred businesses face is that they cannot achieve the economy of scale in comparison to big corporations (for instance, supermarkets) who have the advantage (by achieving the economy of scale) to offer the same products at a lower price (Orth and Green, 2009; Wang and Altinay, 2012). Data from the cross-case analysis suggests that having a good supplier relationship is important and allows these individuals to offer their product at a lower price.

On the other hand, these individuals also mentioned that they could obtain these products on credit as well; they think this is mainly because these suppliers 'know who they are'. This statement is interesting to the researcher because it might explain how these Sri Lankan entrepreneurs develop a good relationship with the supplier. Secondly, Case 5 (C5) and Case 7 (C7) mentioned that they pay on time to make these suppliers (in their words) 'happy'. This can be explained by the psychological contract, which Hill *et al.*, (2009, p.283) viewed as an 'assumed set of reciprocal obligations between parties in a relationship'. According to this theory, looking after each other's needs while a business exchange is taking place seems to be the key factor in these relationships. For instance, these individuals pay their suppliers on time. Therefore, it can be assumed that the suppliers' needs have been satisfied. In return, they offer back their products on credit, at lower prices and other benefits to the entrepreneurs. On the other hand, perhaps 'they know me' could symbolise their reputation (reputation will be extensively discussed in the customer relationship section) as Sri Lankans highly value social recognition in their culture (Samaratunge and Nyland, 2006; Madduma and Watkins-Mathys, 2019). Over time this could build trust between supplier-buyer relationships and certainly benefit the business (Gullet *et al.*, 2009).

6.7 Employee relationship

Building a good employee relationship also seems to be important for some of these entrepreneurs. Most of these participants did not talk about their employees extensively. And the researcher did not have access to interview the employees. But some of these participants, namely Case 2 (C2), Case 5 (C5), Case 6 (C6) and Case 8 (C8), discussed the importance of having a good employee relationship to their business. These four cases commonly mentioned employees who speak the same language and come from a Sri Lankan background, which has benefitted their business in several ways. Mainly, these characteristics enable the entrepreneurs to communicate better with the staff, to manage them, and allow employees to enhance the business's customer relationship. Perhaps, what they refer to here as the same language and background could be related to cultural capital (Throsby, 1999; Altinay, Saunders and Wang, 2014). Hence, the ethnic-specific language and their background (coming from Sri Lanka), or cultural capital, appeared to benefit from developing the employee relationship and managing and building the customer relationship through the employee in the business (Ram, Edwards and Jones, 2007). This can be related to literature as culture, which could potentially lead to economic value in managing people productively as they communicate effectively with the employees (Horvat, Weininger and Lareau, 2003), simultaneously, developing the customer relationship through them to the business, (possibly retaining and attracting more customers) and generating profit and competitive advantage (Lareau and Weininger, 2003). Thus, employing employees from the same backgrounds has its benefits, such as developing trustful relationships (Woolcock, 1998; Ram, Edwards and Jones, 2007). Lastly, one participant mentioned its negative aspects, which ultimately led to permanently closing one of his businesses (Hyun-soo Kim, 2016).

Section 6.1 to 6.7 thus far came up with the themes such as support from the family/ influence, tacit knowledge, previous work experience (having being able to work on their family businesses/or relatives businesses), employee relationships and supplier relationships are influenced by their (Sri Lankan) culture.

Figure 22: Ethnic cultural influence on micro level of the discussion section 6.1 to 6.7

6.8 Customer Relationship

6.8.1 Customer trust

6.8.1.1 Operational benevolence

Many of these participants demonstrated the characteristics of limiting their self-serving opportunism. This is shown because many of the participants mentioned that money is not a priority for them, but that giving the right product information, giving an honest opinion, and hence achieving customer satisfaction is, in fact, more important to them. Orth and Green (2009, p.250) view customer satisfaction as ‘the consumers’ assessment of the extent to which retailer performance on specific dimensions meets or exceeds prior expectations’. Therefore according to the literature, their FLE behaviour on the shop floor limiting self-serving opportunism might exceed the customer’s expectations, hence leading to customer satisfaction. Thus, according to Macintosh and Lockshin (1997), interpersonal ties or social relationships with the customer is an important factor for increasing the salesperson-customer trust relationship. Notably, these individuals also demonstrated that they value the customer presence by mentioning that they ‘treat them like they are family members’ (especially C1 and C2); ‘we care for the customers’ and do not pretend as they value the customers (giving an honest opinion) (Orth and Green, 2009). Treating the customers or any other relationship member as their family member may develop through their culture, as Sri Lankan culture is much more family-centred and supportive and is recognised as a key element in the social security system (Samaratunge and Nyland, 2006). They regard someone as if they are family, in order to express their respect and attention towards the individual (Chapin, 2014; Madduma and Watkins-Mathys, 2019). Also treating the customers as a family member has been seen by some scholars as empathy in other contexts (Parasuraman, Berry and Zeithaml, 1991; Beatty *et al.*, 1996). Hence, this explains why some of the individuals regard their (regular) customers as family members.

6.8.1.2 Problem-solving orientation

On the other hand, data suggest that these participants also achieved their trustworthiness through problem-solving orientation. Problem-solving orientation is defined as ‘the consumer’s evaluation of FLE and management motivations to anticipate and satisfactorily resolve problems that may arise during and after a service exchange’ (Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol 2002, p.18). Case 1(C1), Case 2(C2), and Case 3(C3) showed their front line employee (FLE) behaviour as demonstrating problem-solving orientation. On-site field notes/observation were used to describe their problem-solving orientation. The data suggest that all these cases, namely Case1, Case 2, and Case 3 showed their behaviour towards favouring the consumer’s interest, even if this behaviour cost to the business. These findings align with the definition of problem-solving orientation above and are also in line with Hart, Heskett and Sasser (1990), who mentioned customer problems as an opportunity to show their commitment to the customers, and gain their trust, even when the business is not to blame.

6.8.1.3 Operational competence

Lastly, the same observational data (see the section of problem-solving orientation cross-case analysis) can also be used to describe their operational competence. The researcher had fewer chances (restricted time) to be inside the shop during the interview after the first lockdown, due to health and safety concerns (Coronavirus social distancing). Therefore, limited time on-site led to having less observational data to describe the operational competence, which could have been explained through their behaviour. However, Case 2 and Case 3 observational data have revealed enough findings to explain their trustworthiness generated through operational competence as well. For instance Case 2 demonstrated that his product knowledge translated into observable behaviours which helped a customer to make the desired product choice (Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol, 2002). Case 3 (C3) also reflected this in a post service exchange scenario, where he demonstrated that giving the right product information (knowledge) to the customer (FLE observable behaviour) allowed her to find a product of her

choice as a replacement. Mayer, Davis and Schoorman (1995, as quoted in Orth and Green, 2009, p.249) noted that ‘operational competence is that group of skills, abilities, and characteristics that enable a party to effectively perform a task within a specific domain’. In this case, it has been found that many of the participants have a family business background in Sri Lanka (see the human capital discussion), and they are exposed to ‘tacit knowledge’ (Dessi *et al.*, 2014). Data in other cases, especially Case 2 and Case 3, demonstrated that this product knowledge appeared to concern Sri Lankan ethnic-specific retail food products (such as Case 2, relating to Sri Lankan curry powder; and Case 3, relating to Sri Lankan rice product called ‘Samba’) so that we can assume that they learned this back home, or through their culture (in other words, cultural capital). Therefore, it can be argued that the operational competence of these Sri Lankan entrepreneurs is also influenced by their ethnic culture.

6.8.2 Customer service

6.8.2.1 Customer orientation

Having a good customer service is vital to building a good relationship with the customer, and at the same time may lead to achieving its long-term success and sustainability (Liu and Yang, 2019). Scholars identify the importance of customer service in the family business context, and this is regarded as critical to their business success particularly in the long term (Haq *et al.*, 2021). Data suggested that the customer service of the Sri Lankan ethnic retail business entrepreneurs consists of delivering customer orientated and customer-centric service, empathetic behaviours towards the customer, developing patience towards the customer and letting the customer make the buying decision. Customer orientation is defined as ‘a retail frontline salesperson’s focus on meeting customer needs in performing their job responsibilities’ (Brown *et al.*, 2002, p.111). Many of the participants mentioned that they are concerned about the needs of their customers and orienting their business towards meeting them appeared to be vital for them. Most of these owners rely on feedback from their regular customers to identify the customer needs, hence improving their offering.

6.9.2.2 Customer centricity

On the other hand, data also revealed that these participants make decisions based on customer feedback and therefore make decisions by prioritising the customer. In other words, they allow the customer to play a central role in their business decisions and its orientation. Thus, these participants also believe that every customer's needs are different, hence every customer is different, reflecting that they focused on providing individualised customer service (Gummesson, 2008). It has been found that these descriptions are much more in line with the concept of 'customer-centricity'. Putting the customer first, or according to Tseng and Pillar (2003) customer-centricity is defined as 'a customer-centric enterprise that places the demands and wishes of each single customer in the centre of value creation'. Thus, focusing on a customer-centric approach will lead to customer satisfaction (Shah *et al.*, 2006), and strong customer loyalty (Habel *et al.*, 2021).

6.8.2.3 Developing empathy for the customer

Data suggest that these individuals demonstrate empathetic behaviour towards the customer. According to Wieseke, Geigenmuller and Kraus (2012, p.317) empathy is defined as 'a person's intellectual understanding of the internal state of another person'. Similarly, some scholars view empathy as 'perspective-taking', which allows an individual to understand another person's point of view, anticipate his or her reaction and to deliver their (perceived) needs, opinions or motivations (Devoldre *et al.*, 2010). Thus, data suggest that many of the cases practise empathy as an aim to develop customer satisfaction. Hence, customer satisfaction will eventually lead to customer retention and loyalty (Anderson, 1998). Therefore, it has been found that satisfying the customer is key to creating customer loyalty towards the business (Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003). Also, many of the cases demonstrated that they are concerned about caring for the customer rather than making a profit/sale. On the other hand,

some special cases, namely Case 1(C1) and Case 2 (C2) mentioned that they treat their customers as family members. Treating a customer as if they are a family member can refer back to ‘perspective-taking’ as mentioned above, which also demonstrates empathy (Parasuraman, Berry and Zeithaml; Beatty *et al*, 1996). Thus, this could be related to Sri Lankan culture, as they regard them as their family and show their respect towards an individual (see discussion section of trust) (Chapin, 2014; Madduma and Watkins-Mathys, 2019).

6.8.2.4 Developing patience for the customer

The theme of developing patience towards the customer also emerged from the data. Patience is seen as a skill, and it was found that it benefits businesses positively, especially in the retail business environment (Beatty *et al.*, 1996). Parasuraman, Berry, and Zeithaml (1991) claimed that it is related to customer satisfaction, hence to customer retention (Johnston, 1995). In the current context, the participants also mentioned that they develop patience towards the customer ‘to make them happy’, or in other words, it can be argued that they are concerned with customer satisfaction (Johnston, 1995; Beatty *et al.*, 1996). Thus, Hagedoorn *et al.*, (1999, p.310) describe patience as ‘the act of waiting optimistically’. Consequently, giving time to the customer is a good indicator of how much a business cares for the customer and is central for their business (Shah *et al.*, 2006). Some of the cases mentioned that they give over time to listen to the customer (Case 4 (C4) Case 5 (C5) and Case 2 (C2)).

6.8.2.5 Letting the customer make the buying decision

The fact of letting the customer make the buying decision also appeared to have emerged in the data. These individuals furnish their customers with correct product information and allow these customers to make their own decisions. This approach is also called collaborative selling (Alessandra and Barrera, 1993) Thus, it has appeared that they do not believe in a traditional hard selling technique, which is considered as a ‘shotgun salesperson’ approach towards the

customer, which ignores their needs and cares very little about after-sales (Alessandra and Barrera, 1993). Many of the participants demonstrated that they do not convince the customer to buy something from them, or in other words, many of the statements reflected that they do not want to be involved in the buying decision (Haq *et al.*, 2021). Thus, findings also suggest that these participants do not make the customer spend more than they should in their stores. In particular, one participant mentioned comparing his business with supermarkets. In Case 1 (C1) further elaborated that he does not have any sales promotions which normally make the customer buy more than they should be (Gilbert and Jackaria, 2002; Prendergast, Shi and Cheung, 2005).

Statements like ‘not draining out money’, ‘not running after the money’, and ‘stressing the customer’, perhaps can be referred to as good ethical practice (Mella and Gazzola, 2015). These individuals mentioned before that their selling approach towards the customer is not solely based on earning money, but that satisfying the customer is at their core (Haq *et al.*, 2021). In other words, making the customer needs central to the exchange (customer-centricity) (Tseng and Pillar, 2003). Findings also suggest that giving the right product information is seen to be important as it provides the customer with the right product information to make their choice, which reflects collaborative selling.

6.8.3 Business reputation

Cross case analysis shows that these individuals appeared to maintain their reputation by practising good ethics. Fombrum and Van Riel (1997, as quoted in Mella and Gazzola, 2015 p.41) defines business reputation as ‘a corporate reputation is a perceptual representation of a company’s past actions and future prospects that describe the firm’s overall appeal to all of its key constituents when compared with other leading rivals’. Thus, according to Mella and Gazzola (2015, p.41), ‘ethics are frameworks for human conduct that relate to moral principle and attempt to distinguish right from wrong’. Also, maintaining a good set of ethics leads to maintaining a good reputation; hence it is vital for the survival of organisations in the long term (Mella and Gazzola, 2015). Since these businesses also show the characteristics of family firms, the literature finds that these businesses are not only making decisions to improve their

economic activities but also working towards achieving socio-emotional objectives as well, such as maintaining a good image and reputation of both business and family (Sageder, Mitter and Feldbauer-Durstmuller, 2018). Hence, these socio-emotional objectives motivate the family firms to initiate activities which may benefit other stakeholders who are out with their family (Zellweger *et al.* 2013). Customers refer to reputable companies with the characteristics of being credible, responsive, reliable and trustworthy (Fombrun and Van Riel, 1997). Interestingly, almost every statement given by the participants regarding business reputation mentioned earning the trust of the customer. Therefore, these participants appeared to be practising good ethics by not following unethical marketing strategies (Sihem, 2013), or unreliable or illicit practices which may reflect dishonesty towards the customer and which would eventually breach the trust between the business and customer. Therefore, leading to a bad reputation for the business. Thus, findings revealed that these participants also appeared to benefit from managing a good reputation, particularly with the suppliers who offer products on credit. Practising good ethics is a key role of corporate social responsibility as well. According to Azmat and Zutshi (2012), reputation is important for Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Australia to enhance customer trust. They further found that these individuals manage reputation by also practising ethics, so that they can manage a good trust relationship with the customer, as an attempt to retain them. They also argue that their ethics practices are influenced by Sri Lankan culture. These findings suggest that participants are operating their businesses in more socially responsible ways by practising ethics.

Similarly, aligning with the literature and findings of this study, it can be argued that these participants in the UK also gained their reputation by practising ethics, thereby enhancing the trust of the customers; in other words, ethics as management policy practice (MPP) to gain customers' trust (Bejou, Ennew and Palmer, 1998). Trust is antecedent to loyalty (Orth and Green, 2009). In return, it enhances their loyalty practices.

6.8.4 Loyalty

6.8.4.1 Loyalty determinants

The researcher now draws from the main points of the previous sections (6.8.1, 6.8.2, and 6.8.3) in summative format of loyalty determinants pointing towards answering the main research question of: *how do Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance the trust and loyalty of their customers within the retail grocery businesses in UK?*.

6.8.4.1.1 Customer Trust

Trust is one of the most important and critical factor to impact the relationships significantly to its existence (Moorman *et al.*, 1993; Morgan and Hunt, 1994). The level of ('perceived') trust between these relationships is recognised as a vital building block and can be found in most trust-related models (Wilson, 1995). Trustworthiness is regarded as an 'antecedent' to the existence of trust. According to Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol (2002, p.17) trustworthiness is defined as 'to include Front line employee (FLE) behaviours and Management policy practices (MPP) that indicate a motivation to safeguard consumer interest'. These FLE and MPP observable behaviours include operational benevolence, problem-solving orientation and operational competence. Thus, scholars argue that trust is a critical factor to determine loyalty. The customer who is unwilling to trust the business is unlikely to become loyal to it (Orth and Green, 2009). Therefore, several authors regarded trust as an 'antecedent' to loyalty (Sun and Lin, 2010). Thus, customer satisfaction also leads to loyalty (Bejou, Ennew and Palmer, 1998). Consequently, according to some scholars, customer satisfaction can also be regarded as an 'antecedent' to loyalty (Orth and Green, 2009). The findings of trustworthiness indicate that their management practices and Front-line employee behaviours, such as limiting self-serving opportunism as money is not a priority for them (Operational benevolence); giving the right product information (operational competence); using their (cultural) knowledge; and giving the customer an honest opinion (valuing the customer) appeared to navigate towards the achievement of customer satisfaction, hence the trust. According to Macintosh and Lockshin (1997), interpersonal ties or social relationships with the customer are important factors for

increasing the salesperson-customer trust relationship. They also value their customers by regarding them/ treating them as their family members, because of the possible influence of Sri Lankan culture (Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse, 2015). This is also called 'empathy' (Parasuraman, Berry and Zeithaml., 1991; Beatty *et al.*, 1996). Hence empathy will also lead to customer satisfaction (Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003). Therefore, it can be said that these participants achieved their loyalty by earning the trust through delivering customer satisfaction.

6.8.4.1.2 Service

Having a good customer service is vital to building a good relationship with the customer, and at the same time may lead to achieving its long term success and its sustainability (McCracken *et al.*, 2017). Scholars also identify the importance of customer service in the family business context, and regard it as critical to their business success, particularly in the long term. On the other hand, customer satisfaction can be achieved through service by meeting/exceeding the customer expectation on the service encounter (Kursunluoglu, 2014). Hence, the characteristics of the service and its performance are vital to customer satisfaction, thereby generating loyalty (Kursunluoglu, 2014). Within this case study, findings suggest that these participants include characteristics of delivering customer orientated and customer-centric service, empathetic behaviours towards the customer, developing patience towards the customer and letting the customer make the buying decision (Haq *et al.*, 2021). These participants are orienting their business towards satisfying the needs of the customer and prioritising the customer when decision making. They also provide individualised service, making decisions central to the customer and individualising customer service which can be referred to as the concept of customer-centricity (Gummesson, 2008). This has a profound effect on both customer satisfaction (Shah *et al.*, 2006) and loyalty (Habel *et al.*, 2020). Findings also suggest that these participants demonstrate empathy towards the customer as an aim to deliver customer satisfaction (Bahadur, Aziz and Zulfiqar, 2018). Hence customer satisfaction leads to repeated customers and loyalty (Anderson, 1998). Thus, they also appeared to be more concerned about caring for the customers than the monetary objectives of the business (Orth and Green, 2009;

Haq *et al.*, 2021), in some cases treating customers as their family members in a way to demonstrate empathy (Parasuraman, Berry and Zeithaml, 1991; Beatty *et al.*, 1996). On the other hand, findings also revealed that this behaviour could also be influenced by Sri Lankan culture (Chapin, 2014; Madduma and Watkins-Mathys, 2019). Nevertheless, patience also appeared as a characteristic of the service, and it can also link to customer satisfaction and retention (Parasuraman, Berry and Zeithaml, 1991; Esmark and Noble, 2016). Thus, these participants also seemed to not influence the decision making of the customer. This approach is called 'collaborative selling' where these individuals inform their customers with correct product information and allow the customers to make their buying decisions. Findings suggest that this behaviour can also be linked to ethics, as they do not prioritise money (Mella and Gazzola, 2015) but rather satisfying customer needs is at its core. In other words, reflecting the customer centricity, hence again demonstrating customer satisfaction (Tseng and Pillar, 2003). Therefore, it can be argued they deliver a service focusing on satisfying the customer. Again, these characteristics of service appear to lead to customer satisfaction, thereby they also generate loyalty through their service (Kursunluoglu, 2014).

6.8.4.1.3 Reputation

On the other hand, findings suggest that these participants appeared to maintain their business reputation by practising good ethics. Maintaining a good set of ethics leads to maintaining a good reputation, hence it is vital for the survival of organisations in the long term (Mella and Gazzola, 2015). Since these are family-oriented firms, the literature finds that these businesses are not only making decisions to improve economic activities but are also working towards to achieving socio-emotional objectives as well, such as maintaining a good image and reputation of both business and family. Hence, these socio-emotional objectives motivate the family firms to initiate activities which may benefit other stakeholders who are out with their family (Zellweger *et al.* 2013). Customers refer to reputable companies with the characteristics of being credible, responsive, reliable and trustworthy (Fombrun and Van Riel, 1997). Interestingly, almost every statement given by the participants regarding the business

reputation mentioned about earning the trust of the customer. Therefore, these participants appeared to be practising good ethics by not following unethical marketing strategies (Sihem, 2013), or unreliable or illicit practices which may reflect dishonesty towards the customer, and would eventually breach the trust between the business and customer (Leninkumar, 2017). Practising good ethics is a key role of corporate social responsibility as well. Therefore, findings suggest that these participants operate their businesses in a more socially responsible way. According to Azmat and Zutshi (2012), reputation is important for Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in Australia to enhance customer trust. They further found that these individuals manage reputation by also practising ethics, so that they can manage a good trust relationship with the customer, as an attempt to retain them. They also argue that their ethics practices are influenced by Sri Lankan culture.

Similarly, aligning with the literature and findings of this study, it can be argued that these participants in the UK gained their reputation by practising ethics, thereby enhancing the customers' trust. In other words, ethics as management policy practice (MPP) to gain customers' trust (Bejou, Ennew and Palmer, 1998). The literature mentioned that customer trust is an antecedent to loyalty (Ganesan, 1994; Orth and Green, 2009). Therefore, in return, it enhances their loyalty. Lastly, it can be argued that these participants manage their reputation by practising ethics (as a MPP) which lead to gaining customer trust, hence enhancing loyalty.

In essence, section 6.8 highlights that operational benevolence influenced by ethnic culture (values customer by treating them like family member). Thus, problem solving orientation and operational competence also influenced by their ethnic product knowledge (could relate to tacit knowledge), which influenced by Sri Lankan culture. Service also has influence by culture, especially developing empathy for the customer. Letting the customer to make the buying decision (not draining money), customer centricity (prioritising customer needs making the customer central to the business rather monetary objectives) were common to these businesses. These evidences can be link back to maintaining good ethics (as a MPP). It seemed to be reputation is important for Sri Lankans as it enhances customer trust by managing ethics. These ethics practices also appeared to be rooting from Sri Lankan Culture. Thus, ethics enhances trust, hence loyalty. Customer trust and service also leads to high customer satisfaction, hence loyalty.

Figure 23 Ethnic culture, customer trust, loyalty, customer satisfaction, ethics, reputation, and its relationship with each theme

6.9 Opportunity structure

Market conditions create the opportunities for ethnic entrepreneurs, particularly when there is a product(s) or service(s) targeted at the co-ethnic community of the host country (Aldrich and Waldinger, 1990). However, the opportunities and its structural components continuously change due to facts like disruptive technological developments, various complex market scenarios and globalisation etc. Nevertheless, findings of the Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in the retail context suggest that these participants recognise their opportunity as a result of external triggers. External triggers occur where the entrepreneurial individual decides to form a business activity and, therefore looks out for the market's opportunities (Bhave, 1994). Thus, findings suggest that these entrepreneurs identified their opportunities in two ways. They serve in places that others have missed (places that lack retail shops); and form the businesses around Sri Lankan ethnically concentrated areas. The location seemed to be the key to developing these businesses, as they lacked retail shops. Thus, the location was found to be one of the important factors for retail stores, where it could lead to better convenience for the customer (Litz and Rajaguru 2008).

These participants seem to recognise the opportunities and form the businesses around the Sri Lankan ethnic concentrated areas. This can also be interpreted as an ethnic enclaved area. Some of these participants mentioned that living in the area and understanding their community needs often led to forming these retail businesses. Some of them said that speaking the same language and having the same/similar cultural values, allows them to work efficiently with the employees and develop a good customer relationship (Zhou, 2004).

On the other hand, findings also revealed current opportunities and challenges they are currently facing within the market. Supermarkets seem to be giving these small ethnic retailers challenging competition (Simms, 2012). Particularly, findings suggest that these supermarkets were pressurising smaller businesses into lowering their prices (Burt and Sparks, 2003). In the main, these supermarkets achieve better economies of scale by offering a lower price point,

which creates competition (Clarke, 2000; Ram and Jones, 2008). Similarly, it is found in the literature that these smaller retail SMEs cannot compete with big retail corporations, especially small businesses in the family business context (Danes, Loy and Stafford, 2008). Findings suggest that some of these businesses do not have any online presence, such as websites and social media activities. Lack of online presence could be limiting them in terms of exploring the opportunities in the online markets and future growth opportunities (Beckinsale and Ram, 2006). Some of the participants revealed that they experienced that the number of European customers visiting their shop or presence in the area has increased over time. Case 1 sees this mainly as an opportunity, while others (Case 2 and Case 8) see it as a threat to their businesses. These two cases suggested that they are losing their authenticity. At the same time, one explained his concerns that he might not be able to serve or understand them, as it seems to be that these European immigrants cannot speak the English language fluently. This could be partly due to the recent labour migration from the European Union, where there are no such entry requirements when they enter the country (Cremers, 2016). Thus, this can be interpreted as a negative side of relying heavily on their co-ethnic community for business activities (Ram and Jones, 2008; Ram, Jones and Villares-Varela, 2017).

Findings also revealed the impact of the Coronavirus pandemic on these businesses as well. Supplier delays were mentioned during the lockdown, which in turn impacted their sales. C5 reflected that maintaining a good supplier relationship was vital for him as it led to stock being delivered on time (Cannon *et al.*, 2010). Then, working environment challenges also emerged from the data where lack of staff, managing the business during the lockdown appeared to have been impacted as well.

Interestingly, some of the participants employed their family members (C3, C7, and C8), which showed that these family-oriented individuals have access to labour capital through their family members whenever required (Danes *et al.*, 2009). It is a known fact that the Coronavirus pandemic created uncertainty for businesses. Similarly, some participants also reflected their uncertainty of the situation (Witteveen, 2020).

Figure 24: Summary of opportunity structure discussion

7.0 Institutional embeddedness

Findings suggest that these participants share positive views on rules and regulations in the UK compared to Sri Lanka. Many of them believe that rules and regulations must be in place for a safe business environment for everyone. They appeared to follow the rules, and on some occasions, regardless of the cost. Perhaps this could also be linked back to ethics (Azmat and Zutshi, 2012), because practising good business ethics requires following the law and regulations (Mella and Gazzola, 2015). However, some of them revealed that these rules and regulations are harder to follow at times. They mainly mentioned that there are so many of them to follow. According to Kloosterman (2010), this is one of the reasons why these small business owners end up in low entry barrier markets or informal business activities because of the complexities of regulatory bodies in advanced economies, particularly on taxation, health and safety, and import regulations (Jones *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, these findings suggest that UK regulatory bodies still do not favour ethnic minority businesses in the UK by making too many rules to follow at once, hence reflecting complexity (Ram and Jones, 2008). Therefore these should be (at least) minimised or simplified particularly for these small ethnic businesses.

Three of the cases mentioned that they are witnessing a number of European customers in their shops recently. Interestingly, Case 1(C1) sees this as an opportunity, while others see it as a

threat for their business. First, these business owners rely heavily on their customer feedback or opinions to improve their businesses (Macintosh and Lockshin, 1997; Haq *et al.*, 2021). Second, many of them mentioned that they build customer relationships by ‘talking to them’, which implies communication. Then, language plays a vital role in understanding customer needs and developing their customer relationships. Two of the cases mentioned that these customers of European origin could barely speak English or understand each other while interacting with them. It is a known fact that these Europeans migrated to the UK as being part of the European Union. One of the benefits of being a member of the European Union is freedom of movement. These migrants can move into any country (in this case, UK) of the Europe Union without any entry requirements, such as language or job offers (Hix, Kaufmann and Leeper, 2017). Perhaps, this could partially explain why these European migrants failed to speak in English and built a good customer relationship.

Cases 3 to 8; Coronavirus related findings also appeared in the institutional data as well.

The furlough scheme: findings revealed that participants mostly relied on the furlough scheme to pay their employees and gave positive feedback on the scheme (Witteveen, 2020). On the other hand, some of the Coronavirus related regulations introduced by the government also had consequences for their businesses (Ntounis *et al.*, 2020), for instance, they had to allow only a limited number of customers in their shops; and the social distancing rule appeared to make them lose customers, and therefore impacted on their sales. On certain days, limited trading hours (perhaps on Sundays) also appeared to affect one participant, especially on beverage sales.

Figure 25: Summary of the institutional embeddedness discussion

7.1 Summary :

The discussion revealed characteristics of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs such as motivation factors, which resulted in the conclusion that these Sri Lankan entrepreneurs could not be explained by the push and pull theory of motivation as they possess both push and pull motivating factors. Then, it was revealed that these participants view success much more subjectively. The ability to support their family is the main measurement of success. They have gained their necessary skills and knowledge mainly from a family business background from Sri Lanka, previous work experience in the UK, and from social networks. Thus, it is also found that these entrepreneurs were exposed to ‘tacit knowledge’. Social capital helped them to access finance, labour capital, and information and knowledge. The findings also revealed that many of these businesses showed characteristics of family businesses. These participants also value supplier relationships and tend to manage a good reputation with their suppliers, which benefits the business. On the other hand, findings also revealed the importance of an employee relationship with their businesses. Many of them mentioned that having Sri Lankan background and speaking the same language as their co-ethnic employees has allowed these participants to manage them efficiently, build better customer relationships and at the same time develop a trustful relationship with the employees. These findings also highlight the importance of culture which was beneficial when employing family members, having a good employer-employee relationship, and developing a good customer relationship.

Section 6.8 answered the main research question of *‘how do Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance the trust and loyalty of their customers within the retail grocery businesses in UK?’*, hence achieving the third objective of this thesis. First, these participants gained customer trust mainly through the front line employee (FLE) behaviours. These behaviours included limiting self-serving opportunism and not prioritising the monetary objectives, which leads to customer satisfaction. Thus, findings also suggest that cultural influence also helped them develop customer trust relationships. In conclusion, all these characteristics and behaviours lead to customer satisfaction, hence trust. Then again, trust is an antecedent to loyalty. Therefore, these participants achieved their loyalty by earning trust through delivering customer satisfaction.

The service is also vital to building a good customer relationship. Participants demonstrated that their service includes the characteristics of customer orientation, customer centricity, developing patience and empathy and letting the customer make buying decision. Findings suggests these characteristics drives customer satisfaction, hence the loyalty.

Reputation is vital for any organisation to sustain in the long-term. Maintaining a good set of ethics will eventually lead to gaining reputation. The findings evidenced that these participants practice ethics to gain customers' trust. The findings also suggested that Sri Lankan culture influences them to practice ethics. Nevertheless, it concluded that these participants in the UK also gained their reputation by practising ethics, thereby enhancing the trust of the customers; in other words, ethics as management policy practice (MPP) to gain customers' trust. In return, it enhanced their loyalty practices.

Then the opportunity findings revealed that these entrepreneurs find their opportunities in two ways: first they find the places which lack retail shops; and second, they form businesses in ethnically concentrated areas. Location seems to be the key for their retail business formation. Current challenges and opportunities are also highlighted as supermarkets, European customer presence and lack of online activities.

The Coronavirus impacts were also highlighted - supplier delays, working environment challenges and lack of staff. Equally, having family members and good supplier relationships during this time led some participants to overcome some of the challenges during the pandemic.

Lastly, the findings also discussed the institutional embeddedness of these participants. Many of them shared their positive feedback on the rules and regulations. And at the same time, they shared the challenges they faced in following them. Therefore, these rules and regulations should be minimised or simplified particularly for these micro-business entrepreneurs. Findings suggested that other regulations, such as immigration, raised the importance of regulated entry requirements. The furlough scheme during the pandemic seems to be helping these small businesses. On the other hand, findings suggest that social distancing and safety rules during the pandemic have negatively impacted their business.

The previous chapters (namely chapter 5 and chapter 6), have lead to develop a conceptual model, which explains the Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurship and how they enhancing 'How

do Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhancing trust and loyalty of their customers within the retail grocery business in UK?'. section 6.1 to 6.7 highlights mainly the micro level findings of the Ethnic entrepreneurship and its relationship with the Srilankan Culture. section 6.8 mainly discusses customer trust and loyalty practices, which answers the aforementioned main research question. It is apparent now that the Sri Lankan culture also influence/help these businesses to maintain their customer trust and loyalty practices. Thus, meso-level of the discussion highlights that the social ties also shape these entrepreneurs opportunity structure. The institutional discussion highlights the regulatory issues and its influence to the opportunity structure of these businesses. Drawing from the findings and its discussion from this thesis, the researcher can draw a visual representation of the conceptual model and its relationship as below.

Figure 26: conceptual model to explain Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurship and how they enhance trust and loyalty of their customers within the retail grocery businesses in UK

Chapter 7: Conclusion

Introduction 7.0

This thesis explores Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurship and how they enhance customer trust and loyalty in the retail context. Chapter 6 achieved both the second and third objectives of this study by investigating Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs' current status/background to understand their retail entrepreneurship activities. The third objective was to understand how they enhance trust and loyalty for their customers in the retail business context, hence answering the main research question: *'how do Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance the trust and loyalty of their customers within the retail grocery businesses in UK?'* Therefore, this chapter will attempt to achieve the last objective of this research: *contribute to the knowledge by generating implications/recommendations to enhance their trust and loyalty practices.*

7.1 Research contribution

This research contributes to the knowledge in both theory and practice in the ethnic minority entrepreneurship in UK. Thus, research contributes to extending ethnic minority entrepreneurship in the context of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in the UK. This research study also contributes to understanding the Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs and their activities through the mixed embeddedness model. The model enabled us to understand and gave insight into the rarely mentioned Sri Lankan ethnic group in the UK and their customer trust and loyalty practices. Two of the literature bodies have helped answer the main research question and make sense of the findings of this thesis. These two are: customer relationship marketing and the mixed embeddedness model of ethnic minority entrepreneurship.

7.1.1 Key findings and contribution to the customer relationship marketing

Customer relationship marketing extends, and highly values, customer interaction, customer satisfaction, customer trust and loyalty. Findings suggest that these Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance trust and loyalty in a number of ways.

First, the findings suggest that these entrepreneurs gain their trust through front line employee (FLE) behaviours in operational benevolence; showing the behaviour of limiting self-serving opportunism, and valuing the customer presence. The problem-solving orientation is achieved by showing the behaviour of favouring the customer's interest, even at cost to the business. Operational competence was also demonstrated in that they used their knowledge to give the right product information. Interestingly, operational benevolence and operational competence appeared to be influenced by their culture as well. Then, findings suggested that these behaviours centred on the achievement of customer satisfaction (Bejou, Enew and Palmer, 1998). Then, according to the literature, customer satisfaction also leads to loyalty (Orth and Green, 2009). Therefore, these participants achieved their loyalty by earning the trust through delivering customer satisfaction.

Second, their service included the characteristics of customer oriented and centric service, developing empathy towards the customer, developing patience towards the customer and letting the customer make the buying decision (collaborative selling). These characteristics also centred on achieving customer satisfaction. Importantly some of the characteristics, such as empathy, is also influenced by Sri Lankan culture. This customer-centric approach to the service appeared to enhance their customer satisfaction, hence their loyalty.

Third, findings suggest that these participants appeared to maintain their business reputations by practising good ethics. Maintaining a good set of ethics leads to developing a good reputation; hence, it is vital to the survival of organisations in the long term (Mella and Gazzola, 2015). Being a family firm also influences gaining a good reputation, because, these family-oriented firms not only make decisions for their economic activities but also work towards

achieving socio-emotional objectives as well. Hence, these socio-emotional objectives motivate the family firms to initiate activities that may benefit other stakeholders out with their family (Zellweger *et al.* 2013). Interestingly, findings revealed that these participants' statements gave the impression that they care about the customer's trust in their business. Therefore, these participants appeared to be practising good ethics by not following unethical marketing strategies (Sihem, 2013) or unreliable or illicit practices that may reflect dishonesty towards the customer, and which would eventually breach the trust between the business and customer. Practising good ethics is a key role of corporate social responsibility as well. Therefore, findings suggest that these participants are operating their businesses in a more socially responsible way. Cultural influence may also be significant here (Azmat and Zutshi, 2012). Therefore, it can be argued that these participants practising ethics gain the trust of the customers, or to phrase this differently, ethics as a management policy practice (MPP) gain the trust of the customers. Practising good ethics leads to gaining a good reputation and therefore earning customer trust. Earning trust will lead eventually to customer satisfaction (as mentioned before), hence loyalty. Therefore, it can be argued that these participants manage their reputation by practising good ethics to gain customer trust, which can lead to loyalty.

Lastly, it can be argued that these Sri Lankan entrepreneurs enhance their trust and loyalty by demonstrating customer-centred FLE behaviour and service, which leads to customer satisfaction, and at the same time to practising good ethics (as an MPP); this in turn gained them customer trust, hence loyalty. Therefore, the thesis contributes to the customer relationship marketing in the view of ethnic minority entrepreneurship.

7.1.2 Key findings and contribution to the mixed embeddedness model

The research highlighted the motivation factors of success perception and their resource employability towards the businesses. Findings revealed that these participants could not be explained by the traditional push-pull theory of motivation to explain their motivation factors, because they possess both push and pull factors. These factors are influenced by their situational, cultural, and social contexts that they embedded in (Kirkwood, 2009; Madduma

and Watkins-Mathys, 2019). Thus, findings suggest that these individuals tend to view success much more subjectively. It is concluded that cultural influence (mainly family support) also impacted their success perception as well (Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse 2015). Thus, even though many of these entrepreneurs are educated, the findings revealed that tacit knowledge (coming from a family background) and previous work experience were important to operating a business in the UK. Again, family support and influence were highlighted in regard to human capital as well. Thus, family and social capital were important to them in order to gain financial capital, labour capital and even gaining and sharing knowledge. Other benefits through social capital, such as supplier relationship (Gullet *et al.*, 2009) and employee relationship, also emerged in the data (Lareau and Weininger, 2003). Cultural importance and influence were also highlighted in the supplier and employee relationship.

Opportunity structure highlighted the market structural factors that contributed to these entrepreneurs recognising their opportunities. In the retail context, they recognise their opportunities in two ways: serving the places that others missed; and forming the businesses around Sri Lankan ethnically concentrated areas (Zhou, 2004). Thus, the importance of the location for retail businesses was also highlighted (Litz and Rajaguru, 2008). Furthermore, market opportunities and challenges have also been highlighted. Competition from supermarkets for these businesses was identified as a significant challenge, while the lack of online activities was seen as impeding their future growth opportunities. European customer presence was highlighted as a threat and at the same time, an opportunity. Hence, the consequences of the non-regulated labour migration impact was highlighted. Thus, these Sri Lankan individuals tend to rely on their co-ethnic communities and culture for their business activities. It is recommended that they should move out and serve the mainstream market. Then again, culture could possibly hinder them from having such opportunities (Zhou, 2004). The impact of the Coronavirus also emerged from the findings, including supplier delays, lack of staff, and work environment challenges. Some of the ethnic resources appeared to be useful for them during this difficult time.

Overall, participants view rules and regulations in the UK positively. They follow the rules, even if it costs them. These findings also reflected their commitment to practising ethics. However, the complexity of the regulations was highlighted (Kloosterman, Van der Leun and

Rath, 1999). And findings also stressed that entry requirements for immigration should be regulated. Coronavirus related data was highlighted again relating to the regulatory body. The furlough scheme was highlighted, and participants gave positive feedback. Other regulations, such as social distancing rules, limited trading hours, and their negative impact were further highlighted.

Therefore, these findings revealed the contribution to the mixed embeddedness model, which argues that ethnic minority entrepreneurs and their businesses are not only influenced by their socio-ethnic cultural factors, but also by their broader economic and institutional environments which these entrepreneurs are embedded in (Kloosterman and Rath, 2001).

7.2 Implications and recommendations of the findings

7.2.1 Implications for researchers

The research findings in the context of entrepreneurship explain how these ethnic entrepreneurs enhance their customer loyalty and trust practices by extending the current mixed embeddedness model of ethnic minority entrepreneurship. In the current context of customer relationship marketing and ethnic minority entrepreneurship, this thesis explains how these ethnic minority entrepreneurs enhance their customer trust and loyalty within the socio-cultural, economic and institutional environment they are currently embedded in. Secondly, it enhances our understanding of how culture influences their business practices (specifically ethics and reputation), relationships, and decision-making.

It is noteworthy that researchers can use these findings and develop a model to understand trust and loyalty practices within other ethnic communities.

7.2.2 Implications for practitioners

Places that lack retail shops within the community, and notably ethnic concentrated areas, have provided these ethnic entrepreneurs with a niche market opportunity for their business activities. Relying on such places and co-ethnic communities benefitted these Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in terms of co-ethnic customers, suppliers, and employees sharing cultural values in order to compete with a wider saturated retail market. The culture and social connections also seem to be reasons that they flourish in these places. Findings also suggested that these entrepreneurs, in showing their informal behaviour towards the customer relationship (e.g.; treating them as a family member), in gaining a reputation and in following ethics are part of/ or are influenced by their culture. The importance of co-ethnic communities for the existence of these businesses is apparent. There are factors found in the data that could impact community existence in the UK. One factor is that a decline in South-Asian population in the UK may occur due to the strict regulations for immigration placed by the UK government.

A further factor, as findings suggest, is the non-regulated labour immigration from European countries. Non-regulated means EU member residents can arrive anytime without any entry requirements, such as language competency or a job offer. Once they arrive in these areas for living, as some cases confirmed, perhaps the reason why these migrants failed to communicate (in English) with these business owners. As they heavily rely on communication to build their customer relationship, some participants stressed their concerns over failure to do so with Europeans. As the Brexit referendum occurred, perhaps this could be regulated. The Migration policies after Brexit are still debatable, and uncertain (Hix, Kaufmann and Leeper, 2017). On the other hand, this may further reduce the number of people entering the UK, specifically from South-Asian regions.

Therefore, practitioners need to be cautious in relying solely on culture-based co-ethnic communities as this might not necessarily be sustainable in the future. These practitioners can diversify or find new ways of doing business, such as breaking out from their co-ethnic market and finding new ways to serve the mainstream customers (Ram and Jones, 2008). It has been found that these entrepreneurs also lack online presence/business activities. Thus, internet-based business or e-commerce could be an opportunity to capture, expand and target ethnic or

mainstream consumer markets (Beckinsale and Ram, 2006). The Coronavirus pandemic has shown these individuals the importance of e-commerce. In other words, being aware of potential future scenarios based on the environment they are currently embedded in and understanding ever-changing customer behaviours would enable them to plan and strategize future opportunities, hence avoid uncertainties. For instance, the Coronavirus pandemic has exemplified how these ethnic entrepreneurs relied on their family and social network to survive and to conduct their businesses. On the other hand, it also demonstrated their uncertainty towards the future by only looking at one business model.

Thus, in the context of customer trust and loyalty practices, Sri Lankan entrepreneurs relied on an informal relationship with the customer, suppliers and employees. The majority of the findings revealed that these relationships would often lead to customer satisfaction, enhancing trust and loyalty. But practitioners need to understand the disadvantages of these informal relationships (Den Butter and Mosch, 2003; Danes *et al.*, 2009). In the customer relationship, many of the participants focused on satisfying the customers, which leads to high customer satisfaction even though, as was often demonstrated, this was at a cost to their businesses. These exchanges were mainly demonstrated with their regular customers, hence reflecting a trust relationship. Case 2 revealed the negative side of these informal relationships with employees based on trust, where the business owner eventually had to close the business (Den, Butter and Mosch, 2003). Practising ethics allowed them to gain a good reputation, and hence trust and loyalty. Indeed, other policies regulating these exchanges, such as return policies, formal employee contracts, and transparency, could further benefit from gaining a reputation, hence enhancing trust and loyalty.

7.2.3 Implications for policymakers

The research findings suggested that supermarkets significantly impacted their everyday business, especially with the price section. The research also found that mini supermarkets which developed around small communities specifically made this competition more intense. On the other hand, these small businesses depend mostly on their aforementioned small communities, creating value in terms of location (convenience). Therefore, these mini supermarkets should regulate these locations, and policies should be put in place to support these small business owners. Thus again, this is one of the disadvantages of relying on the community as a business. Therefore, as a recommendation, these small business owners can look beyond their communities and expand their business into a wider society.

One of the important factors that emerged from the research study is their human capital. The majority of the participants mentioned that they have gained their human capital in terms of previous work experience and family business background. It appears that these participants lacked business knowledge, therefore, offering targeted retail industry training programs that would enable them to gain necessary business and industry knowledge would enhance their small business practices and sustainability.

On the other hand, access to finance remains a challenge with ethnic minority entrepreneurs. The findings suggest that long processing times and uncertainty forced these ethnic entrepreneurs to rely on their family and social network to access financial capital. Therefore, the government and other responsible bodies should support minimising the processing time and uncertainty within financial institutions. Also, educating them in accessing financial requirements and the mechanisms therein should be essential in this case.

Findings also revealed that these participants are having difficulties in managing rules and regulations. They believe that there are too many of them to follow, hence representing the complexity (Kloosterman, 2010), particularly health and safety, taxation and import regulations. As a support, policy makers can consider these findings and work towards simplifying or implementing easy to follow regulations. On the other hand, entrepreneurs should be aware of the changes in these regulations as following the rules and regulations are

part of managing good ethics. Lack of knowledge or breaching the rules and regulations may lead to a bad reputation.

In the case of the Coronavirus pandemic, many of them appreciated and actively used the furlough scheme to pay their employees. Other rules and regulations to reduce the spread of the virus may appear to have negatively impacted some businesses, such as social distancing rules and trading on particular days. Policymakers could find ways or solutions during the pandemic to minimise the impact of these rules and regulations.

Regulations regarding immigration should also be reviewed due to Brexit, especially entry requirements. But, to emphasise, these regulations should be equal and immigrant friendly, as these businesses mainly depend on their co-ethnic communities and culture.

7.3 Limitations of the research

This research extends and supports the literature on ethnic minority entrepreneurship. The analysis is based on Sri Lankan ethnic minority groups in the UK and therefore does not imply that this research can be generalised to other ethnic minority entrepreneurial communities. The first limitation is the small sample size; a total of eight Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs were selected. In-depth unstructured interviews with field notes were used for data gathering. The Coronavirus pandemic and lockdown significantly impacted the researcher's data collection process. Thus, it also considerably impacted the sample size of the participants, because many of the other possible participants refused to participate in the research due to the Coronavirus. However, the researcher gained access to data before (two samples), and after the lockdown eased in July 2020 (a total of a further six samples).

Furthermore, the main location was limited to London, primarily due to the ease of access and the highly concentrated Sri Lankan community presence in London boroughs. Findings may differ at local, regional and national levels (Kloosterman and Rath, 2001). The researcher did not have access to interview the employees or potential family members, which could have given rich insight to the findings.

7.4 Contributions to methodology

The study methodically provides a good understanding of Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurship in the UK. Even though these Sri Lankan entrepreneurs are very conservative regarding sharing their information with third parties (Azmat and Zutshi, 2012), sharing the same culture and being embedded with the Sri Lankan community has helped the researcher to make this research study possible. Then the Nvivo software helped the researcher to organise, retrieve and understand key themes effectively (Glaser, 2007). The other significant impact was the Coronavirus pandemic and the government action to lockdown. This had a serious impact on data collection. As a consequence, the researcher did not collect data between late March to the beginning of July. The researcher then started to collect the data as soon as the first lockdown rules were eased and it was safe to visit. Unstructured interviews allowed the interviewer to guide questions about the Coronavirus pandemic issues to the entrepreneurs and their businesses.

7.5 Future research

This could be one of the unique empirical findings in Sri Lankan entrepreneurs in the UK context, especially regarding customer trust and loyalty practices in small Sri Lankan ethnic businesses. However, the researcher further thinks that the following areas are worth researching to contribute to the body of knowledge in ethnic minority entrepreneurship in the future.

- a. The thesis findings are based on a small sample size of Sri Lankan entrepreneurs. It would be worthwhile to investigate these small ethnic businesses' customer trust and loyalty practices involving a larger qualitative inquiry into the retail and/or other service sectors. Expanding regional or national contexts would give fruitful insight and contribute to the body of literature significantly.

- b. As these businesses are family-oriented, the current study did not have access to interview the family members and staff. It would also be of interest to investigate the same phenomenon, including their views, which might give interesting insights into customer trust and loyalty practices.
- c. Findings suggest that culture plays a significant role in shaping the behaviours of the business and owners. It would also be interesting to investigate what cultural factors contribute to enhancing their customer trust and loyalty practices.
- d. This research is based on the owner's perspective of trust and loyalty practices in their businesses. It would be worthwhile to investigate the customer's view of these businesses, especially in Sri Lankan ethnic concentrated areas. This would enable us to understand their view of these ethnic retail businesses and factors that would further enhance trust and loyalty practices.
- e. The finding suggests that many of these entrepreneurs view their success subjectively, hence this is limited to describing their success objectively. Again, without objective measures such as financial or other related data, it is difficult to analyse the performances of these businesses. Hence it is difficult to describe their sustainability overall. A larger quantitative inquiry to investigate their success factors and its relevance to sustainability would enable policymakers and practitioners to support and improve their business practices in the future.

7.6 Summary:

The chapter summarises the conclusion of the entire study. In light of the findings (Chapter 5), and its discussion (Chapter 6), I believe that this research delivered the appropriate explanation to the main research question of '*How do Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneurs enhance the trust and loyalty of their customers within the retail grocery businesses in UK?*'; that is, these ethnic entrepreneurs enhance their customer trust and loyalty through multiple ways. Findings suggested that they gain customer trustworthiness, hence trust, by demonstrating operational benevolence, problem-solving orientation, and operational competence and so oriented their behaviour to deliver customer-focused satisfaction. Customer satisfaction was found as an

antecedent to loyalty. Their customer service skills also appeared to have characteristics such as empathy, patience, customer centricity, customer orientation, and letting the customer make the buying decision, which, in return, drives high customer satisfaction. Therefore, the service also leads to gaining customer loyalty. They are practising good ethics in their businesses to build good reputations. The ethics will also enhance customer trust with the business, hence gain loyalty. Thus, findings suggest that these Sri Lankan entrepreneurs entered the business influenced by both push and pull factors. They view their success much more subjectively, and they value family presence in the business. Their human, financial, labour capital mainly came through their family and social networks. As with other South Asian counterparts, their culture also plays an important role in shaping their entrepreneurial activities. Current opportunities and challenges, along with the impacts of the Coronavirus pandemic are also discussed. Theoretical and empirical contributions were highlighted. Implications of this research study for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers were mentioned in this chapter. Lastly, the research limitations, contributions to the methodology and future research paths were discussed.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Defining Key Concepts

Ethnic Resources

Ethnic entrepreneurship resources discuss the nature and various types of resources accessible to the particular ethnic group. It contributes to the current theory to understand how these ethnic resources are deployed and explored for the sake of economic development (Dana *et al.*, 2020). These resources are vital tools for ethnic minority entrepreneurs as it could significantly help to gain success and minimise the disadvantages they face (Villares-Varela, Ram and Jones, 2018).

Human capital

Becker (2009, p.134) described human capital as knowledge and skills collected by any given individual's learning process to enhance productivity; whereas Armstrong (2006, p.66) defined the concept as individuals who create, retain and practice skills and knowledge and generate intellectual capital. Similarly, Light and Gold (2000) describes any investment made by individuals for their productivity. At the same time, the term productivity means an individual's capability to 'add value' by doing their work (Bhatti and Zaheer, 2014).

Knowledge

Davenport and Prusak (1998, p.1) viewed knowledge as: 'information that has been combined with experience, context, interpretation, and reflection'.

Tacit Knowledge

'Tacit knowledge' means that knowledge is hard to codify and may transfer in ways of experience and straight exposure (Dessi *et al.*, 2014). Thus, tacit knowledge of the same phenomenon reflects a deeper understanding of its nature and processes that is difficult to pass

on, and may only be developed, over time, through close, personal experience of the phenomenon (Lane and Lubatkin, 1998; Dessi *et al.*, 2014).

Social capital

According to Ryan *et al.*, (2008), social capital can be viewed as a social structural function which can produce an advantage, while Putnam (1992) described social capital as ‘connections’ within and in-between the social networks and its value creation to the individual. Generally, social capital describes the relationships, connections, and interdependencies among individuals/organisations or groups based on shared trust, respect, and confidence in a reciprocal way (Ram; 1994; Danes *et al.*, 2009; Ivy, Larty and Jack, 2015). Likewise, there are two types overall to the social capital; ‘bridging’ social capital and ‘bonding’ social capital. Bridging social capital means forming the value from networks outside their ethnic group (Beaudoin, 2011), while bonding social capital is the value formation from or in-between ‘homogenous’ groups.

Labour capital

There are two dimensions for ethnic-centred labour capital when attempting to explain the phenomenon. The first dimension is employing ethnic labour, and the second is the circumstances that occurred after the succession of the ethnic entrepreneur. Minority enterprises, especially when collecting resources like labour, business information, and necessary capital from their co-ethnic group, are particularly important when forming the business (start-up stage), which, in turn, is vital for its survival and existence (Waldinger, 1986; Ram *et al.*, 2001). The second dimension that occurs, as mentioned above, is when succession takes place. For instance, Asian firms are likely to operate and survive by consistent participation and contribution of their family members (Ram *et al.*, 2001; Samaratunge, Barret and Rajapakse, 2015). Therefore, family integration to the business is vital for the ethnic entrepreneur as it helps the sustainability of the venture (Kidwell, Hoy and Ibarreche, 2012).

Financial capital

The financial capital attempts to explain accumulated wealth among the members of ethnic groups and their entry into the host country's financial resources (Schmitt-Rodermund and Silbereisen, 2008). Developing a business idea into a venture involves start-up funds and other essential financial capitals to minimise the barriers and risks (Ram *et al.*, 2002). However, access to finance for the minorities and their small ventures in their host country (for example, accessing to bank loans) seems to be much harder than the main stream entrepreneurs (Ram and Smallbone, 2003). To overcome the barrier, ethnic entrepreneurs look for alternative methods for gaining financial capital. They often achieve this through social networks (often their family members and friends) (Kraybill, Nolt and Wesner, 2010).

Relational capital

Relational capital is a type of social capital which exists in the form of the amount of trust, respect and reciprocity between the actors (Cousins *et al.*, 2006). In other words, relationships are formed and are used as a capital to benefit the business activity within the social network that the entrepreneur is embedded in (Yee, 2015).

Cultural capital

According to Light and Gold (2000), cultural capital is viewed as a 'class resource' rather than a materialistic resource. Some view this as anything classed as cultural capital, an asset which symbolizes cultural value (Throsby, 1999). This could be music, food or cuisine, fashion, art and literature etc. (Light and Gold, 2000). This type of cultural knowledge is interpreted as cultural capital, hence it is used for economic purposes or to an individual's advantage for increasing their business network or welfare (Throsby, 1999). Generally, cultural capital is gained through the family or by schooling (Habbershon, Williams and MacMillan, 2003; Danes *et al.*, 2009). Thus, inherent in cultural capital, especially habits which descend due to being part of the culture or other cultural dispositions, could play an important role for pursuing success (Bourdieu and Passeron, 1979).

Culture

Hofstede (1984, p. 82) defines culture as: ‘the collective programming of the mind which distinguishes the members of one group or society from those of another’. He further explained how cultures are transferred and/or maintained: ‘culture consists of the patterns of thinking that parents transfer to their children, teachers to their students, friends to their friends, leaders to their followers, and followers to their leaders’ (Hofstede, 1984, p. 82).

Cultural Values

Cultural values are: ‘concepts or beliefs about desirable end states or behaviours that transcend specific situations, guide selection or evaluation of behavior and events, and are ordered by relative importance’ (Schwartz and Bilsky, 1987, p. 551). Furthermore, Schwartz (1999, pp. 24-25) defines values as:

conceptions of the desirable that guide the way social actors (e.g. organisational leaders, policy-makers, individual persons) select actions, evaluate people and events, and explain their actions and evaluations... values are trans-situational criteria or goals... ordered by importance as guiding principles in life.

Society

An important definition of society is offered by Archer (1995, p. 2):

Society is that which nobody wants in exactly the form they find it and yet it resists both individual and collective efforts at transformation - not necessarily by remaining unchanged but altering to become something else which still conforms to no one's ideal.

Thus, Makumbe (1998, p. 305) views society as:

an aggregate of institutions whose members are engaged primarily in a complex of non-state activities - economic and cultural production, voluntary associations, household life - and who in this way preserve and transform their identity by exercising all sorts of pressures or controls upon state institutions.

Ethnic entrepreneurship

The general definition of ethnic entrepreneurship can be viewed as: ‘a set of connections of network and routine patterns of engagement/interaction between the people who share a same national background or migration experience’ (Azmat, 2010, p.41).

Immigrants

The term ‘immigrants’ is applied to the people who arrived into the host country over the past years or within the decades, and these migrants are excluded from the ethnic-minority groups who have migrated, settled, and lived in the host country for generations (Volery, 2007).

Immigrant entrepreneurship

Immigrant entrepreneurship is: ‘the process of an immigrant who establish an business activity in a host country (or country of he/she is seeking for settlement or settled), which is not the immigrant’s country of origin’ (Khosa and Kalitanyi, 2014 p. 206). In other words, an immigrant is one who carried out entrepreneurial activities in the host country not long after (first generation) arrival to the host country, by using the personal social networks or by their own initiatives (Chand and Ghorbani, 2011).

Immigrant owned business

Business activities operated and owned by the immigrants in the host country can be referred to as an immigrant-owned business (Volery, 2007).

Ethnic minority businesses

Ethnic minority businesses is referred to as: ‘businesses that are owned and staffed by ethnic minorities’ or ‘ firms that serve an ethnic minority clientele base ‘ or business activities whose ownership is based on the ethnic origin of the owner(s) (Ram *et al.*,2012, p. 505).

Familiness

Family influence and its relationship with the business is also known as: ‘the concept of familiness’, where it is defined as business venture resources and its systems which could result from family interactions (Habbershon, Williams and MacMillan, 2003; Habbershon, 2006).

Ethnic people

Yinger (1985, p.159) views ethnic people as:

a segment of a larger society whose members are thought, by themselves and/or others, to have a common origin and to share... a common culture... participate in shared activities in which the common origin and culture are significant ingredients.

Social Embeddedness

The embeddedness approach explores the nature, depth, and extent of an individual’s connection(s) into the environment and its influence on their business activity (Aldrich *et al.*, 1986; Granovetter, 1985; Whittington, 1992). Furthermore, it allows an understanding of these wide-ranging socio-economic factors (such as, political, cultural, structural and even cognitive) and their influence. Hence these factors could encourage/promote and/or impede the entrepreneurial process/activities (Dacin, Beal and Ventressca, 1999; Karlsson and Dahlberg, 2003).

Mixed embeddedness Model

The model considers the entrepreneurial individual's embeddedness to their social networking, institutional regulatory environment, economic and social context of the host country (Kloosterman, Van der Leun and Rath, 1999; Kloosterman, 2010). It is a known fact that these various entrepreneurial business ventures do not appear out of nowhere. Hence it is due to the

practice of being embedded in social and cultural activities (Kloosterman, Van der Leun and Rath, 1999).

Opportunity Structure (Meso-level)

The opportunity structure is presented in the 'meso' level of the entrepreneurial environment. The phenomenon of ethnic entrepreneurship is mainly based on this opportunity mechanism within the country/region of the host country, which these individuals are embedded in (Kloosterman, Van der Luen and Rath, 1999). This mechanism/structure allows the market to access opportunities and even enables creating service(s) and product(s) offered by it as well. Thus, these opportunities and their availability are generally regulated by the host country institutional or legal factors, which can be examined under locally, regionally or nationally (Kloosterman and Rath, 2001; Ram, Jones and Villares-Varela, 2017).

Institutional embeddedness (Macro-level)

The wider 'macro' level of the model looks at factors such as the governmental regulatory and legal boundaries of the host country and its impacts on minority entrepreneur and their business activities from an economic standpoint (Rath 2006; Kloosterman, 2010).

Enclaved area

According to the ethnic enclaved theory, the demand for the ethnic goods and services can only be supplied by co-ethnics who are familiar with the buying preferences and the needs of the ethnic group, which causes them to start up the ethnic business activities (Greve and Salaff, 2005). On the other hand, the theory also suggests that these entrepreneurs are based on sophisticated co-ethnic social networks within a self-sustaining ethnic enclave (Rafiq, 1992), and yet are limited to its co-ethnicity, location and co-ethnic social structures (Zhou, 2004).

Customer Trust

According to Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol (2002, p.17), trust is defined as: ‘the expectation held by the consumer that the service provider is dependable and can be relied on to deliver on its promises’.

Customer Trustworthiness

Thus, consumer trust appeared to develop with retailers in two distinguishable ways (Orth and Green, 2009). Those are Front line employee (FLE) behaviours and Management policy practices (MPP). Trustworthiness is regarded as an ‘antecedent’ to the existence of trust (Anderson and Narus, 1990). Therefore, again according to Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol (2002, p. 17) trustworthiness is defined as: ‘ including Front line employee (FLE) behaviours and Management policy practices (MPP) that indicate a motivation to safeguard consumer interest’. It was found that observable behaviours and management practices are important for both FLE and MPP trustworthiness (Ganesan, 1994; Orth and Green, 2009).

Customer Loyalty

According to Oliver (1999, p.34), loyalty is viewed as:

a deeply held commitment to rebuy or re-patronize a preferred product/service consistently in the future, thereby causing repetitive same-brand or same brand-set purchasing, despite situational influences and marketing efforts having the potential to cause switching behaviour.

The loyalty of a customer is usually demonstrated in a number of ways within particular business activities. For instance, repeat purchasing, tendency to spend good amount of money in the business, and positive word-of-mouth are commonly found in the literature (Orth and Green, 2009).

Customer Relationship

Generally, customer relationship and its importance is found in the literature of relationship marketing (Gilboa, Seger-Guttmann and Mimran, 2019). Gronroos (1996, p.7) defined relationship marketing as:

relationship marketing is to identify and establish, maintain, and enhance relationships with customers and other stakeholders, at a profit, so that the objectives of all parties involved are met, and that done by a mutual exchange and fulfilment of promises.

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction regarded as the main outcome of customer and seller relationships (Anderson and Sullivan, 1993). Orth and Green, (2009, p. 250) view customer satisfaction as: ‘consumers’ assessment of the extent to which retailer performance on specific dimensions meets or exceeds prior expectations’.

Business Reputation

Fombrum and Van Riel (1997, as quoted in Mella and Gazzola, 2015, p.41) defines business reputation as:

a corporate reputation is a perceptual representation of a company’s past actions and future prospects that describe the firm’s overall appeal to all of its key constituents when compared with other leading rivals.

Ethics

According to Miesing and Preble (1985, as quoted in Mella and Gazzola 2015, p.41), Ethics are: ‘frameworks for human conduct that relate to moral principle and attempt to distinguish right from wrong’. Therefore, some argue that ethics could essentially gain customer trust (Azmat and Zutshi, 2012). Trust is an antecedent to loyalty (Orth and Green). Then it can be

argued that practising good ethics will lead to gaining trust, and hence loyalty over time (Mella and Gazzola, 2015).

Empathy

According to Wieseke, Geigenmuller and Kraus (2012, p.317) empathy is defined as: ‘a person’s intellectual understanding of the internal state of another person’. Similarly, some scholars view empathy as a ‘perspective-taking’, which allows an individual to understand another person’s point of view, anticipate his or her reaction and to deliver their (perceived) needs, opinions or motivations (Devoldre *et al.*, 2010). These ethnic entrepreneurs tend to show their empathy as an aim for satisfying the customer (Haq *et al.*, 2021). Indeed, customer satisfaction will eventually lead to customer retention and loyalty (Anderson 1998; Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003). Ethnic culture could also be an influence in demonstrating empathy (Parasuraman, Berry and Zeitbaml 1991; Beatty *et al.*, 1996).

Patience

According to Hagedoorn *et al.* (1999, p.310) patience is described as ‘the act of waiting optimistically’ .Thus, developing patience has also been viewed as a skill in their service (Beatty *et al.*, 1996). Parasuraman, Berry and Zeitbaml (1991) claimed that it is related to customer satisfaction, hence to customer retention.

Customer orientation

Brown *et al.* (2002 p. 111) define customer orientation as: ‘a retail frontline salesperson’s focus on meeting customer needs in performing their job responsibilities’. In other words, the concept focuses on customer satisfaction in the long term and on the achievement of short-term sales targets and can be applied at both firm and individual level (Brown *et al.*, 2002).

Customer centricity

While on the other hand, customer centricity is defined as: ‘a customer-centric enterprise that places the demands and wishes of each single customer in the centre of value creation’ (Tseng and Piller, p.3). Thus this focuses on a customer-centric approach which will lead to customer satisfaction (Shah *et al.*, 2006), and strong customer loyalty (Habel *et al.*, 2020).

Limiting self-serving opportunism

This refers to ‘limiting’ the opportunistic behaviour. The opportunistic behaviour is defined as ‘self-interest seeking with guile’ Williamson (1975, p.6 as quoted in Morgan and Hunt 1994, p.25). Thus Jones (1984, p.279 as quoted in Morgan and Hunt 1994, p.25) observes that ‘the essence of opportunistic behavior is deceit-oriented violation of implicit or explicit promises about one's appropriate or required role behavior’.

Coronavirus Pandemic

The World Health Organization (WHO) officially declared the SARS-CoV-2 virus outbreak a Public Health Emergency of International Concern on January 30, 2020 and a global pandemic on March 11, 2020. Countries were urged by WHO to adopt strict social distancing and quarantine measures to avoid virus spread and to protect public health. Despite fragmented international efforts to contain the spread, SARS-CoV2 has spread to 213 countries (Hiscott *et al.*, 2020 p.1).

Furlough Scheme

As a result of the lockdown and reduction of economic activity, many employers were forced to drastically reduce the number of work hours of their employees or to lay them off (permanently or temporarily). Similar to other European countries, the UK government implemented a furlough scheme upon issuing the lockdown aimed to maintain income for workers and households. This scheme allowed employers to apply

for grants to keep many employees on their payroll at 80% of their regular pay (Witteveen, 2020 p.1).

Appendix 3: Individual Case Analysis

Appendix 3 presents the individual case analysis. A case description and key insights for each case can be found in Chapter 5 (section 5.1).

Analysis of Case 1 (Ravi-C1)

Individual-level of Analysis (Micro-level):

Motivation to be in the business

Basu and Goswami (1999) found that for ethnic entrepreneurs to be motivated to be in business, there are either ‘pull’ factors (where the ethnic minority entrepreneurs are attracted to form a business); or ‘push’ factors (where ethnic entrepreneurs are pushed to have a business e.g.: as a result of unemployment).

In Case 1, C1 appeared to be ‘pushed’ to form a business rather ‘pulled’ in to have a business. C1 mentioned that he had to form a business due to redundancy and he couldn’t find any other similar jobs at that time.

“In Sri Lanka, I used to run our restaurant, jewellery shop, stationery and came here (UK), got back in to study IT and landed a job, lost the job due to redundancy, couldn’t find any good job relating to the field and ended up doing a business in retail.”

Nevertheless, after that, C1 further mentioned that the decision-making power (or achieving autonomy) he has in his business also kept him motivated to not apply for a mainstream job.

“We have managed to run this business for a long time now. But you are in power to do anything. That’s` the motivation of doing business. Obviously, I had a business background

before. And we decided, why work for somebody else, let's work for ourselves instead. And we just went through with it."

C1 also mentioned again about achieving autonomy or in other words, independence, of his family business.

"I do not regret that we are a family run business, now I see this as a positive way, we can make our own decisions; if we want to shut this now and go somewhere, we can go and nobody says anything to us. Because we exactly know what we are doing."

Success perception

The ethnic entrepreneur is much more into subjective measures in the case of considering their success (Brockhaus, 1982); such as their religious and cultural believes, social status among the community, investing their time and efforts to improve managerial skills, the individual satisfaction of running a business (Solymossy, 1998), and asserting that they have put their personal traits to good use etc. (Ibrahim and Goodwin, 1986).

In Case 1, C1 sees himself as a success in both his personal and business life. He believes that he achieved more than he wanted through the business and generates enough to maintain his family life (individual satisfaction).

"how you measure your success in a way that you want to look at it. I believe I'm a successful person, I'm a successful leader and I'm successful in business. There are ups and downs in the period. But overall in this time, I'm a successful person. I came into this country with nothing. Today, 30 years down the line, I think I have achieved more than I wanted and for my family."

Family relations

Family influence and its relationship with the business is also known as ‘the concept of familiness’, where it is defined as a business venture resource and its systems which could result from family interactions (Habbershon, Williams, and MacMillan, 2003).

C1 shows a strong influence from his family in Sri Lanka on the family life he has in the UK. His family used to have a business back in Sri Lanka when he was growing up. On the other hand, C1 acknowledged that it has also given him good knowledge about interacting with the customer and has improved his customer service skills.

“Yes of course. We were running a small stationery business, which needed to be manned 9-5 every day. After leaving school, I was there at all the time. At an early stage, it helped me to understand how to interact with customers, understand them and giving what they want.”

On the other hand, Sri Lankan society highly values the importance of education. This could be one of the reasons why the country has had a high literacy rate (above 90%) for a long time. Sri Lankan education system is known as ‘highly competitive’ (Fernando and Kenny, 2018). This also reflects in C1’s statement:

“But when I came here, my primary motivation was not to be involved in any business, get a qualification and do something else. In our education system (Sri Lankan), you have to be top, in order to get into the university. Unfortunately, I didn’t get that opportunity, so I was studying self-teaching IT in that stage in my life, while I was helping in my dad’s business back home. In Sri Lanka, I used to run our restaurant, jewellery shop, stationery shop and then came here, got back in to study IT and landed a job.”

C1 further elaborated on the strong support and involvement from his family members in the UK, while running the business today, especially from his wife. This shows how the Sri Lankan ethnic entrepreneur integrated 'familiness' in his business and employs the ethnic human capital as family.

“my wife, my family are highly involved with this business. Like my son comes and helps me out, my brother when he is around, he helps me out you know. We are all acting and contributing to the business in different ways.”

C1 further added:

“Of course you have to ask for help from the family members eventually because you can't take it all in only by yourself.”

Several scholars have mentioned the significance of family influence and its importance when running a business (Sirmon *et al.*, 2008). Some have found these types of social capital, formed through interacting and maintaining a trustful relationship, are vital to initiate self-employment (Hoffman, Hoelscher and Sorenson, 2006; Pearson, Carr, and Shaw, 2008) among minority ethnic entrepreneurs (Sanders and Nee, 1996).

This is also true for C1, where he mentioned that the trust relationship is also vital for him to run the business. According to C1, it is safe to use family members to operate the business, especially his wife, particularly when dealing with the money.

“Because you have no control, that's one of the reasons why I rely on my family members, especially my wife on money things.”

And then he further added that he doesn't allow anyone else to deal with the money other than him or his family members.

“Money is very important and we need to do this very securely, we can't allow anyone else to be involved, but me or any other member in our family.”

Again C1 mentioned about trust among the family members:

“When you don't have a family business that basically means you don't have any trustworthy staff. We have raised our children behind the counter. This is like my home. Then, when we are a little bit better with our business, then we employ staff.”

Social capital

Essentially, the embeddedness approach argues that the nature, depth, and extent of an individual's connection(s) into the environment, are structuring essential elements of a business's activity (Aldrich and Waldinger, 1990). However, Rath (2006) claims that ethnic entrepreneurs involve their 'ethnically specific economic networks' to be able to enhance or facilitate their entrepreneurial activities. These networks could often provide vital resources to their day to day business activities (Ram, 1994), such as labour, capital, engaging with clients and suppliers, and start up knowledge etc. (Rath and Kloosterman, 2002).

C1 explained how important it was for him to have social networking, and the benefits to his business, especially gaining business knowledge.

“Because if you are running a shop, you are able to solve any problem that comes towards you or your business. At the same time, if you are socially involved either community wise or business-wise networking, I mean working all kind of these things, if you have a problem you put it to them, and they will come up with their own ideas - okay I did like this, can you try this

way - so then we can make a judgement. So when we applied that particular solution, you most of the time ended up solving the problem or you can look for alternative solutions by asking the people or friends who do the similar business. So, we gather a lot of knowledge by talking to our fellow friends, family relatives, fellow Asians. They are necessary even if they may or may not be in the business. Sometimes I speak to the customers as well.”

Financial Capital

However, for the minorities and their small ventures in their host country, accessing finance (for example, accessing bank loans) seems to be a lot harder than for the mainstream entrepreneurs (Ram and Jones, 2008). To overcome this barrier, ethnic entrepreneurs look for alternative methods to gain financial capital; for instance, their social network (often their family members and friends) (Kraybill, Nolt and Wesner, 2010).

C1 explained through the theory above how he gained access to finance using his social contacts. C1 mentioned that he usually borrows money from his friends and family members.

“We borrow from friends and family and we borrow our own money. That’s the big difference between the bigger corporate company and smaller family run businesses. We never rely on the bank.”

Then again, C1 explained how much quicker he can access finance through his social network than accessing finance through a financial institution in the UK.

“You may get the loan, most of the time you are not; it takes a long time, and they (bank) are telling us to give this, give that documents and it takes forever. If you can’t pay back, you might be running into all sorts of troubles you know. When you are asking money from your friends, most of the time I can get it done within hours or within a day or two, that kind of reputation I built with them.”

Customer relationship related findings

Trust

The case of C1 also showed Front line employee behaviour (FLE), particularly according to the literature, of operational benevolence, where he showed characteristics like limiting self-serving opportunism.

“I don't know much about it. But I feel that to get more customers to do these kinds of things is wrong you know. Because you may get more money, but you actually waste their money to get you more money. I don't want to feel it on me about my business.”

According to the literature, DeWulf *et al*, (2001) argues that family businesses value the customers more than non-family businesses, and hence this may reflect their behaviour as operational benevolence. This appeared to be true for Case 1 as well. C1 mentioned how he values the customer presence, particularly the regular customers.

*“We very caring about the customers, it is not like t***o like you don't care about them and you don't even know your customers, I just don't treat them like I really need their money and I'm going to make them spend as much as they can. You see this is not my philosophy. Here we care about them. I know most of my regular customers - about what is happening in their life or even in their family. So that's how much the customers are bonded with us. We joke around, they joke with us, and we laugh together, giving them a pleasant time. Each individual here is different from others, so we keep that in mind when we interact with them. And we have to work like that to keep the customers happy and give a different approach than the other big ones.”*

While the researcher was carrying out the interview, the researcher had a chance to witness an interaction between a customer and the C1 (participant), which gave a good understanding of C1's problem-solving orientation with a customer who made a complaint about a purchase she made before. This reflected front line employee behaviours through problem-solving orientation. It also demonstrated the (FLE) behaviour of placing the customer's interest first and caring for the customer even though it is at a cost (offered a product exchange for an unsatisfactory product) to the business.

(Note: the researcher asked for a verbal consent to write down a note of this whole conversation from the customer as well).

Customer 1: "you told me last time this (a crisp packet) would be good."

The customer sounds a bit disappointed.

The shop owner (the participant): "why is it not good?"

Customer 1: "it was ok for me, but my daughter didn't like it at all."

Shop owner: "oh, I am really sorry for the disappointment. Don't worry, I'll get you the one you buy normally."

The shop owner went to one of the aisles and came back with the packet of crisps.

Shop owner: "here take this one, Madam." He handed it over to the customer.

Customer 1: "oh, you know what I want. Thank you. How much is it altogether?"

Shop owner: "ahh, don't worry, Madam. You get this one for free from me. Say hello from me to the little girl."

Service

Customer oriented approach

In the case of C1, he mentioned how he orientates his business towards being more European customer-friendly due to the declining South-Asian customer presence in the business area.

“ I started with Sri Lankan, South Indian and English retail items. Now I have ended up with mostly Eastern European/European retail products.”

And then, further elaborating on how he is concerned about customer needs and how hard it is to make changes, he states:

“I make sure I do changes to meet the customer needs. That is a very difficult task you know.”

Customer centricity

In Case 1, C1 explains how he believes in his regular customers' feedback and opinions in terms of regular changes he makes in the business. In other words, allowing the customer to play a central role in the changes that C1 makes in the business.

“You talk to the customer, trust me, most of the time you can really count the customers, especially ones who have come to the shop for a long time. In terms of feedback. I talk to the customers like - what do you like to see here and there - like that you know. So like that, I make sure I do changes to meet the customer needs.”

On the other hand, part of the customer-centric approach is also known as giving a more personalised service for the customer. In Case 1, C1 appears to have given a more personalised service to the customer so that the customer felt more welcome and special.

“Here we care about them. I know most of my regular customers, about what is happening in their life or even in their family. So that is how much the customers are bonded with us. We joke around, they joke with us, and we laugh together, giving them a pleasant time. Each individual here is different from others, so we keep that in mind when we interact with them.”

Being empathetic towards the customer

Empathy has gained by C1 in a way that, how it would feel himself if he would have been in the same situation as the customer.

“she has been a regular customer in my shop for years. And I don’t want to lose her. And the other thing is that you can’t sell something that customer doesn’t like, especially their kids. I have kids too. I know what it feels like.”

On one occasion, C1 demonstrated empathy towards not only the customer but their family members as well. This has shown how bonded C1 is with his regular customers; sharing each other’s day to day events with each other shows how C1 built his rapport with the customer using empathy as a tool (Parasuraman, Berry and Zethaml, 1991).

Shop owner: “how is your sister now Madam?”

Customer 2: “she is a bit ok now, she is going to the hospital for the clinic regularly. You know she can do things on her own now. But thank you for asking.”

Shop owner:” ahh, that’s good news. God bless for her.”

The shop owner packed the stuff for her. Customer 2 paid the bill.

Customer 2: "where is your wife? I haven't seen her today."

Shop owner: "ohh, she is on her way, she went to pick up our kids from the school."

Customer 2: "oh, I see, say hello for me. See you then, bye."

Shop owner: "I will. See you, take care, bye."

Customer satisfaction concerns

C1 can be also aligned with the literature, where he looks out for the customer more than attempting to make a sale (Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003). C1 satisfied a disappointed customer with a free replacement where he could have charged for it, demonstrating that money is not always the objective for Case 1. The whole situation went as follows;

Customer 1: "you told me last time this (a crisp packet) would be good."

The customer sounds a bit disappointed.

The shop owner (the participant): "why is it not good?"

Customer 1: "it was ok for me, but my daughter didn't like it at all."

Shop owner: "oh, I am really sorry for the disappointment. Don't worry, I'll get you the one you buy normally."

The shop owner went to one of the aisles and came back with the packet of crisps.

Shop owner: "here take this one, Madam."

He handed it over to the customer.

Customer 1: "oh, you know what I want. Thank you. How much is it altogether?"

Shop owner: "ahh, don't worry, Madam. You get this one for free from me. Say hello from me to the little girl."

Developing patience for the customer

In the case of C1, he demonstrated how patient he was when listening to the customer 1(above):

“Oh, I am really sorry for the disappointment. Don’t worry, I’ll get you the one you buy normally.”

He offered a replacement free of charge and then Customer 1 left, satisfied, at the end of the exchange. He further mentioned that he doesn’t want to lose a customer over a crisp packet and wanted to see her back again in the shop.

“she has been a regular customer in my shop for years. And I don’t want to lose her. And the other thing is that you can’t sell something that a customer doesn’t like.”

Let the customers make the buying decision

C1 believes that, as a shop owner, he shouldn’t be convincing customers to buy something from him. Instead, the customer is free to make the buying decision for themselves. He doesn’t believe the salesperson approach in his business. This is much more in line with collaborative selling where it generally means to not pressurize the customer into buying anything; instead, the seller may help or give information to make the purchase which does not involve them making the decision for the customers on their behalf.

This appeared to be demonstrated in Case 1 when a supplier conversation took place as the researcher was visiting the shop.

“Listen, I don’t convince my customers to buy things that they don’t need. They will buy anything they want if needed. I’m not going to be a salesperson. You bring something that can

be sellable, quality one. I tried this drink myself and it doesn't taste good. I am sorry my friend, I can't allow this product in my shop. You have to take this with you."

Business reputation

C1 thinks that using promotional tools and other sales strategies would actually drain customer money, rather than saving money. He argues that promotional deals or pricing strategies will lead the customer to waste their bought products because either, it could be expired by the time they actually use it, or dumped in the bin due to limited space.

"I never push the customers to buy something. I don't have value for money deals like 'buy one get one free'. Customers tend to think that this gets you more value for money. I would say no, because most of the products you buy end up in the bin; either it has expired before you use it, or you have to throw it away because your house is full."

The researcher probed further to get an idea of how he could see that the supermarkets learned and used consumer buying behaviour to boost their sales. Then the C1 came up with an answer which may give an idea as to how he would want other people/ customers to view his business (reputation). He believes that using these strategies are wrong because these supermarkets get more money by wasting customers' money; he further explained that he would not want to practice it as he does not want to feel wrong about his business. Perhaps here he may be mentioning about practising good business ethics, in a socially responsible way.

"But I feel that to get more customers to do these kinds of things is wrong you know. Because you may get more money, but you actually waste their money to get you more money. I don't want to feel it on me about my business."

Thus, C1 thinks that listening to the customer and responding to their complaints immediately may have an impact on the business name.

“If I didn’t do anything about her complaint, it is not good for the business name.”

Economic/ opportunity structure (Meso level analysis):

Serving customers with low spending power

C1 claimed that he often ran into problems when people came to his shop and asked for price reductions as a result of supermarkets offering a lower price than his business in the area, even though the price difference isn’t that huge. That could possibly mean that these customers have low spending power.

*“And one more thing, here are middle-class people, they always look for value, they compare us with the bigger supermarkets, I don’t know what to say that, but it is for me very unreasonable, not the regular ones, but some random people come up and ask - oh, I bought these on that t****o Express down the road at a lower price than this, can you lower the price for me - and the arguments go on. Sometimes the difference is around 50p, but some people want to lower the price. We can’t lower more than that, but if I say to them, they won’t come here.”*

Supermarkets as a challenge/ competition

C1 also mentioned how supermarkets challenge him as a business, pressurising him to offer a lower price point due to their buying power.

“You know, supermarkets have their buying power, these cost-cutter chains alike have their own buying power.”

Declining South-Asian/Sri Lankan customer demand

C1 further elaborated on the ever-changing market demand over time and how he has felt it over the period. C1 explained how things started to change when he experienced that the number of customers coming to the shop was decreasing - especially the South-Asian community. He thinks this is due to the rental/ property market in the area.

“here what we can see most of them are residential customers, because I have run this business for such a long period of time. We know 1-2 generations of customers like we know their parents, we know their brothers and sister and all. Now here is changing, most of the residents have rented out/ or sold their properties around here.”

Therefore, he believes it is harder to get to know the customers than it used to be. C1 sees his South Asian community declining over the time and slowly he sees there are more European customers. This could be partly due to the Eastern European labour migration to the UK in recent years, and tougher migration restrictions placed for non-European nationals, especially in the case of Sri Lankans, Indians and other South-Asian nationals.

“You are having lots of different types of people and because of that reason you are having lots of different customers here. In that way you get to know customers - it is not stable like it used to be before. One day you see Indians, Sri Lankans and all sorts of South Asians and slowly now you see all these Eastern Europeans.”

Language barrier (European) to serve the market

C1 explained he had a hard time because of the customers who don't understand the English language properly. So sometimes he cannot communicate with these Eastern European customers efficiently.

“now you see all these Eastern Europeans not able to speak to you or you can't speak to them, they do not speak very much English as well you know. So yeah, I have to face different customers, customers moving around this area often, it's very dynamic.”

Evolving European customer demand

Due to the declining demand in Sri Lankan/South-Asian retail products, C1 explained that he changed his product range to meet the Eastern European customer demand. C1 further added how he was coping with the situation as an opportunity.

“Every month we have to think about what sort of things we need to change, like what items we have to cut out or introduce. I started with Sri Lankan, South Indian and English retail items. Now I have ended up with mostly Eastern European/European retail products. It is a total shift, and still, we are learning, what to keep and what not to keep; as you can see, some of the Sri Lankan products are highly reduced, due to low Sri Lankan presence - there are Sri Lankans here, but they are very low compared to a decade ago.”

Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)

Government policy on migration.

European Union labour migration

C1 mentioned that on one occasion he had been observing the number customers originating from South Asia decreasing and the number of European people coming to his shop gradually

increasing. This could be partly due to the high number of European migrants to the UK in recent years, where these migrants do not necessarily need to have any form of entry requirements (free movement of people) such as having the ability to speak the English language and any other educational or professional qualifications. This is one of the benefits of being a member of the European Union (EU) for any country. The lack of restrictions on EU migrants to work or settle have led in recent years to a high number of European people coming into the UK. Perhaps, this might have negatively impacted the South-Asian ethnic minority businesses.

“You have lots of different types of people and because of that reason you have lots of different customers here. In that way, getting to know customers is not stable like it used to be before. One day you see Indians, Sri Lankans and all sorts of South Asians and slowly now you see all these Eastern Europeans who are not able to speak to you or you can’t speak to them, they do not speak English as well you know. So yeah, I have to face different customers, customers moving around this area often, it’s very dynamic.”

Restrictions on non-EU migration

On the other hand, non-European migrants such as South-Asians entry requirements have been strictly regulated over the years, due to strict policies from the government for the non-EU migrants; many of them have to leave the country, are not able to immigrate to the UK easily which has made it harder to settle in the country over the years. Therefore this might indicate why C1 is seeing South-Asian customers disappearing from his area over the years. But importantly, C1 sees this as an opportunity, he is re-orienting his business to meet the (European) customer demands rather sticking with South Asians.

“Every month we have to think about what sort of things we need to change, like what items we have to cut out or introduce. I started with Sri Lankan, South Indian and English retail items. Now I have ended up with mostly Eastern European/European retail products. It is a

total shift, and still, we are learning, what to keep and what not to keep; as you can see, some of the Sri Lankan products are highly reduced, due to low Sri Lankan presence - there are Sri Lankans here, but they are very low compared to a decade ago.”

Import regulations

Lastly, C1 sees that import regulations do not motivate him to import anything from Sri Lanka. Therefore he relies more on local suppliers.

“We don’t import anything directly, but we are relying on the suppliers at the moment. Because a lot of rules and regulations have been involved when attempting to import here. It is very difficult.”

Analysis of Case 2 (Van -C2)

Individual-level of Analysis (Micro-level):

Motivation to be in the business

Independence

C2 mentioned that he doesn’t like to work under somebody else, and he likes the decision making power within the business, which made him leave the full-time job at the time. Therefore it appeared that he was ‘pulled’ into the business rather than ‘pushed’ into forming a business, unlike C1.

“I worked in a supermarket for five years and got experience. Then I felt that was enough of working somebody, why not open a shop on my own, so nobody tells me what to do and that’s the freedom I wanted. So I left the job.”

Success perception

C2 views success as being when he and his family can live a better life and have no fear of any debts for his family and his business. He doesn't want to become a millionaire. Therefore, he is using 'subjective measures' to view his success; in other words satisfying himself and his family needs through his business.

“All we need is to live nicely and safely, that's all. I don't even want to be too blind to believe that I want to become a millionaire one day, no and I don't want to think like that. I don't want that much and the reason is, I just want to live nicely with no fear of debt for the business and family and that's it.”

Family relations

Case 2 is also a family run business; even though C2 does not frequently mention his family as much as in Case 1, he mentioned that his wife is involved in his business with admin work and also that the business is registered under his wife's name. She comes from time to time to take care of the admin work and importantly, he mentioned that employing someone in the family eliminated the need of outsiders to trust, further elaborating the 'familiness' within his business.

“she comes sometimes to do some paper work with me. Because it is very important, in these serious matters, it is very important that I must ask help from someone I can trust. So she just does that. Other than that she has been doing the most important thing for me - taking care of our family.”

When gaining business knowledge, his brother, who used to own a business in UK, also supports him from time to time,

“sometimes my brother shares his views and experiences on certain things as he used to have a business.”

Apart from sharing knowledge with his family members, previous working experience has also helped him to learn necessary skills for the business.

“of course, working in Tesco helped me a lot - managing people, the till, and dealing with customers and more. Otherwise I would be lost.”

Social Capital

Supplier relationship

C2 mentioned that he developed a good relationship with the suppliers over time, which is in return beneficial for his business, particularly when he is out of money.

“if I say to them I don't have any money or can I pay later, they never say no, they know who I am, they deliver to me straight away. They don't do that to every shop.”

Again, he added that he gets benefits such as discounts, and low prices while getting the products in larger quantities, so it enables him to sell them back to the customer at a cheaper price.

“they are always asking me if I'm doing good, they give me really good discounts, low prices when I buy bulk from them, so I can give it at a cheaper price to my customers. I think I do have a really good connection with them.”

Employee relationship

C2 values his employees, hence he treating them as his own family members, which exemplifying the trust relationship.

“speaking the same language and coming from Sri Lanka makes it very easy to work with. Especially customers, not only from Jaffna, but if they speak Tamil or Sinhalese, I can easily understand the customer and start a good conversation. That way I make a good connection with them. One guy still works for me here, and he came from Jaffna Sri Lanka. Since I came to London nearly thirty years ago till now, he is still with me. I'm not treating him like any other staff, but I like to treat him as my close friend or like a family guy.”

At the same time, he also mentioned the negative aspect of these trust relationships, where he ran into trouble, and ultimately this led to closing one of the businesses:

“I had terrible trouble also, you know I've had a business before this, that time I couldn't do that properly, because a trusted lot of staff over there they have done terrible things to my business, so I lost a lot of money over there as well. I finally sold that business there (Surbiton) while I'm doing the business here. At the moment I'm staying with one business because I don't want to lose any more money or get into trouble by trusting people.”

Issues with friends/ partnership (the downside of social capital)

In Case 2, C2 appears to experience the negative side of being socially embedded. Here, he described how he joined in a partnership with some friends and started a business. First, he found a business venture and it was operated by another owner. He inquired about taking over the business, then the former business owner agreed to let him take it over for £60,000. He didn't have that amount of money himself at the time, so he discussed with some friends he had and they invested money as a group as a partnership. He said it was running well for a while. Then the rest of the members of that partnership seemed to ignore their responsibilities towards the business and put the stress of running the business onto C2 as it was his idea in the first place. Those people started to get their share by barely contributing towards the business other than investing the money, and C2 said he had a very hard time running the business.

Therefore, C2 felt that he would be better off out of the business so he left the business and started his own. In conclusion, whether C2 liked it or not, he had to work hard for himself to meet the needs of those friends who invested in the business because of him. Therefore, this is much more aligned with the ‘downside of the social embeddedness’ (Hyun-soo Kim, 2016).

“so I talked to the owner and he said - you have to put down capital of around £60,000. I talked to two other friends and together the three of us could share it, basically making us business partners. So we did it. I think we did really well in the beginning. Then, in the middle of the journey, they started to treat me very badly or something, like I had to do all the cash and carry, all the marketing side, you know I had to wake up like 2-3 o’clock in the morning to start the shop. It was very clear to me what they were doing there; at the, end of the month they just came to take their share and they basically did nothing. It was just a waste of money and my time over there, I just left from there.”

Customer Relationship related findings

Trust

On one occasion, the researcher was able to have an opportunity, while carrying out the interview, to witness another participant (C2) and customer interaction. This whole conversation appeared to reflect the problem-solving orientation of the participant (C2). In this conversation, when asked by a customer which product was better, in order that they could make a better choice, C2 recommended a product based on his personal view. At the end of the conversation, the customer trusted him and bought the product recommended by C2. Interestingly, C2 offered the customer a full refund, just in case he was not satisfied with the product, showing his problem-solving orientation through after-sales service, even at a cost to the business (Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol, 2002).

(Again, verbal consent was obtained from the customer, while the interaction took place)

Shop owner 2 (C2): "may I help you, sir?"

Customer: " yes, anna (brother) I am a bit confused about two curry powders I have here."

Shop owner2: "yes, one is from Sri Lanka, the other from South India."

Customer: "oh I see, which one is better?"

Shop owner: "well these curry powders are both great, I don't sell anything here of low quality.

All top brands from top suppliers in this shop."

Customer: "hahaha, I know, that's why I have come here for a long time. Which one is better?

Normally my wife comes here often."

Shop owner2: "I know you are a Sri Lankan; if you like the spiciness, I would go with the Sri Lankan one obviously. The South Indian one is less spicy than the Sri Lankan one and has a slightly different smell after you cook it. If you are making a Sri Lankan curry you can go with Sri Lankan curry powder, I just gave my honest opinion, but still, the choice is yours.

Customer: " Oh I see, I thought they basically looked the same and the South Indian one is a bit more expensive than the Sri Lankan one. I will take your advice this time. Thank you."

Shop owner2: yes, the South Indian one sells here in UK more than the Sri Lankan one. It is £3.00 more expensive than the Sri Lankan one, I think

Shop owner 2: "may I ask what curry you are trying to make with this powder?"

Customer: "we are making some dishes over the weekend. Hmm, which one is especially most suitable for a prawn curry?"

Shopowner2: "if I am honest with you, I would take the Sri Lankan curry powder over the South Indian one. This one (South Indian) is nice and I get more profit out of it too. Money is not the point but really, it doesn't have the Sri Lankan flavour. Take my word, have the Sri Lankan one, use it. If you are not happy bring that back to me and I will refund your money in full."

Perhaps this behaviour can also link to operational competence. It is clear that his product knowledge translated into observable behaviours (Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol, 2002), which helped a customer make the desired product choice.

C2 appears to show FLE operational benevolence by limiting his self-serving opportunity, where he could have made more money by recommending a more expensive one to the customer, yet he recommended a less expensive and the most suitable one, based on his personal view.

“if I am honest with you, I would take the Sri Lankan curry powder over the South Indian one. This one (South Indian) is nice and I get more profit out of it too. Money is not the point but really, it doesn't have the Sri Lankan flavour. Take my word, have the Sri Lankan one, use it. If you are not happy bring that back to me and I will refund your money in full.”

Then again, as a family business, C2 demonstrated how he values the customer by mentioning that those regular customers are like his family members and he values their honest opinions in terms of getting feedback. He further said that this could be partly due to his long business operation in the area.

“I have been here for thirty years, I know my regular customers, most of them very close to me. I listen to them often, these customers are like my family members, I think they are very honest in terms of their opinions. You need to respect them first and earn their respect over time and it takes some time.”

Service

Customer oriented approach

However, C2 also orientates his business more towards being Sri Lankan customer-friendly, based on the regular customer feedback/opinions. He is targeting the Sri Lankan community, especially in the area, but he also mentioned that he doesn't want to add European products even though there is an opportunity to serve them in the area.

“I did add some products based on their reviews and removed what they felt was unnecessary. That's why I didn't add Eastern European items in my shop so far.”

Customer centricity

On the other hand, he values the customer feedback here, so he removes/ improves the products over time based on the regular customer feedback. In other words, he put the customer first in terms of the product selection in the shop which can also be seen as a 'customer centricity'.

“When some customers complain about certain products, I either improve the quality of the product or remove them from my shop. I make sure there are no complaints about the same product over and over again.”

Developing empathy towards the customer

Treating as a family member

In Case 2, C2 also mentioned that he treated his customers as if they are his family members. He further explained that he has been in the business for a long time which might contribute to developing such a relationship over the period.

“I have been here for thirty years, I know my regular customers, most of them very close to me. I listen to them often, these customers are like my family members, I think they are very honest in terms of their opinions. You need to respect them first and earn their respect over time and it takes some time.”

Thinking on customer satisfaction rather than the money.

The conversation which took place between the customer and the C2 clearly showed that C2 was more into satisfying the customer than making money. It concluded that making money is not the point, but getting the right product for the customer is.

“take the Sri Lankan curry powder over the South Indian one. This one (South Indian) is nice and I get more profit out of it too. But money is not the point here.”

Developing patience for the customer

When a customer approaches him in the business questioning or asking for more information regarding a product, he always welcomes them and he makes sure the customer feels that they are being listened to. In these kinds of scenarios, it also shows the customers that he, as a business, is kind and patience towards them. He believes that it is the sign of quality service, because, in the end, it can help the customer to leave the shop satisfied and potentially make them return to the business again. If not, it would end up like any other supermarket in the area.

“When a customer comes to the shop and asks questions like that, you need to make the customer feel that we are listening. I took the time to listen to him, he is a young one like you. I am older than both of you, so I need to show that I am the older person (maturity) here. Sometimes it feels some customers are really annoying or impatient, especially at rush hours like now. But you need to be very kind and be patient with them. If you not, you not giving a good service. Then this shop becomes more or less like those big supermarkets. At the end of

the day we need to make sure he goes out from this shop with a happy face and satisfied, so he will return here again.”

Let the customers make the buying decision

Observing C2 with the customer interaction showed characteristics of collaborative selling, where C2 gave all the information needed for the customer to make a decision about a product; yet he did not pressurize the customer to buy the expensive one or any of those products and still gave the customer the choice to buy.

“I know you are a Sri Lankan - if you like the spiciness, I would go with the Sri Lankan one obviously. The South Indian one is less spicy than Sri Lankan one and has a slightly different smell after you cook. If you are making a Sri Lankan curry you can go with Sri Lankan curry powder. I just gave my honest opinion, but still, the choice is yours.”

Business reputation

According to C2, as a result of maintaining a good reputation of the business for a long time, the supplier relationship has become stronger than ever and these suppliers appeared to trust him as a business when delivering emergency credit, which he believes these suppliers do not do to every shop in London.

“if I say to them that I don’t have any money or can I pay later, they never say no, they know who I am, they deliver to me straight away. They don’t do to every shop. There are a lot of Sri Lankan shops in London, and among those, there are a couple of Sri Lankan shops that you can really count on!! And one of them is my business.”

Moreover, he also claimed that managing reputation for such a long time gave his business a 'brand value' of which everyone became aware (Sri Lankans) and he worked so hard to create a good impression about his business among the customers and suppliers over the period.

“Thirty years in business, the brand value, yes you can tell that brand value, the name also I think I used in the business has reached everyone's mind (Sri Lankans). You can ask anyone, I've worked so hard to create a good impression about my business among the customers and suppliers too.”

Also, he mentioned that he has been doing his business for such a long time now in the area, so he knows many of the local people very well.

“I have known all the customers from New Malden for nearly thirty years. So everybody knows me. If I stand outside right in front of my business, I know nobody goes to other shops, that's how much I know them.”

Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)

Sri Lankan ethnically concentrated area (ethnic enclave) - low language barrier

Case 2's business is situated in a Sri Lankan ethnically concentrated area. One of the main advantages of a business in an ethnic enclaved area is engaging with customers easily due to low-language barriers, where these customers (Sri Lankans), business owners and even staff speak the same language and share similar cultural values. In Case 2, C2 shared a similar statement, where he mentioned that he can be much more connected with the customers with Sri Lankan languages than the English language.

“yes, speaking the same language and coming from Sri Lanka makes it very easy to work with. Especially customers, not only from Jaffna, but if they speak Tamil or Sinhalese, I can easily understand the customer and start a good conversation. That way I make a good connection with them.

He further explained that being able to share the same language has also benefited him in building a good relationship with the staff as well. He mentioned this particular staff member from Jaffna Sri Lanka, who he had working with him in the shop for over thirty years. C2 now believes that relationship with him is so strong that C2 treats him as his own family member.

One guy still works for me here, and he came from Jaffna Sri Lanka. Since I came to London nearly thirty years ago till now, he is still with me. I'm not treating him like any other staff, but I like to treat him as my close friend or like a family guy.”

Online presence

Even though there are many more opportunities available online, especially to promote the business, C2 focused much more on a traditional way of marketing than new technologies to promote the business. For instance using the search engine optimisation, where social media appeared to be not really important to him.

“I don't put it on Google, I'm not involved in these things very much, but somebody has put it on for me on the search engine.”

Using word of mouth to promote the business

It is a known fact that these ethnic ventures promote their business through word of mouth using their ethnic customers. This appeared to be true for C2 as well. He mentioned that earning respect over time helps him to get more customers through the existing ones and get his business name known to every Sri Lankan living in the area.

“you need to respect them first and earn their respect over time. It takes some time but most of the time it helps me to get me more customers and get my business name known by every Sri Lankan customers in the area.”

Evolving European customer presence

C2 mentioned that over time he witnessed more European customer presence in the area than there used to be. This could be partly due to the arrival of European labour migrants. He said he has an opportunity to serve these European customers in the area as well. But he doesn't want to be like any other retail shops around the area and lose his business authenticity as a Sri Lankan business.

“If you go outside, there are a lot of European people walking by than there used to be 10-15 years ago. But what I realised that if I added European items in my shop, it would become like any other Off Licence. No, this is pure Sri Lankan I want it to be that way.”

Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)

Issues with rules and regulations

C2 wanted to open a restaurant at some point, but the council refused to give him a license to operate as a restaurant, so he came up with the idea of the retail shop instead and wanted to pay the mortgage through the business.

“This area’s council refused to give me the a3 licence because I wanted to open a restaurant, but they didn’t give me it to me at that time but not now, nowadays they (council) gives it to everybody. So I have to pay the mortgage somehow isn’t it, so I eventually opened this little shop in our small community.”

Analysis of Case 3 (Dan-C3)

Individual-level of Analysis (Micro-level):

Motivation to be in the business

It appeared to see that C3 was ‘pulled’ to have a business, particularly because of the decision making power and financial benefits.

Independence

C3 mentioned that he was motivated to be in the business because of the decision-making power he has within his job, and there is no one in his business at the top telling him what to do. In the end, he creates jobs in his business rather than working for somebody else, or, in other words, achieves autonomy.

“I would rather create a job than a do a job. Nobody says anything as to what I do. There is nobody on top commanding me.”

Financial benefits

C3 was also motivated to be in the business by the financial benefit he could get from the business. He further mentioned that he makes more money than he used to do in a full-time job.

“Plus, I make more money than I can make from a full-time job.”

Success perception

In the context of success, C3 believes success is quantified when his business operates profitably and generates enough money to maintain the business and thereby he has a healthy family life. Therefore, similar to C1 and C2, C3 also uses subjective measures to view success for himself.

“For me, it is about the profit you generate through your business and the cash flow you have with your business. Money should come to your business and you should maintain a healthy business and family life.”

Family relations

‘Familianness’ was also elaborated in this case. C3 employs his wife as an accountant where she keeps sales records, end of the day reports and other bills on track, and enters them in a spreadsheet for future records for the business. He said she plays an important role in regards to running his business.

“yes, my wife supports me very much, she is the one that keeps my records and other paper work on track. Once I get home, I give her the end of the day report and other customer receipts and she enters them into the Excel sheet. She is basically my accountant. She is my backbone for everything I do in this business.”

On the other hand, I probed further as to why he would involve his wife in managing the finances; C3 replied that he doesn’t trust anyone more than his wife, hence elaborating on the trustful relationship mentioned in the early cases.

“in money things, I don’t trust anyone other than my wife. Not even my main accountant.”

Similar to Case 1, C3 also has a close relative running a business in Sri Lanka, where he thinks it is a well-run business according to his point of view and those relatives sometimes help him to get business information when needed.

“I ask for some business information from my brother in Sri Lanka who runs ‘MDK’ back home.”

Furthermore, he thinks that the business (namely MDK) and the person who runs it back home is an inspiration to him as well.

“We have a very successful business in Sri Lanka. Maybe you know them, it’s called MDK, the rice flour and other food products. In our business back home, we have nearly 600-700 people working for the business. Now they expect to expand the business into the hospitality sector. The owner is my very close relative and a person who is an inspiration to our family. You can look at the way he has done things.”

Social capital

Finding staff

C3 claimed that he found the staff members through the people in the area and his contacts, where he doesn’t need to advertise normally.

“I did not advertise, I know a lot of people in the area as well. Then, through my contacts, I got to know some employees and then I employed them.”

Obtaining information about the business premises

C3 revealed that he has been living the area for a long time as he moved in more than twenty years ago. He often passed by this place not knowing that this place was up for sale at the time when he was intending to open a business in this area. He also mentioned that one of the reasons for selecting the place was that he knows a lot of people nearby, which could benefit him even more. Finally, he came to know that the premises were available through his friends in the area and they convinced him to buy the place as well.

“I basically grew up in this area in London, I know a lot of people in this area. I just saw an opportunity to start a business in this area, so I took it. I have a lot of friends around and I was passing by this shop for many years, and I didn’t know this was available. And one day one of my friends told me this place was available for sale, they are the ones who persuaded me to get this place.”

Customer relationship related findings

Trust

It is noted that front line employee behaviours are seen through problem-solving orientation. In this conversation, C3 managed to make an unhappy customer much more calm and become satisfied with the service. He offered a full refund or exchange and gave the right product information, so that possibly the customer could avoid such a product in the future.

(Again, verbal consent was obtained from the customer, while the interaction took place)

Customer: “this was not the rice I wanted, plus you can’t eat this rice; it tastes and smells horrible once it cooked.”

Shop owner 3 (C3): “oh, I see (he is looking at the bag of rice, put his hand inside the rice bag and took out some of the seeds). Nothing wrong with the rice and it has not gone bad, Madam. This is called ‘Samba’. This type of rice smells, but back home, it is not a bad smell for us; there is a way to prepare the rice for cooking and there are certain Sri Lankan curries that go with it. Not all people like it even in Sri Lanka. But, no problem Madam - what do you want from us, full refund or exchange?”

(Now the customer changes her mind and she looks much calmer than before)

Customer: “can I have an exchange, please? Because I don’t want to come on another day.”

Shop owner 3: “yes of course madam. Malli (called his staff member), take this madam with you and let her decide what rice she wants and bring it here. I will sort it out.”

The above conversation can also be interpreted as operational competence, where C3 demonstrated giving the right product information (knowledge) to the customer (observable behaviour) and made her find a product through her own her choice as a replacement (Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol, 2002).

Nevertheless, C3 appeared to have shown the similar characteristics as C1 and C2, where they used the FLE (front line employee) behaviours rather than management policy practices in the business to develop trustworthiness. As it emerged in the data in Case 3, C3 appeared to show limited self-serving opportunisms while interacting with a customer. A customer came into the shop in Case 3 to get a refund for an unsatisfactory product which she had bought before. After a conversation with C3, she changed her mind to exchange it for a similar product. The product she chose from the shop was more expensive than the faulty item she wanted to replace it with. C3 exchanged it happily for the customer and didn’t charge her the balance as he demonstrated the ‘limiting self-serving opportunity’ on himself.

“No Madam, you don’t need to do that. If you took an even more expensive one than this, I would still exchange it for you.”

Later the researcher probed him as to why he would do all that. He explained that the customer is a regular to the business, which was one reason why he didn't even ask for proof of payment or anything like that and hence, this shows C3, as a business, trusting the customer and demonstrating a willingness to assume fiduciary responsibility.

“you see, I didn't even ask for a receipt as a payment proof. Because I know she is a regular here. She knows that I already know her. You don't want to let down our regular like that.”

Similarly, C3 said in the interview that he always makes sure that the customer feels welcome and valued. One of the things he does with those regular customers is to remember their names, as he believes this is a good and effective way to make the customer feel welcome to his business even though it is hard at sometimes. He also mentioned that those small things matter to them. Once he has built this connection with them, he found that these customers tend to become retained customers.

“Always you need to make them feel welcome - if you manage to talk to them and remember their names even, now that's a big advantage. Always the first time they come to my business, they believe they are like any other customer. But when they come the second time, when you greet them, they go like 'ahh you remember me'. I, as the business owner, always want to remember their names. I know this is not very practical and it is hard sometimes. But I try my best. I always tell my staff to remember their names, not in a wrong way. Those small things matter to them, especially regular customers, they are my top priority. Once you build that connection with them, I always find they come here again and again.”

Service

Customer-oriented approach

C3 mentioned that he introduced a short-eats food unit inside the retail business, where he sees the high potential from travellers walking in front of his shop. Once these potential customers are inside his shop, he realised that these travellers are not interested in buying Sri Lankan food ingredients or ready to eat food items that were offered from his shop at the time. So, he listened to what these customers wanted from his shop instead. He saw the potential for Sri Lankan short-eats or ready to eat savoury products from his shop. He arranged a selling unit inside his shop, which is visible to the outside. Therefore, listening to the customer and orientating the business to meet the customer needs is also evident in Case 3.

“But I’m working to attract these walking travellers who come to sightsee in London. They do not buy ingredients. I talked to them and saw what they wanted was unlike other customers who come here for shopping retail items, these travellers wanted something to eat on the way and that is one of the reasons why I opened this short-eats unit.”

Customer centricity

Even though C3 opened this unit, he still finds some issues with these foods, such as the spiciness, the ingredients and the simplicity. C3 believes that some Sri Lankan foods cannot be made without adding spices, therefore he removed the food items where he could not reduce the spiciness, while increasing the simplicity. In other words, allowing customers to play the central role in product selection.

“I had to reduce the spiciness, ingredients and increase the simplicity of these food items. There were a lot of complaints, especially from these tourists, in regards to spiciness, I had to remove some foods because you cannot have some Sri Lankan foods without chillies and other spices.”

Being empathetic towards the customer

Thinking about the customer's point of view and facilitating customer satisfaction

C3 thinks customer satisfaction is more important than the earning the profits and offers free complimentary products even though it is at a cost to the business, Thus, he also views that focusing more on customer satisfaction will eventually increase loyalty and customer retention in the long run.

“Ceylon tea bags might cost me a little. But I know one thing for sure - at the end of the day, she is satisfied and left, and I know she is going to come back again. You kind of keep the loyalty for your business like that.”

Developing patience for the customer

It has emerged that C3 was in a situation where he had to deal with a particular customer who was unhappy about her purchase from the shop. C3 approached her in a more orderly and calm manner, he took time to listen to what the customer had to say, gave a much more expensive product exchange than she had bought in the first place and the customer left the building satisfied. C3 mentioned that he employs patience as a way to show the customer that they have been listened to and also, he said it shows that, as a business, he cares for their concerns as well. In other words, he uses patience as a technique to increase customer satisfaction and gains customer retention for his business.

“you saw that one customer was not happy. The other thing is that giving the exchange back, I lose the money. But if I deny giving her an exchange or refund, if I argue and make her even angrier this doesn't solve the problem. You need to show you care, you make them calm, and show compassion towards to them. If not, possibly I lose a regular customer.”

Let the customers make the buying decision

In line with C1 and C2, C3 also shows the characteristics of collaborative selling. C3 explained to the customer about a certain rice product from Sri Lanka; he explained in detail to the customer who thought the product might have been expired. He cleared up her misunderstanding regarding the product, allowing her to make the choice. In this way, he made it clear that this product is not made for everyone, even in Sri Lanka.

“Nothing wrong with the rice and it has not gone bad, Madam. This is called ‘Samba’. This type of rice smells, but back home, it is not a bad smell for us; there is a way to prepare the rice for cooking and there are certain Sri Lankan curries that go with it. Not all people like it even in Sri Lanka.

Business Reputation

It is evident in Case 3 that C3 also expects to maintain a strong business reputation in the long run. He mentioned that integrity, credibility and hard work is as important as earning the trust of customers and how he treats them as a business gives a good image of the business in the long run.

“I think integrity, credibility, quality and hard work. And you have to earn the trust of customers. You can’t create the trust. I think it develops over time. The quality of your food products, customer service and the way you handle each and every customer. You need to talk to them and in that the way you present yourself as a business which gives the customer a good impression about your business in the long run.”

Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)

Serving places that others missed

It is noted that Case 3's business is situated in Central London, where there are no Sri Lankan focused food retail shops around. This is an opportunity that was missed by others especially working Sri Lankans in Central London. C3 mentioned this in his interview and he was reminded how he used to go to these enclaved places while he was working in Central London.

“Sri Lankans working in Central London and who don't want to take a separate tube to go to Harrow or Wembley to buy Sri Lankan stuff, just like me in the past.”

Coronavirus impacts:

Coronavirus decreasing sales and making fewer profits.

C3 mentioned that his small family run business is struggling to keep up with the impact of the pandemic. He also mentioned that, as a business, they are making fewer sales and profits than they used to in pre-lockdown days.

“it is very difficult, we are small family-run businesses hit even hard. We have to keep working hard, still didn't make much profit compared to pre lockdown days.”

Supplier delays due to the pandemic

C3 also said he had issues with supplies which was problematic and that this kept letting him down as a business.

“Lack of supplies, supplier delays to delivery and low sales stats kept letting us down.”

Working environment challenges

Lack of staff due to safety measures

C3 mentioned that lack of staff was another issue for his business. So it led him and his wife to work even harder as a business. He employed one member of staff with him who lived nearby during the lockdown period. The other two members of the staff went on furlough.

“Problem was who was going to work in the lockdown. So I had to work myself, my wife whenever she could and one other staff member who lived nearby and all the others have gone on furlough.”

Managing hygiene standards due to Coronavirus and at the same time managing the business made this a difficult and challenging time. Therefore, C3 said that he had to limit the number of customers inside the shop as well:

“the shop floor needs to be cleaned continuously. There is a health risk for everyone. So I limit the number of people inside the shop as well. Managing everything at once was a very difficult time for me.”

But online sales increased due to pandemic

C3 mentioned that his online sales through partner websites (eBay, Amazon etc.) were doing well after the lockdown. This could be as a result of people staying at home due to safety measures by the government to control the virus.

“our online delivery system is working really well at the moment. People can order their groceries and other food items through our partner websites.”

Business uncertainty

C3 further reflected on how his business and investment activities were impacted by the Coronavirus pandemic. He further mentioned that it is too risky to spend money on marketing or any other business activities due to the uncertain environment.

“We just put the brakes on due to the pandemic. It is too risky to spend on marketing or anything else, because this is a very uncertain time for everyone.”

Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)

Financial support from the government due to pandemic

C3 appreciates the UK government approach to a small family run business like his. He further mentioned that this kind of encouragement motivated him to be in business throughout the lockdown:

“This is the most generous and helpful government I have witnessed so far. People should appreciate these kinds of encouragement to small family-run businesses like us.”

Many regulations to follow and it does sometimes lead to spending a lot

C3 mentioned that the local council in the area follows strict health and safety regulations, especially in food and retail businesses. Hence, he had to spend a lot of money to bring the standards back up to meet the local council standards, particularly when he took over the building from the previous owner, who had left the place dirty:

“Another thing is like so many rules and regulations in the council. Since this is a food retail shop, health and safety regulations are very strict. I took over this business from another owner on lease. They made this very dirty. I had to spend a lot of money on health and safety standards to meet government regulations.”

Allowing less customers due to pandemic.

C3 said that he had to limit the number of customers who were allowed to be in the shop at one time due to regulations:

“like the 2m rule and face masks - this almost brought us down. This is a small business you can see we have very limited space. Since there is this 2m rule we can't allow more than 6-7 people inside the shop at one time. Either the customer has to wait, or like many of them they leave. Now this is frustrating for me.”

But overall rules and regulations must be in place

Finally, C3 overall is optimistic about the rules and regulations in the UK for small businesses. He further mentioned that implementing those rules and regulations results in good health and safety standards and a safe environment for people and businesses. Therefore businesses should always follow them:

“Rules and regulations are implemented to make sure there will be good quality standards of our food items, provides a good business environment for us as businesses and for the people, health and safety of all of us. I think we should follow them.”

Analysis of Case 4 (Ken-C4)

Individual-level of Analysis (Micro-level):

Motivation to be in the business

It has emerged in the data that C4 was ‘pulled’ into having a business rather than being ‘pushed’ to form one, unlike Case 1.

Independence

C4 mentioned that there is a difference between having a full-time job and owning a business which equates to either ‘you have to do it’ or ‘you like to do it’. He further mentioned that having the choice to have a business was what he likes, so he can rely on himself, survive, and move with the business. In that way, he feels much more independent about himself.

“There is a difference between jobs which you have to do it, and in business, one which you like to do. So, this is my choice, I like to do this. I rely on this, I survive on this and I get on with business. And I feel like I’m more independent in this way.”

Financial benefits

C4 finds having a business can make him more money than having a full-time job, while enjoying it.

“I find this as a business, not only hoping to get more money than a fulltime job, but I enjoy this.”

Previous workplace experience

C4 further mentioned that his previous work experience and his previous employer also made him think that he could probably run a business on his own.

“Basically, I was running the business, I managed all the ins and outs like purchasing, to recording, selling and even employing as well. I think I did a better job over there. That’s where I decide, I can do this on my own. The thing is my boss taught me so many things and he helped as well.”

Success perception

C4 described how he sees success. On his scale of success should be his family wellbeing, his kids should have a good education and he should be able to maintain a good financial status to support them and on top of this, he should have good mental and physical health. Therefore, C4 also uses subjective measures for success for himself, just like C1, C2, and C3.

“you should be a success in your family life and support them, your kids should have a good education, and your wife should support whatever you do and love you. You should make a good amount of money to support them and for you to have good mental and physical health.”

Family relations

C4 mentioned how his wife was involved in the business and how she helps him with the paperwork, helping on the till as a staff member, even working alongside and being supportive towards other staff members in the business. This elaborates on the familiness in the business.

“my wife, she is a huge helping hand, she comes now and then helping me out with my paperwork, gets my lunch, she sometimes helps me on the till and gives a hand with my staff as well.”

Thus, when the researcher probed him to explain the reason why he started his business particularly around this area, he came up with the reply that he knows the people in the area and it is easy to travel from where he was living at the time, so it allows him to look after the family.

“I know the people here, it is easy to travel and look after my family. This was an ongoing business at the time. So, I took it over.”

C4 mentioned that he gains business knowledge from his father back home from time to time. He further revealed that his father, who used to run a business back home, was good at managing people.

“I did ask for advice and I still do ask, especially from my father from time to time. Not only in the business sense but in my personal life as well. My father was really good with managing people.”

Apart from that, when the researcher further probed about the family business back home, he mentioned that he primarily gained his business knowledge and skills when working in the UK from other businesses.

“I worked so hard on the tills of other businesses, I got experience from those businesses. And I saw and experienced how people buy things, how to talk to them to get to know them. You

have to be very careful when you work in those shops. Because you need to keep every receipt you make every day, properly arrange them and record them. Because you need to make two sets of receipts in a day You need to keep them, you need to stack them and you need to hand them over to every day to the accountant or I would say the owner of the business at the time with the till balance. It was a very responsible job at the time.”

Social Capital

Getting cheaper product information

C4 mentioned that as a retail shop owner he was required to buy large quantities of supplies (bulk) for his shop. As business owners across London, C4 explained that they communicate with each other and share information regarding as to where to buy these bulk products for a cheaper price. C4 said it helps him to lower the costs as well.

“some of my friends have businesses in the Croydon area and some of them in the North London area. You know sometimes we need to buy bulk, it could be in big supermarkets or cash and carries I told you before. We communicate with each other once we have found out where the cheapest place is to buy these kinds of product and how much this costs. So we get these kinds of information from each other so it helps us a lot keep the costs down as well.”

Supplier relationship

C4 also mentioned how he sees his supplier relationship. He mentioned that he can buy products from his suppliers (cash and carry in this case). He also mentioned that this is because of the length of time being in business with them and they recognise him very well as a business (reputation).

“I can buy from the cash and carry on the account as well; for example if I say I don't have money they will always provide me with credit. I have been in this business for a long time now so they know who I am.”

Obtaining equipment

On the other hand, C4 explained that, in the beginning, he received a much-needed shelf from one of his friends who also running a similar business. C4 mentioned that it was very expensive at the time. As time went by, they also shared other equipment, such as freezers, with each other. C4 further said that, at the end of the day, they are the ones who helped him a lot and at the same time advised him too.

“now you can see there is a shelf at the end of the shop. That shelf was very expensive at the time. I got it from one of my friends at his shop. It has been with me now for years. There are like other things we shared like freezers etc. The point is they were helping me, advising me when I was setting up this business where to get stuff and what to do..”

Finding staff

C4 lastly mentioned that he gets his employees through his social contacts and in that way, he can get trustworthy people as they would be dealing with the money of his business.

“When I employ people, I always get them through contacts, you know this kind of business, we are all dealing with money and all that, so I need to find trustworthy people.”

Customer relationship related findings

Trust

C4 also aligned with C1, C2, and C3 where he showed operational benevolence by limiting the self-serving opportunities. Hence, he mentioned that he liked to give a more honest opinion to the customers rather than losing money in that making the customer buy the right product is very important to him.

“I give them my honest opinion. I might lose money, but making the customer buy the right one is the key.”

On the other hand, according to DeWulf *et al.* (2001) treating the customers with respect is one of the ways that family businesses develop consumer trust. Similarly, C4 mentioned that he treated the customers nicely and made them feel welcome. Further, he explained that he uses this to attract customers to his business.

“You need to treat them nicely. Like, show you care and welcome them. If you put these together, that's it and you are going to do well. I mean you need to know how to treat them or serve them. I think you need to have that attraction for your business, especially when you do retail.”

Service

Customer-oriented approach

C4 also shows that he is more concerned with identifying the needs of the customer when running the business. On one occasion, he mentioned that he no longer sells ethnic products in his shop as it is not meeting the needs of the customers (English) in the area.

“My customers are locals, English and European people. So, I don't sell ethnic-specific products here anymore as I don't have customers to sell it to in this area nowadays.”

On the other hand, C4 also said that he asks the customer directly what they want, in a scenario where he sees them looking confused or moving around inside the shop. If he can understand what they are asking, he gives it to them by himself without wasting their time. If not, at least he suggests a substitute and makes sure the customer is satisfied with their needs. He believes in not letting the customer down, which is very important to him.

“Sometimes if the customer looks confused or is moving around, I ask them what they want directly. If I can understand what they are asking for and I have it in my shop, I always give them what they need without wasting their time. If not, I see if I can provide at least a substitute, that way I hardly let my customer down. That’s the main thing.”

Customer centricity

When the researcher asked C4 a question about the competitive advantage of his business, he mentioned that, as a businessman, he pays attention to the customers; plus, he tries to understand their needs. He further mentioned that, along with those, he adds or removes products from the shop regularly according to the customer feedback. This allows customers to play a central role in product selection. He thinks this is one of the reasons why some customers come to his shop rather than going to the big supermarkets.

“you need to pay attention to your customers you know. You need to understand them and their needs. I add or remove whatever I sell here according to their feedback. You need to do that now and then. They don’t go to Tesco, they come to me, because they know what they are getting from here.”

Being empathetic towards the customer

C4 achieved empathy here by considering the customer’s side and understanding their needs rather than business objectives, even for one single customer. Here, C4 describes that he has a regular customer who buys one particular product often. But this item has almost no sales from other customers. C4 believes that removing that item from the shelf would make her unhappy. So, he keeps it on the shelf, just for her, so she will not be disappointed.

“I have a regular customer, and she always comes to buy one particular food item from my shop. She really needs it, but there aren’t many sales of it with other customers. But I would keep it just for her and she is not going to be happy if I removed it from the shelves anyway. I would say she is a good purchaser as well. She sometimes buys a good amount of shopping as well. So, I don’t let her down, I make sure the product is there for her.”

Developing patience for the customer

C4 mentioned that he also developed patience with the customers. He said that he likes to talk to the customers, amongst those, when some of these customers are less talkative and not in a good mood he is very careful and patient when these types of customers around. He thinks one of the reasons that he could develop this skill is due to his tolerant nature. With time, he has managed to calm down the customer, listen to them, and make them feel good by using humour. He believes these kinds of skills take time to learn for him and in the end, he makes sure the customer leaves the building happy.

“Since the morning, I have talked to different customers if they are interested. Some of them don’t talk much. Some of them are not in a good mood when they are talking to me. I understand them. I’m a tolerant person. I’m very careful and am patient when they are around. There were some times I had to calm them down, listen to them, and throw some jokes to get their happy face back. I think it took some time for me to learn how to face these kind of customers. But many of the regulars like to talk to me. They leave the building happy.”

Let the customers make the buying decision

C4 demonstrated that he also develops collaborative selling more than a pressurized salesperson approach. According to C4, making money while losing customers is useless for his business. He believes that he looks after the customer by giving an honest opinion to enable them to make the buying decision, even if he loses money in that situation. He thinks that

making the customer buy the right product is very important to him as a business. This is one of the factors that made him stay in the business for eight years and created retained customers over time.

“There is no point in making money while losing my customers. So, I need to look after them. They ask my opinion on certain products here. I give them my honest opinion. I might lose money, but making the customer buy the right one is the key. I’ve been here more than eight years now, I think I did the right thing, they know it and they listen (customers) to me, especially regulars.”

Business reputation

Again, similar to previous cases, C4 also works to earn a good reputation as a business in the area. He explained that he earned such a good reputation running a business for a long time that suppliers will not hesitate to supply on credit. He believes that as far as he is concerned, he never did anything to damage his reputation as a business, and getting supplies on credit is one of the advantages he gets out of it.

“I can buy from this cash and carry on account as well. For instance, if I say I don't have money they will always provide me with credit. I have been in this business for a long time now they know who I am. I have never, as a business or person, damaged my reputation and this is facilitated when you have your own name.”

C4 mentioned that he keeps customers’ unattended items with him, elaborating on the theme of caring for the customer and practicing good ethics for his business, and he gives them back once the customer returns. He further said that customers have never lost anything they have left in his shop.

“Sometimes they leave things in the shop, like umbrellas, bags, wallets and all that. I always keep their things with me, till they come back again and I hand them over to them. They never lose anything they have left in my shop.”

Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)

Not many retail shops around the time he took over the business in the area.

C4 said that one of the main reasons that he took over the current business is that there weren't many retail shops around the area. Plus, he knows the people in the area, and it is much easier for him to travel after the job and look after his family.

“Here, there were not many retail shops around at the time, not as much as now. Also, what kind of people live in this area and I also live nearby this area. I know the people here, and it is easy to travel and look after my family.”

Mini-Supermarkets as a challenge in the area.

C4 believes that the mini supermarkets are giving his business great competition. There are two big retail names in the area, and these supermarkets attract more customers for fresh products by offering cheaper prices than his business. Hence, he had to reduce his fresh product offerings to reduce waste.

*“business is the competition from big-name mini supermarkets. When I talk about the competitors, they are like Express stores. There are two of them around the corner now, one from the S***** and the other t***o. With the fresh products, I can't even compete with them. They have nice refrigerators and they get more fresh products at a cheaper price than me. After they opened these shops, I had to reduce the stock to minimize waste.”*

Stock management as a challenge

As mentioned earlier, C4 struggles to keep a variety of products in his shop due to the small space he has in his shop. Thus, due to lack of space, C4 has difficulties keeping up with the limited stock he has in his shop, where he mentioned that he had to keep going to the cash and carry to buy products frequently and restocking them.

*“If we don’t have enough space to keep different products, it’s hard to keep customers. Like if you go to t***o you buy many things in one place rather than go to many places so you can save time even if it is expensive. So that is the main thing. I try to do a similar thing. So what I’m doing - I go to the cash and carry all the time and I bring the things and whatever the stock is going out I always fill it on my own, that’s what I do most of the time.”*

Coronavirus impact:

Customers prefer mini supermarkets over him due to Coronavirus safety standards.

C4 further mentioned that because of his smaller business capacity to hold a limited number of customers and there is not much space inside the store, customers felt more secure when they shopped inside big supermarkets, even though he takes safety measures seriously in the lockdown situation.

“you know, this shop is very small compared to other competitors, there are no standing queues and no limits, but it is safer here and not many people come here, and most of them in these lockdown days normally run for the supermarket. So, you are safe and sound when you shop. I do take safety measures. I do feel like I did a better job in the lockdown situation.”

Creating a safer shopping atmosphere to keep up with the competitors

C4 said that he is creating a safe atmosphere by offering sanitizers, serving with masks and gloves similar to supermarkets, so that customers can have a safer shopping experience than with the supermarkets.

“I always look after them, I help them, in these situations. I safely serve them, and allow them to safely shop. I have hand sanitizers available for free as they enter the shop, I wear gloves and masks when the customers arrive. I want this place to be much safer like the supermarkets.”

Opportunity to serve new customers as supermarkets couldn't keep up with the demand they received

C4 explained that even though these supermarkets attracted more customers than his business in the area, they eventually could not meet demand, and created long queues outside, and this resulted eventually in him gaining more customers.

“At the end of the day the big supermarkets got very busy and there were a lot of queues outside their buildings. So get more customers because of it.”

Overall sales were up during the lockdown

Lastly, C4 mentioned that his sales went down slightly, but overall he made more money than the previous year and sales gradually increased during the lockdown.

“Sales slightly went down during the lockdown. Overall, I made more money than I did, comparing the last year's sales record. Gradually sales picked up during the lockdown.”

Limited staff availability due to health risks

C4 described that he had limited staff available during the lockdown and afterwards. He further mentioned that he didn't have any option but to furlough them. As a solution to the problem, he had to increase his own working hours in the shop.

“Two of my staff were furloughed due to the health conditions they have. I did not have any options. So all I did was to expand my working hours in this business and other businesses as well.”

Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)

Due to Coronavirus, the government has made it compulsory for businesses to close earlier than usual. This has impacted C4 as well. C4 mentioned that as a result of the government he could manage to go home early, but that has impacted his sales, especially in late nights, and particularly with alcohol and beverages.

“the government made us shut the shop early as well. I could go home early, but that impacted the sales as well, especially the alcohol section at night.”

Thus, C4 appreciates the government's support during the pandemic, especially the furlough scheme, where he mentioned that it is a big relief for him that the government pays the staff wages (80%) on behalf of his business.

“the furlough scheme is really good. Otherwise, I don't know how I would pay staff wages. It is a big relief, to be honest.”

When the researcher questioned C4 regarding the operating environment in comparison to Sri Lanka, the C4 had a positive impression regarding the current rules and regulations in the UK. He believes that there are advantages and disadvantages, following the rules and regulations is pretty much straightforward and once he followed them, he doesn't have any issues with anything or anyone, unlike in Sri Lanka.

“here everything is straightforward, unlike Sri Lanka. There are advantages and disadvantages on both sides. On the plus side, you don't have any hiccups - you just have to follow the law and regulations and you are fine.”

Analysis of Case 5 (Sura -C5)

Individual-level of Analysis (Micro-level):

Motivation to be in the business

C5 also elaborated the ‘pushed’ factors to form a business; job insecurity and financial gains to support his family have emerged from the data.

Job insecurity

C5 mentioned that one of the reasons he is motivated to be in the business is that nobody tells him to leave the job, which usually happens at some point with a fulltime job. He believes that nobody will take the job away from him because he is the owner of the business.

“I think at one point they will tell you to leave the job. But here, you have no one to get me out of this business because I am the boss.”

Financial gains for supporting the family

When the researcher asked the question as to what drives him to have a business, he replies that it is mainly the financial gains he gets from his business, and hence he can support his family.

“I would say mainly profit or money, because you know you have a family to support.”

Success perception

It was found in the interview data from C5 that his perception of success, however, might be aligned with objective measures. He revealed later in the interview that the growth of his business or, in other words, expanding his business to multiple retail shops in London, is interpreted as a success.

“I see success as business growth.”

Family relations

C5 frequently mentioned his family and their business back home in Sri Lanka. His parents currently run a business in Sri Lanka in the retail sector. C5 also mentioned here that his parents' business is a sort of supplier to his business in the UK as he asks for certain products to be shipped here.

“my parents have their own business, similar to retail. But they don't run a business like this. They are more like a supplier to the grocery shops in Sri Lanka. But they are at the moment a supplier to me as well. I ask them for a certain product to be shipped here.”

Thus, C5 revealed his parents' involvement in increasing the variety of items for the shop in the UK, where his father's contribution for this issue was taken on an expert level and indeed, it elaborated the 'familiness' in his business.

"I increased the variety of the items. My parents from back home also supported me a lot on this. Especially my father, I think he is an expert in these kinds of things."

Knowledge and experience

Family business relations has helped him to gain specific and necessary knowledge. But, it also appears that his previous work experience and knowledge have certainly helped him to expand his business over time as well.

"By the time I also had a good experience in the field; with that, over time, I managed to expand the business."

Social Capital

When the researcher asked about who helped him to get the business started, albeit not particularly in the start-up team. He mentioned his friends who helped him all the time.

"I have some good friends, they help me all the time."

Finding staff

Then C5 revealed that he found staff through his friends, family members and other contacts. He put advertisements in the front of his shop as well. But later, he mentioned in that way he can employ someone he knows.

“through my contacts, family members and friends. I also put on an advertisement in front of the shop. But I prefer to employ someone I know.”

Financial access

C5 mentioned that he struggled financially a lot in the beginning. However, in some of those situations, his friends helped him financially to get through his difficulties.

“financially I was struggling a lot. But some of my few friends helped me during that difficult time.”

Labour capital

When the researcher probed further to ask whether these friends only helped him financially, C5 then explained that they not only helped financially but in other areas, such as labour works which requires a considerable amount of manpower and getting people organized.

“but in other areas as well, like helping in some labour works that need a lot of manpower, getting people together and so on.”

Managing a good supplier relationship

C5 mentioned several benefits in managing a good supplier relationship with his business; notifying product availability, offering a discounted price for his business, and purchases on credit were some of them, especially during the lockdown situation. Lastly, C5 believes paying on time by cash payments made his suppliers satisfied during the lockdown.

they were very helpful, they called me whenever a product came available to buy from them, they know me very well. Also, they managed to give me the items for a low price at that time as well. You know I could also get the product on credit as well. But I didn't do it, once delivery was done to the shop, I paid them on time with cash, so they were also happy during that time as well."

Employee Relationship

C5 mentioned that Sri Lankan originated employees are easy to understand due to speaking the same language and this develops a good customer relationship and connection:

"They know our culture and the way we operate - it is a bit different from other retail shops. The languages we speak, it is much easier and you can understand them if you are from the same country. On the top of this, you get the Sri Lankan customers all the time in this shop, and every customer is different, they want us to know them most of the time individually and that's exactly what we give them. So you can have good communication and a connection with the customers as well."

Customer relationship related findings

Trust

The researcher questioned how C5 generally interacts with his customer. What was revealed is that C5 tends to think from the customer's point of view or think like the customer in regards to feedback. If it is bad, he would react immediately to rectify the issue and he hopes by doing this, that this would make the customer come back again to the store. This behaviour, thinking like the customer or thinking from the customer's point of view, reflects that he prioritises the customer's interest rather than being self-interested in his business. In other words, according to Sirdeshmukh, Singh and Sabol (2002) creating trust through operational benevolence.

“I try to be on their ground as much as I can, especially as the owner and I think like them. If it is bad, I sort it out immediately. I want them to come back to the store. That is our success.”

Service

Customer oriented approach

Understanding the customer and serving their needs, is indeed recognised as a customer-oriented business. C5 attempts to explain it by mentioning that he understands their needs and therefore orientates the selection of products to serve the needs of these customers; hence it will also determine the future success of the business as well.

“listening to the customers, understanding what they need, the product selection you have with your business and the quality of these products will decide whether your business will succeed or not in the future.”

Customer centricity

C5 revealed that every customer is different. He believes that these customers expect to be treated in an individualistic way. In other words, it might require a much more personalised service, especially for Sri Lankan customers who come into his shop. Treating the customer as special or delivering a service which puts the customer first, is also called customer centricity (Shah *et al.*, 2006; Gummesson, 2008).

“you get the Sri Lankan customers all the time in this shop, and every customer is different, they want us to know them most of the time individually, and that’s exactly what we give them.”

Being empathetic towards the customer

C5 mentioned that he is always thinking from the customer’s side when it comes to feedback from the customer - whether good or bad. First, before he gets these views from the customer he makes sure the customer feels good and is comfortable sharing their views with him. Perhaps this could be linked back to the literature that empathy is a well-known tool for rapport building which allows front line service people like C5 to see the customer’s point of view (Gremler and Gwinner, 2008).

“I greet them, I talk to them, see if everything is ok, and once the customer is familiar with me, they always talk good or bad. I always think of the customer’s side.”

Developing patience for the customer

C5 believes that making a customer calm and ready to listen is a skill. He mentioned that when the customer is listening, then he expresses his point of view, which might mean avoiding any conflict when communicating with the customer. He also points out that if someone gets angered easily by something said by someone, then customer service would not be a suitable

job for them. This in turn implies that tolerance and patience towards the customer is a skill that develops over time, as he has learnt from his 15-year work experience.

“Sometimes you have to make the customer calm and ready to listen. Then you can contribute your point of view. If you get angry very easily with someone, this is not the job for you, definitely take time to learn to deal with customers. That’s what I learnt from my 15-year work experience.”

Let the customers make the buying decision

C5 mentioned that he increased the product variety so that customers don’t need to come to him and ask general questions regarding the choices they are about to make. By increasing the product choices, he tries to eliminate those interactions and interestingly he mentioned that often with the regulars, he has to make the decision for them in the end. He believes that it shouldn’t be that way and he should not be involved in their buying decision, which is up to the customers themselves. In other words elaborating more of a collaborative selling.

“I think it was a really good idea to increase the item variety, so customer can make a good choice by themselves. I don't like walking up to me and asking which one is better, is there any more choices and at the end, I have to make the decision for them. I don't think I should do that, this happens to me especially with regular customers who know me.”

Business reputation

C5 also appeared to have committed to maintaining a good business reputation. He revealed that he buys quality items from well-known brands to sell for his customers. Hence, suppliers help him also to find branded products for his shop. He believes that if he decides to get cheaper products for his shop and eventually sells them to the customer, it will damage his business reputation faster than the time he invested to build it.

“I make sure I always buy quality items for my shop - well-known brands which are in the market for so long. My suppliers help me out on this, because it takes a second to damage our years of reputation by making a cheap decision.”

Economic/Opportunity structure Analysis (Meso-level):

Family relations helped him to acquire a business

At the beginning of the interview, C5 mentioned how he started the business and took the opportunity to own the business from a family-related business owner. First, C5 started work as an employee in his business. After five years, the previous owner wanted to sell the business. So, C5 took the opportunity to ask him to hand over the business to him. Lastly, he mentioned that the previous owner of the business also helped him a lot at the beginning of the process. This can be related to literature as Yeung (2002) found that ethnic entrepreneurial opportunity recognition could be promoted or hindered by their social relations.

“first of all the previous shop owner was related to me. So, he said he wanted to sell the business. So I asked him, can I run the business? At the time, the business was very low. So he said ok. It was a bit risky, but I was young. Anyway, I took that risk and bought the business. The previous owner also helped me a lot in the beginning.”

Living in a Sri Lankan ethnic enclaved area

C5 mentioned that he has lived in the Sri Lankan immigrant concentrated area for a long time. However, according to him, there was no quality Sri Lankan retail shop around the area. It may have persuaded him to take over the business as an opportunity to serve the gap in the local market.

“I have lived in this area for more than fifteen years. I know the community, there are a lot of Sri Lankan people also living in this area. I know all these Sri Lankan people coming to this shop for sure. We are near to them and I can close the shop and go home in walking distance. It is easier for me and we don't have a quality Sri Lankan retail shop near to us.”

Lacking online presence

C5 said that he is further behind than other businesses when it comes to an online presence, which he currently lacks.

“I need to have more online presence for my business. Currently, we are very behind than other businesses.”

Coronavirus impacts

Supplier delays during the lockdown

C5 mentioned that there were supplier delays due to Coronavirus lockdown. But C5 managed to restock as soon as possible as a result of a good supplier relationship.

“We had issues with supply delays, but we managed to stock up just right on time. You know I have other shops and I have good suppliers - I kept ordering and they kept delivering.”

Service delays during the lockdown

During the lockdown there were delays in his service due to safety concerns and allowing only a limited number of customers inside the shop, which ended up with queues outside the shop.

“There was a delay in service. I had to take five customers at once, let them shop and let those out and get new customers in and serve them like that. There was a huge queue outside my shop.”

Overall sales increased

However, just as in the previous case, C5 revealed that he had made a good profit, due to the increased number of customer presence and purchasing during the lockdown period.

“During the lockdown, just at the beginning of the lockdown, I reached a higher profit, you know the people kept coming, and they cleared the shelves. The shop looked very empty till we refilled.”

Challenging working environment during the lockdown

C5 further mentioned that even though he had an opportunity to increase sales during the pandemic, C5 was struggling with the management duties during the pandemic, such as controlling the number of customers who could come inside the shop at once, which led to some of them being unhappy. As C5 has multiple shops around London, he had to frequently check the staff in other sites, keep up with the suppliers, stock and have daily briefs with the Coronavirus news; these were some of his duties he struggled with many times during the pandemic.

“I had to take so many decisions on myself. Like the number of customers who were allowed to enter the shop. So, I told you before, I allowed five people at once. It was very hard to control the customers as some of them were very unhappy. Checking the staff throughout the service, to see if they needed a hand, especially on other sites, was another struggle. Supplies, checking stock, removing unnecessary items and getting up to date information regarding the lockdown situation was a must.”

Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)

Using government support (furlough) during the pandemic.

C5 believes that the government furlough was very helpful for him during the lockdown. Thus, along with that, he said he gives other incentives for the staff to keep them satisfied during these difficult times.

“yes, I do. It is very helpful and I also give them the other benefits like bonuses and discounts and keep them happy.”

Using council information to make decisions

C5 revealed that they opened a new retail shop in Bromley in London last year after they researched the area.

“We opened a shop in Bromley last year after we researched the area and the people who live in that area. After a year, it is a huge success.”

Interestingly, when the researcher questioned who gave him the necessary information to make that decision, he explained that the local council made it available to them, and it was a huge help to him in making that decision as a multiple shop owner.

“The council have been very helpful over there. They gave us precise information we needed. I think it was a huge deal for us before making a decision.”

Import and tax regulations in UK

C5 further mentioned that he occasionally imports goods from Sri Lanka and once arrived in the UK, they take a long time to clear the authorities. Hence, it impacts product quality.

“Sometimes we bring stuff from Sri Lanka, but also not really easily, because here they put on taxes and take a long time to clear.”

Lastly, C5 has shown a positive impression regarding the rules and regulations in the UK. C5 believes that rules and regulations are helpful for him to run the business much more easily and smoothly compared to Sri Lanka.

“I think it would be easier to run a business in the UK than in Sri Lanka. I think because of the rules and regulations in the UK, it is really helpful for us to run a business smoothly.”

Analysis of Case 6 (Hesh-C6)

The individual-level of analysis (Micro-level):

Motivation to be in the business

Previous job dissatisfaction

C6 mentioned that he was looking into opportunities to run his own business. Interestingly, he was not satisfied with his job at the time, because he found that employers he had at the time did not know how to get the most out of him.

“When you work for someone else, they don’t know how to get 100% out of you. It happened to me in the past.”

Independence

In line with some of the previous cases, C6 also revealed that he left his fulltime job to form a business in order to be independent.

“I used to have a job before all of this. I left that to have my freedom.”

C6 said that he can make any decision within his businesses, whether right or wrong. He has the ability to do anything and no one else can tell him anything; this could also refer to autonomy.

“When you run your own business, no one tells you what do to, you do what you want to do, whether it is right or wrong.”

Success perception

C6 appeared to have subjective measures to view success as well.

According to Soly-mossy (1997), social status within the community that the ethnic entrepreneur is embedded or lives in, and personal satisfaction is also viewed as success (based on subjective measures). C6 appears to have similar characteristics. He mentioned that when a satisfied customer recommends his business to another within his community he viewed this as a success.

“in my view, if the customer is satisfied by our service and products, and they recommended to another potential customer or share within the society, then I see this business is successful.”

Then again, he further explained that his personal life is also fulfilled by not having any debts, living a good life and supporting the family, which can also be viewed as subjective measures for success.

“In terms of personal life, having no debts, earning enough to live on my terms with a good life and fulfil my family needs.”

Family relations

C6 mentioned that he also comes from a family business background as his parents operate a catering business in Sri Lanka. He revealed that even at such a young age, he experienced the business environment.

“at the moment my parents are running a catering business in Sri Lanka. My father was in these kinds of business, even before I born. I experienced a business background since as far back as I can remember.”

Then he further explained the nature of his family business back home; they have worked collaboratively as a family business, without even worrying about financial benefits that normally come with a job.

“yes, of course, it is a family business you know, everyone is helping each other, regardless you gonna get pay or not.”

Thus, C6 mentioned that when he was involved in the business back home, he learned certain skills, such as managing customers and staff.

“it is a family business you know, everyone is helping each other, regardless you gonna get pay or not. I couldn't be involved in my family business back home at the moment as I settled here. But I have a good experience from back home on customer handling, how to manage and treat your staff well in your business.”

Financial capital

Then C6 mentioned that his father helped him financially at the beginning. He also helped him find the staff and promote his business through his contacts in the UK.

“from the beginning financial terms, yes. My father is a huge help for me. And also he helped me how to find the staff through his contacts here and how to promote my business.”

Finally, he mentioned his wife’s involvement with his retail business, particularly with paper work or as a staff member to help him in the busy times, elaborating the ‘familiness’ in his business even more.

“my wife is involved as you can see. When I need a hand, when I'm busy document processing, I always ask her to help.”

Social Capital

Sharing the knowledge

C6 revealed that he is involved in some sort of business network, which helps him and others share their knowledge and experiences each other. So, it can be of benefit and be helpful for each other to operate the businesses.

“you are asking about the networking, yes we help each other if they need some knowledge regarding the business or any sort, we are kind of like a small group, or you can say in this case, some sort of network of trustworthy people who help each other.”

Finding the staff

C6 mentioned that he found his staff through his friends, contacts and some through customers as well.

“most of them I find through my friends, contacts and some of them I find through customers as well.”

Interestingly, when the researcher probed as to why he did this particularly from his social circle, C6 then explained that, in that way, he knows who he is employing for his business rather than employing a stranger who may be a good person or not. In the case of a bad person, that leaves him with a hard and possibly time-consuming situation and one which could possibly damage his business reputation.

“I should know who I employ, in that way I can know who I am dealing with rather than finding on the internet and employing a complete stranger, who we don’t know whether is a good

person or not. If that person is a bad person, certainly it is hard and time consuming because these people know how to get around with the law, leaving bad business reputation.”

Employee relationship

C6 mentioned that having employees who come from the same cultural background and who speak the same language as him is beneficial for his business in certain ways; such as it is easy to communicate and manage them, and these employees tend to develop good customer relationships for his business:

“I believe that Sri Lankan staff - for me, I found that I can easily control them. Easy to understand them, as most of the time we are from the same cultural background, and speaking the same language is an extra skill for the job and creates a relationship with them. I normally evaluate them by increasing positive feedback from the customers, how they approach them and help them to find what they want. I found most of the time, Sri Lankan staff I have here are very helpful for the customers.”

Customer relationship related findings

Trust

C6 revealed that providing a good service is key to earning customer trust. He further explained that giving the right product information, without hiding anything from the customer, might mean giving the correct information to the customer so that they can make their own choice, even at a cost to the business. He believes that when he gives an honest opinion to the customer, with the right price, and makes them feel cared for by the business, these customers tend to return to him and he has witnessed this over and over again. In essence, C6 with his business is also elaborating the operational benevolence through limiting self-serving opportunism.

“if you give good service, give them the right product information, no misinformation, the right price, no high prices and if you honestly care about your customers, they always come

back. I witnessed this over and over again, customers trust you when they feel that you honestly care for them.”

Service

Customer oriented approach

C6, however, orients his business to serving the needs of the customer as well. He said that, in the beginning, he targeted everyone in the area to serve; but according to him, it did not work for him. Instead, he started to identify frequent customers and their backgrounds (perhaps he meant here the country of origin or ethnicity), especially with the frequent visitors for his business. He then started to communicate with them and attempt to get feedback, revealing, perhaps, what products there should be, what improvements etc. C6 believes these customers feedback eventually helped him to increase the products offered in his shop, with well-branded quality products. After five years, the less profitable business turned into a business without any losses. In the end, C6 mentioned that a business needs to understand what the customer wants from it and adjust if necessary to provide it, which elaborates the customer orientation.

“Things I offer here are a mixture of everything, like some of the things are for local English/European people and others are for Sri Lankan/South Asian people. The idea was to serve everyone in the local area, but it didn't work for me. After a while you slowly identify your customers' backgrounds, where they come from, particularly frequent visitors. When you try to talk to them they give you feedback, and that's the key. Slowly, I increased the product variety with some well-branded quality products based on their feedback. Fast forward five years, I would say I am running a business without any loss. You need to understand what they want and adjust your business to give it.”

Customer centricity

C6 appeared to also have a personalised customer service, especially for his regular customers, elaborating customer centricity. C6 mentioned that he is familiar with his regular customers,

and if these customers want to make any complaints or express anything else, they will get treated well. Perhaps it means he serves them in a personalised way and makes sure they will come back to the store once again.

“my regular customers, I'm very familiar with them, they trust me, I trust them. If they come up with anything I make sure they are treated well and make sure they come back again to the store.”

Being empathetic towards the customer

C6 mentioned that they treat their customers in the same way as when his wife and himself visit another shop i.e. how they would want to be treated as a customer in that shop. Hence, this behaviour can be linked with empathy, as C6 seeks to understand another person's (customer) view and provide their (perceived) needs (Devoldre *et al.*, 2010)

“me or my wife, whenever we go any other shop, how we wanted to be get treated by the staff of that shop, the same way we do with the customers here. Every time it works.”

Then again C6 revealed that giving the right product information without giving any misinformation, and giving the right price, is a way to care for the customer so that they always come back and he experienced this over and over again. This elaborates on the fact that money is not the priority and indeed, customer satisfaction seems to be an objective here, as its links with customer retention.

“if you give good service, give them the right product information, no misinformation, the right price, no high prices and if you honestly care about your customers, they always come back. I witnessed this over and over again.”

Developing patience with the customer

C6 revealed that having a good understanding of what the customer is asking is very important to him i.e. don't pretend that you, as a business, understand them and shake your head as it might lead to get a bad impression about business and leave the customer unhappy and angry. As a solution to that, C6 suggests listening to the customer by giving them your full attention as a staff member, because he thinks listening first and giving output second is a basic communication skill. Lastly, he mentioned that as a small business like them, kindness and patience is very important to them. Perhaps this might elaborate that C6 as a business develops patience and kindness to maintain his business reputation.

“Being nicer, giving a warm welcome, a good understanding of what they want, especially if the customer gets an impression that you don't understand what they are asking and shake your head, they are getting very angry and that's not a good impression for the business. We need to show them we understand them by really listening to them, giving full attention to them, no magic in that, it is just basic language skills. I always tell my staff as well, patience and kindness are very important to any business like us.”

Let the customers make the buying decision

When the researcher asked about his offering other than the monetary value for the customer from his business, C6 explained it by comparing his shop with the supermarkets he has nearby. According to him, caring but not neglecting and getting exactly what they need from his shop is important, and on top of this he does not expect to drain the money of his customers. Perhaps, draining their money could be about larger supermarkets using sales promotions to maximise their profitability, and indeed making the customer spend more than they should (Gilbert and Jackaria, 2002; Prendergast, Shi and Cheung, 2005). In other words, it might also mean promoting collaborative selling rather than being a salesperson to his business.

“We give quality service in comparison with other supermarkets. You are not neglected, you get what you want, especially for Sri Lankans. Nothing more nothing less, they can buy whatever they want from my shop, if they want. For sure we are not draining their money.”

Business reputation

C6 believes that building a reputation in genuine ways is important to him because he thinks that maintaining a good reputation may link to the future of the business.

“You see, I built my reputation in this business so far in genuine ways, not the other way around, because it is your future.”

When the researcher posed a question regarding why he always employed someone he knows through his social network, C6 revealed that finding staff through the internet and employing a stranger would be a risk to his business as he doesn't know these employees' backgrounds. If that person is bad, C6 believes these people always end up giving him a hard time and consuming his time. He believes these kind of 'bad' people know how to bypass the law or use it to their own advantage, and that could lead to damaging his business reputation.

“yeah, because I should know who I employ, in that way I can know who I am dealing with rather than finding on the internet and employing a complete stranger, who we don't know whether is a good person or not. If that person is a bad person, certainly it is hard and time consuming because these people know how to get around with the law, leaving bad business reputation.”

C6 believes that as a business, he should be honest with the customer, by not doing anything fake or anything that would create dishonesty with the customer. C6 thinks that would damage

the trust relationship between him, and as a business, with the customer. Finally, C6 mentioned that the image of the family business also matters to the customers.

“I think you should be honest what you doing, if you are doing anything dodgy or fake, eventually customers won't trust you or your business. Your image as a family business I think also matters to the customers.”

Interestingly, C6 makes sure he does not have any illegitimate business practices, employing staff through his social network so that they are more trustful for him and for the business, and attempting to maintain a good trust relationship with the customer; hence this contributes to maintaining a valuable reputation as a family business. Thus, these behaviours, according to Gbadamosi (2004), can relate to his definition of business ethics as ‘a set of rules that stipulate how businesses and their employees ought to behave’. Hence, Mella and Gazzola (2015) found that behavioural ethics are important to maintaining a good business reputation. Therefore, C6 attempts to maintain good business ethics so that he can maintain a good family business reputation.

“I should know who I employ, in that way I can know who I am dealing with rather than finding on the internet and employing a complete stranger, who we don't know whether is a good person or not. If that person is a bad person, certainly it is hard and time consuming because these people know how to get around with the law, leaving bad business reputation.”

Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)

Low market entry barrier

C6 mentioned how he ended up starting a retail business in the beginning. First, he explained that it was difficult for him to decide between hospitality, health and retail. Second, he realised that retail needed the lowest start-up capital to open a business when compared with the aforementioned sector types. Finally, he thought he should go for the retail business as it is low risk.

“Then I was thinking, which sector I should go for, in my mind, it was a bit difficult to decide between hospitality, health sector or retail. Then I thought, if I had gone for hospitality or catering, then I would need more money to start the business, needs a lot of labour and equipment. If anything goes wrong, I will lose everything. It was too risky at the time. If I start the retail, I wouldn’t be needing that amount of money and people in the beginning. So I thought it is a good opportunity, just to start the business smaller, and see how it goes.”

Sri Lankan immigrant concentrated area

C6 mentioned that, when he was familiarised with the people and area, he found that it was easy to manage the business. Then again he mentioned that Sri Lankan and South Asian people are living in the area as well. Perhaps he might be attempting to express here a reference to having similar cultural background and languages.

“it is very easy to handle a business when you know the area and the people. As you know Sri Lankan people and South Asian people are living here as well.”

Cultural values for better job performance

C6 believes that, as a Sri Lankan retail shop owner, having staff who are originally from Sri Lanka means they are easier to control, understand and communicate with. C6 reviews his staff members by customer feedback and monitors how they interact with the customers. He found that Sri Lankan staff are more helpful to the customer than other local staff members.

“I believe that Sri Lankan staff, for me I found that I can easily control them, it is easy to understand them, most of the time we are from the same cultural background and speaking the same language is an extra skill for the job and creates a relationship with them. I normally evaluate them by increasing positive feedback from the customer, how they approach them and help them to find what they want. I found, most of the time, the Sri Lankan staff I have here are very helpful for the customers. I'm not saying other staff from other countries are bad. They are also helpful too.”

Language barriers

C6 also mentioned that he sometimes has to become involved in conversations between Sri Lankan staff and foreign (English) customers as he found they had difficulty communicating in the English language; then he becomes involved with the customer on behalf of the staff, helps them and makes sure they are satisfied with the service.

“There are some language difficulties with foreign customers, then I would always get involved with their conversation and sort out the customer, making sure they are happy.”

Coronavirus impacts

Overall price increased in products.

C6 was forced to increase the price due to suppliers demanding a higher price for the products.

“I had to increase the price because suppliers increased the price.”

Challenging working environment during the lockdown

Then C6 also revealed that lack of staff meant he and his remaining staff had to work extra hours, especially when the shop floor got busy.

“I just work myself and other remaining staff to run this shop. It is very hard to manage when it gets busy and needs to be refilled.”

Lack of staff during the lockdown

C6 revealed that during the lockdown, he had to cut down some of the staff due to their health risks.

“I had to cut down the staff. Three of my staff in this business and all the people in the health service have stopped their jobs. We have got single mothers, students and older people as our staff.”

Number of customers increased during the lockdown

C6 revealed that he has kept the business open specifically for his regular customers, but that he has had a lot more new customers than usual.

“We have to keep running the business for our regulars especially. But we get a lot of new customers than usual.”

Business uncertainty

However, C6 thinks that his business uncertainty has impacted his business negatively. So he has currently stopped his business expansion plans.

“But this Coronavirus situation hit our businesses really hard. So, I still can't say, because I'm not sure what's gonna happen in the next few months.”

Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)

Financial access through institutions

C6 appeared to be having difficulties accessing finance through financial institutions in the UK. He revealed that the processing time and the information that he has to provide to gain access takes a long time

“Lending money from a bank takes you long time to be approved and they check the computer asking a thousand questions and at the end of the day they consume your time and give back nothing.”

Tax and other costs are high in London

C6 mentioned that he found operating a business in London is expensive, especially staff wages and taxes.

“when you are operating your business in London, the cost is very high, staff wages are high, and taxes and other regulations.”

Furlough scheme

C6 appreciated that the government took action to take care of the vulnerable staff and others during the lockdown.

“We got single mothers, students and older people as our staff. They are being furloughed. I really appreciate the government took this action.”

Overall positive impression on rules and regulations in UK

C6 lastly mentioned that the rules and regulations in the UK have helped him to regulate his business, and that, by following these rules this makes it a safer place for everyone, even though he finds them sometimes a little difficult to cope with.

“there is a big difference - in Sri Lanka as a developing country we don't have as many rules and regulations as we do here; in the UK, we have a lot of rules and regulations which actually help to regulate the businesses, work according to the rules and make a safer place for everyone. There are a lot of rules to follow which I sometimes find a bit difficult to cope with as a small business owner.”

Analysis of Case 7 (Mahi -C7)

Individual-level of Analysis (Micro-level):

Motivation to be in the business

Lack of job opportunities within the local market

C7 mentioned that he used to work in a supermarket as his main job. When he found a place which he finally felt he could move to with his family, at the same time it was hard for him to maintain the job he was doing as the travelling distance was an issue for him. So he started to look for job opportunities in the area where he was trying to move to with his family. Then, C7 mentioned that it took a long time to find job opportunities within the local job market and the ones he found were offering lower wages.

“This was a very hard process and took a long time. I found some jobs in retail, but not for the same amount of money I used to get paid in my previous jobs, it's lower than that.”

Language barriers

It also appears that C7 faced a language barrier in communicating with people as he didn't understand their (English) accent in the beginning.

“I had experienced it till I got to know the people and importantly the language. Sometimes I didn't understand their accent in the beginning.”

Money for survival

C7 mentioned that one of the reasons he ran a business was to earn money to survive, to feed his family, and to give a good education to his children.

“We need money to survive, to feed the family, we are four of us. My kids need to have a good education - that requires money.”

When the researcher probed further regarding what drove him to run his business during the pandemic, C7 revealed that he had to run the business like he used to before, or take the opportunity to run it because of the survival of the business; and he needed money to live. This reflects his motivation to run the business.

“We have to carry on what we did before, doesn't matter. If your business can run these days, I think you should run it, at least for your business survival and you need to make money to live.”

Success perception

C7 mentioned that he sees success as teamwork, hence he runs his business not just for himself.

“Success - I take it as teamwork, basically this is not for myself.”

C7 appears to use subjective measures to view success as well. First, he made money to have a good, stress free family life for himself; hence this is one of the reasons why he formed the business in the first place.

“earn money enough to have a good stress free life for me and my family. One of the reasons why I have started this business is my family.”

Secondly, he also thinks that success is having support from his family members and having a good family bond at the same time as having them run the business.

“My wife and my kids support what I do. They always come and help me whenever I need. I mean I'm lucky that we have a good family bond. I think I'm successful in that as well. At the same time, we think about our business as well.”

Family relations

C7 mentioned how his wife is particularly involved in his business. C7 further revealed that she helps him manage the paper work and gathers information for his business, and also gives feedback.

“my family and my wife support me all the time for this business. And she helps me with my paperwork almost all the time. If I want to introduce any product in the shop she looks for it even online. Gives her feedback. She is better at information gathering.”

Then he further mentioned that other members of his family are involved in his business. IN the beginning, his uncle shared knowledge with him for finding good products; he also mentioned giving quality products and having a good reputation in the business.

“my uncle helped me a lot when I was starting. He has given his advice on how to find good products, it's all about the quality of your goods and your business reputation.”

Previous family businesses back home helped C7 to learn necessary skills, which he appeared to use for his business today.

“Like I told you before, I used to work for him part-time back home. It has helped me a lot to learn how to interact with the customers, give a nice service and work along with them.”

C7 accessed finance through his family assets. He further mentioned how he was struggling in the beginning due to lack of financial stability when forming a business. As a result of this, he didn't have much stock in the early days.

“The main issue was I wasn't financially stable. I invested all my savings from the full-time job, I had to sell some of my assets like my car and wife's jewellery, even what she was given by her family and all that. We, as a family, sacrificed a lot to this business. We had to start from scratch, we didn't have much stock, to be honest, in the beginning.”

C7 also mentioned that his wife helps him on the work floor to serve the customers.

“me and my wife stand behind the till and serve our customers.”

Social capital

Supplier relationship

C7 appeared to have a good relationship with the suppliers over the years. As a benefit, they were always ready to supply him whenever he placed an order.

“I have my good old regular suppliers. They have been with me for a long time. Milk and newspapers. Whenever I ask something about their availability, they supply it to me fast. I pay on time. I have had good suppliers over the years.”

Sharing knowledge and information

One of the benefits of having a social network is sharing information between them to run their businesses smoothly. C7 appeared to maintain a good social business network.

“I have friends who own or run businesses, who are Sri Lankans. We sometimes share relevant information.”

C7 further revealed how he connected with the local people in the area. He also mentioned that his good work ethic and by doing no wrongdoings in his shop helped him to make a good impression for the customers, in that they knew they would get nothing but quality products and service from his family shop.

“I find people always tend to talk with me, the locals. They know me over the years, how hard I was working to serve them. They know I don’t do any dodgy things. They know they gonna get quality products from me, in this family shop.”

Financial access

C7 also appeared to have financial access, the opportunity to explore and access to labour capital through his social surroundings.

“probably my friends, some have recently helped me financially as well. You know sometimes my friends help me out by giving more information, what's going on with Sri Lankan community and what opportunities we have and all that. Some friends helped me out to renovate this shop in the beginning and sometimes even lend their hand.”

Customer relationship related findings

Trust

C7 mentioned that one of the good indicators to check whether he has built a good customer relationship is to see if customers pass the other shops to visit his shop. C7 further revealed that one of the good inputs to building such a relationship with the customer is to be honest as much as possible when they are inside, even when he knows that he is not going to make any sale out of it. He finally said that being honest to the customer may have a link to customer retention. This also elaborates on limiting self-serving opportunism through operational benevolence.

“You should talk to them if they pass the other shop and come to you. That means you have built a good connection with the customers. You should be honest with them as much as you can be, sometimes you are not gonna make a sale out of it, but normally I see them back in here. I get their feedback and use tis to improve. I always manage to keep quality products in-store. No fake things or lies.”

Service

Customer-oriented approach

C7 demonstrates that he identified the customer needs in the area by mentioning that he sells organic milk and free-range eggs which sell fast and he mentioned that people prefer quality products over cheap ones from his shop.

“it’s the quality I give my customers. You know in this area, customers would spend more money on the quality products. Like here, its most popular milk is organic milk. I hardly waste them. Free-range eggs sell fast, and people tend to ask if there is none. I never let down them over the quality. Especially in this area, I found that people like to have more quality items over the cheap.”

Customer centricity

C7 demonstrates customer centricity by treating each customer differently. He mentioned that he does not ignore the customers in his shop. He believes that each and every customer is different in their own way, hence they have their own needs, elaborating customer centricity through individualised service.

“You can’t ignore your customers. Everyone is different in their own way. They have their own needs.”

On one particular occasion, C7 describes one customer in the local area, elaborating on individualised service which may actually link to business reputation.

“she has lived here almost all her life in this area and she knows almost all the people. She appreciates it now, she will tell it to other people and it will go customer to customer. That’s how I built a name for this business in this area.”

Being empathetic towards the customer

Again, C7 explained that he or his wife never had issues with the customers. Then he mentioned about not pushing the customer in order to make money, hence their objective is not only to earn money, but to make the customer happy. This behaviour also shows the customers that C7, as a business, truly cares about the customer rather than attempting to make a profit.

“We never had any issues with the customers, we know how to treat them, they know we not running after the money, we are not pushing them to make more money, we make sure they are happy at the end of the day and that's what matters to us.”

Developing patience for the customer

C7 mentioned how he normally behaves in front of a customer, especially when it is a busy time. He mentioned communicating politely when he is in a rush. This might exemplify how he uses patience/tolerant behaviour to get the customer's attention, even in the busiest times.

"I always ask them how they are doing and what they need. Make sure I communicate with them politely, even if I am in a rush."

Interestingly, C7 revealed that, even if 'pushed' by the customer to his limit, he would still deliver. Then he mentioned that he is 'careful' when communicating with the customer because it might take one word to offend them or to be misinterpreted by the customer. Thus, if the customer is angry, C7 makes sure to 'calm' them down and listen. He also believes that these kinds of characteristics are developed over time. In other words, this might exemplify his tolerant behaviour towards the customer and the patience he has been developing over time.

"if I can provide something for the customer and even if they push me to the edge I would still do that in that sense. You need to be very careful here, your words matter to them because it sometimes takes one word to offend them. If the customer looks angry, you need to calm them down and listen. It works sometimes, but sometimes it doesn't. It comes with good experience with customers over time."

Let the customer make the buying decision

Again, interpreting the same sentence mentioned above, here C7 also appeared to be developing collaborative selling rather than other methods. He reiterates 'pushing' the customer to buy more things from them and he believes that, over time, the customer knows in the area that he as a business which is not only after the money.

“We know how to treat them, they know we not running after the money, we not pushing them to make more money, we make sure they are happy at the end of the day and that's what matters to us.”

Business Reputation

C7 revealed that by providing individualised service to the customer and taking care of their individual needs this will essentially lead to spreading a positive message to other potential customers in the area; hence it will enable him to maintain a good business reputation.

“You can't ignore your customers, On top of that, she has lived here almost all her life in this area and she knows almost all the people. She appreciates it now, she will tell it to other people and it will go customer to customer. That's how I built a name for this business in this area. Reputation is very important to me.”

C7 thinks that locals have known him over the years, and know how hard he works to deliver customer needs. And importantly, he mentioned that he doesn't do any 'dodgy' things and that these customers tend to know it, which could be related to maintaining good business ethics and moral principles for managing a healthy customer relationship; hence it helped him to develop his reputation.

“I find people always tend to talk with me, the locals. They know me over the years, how hard I was working to serve them. They know I don't do any dodgy things. They know they gonna get quality products from me, in this family shop.”

Again, C7 also revealed that he truly cares for the customers, as mentioned earlier, and that earning money seemed not to be the sole purpose here. Instead, C7 wants to be honest with his

customers as much as he can , without lies or fake things which could trick them. He sees that it helped him to retain those customers as well.

“You should be honest to them as much as you can be, sometimes you not gonna make a sale out of it, but normally I see them back in here. I get their feedback and use it to improve. I always manage to keep quality products in-store. No fake things or lies.”

Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)

Low entry barriers to the market.

C7 mentioned that, in moving to a new area in London, it took a long time for him to decide whether he should leave his job or not. Then he found new job opportunities related to his work experience in a nearby area. But according to C7, it was underpaid and less than he used to be paid by his previous job. Therefore he decided to open up a business related to his previous work experience, which would allow him to earn more money than any other jobs he was doing at the time, even though losing his job was a risk to him. If he made a loss from the business, he could easily go back and find a job. This exemplified the low entry, low exit barrier market influenced C7 to form a business.

“I didn’t know where to start and how to start with this. Because it is not easy to find a place that ticks all the boxes. Then I realised, if moving further away from where we used to live, I would have to find another job. This was a very hard process and took a long time. I found some jobs in retail, but not the same amount of money I used to get paid in my previous jobs, it's lower than that. As I have previous working experience in a retail business, I thought why not start my own business where we are about to move to. Leaving a job was risky, but if you lose, you can go back and work for someone like in the beginning. Not a big deal. But I thought this is the best and only option, to make money better than a job.”

Having a good community and lack of retail shops

C7 mentioned that in the beginning, he checked the community before he formed a business in the area. He found that it was made up of professionals and it looked to be a 'posh' area. Perhaps 'posh' means that to him that there was a low crime rate in the area, and where the people had good spending power. At the same time, he revealed that there weren't many retail shops around where he was looking and this influenced him to take an opportunity to form a retail business in the area:

"I checked the community in the area, what people live in this area. Here people are quiet professionals and it is a 'posh' area. No troubles. The area hasn't got many shops around - this was a bonus for me. Population-wise, I knew it is not going to be busy. But I realised I could do something. So now I have a good clientele and I have got to the point where customers sometimes shop with a trolley rather using a basket. That means my business has improved a lot from what it used to be."

Coronavirus impacts

C7 revealed several issues he has faced during the lockdown. Overall sales were low during that time, perhaps partly because the frequency of the customers shopping was lowered due to safety risks. Then he mentioned the limitation of customers in the shop due to safety measures, eventually losing out on the number of customers in the shop at one time. Lastly, he mentioned that he had supply delays and product cost was higher at the same time.

"my sales went down. People were afraid to go outside. Some people went shopping for a month at a time. We did not allow many customers in at one time, eventually losing the customers. We had issues with the suppliers, there were huge delays for the supplies. And they were expensive at the same time."

Lack of staff

C7 said that he sent his remaining staff on furlough, mainly due to cutting down on the cost and the lack of stock managing or other duties. At the moment, he and his wife are serving behind the till.

“I don’t have staff these days in my business. I had to furlough them to cut the cost, and me and my wife stand behind the till and serve our customers. The other thing is we don’t have many customers, we don’t have much stock managing or refills. I think it is good to furlough them.”

Business Future uncertainty due to the current situation

C7 believes that he does not have a permanent plan if the current lockdown situation continues, but he thinks he can adapt to the new uncertain environment. He fears there will be uncertainty about how he can get the supplies to sell as he is currently having issues with supply delays.

“I don’t have a fixed plan of what I am going to do if this continues. What I have to do is to change according to the new uncertain environment. And see how it goes. But if there are no suppliers to give the supplies and cash and carries don’t have the goods I need, then what can I sell?”

Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)

Certainty about government can avoid uncertainty

C7 said that he is positive that the current government will take action to avoid uncertainty created by the pandemic for his businesses in the UK.

“I don’t have a fixed plan of what I am going to do if this continues. What I have to do is to change according to the new uncertain environment. And see how it goes. But if there are no suppliers to give the supplies and cash and carries don’t have the goods I need, then what can I sell? The thing is I am positive about the future. I don’t think this government will allow that to happen anytime soon.”

C7 thinks that overall rules and regulations should be in place in order to operate businesses safely and the UK at the moment has this, unlike Sri Lanka where he thinks more should be done.

“in here I found it pretty straight forward and easy if you have the money and the people. But back in Sri Lanka, there are not many government regulations or even though we have them, it is not properly executed, corruption everywhere, and the underworld. Here in the UK, you have sets of rules and regulations that work, are safe to work, have good police around the area, and have a security system. And I am happy to be here.”

Analysis of Case 8 (Sachin -C8)

Individual-level of Analysis (Micro-level):

Motivation to be in the business

Previous work experience

C8 mentioned that he worked in many retail shops for years, and he got enough experience over the time about these businesses. Plus, these employers have influenced/motivated him to run his own business in the future.

“I started work in different Off Licence shops for years. I learnt about these kinds of businesses a lot as I got older. Also, these business owners encouraged me one day to run my own business.”

Independence

It has emerged in the data that job flexibility, decision making power and job security have motivated C8 to run his own business all this time.

“when you are running a business, you can work whenever you want to, you are your own boss, nobody tells you what to do, you will make mistakes, you will make losses and you will learn from them. Nobody is here to say anything and sack you. There are a lot of benefits for standing on your own feet.”

Financial benefits

C8 mentioned that there are more financial gains from a business than being employed by someone. This also motivated him to operate a business.

“Once you get employed by someone, you will almost always get a fixed salary every month. Here, nobody is stopping you making money - you can earn.”

Success perception

C8 appeared to be using subjective measures to view success. Thus, he mentioned that he trained himself to become more independent so that he could be the person he always wanted to be, which elaborates that he sees success as being independent.

“Day by day you need to train your mind, then you have a plan on how to become independent, standing on your own feet. Then you work hard for the person you want to be.”

Interestingly, he elaborates here on his decision-making power within his business; hence, he does not rely on anyone's approval. Again, this could link back to independence, which is a subjective measure to view success.

“I like to work for myself and I like the freedom it gives back. I can make the decisions at any time. I don't need anyone's approval.”

Family relations

C8 elaborated on how his family is involved in the business - mainly his wife, who contributes as a staff member and takes care of most of the admin work inside the shop.

“my wife helps me a lot. She sometimes comes behind the staff all day if I am running out of staff for the shop floor. She takes care of the online ordering and paper work most of the time.”

His two younger brothers have also been helping him from the beginning, and even now in this difficult pandemic situation.

“well, my two younger brothers have helped me and are still helping me even during this difficult time.”

Knowledge and Experience

C8 further mentioned that he emigrated to the UK when he was sixteen years old. And he started to work in different retail shops when he was 16+ years old. That allowed him to learn the retail business, the English language and other necessary skills over time.

“I came here when I was 16+ years old. I started work in different Off-Licence shops for years. I learnt about these kinds of businesses a lot as I got older. My English is way better now and I can handle two businesses, plus I know how to manage customers.”

Social Capital

Access to finance

C8 revealed that he borrowed some money from his friends to run his business at the beginning, which he later successfully managed to pay back to them.

“I borrowed some money from my friends and put all the money into the business, eventually I have been able to pay their debts and run this business properly.”

Finding the staff

C8 mentioned that he found staff for the business through his social contacts. In that way he can get to know who he employs and at the same time, sharing similar cultural values (background) allows him to work with them easily.

“Staff I have found also from my contacts. You have to know who you are employing, plus it is much easier to work with the people who have the same background as you.”

C8 mentioned that having a business where he has lived most of his life in London, allows him to reach his family quickly, and being connected to the social surrounding enables him to run the business easily.

“I live here. It is easy to open a business where you can reach your family very quickly. And also I know a lot of people in this area since I moved here from Sri Lanka. I think it is easy to run a business when you know the people in the area as well.”

Customer relationship related findings

Trust

C8 revealed on one occasion that he does not want to increase the price of his products as an opportunistic reaction to the pandemic situation. He further said that he does not want to put pressure on the customers, hence 90% of the customers are locals and he thinks they recognised him as a trustworthy business. Therefore, this might elaborate that C8 truly cares for the customers by limiting the self-serving opportunism as a way to show operational benevolence behaviour.

“I don't want to increase the price. I'm not pressing on the price. Because, in this shop, 90% of the customers are locals living in the area and all the locals know me, they know I'm not like that - taking advantage of the whole lockdown situation, and increasing the price for the products I sell here - it's not good in the long run.”

Service

Customer oriented approach

C8 understands that there are Sri Lankans, English, Europeans, and South Asians living in the community. So he attempts to serve everyone's needs.

“You can't say there are a lot of Sri Lankans or a lot of English, European and South Asians living here. I can say it is a mixture of t all the ethnics I mentioned in this community. I have something for every group.”

Then again C8 revealed that he serves the customer's expectations through his shop while attempting to make them happy. Also, he tends to question why the customer should come to his shop rather than others. Perhaps this is how C8 understands the customer orientation through questioning himself. In essence, he is serving the current needs of the customer and might be assessing future needs by comparing his business with other businesses in the area.

“whatever the customers expect, I provide them through my shop. I always make an effort to make the customers happy. Important thing here, why they come to your shop, and not go to the others.”

Customer centricity

C8 further revealed that questioning why the customer should come to his shop rather than other shops in the area helps him to understand the customer's point of view and their needs, making the customer needs a priority; hence he orientates the business towards them. Therefore this could be argued as customer centricity. As a result, he introduced a parcel collection service and utility bill payment service in his shop, which has increased his sales.

“important thing here, why they come to your shop, and not go to others. I always think like that to understand their point of view and their needs. Recently, I have introduced a parcel collection and utility bill payment point in this shop. I think that has also increased sales.”

Being empathetic towards the customer

C8 revealed that having a retail shop near to the customer's home does not necessarily mean that these customers need to pay extra money for the business as these customers normally do in other businesses in the area. He also believes that setting a price the customer can afford on a quality product, with welcoming service, may help to retain the customers over time. This elaborates the empathetic behaviour as he attempts to care for the customer rather than trying to make a profit.

“Because this is an Off Licence near to their houses that doesn't mean they need to pay a high price for the products. You see, customers can buy the same things from other shops nearby as well. If you make the customer welcome here, set the affordable price on quality products and deliver good service for them, I think they will always come back.”

Developing patience for the customer

C8 believes that he is always listening to the customer as he is always open to talking with the customer. On the other hand, with customer complaints, he always listens first as they might be right or wrong; either way, he believes that he has to listen to them with politeness. He also thinks that staying calm in these situations and reacting to them accordingly is a pathway to building a good reputation.

“I always listen to the customer as you can see, and my customers also know I am a very talkative person. Sometimes they come up with complaints, you have to listen to them, they might be right or they might be wrong. Either way, you have to listen to them very politely. And then explain the situation to them, who is right and wrong. Also, you need to be very calm in most of these scenarios. If you are not, it is not good for you or the shop’s reputation.”

Let the customer make the buying decision

Importantly, C8 does not want to increase the price and put the pressure on the customers during the lockdown; many of his customers are locals and he knows them.

“I don’t want to increase the price. I’m not pressing on the price. Because, in this shop, 90% of the customers are locals living in the area and all the locals know me.”

Thus, C8 further mentioned that he does not want to pressurize the customers to buy products from his business to increase sales, which elaborates on collaborative selling.

“you can’t stress customers to buy stuff from your business to increase sales.”

Business Reputation

C8 thinks that being patient towards the customer, calming them down and through tolerant behaviour and how he behaves in such scenarios, may impact his business reputation.

“Sometimes they come up with complaints, you have to listen to them, they might be right or they might be wrong. Either way, you have to listen to them very politely. And then explain the situation to them, who is right and wrong. Also, you need to be very calm in most of these scenarios. If you are not, it is not good for you or the shop’s reputation.”

C8 believes that a customer will trust the business over time; hence he, as a business, does not rely on cheap and low-quality products in the business, especially in the case of expanding the business to another area, or nearby location. According to C8, customers are attracted to established brand names over time, so the business can avoid marketing or any other promotions to get new customers. Hence the people in the area know that his business is built through genuine means. Perhaps C8 thinks that the secret to building a good brand name over time depends on maintaining a good reputation as well.

“A customer will trust you as a business because you are not selling cheap and low-quality products to make money to stay in the business. When you open the same shop nearby or in another area, people know your business already, you don’t have to do marketing or anything, they just come to your shop just by the name. Also people in this area know me, they are my customers and they know I do not do any fake things.”

Economic/Opportunity Structure Analysis (Meso-level)

Access to finance

Accessing finance appeared to be difficult for C8 as well. He mentioned that he had very small start-up capital for his business.

“managing finance was a struggle. I had a very small amount of money to start the business”

High competition in the market

C8 is facing high competition within the current market. He mentioned that if the service is slow, product variety and the price point will determine his business survival, especially with supermarkets and other retail shops in the area.

“In this business people won't give you a chance, if you are late to serve, they will go to next door, if you don't have what they looking for they will go to supermarkets and if you increase the price, they will find a cheaper place like that.”

Language barriers to serve European customers in the area

C8 mentioned that he recently experienced European customers in the area. He further mentioned that these customers have difficulties understanding or speaking English and vice versa and he struggles to serve them as a result of it.

“Recently there are a lot of Europeans starting to live here. Sometimes I can't understand what they are saying or questions regarding some product or items, because they can barely speak English.”

Lacking online presence

C8 claimed that he does not have any online activities to promote or to seek growth opportunities within the online retail market.

“We don’t have online presence and promotions at the moment.”

Coronavirus impact

C8 was also impacted by the Coronavirus situation, during the lockdown and after.

Overall sales went up during the lockdown with high demand despite the supplier delays

C8 mentioned that his overall sales during the lockdown have increased with high demand. And at the same time, his business experienced supplier delays during the period.

“I know a lot of businesses might have told you a different story, but for me, I’m being very busy. During the lockdown, my sales went up, I almost couldn’t keep up with the demand. Supplies were late, to be honest.”

Challenging working environment due to lack of staff

C8 mentioned that he had to reduce the staff during the lockdown and after the lockdown. He managed to get two of the staff members back to work after being furloughed, but with reduced hours to reduce the costs.

“I had to cut the staff. Two of them I got back after being furloughed. I can’t give many hours because we close the shops early nowadays to reduce some cost.”

C8 explained how he managed the business during the lockdown and after. As a family business, his wife helped him due to the shortage of staff; in particular, updating paperwork with suppliers and managing the stock was vital to them:

“it is hard nowadays. My wife was helping me during the lockdown because we were short of staff. We needed to check the stock and orders for the next day when supplies were delayed, and we needed someone to look after that and paper work. Normally me or my staff do that, now my wife has to do them. She also works hard. Because you need to update your stock.”

Business future uncertainty

C8 mentioned that he thought the pandemic would end soon. But, as the vaccine had not been deployed when he gave this interview, he believes that people might have to live with the virus for months. Due to new social distancing rules and regulations placed by the government, he allows fewer customers inside and leaves others to wait or find another shop. He does not want to plan anything as this creates uncertainty:

“I don’t know to be honest. It is very uncertain now. I thought this was going to finish soon. But I think until we find a vaccine, we will have to live with the virus, we have to allow fewer customers inside the shop than we used to. Some of them don’t want to wait, and they go next door sometimes. It is impacting our business negatively as well. I won’t plan anything yet, and I will see how it goes.”

Institutional embeddedness Analysis (Macro-level)

C8 believes that running a business in the UK is far better compared to Sri Lanka. As a Tamil person who grew up in a period of civil war and afterwards, he believes Sri Lanka, as a country, still needs to improve their legal system. But overall, he is happy to run a business in the UK. He also stresses that supermarkets and other retail giants need to be regulated as they take away his customers by opening mini supermarkets near their businesses.

“I think running a business is easier here than in Sri Lanka. I'm Tamil, so you know what kind of situation there was 20 years ago. Plus, as a Sri Lankan, we need to put regulations and law systems in place. At the moment, I don't think those kinds of things are working there effectively yet. In Sri Lanka, rules and regulations are very important to run any kind of a business. I am very happy about running a business here. But there are some regulations to put in place for the big supermarkets. They are taking away customers from us by opening a mini supermarket around our businesses. I think we need some laws or regulations to control this.”

